

INTERSECTING LGBTQI LANGUAGE EDUCATOR IDENTITY
NEGOTIATION, EXPERIENCE NAVIGATION, AND INSTITUTIONAL
HETEROPROFESSIONALISM: INSIGHTS FROM A CASE STUDY

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HETEROPROFESSIONALISM: INSIGHTS FROM A CASE STUDY**

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ABSTRACT

INTERSECTING LGBTQI LANGUAGE EDUCATOR IDENTITY NEGOTIATION, EXPERIENCE NAVIGATION, AND INSTITUTIONAL HETEROPROFESSIONALISM: INSIGHTS FROM A CASE STUDY

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A dearth of global scholarly attention to the presence of LGBTQI educators is incontrovertible despite the challenges confronting them in their workplace contexts. However, critical analysis of their experiences is pivotal to understanding the importance of diversity, inclusivity, equity, and social justice. Previous research has been observed to delve separately into three primary dimensions, i.e., identity-based, experience-based, and ideology-based discussions. A niche is present regarding the intersectionality of the three aforementioned viewpoints. Accordingly, drawing on the concepts of heteroprofessionalism (Mizzi, 2013), and intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989), this study explores the intersection of LGBTQI language educator identity, experiences, and the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism from the perspective of a 26-year-old bigender/pansexual ESL tertiary level educator practicing in the Turkish context for four years. A case study approach was utilized to explore how the participant perceived this intersectionality. Through in-depth analyses of semi-structured interviews, gained deeper insights into the participant's

thoughts and feelings were gained. Also, solicited journals enabled better access into the participant's experiences and how she reflected on them concerning her own perceptions, thoughts, and retrospections. Finally, through participant-generated observation reports, deeper insights into pre-determined target behaviors of individuals within the participant's workplace environment and how she perceived those behaviors were gained. It was observed that institutional heteroprofessionalism had notable influences on the participant. The findings in this study have critical implications for the design of nonnormative workplace environments for LGBTQI language educators, as well as calling for relevant further research to promote support and equity for these practitioners.

Keywords: Queering ELT, queer teachers, queer teacher identity, queer teacher experience, heteroprofessionalism

ÖZ

LGBTQİ DİL EĞİTMENİ KİMLİK MÜZAKERESİ, DENEYİM SEYRİ VE KURUMSAL HETEROPROFESYONELLİK KESİŞİMİ: BİR DURUM ÇALIŞMASINDAN İÇGÖRÜLER

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Mesleki çalışma alanlarında karşılaştıkları zorluklara rağmen, LGBTQİ eğitimcilerin varlığına yönelik küresel akademik ilgi oldukça yetersizdir. Ancak, yaşadıkları özgün deneyimlerin eleştirel analizi; çeşitlilik, kapsayıcılık, eşitlik ve sosyal adaletin önemini anlamak açısından büyük önem taşımaktadır. Alanyazındaki araştırmaların çoğunlukla kimlik, deneyim ve ideoloji temelli tartışmalara ayrı ayrı yoğunlaştığı gözlemlenmiştir. Bu üç bakış açısının kesişimselliğine dair bir boşluk olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Bu doğrultuda, karşıcinsel meslekçilik (Mizzi, 2013) ve kesişimsellik (Crenshaw, 1989) kavramlarından yararlanarak, bu çalışma; Türk coğrafyası bağlamında dört yıldır görev yapmakta olan, 26 yaşında, çift cinsiyetli/panseksüel bir İngiliz dili eğitimcisinin, LGBTQİ dil eğitmeni kimliği, mesleki deneyimleri ve karşıcinsel meslekçilik kavramının kesişimini incelemektedir. Bu kesişimselliğin katılımcı tarafından nasıl algılandığını incelemek için nitel bir durum çalışması yaklaşımı kullanılmıştır. Yarı yapılandırılmış mülakatların konusal analizleri aracılığıyla, katılımcının düşünce ve duygularına dair içgörüler elde edilmiştir. Ek

olarak, ön tanımlı günceler, katılımcının deneyimlerine ve bunlara yönelik düşüncelerine ve geriye dönük değerlendirmelerine dair daha derin bir gözlem fırsatı sağlamıştır. Son olarak, katılımcı tarafından oluşturulan gözlem tutanakları aracılığıyla, çalışma ortamındaki bireylerin önceden belirlenmiş hedef davranışlarına ve bu davranışları kendisinin nasıl algıladığına ilişkin daha ayrıntılı bilgiler elde edilmiştir. Kurumsal karşıcinsel meslekçiliğin, katılımcı üzerinde dikkate değer etkiler oluşturduğu gözlemlenmiştir. Bu etkiler; yoğun duygular, mesleki kariyerin sona erdirilmesi korkusu, susturulma ve çoklu kimliklerinden herhangi ikisinin kesişiminden doğan özgün baskı biçimleri gibi durumları içermektedir. Bunlar çoğunlukla örtük saldırganlıklar, örtük veya açık fobik tutumlar, karşıcinsel düzgüsel yapılar ve eylemsel tutumlardan kaynaklanmaktadır. Bulgular söz konusu eğitimler için kaide dışı çalışma ortamlarının tasarımına yönelik çıkarımlar ortaya koymaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: İngilizce öğretimi kuirleştirmek, kuir öğretmenler, kuir öğretmen kimliği, kuir öğretmen deneyimi, heteroprofesyonellik

Sin miedo...

I dedicate this thesis to those who do it without fear.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

PLAGIARISM	iii
ABSTRACT	iv
ÖZ.....	vi
DEDICATION	viii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	ix
TABLE OF CONTENTS	x
LIST OF TABLES	xiii
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	xiv
CHAPTERS	
1. INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1. Background to the Study	2
1.2. The Niche and the Research Problem	4
1.3. The Purpose of the Study	6
1.4. Significance of the Study	8
1.5. Conceptual Frameworks.....	10
1.5.1. Heteroprofessionalism.....	11
1.5.2. Intersectionality	13
1.6. Definitions of the Key Terms.....	15
2. LITERATURE REVIEW.....	18
2.1. Identity-Based Discussions	20
2.2. Ideology-Based Discussions	27
2.3. Experience-Based Discussions.....	31
2.4. The Turkish Context.....	37
2.5. The Niche	40
3. METHODOLOGY	43
3.1. Definition and Justification of the Research Design	44
3.2. Sampling of the Study	47
3.3. Participant of the Study	48

3.4. Research Setting.....	52
3.5. Data Collection, Instrumentation, and Analysis Procedures.....	54
3.5.1. Data Collection.....	54
3.5.2. Data Instrumentation.....	58
3.5.2.1. Interviewing.....	59
3.5.2.2. Journaling.....	60
3.5.2.3. Participant-Generated Observation Reports.....	62
3.5.3. Data Analysis.....	65
3.5.3.1. Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA).....	67
3.6. Validity Checks.....	70
3.6.1. Advisory Supervision.....	71
3.6.2. Professional Consultation.....	72
3.6.3. Reflexivity.....	72
3.6.4. Peer Debriefing.....	73
3.6.5. Data Triangulation.....	74
3.6.6. Member Checking.....	75
3.7. Researcher Positionality.....	76
3.8. Ethical Considerations.....	79
4. FINDINGS.....	82
4.1. Research Question 1.....	83
4.1.1. Realization of Her Positioning.....	83
4.1.2. Perception of Heteroprofessionalism.....	86
4.1.3. Perceived Dangers of Heteroprofessionalism.....	87
4.1.4. Professional Experience of Heteronormativity.....	90
4.1.5. Institutional Exclusion and Microaggressions.....	92
4.1.6. Acknowledging the Impact of Heteroprofessionalism.....	98
4.1.7. Allyship and Aloofness at the Workplace.....	101
4.1.8. Resisting Heteroprofessionalism.....	104
4.2. Research Question 2.....	106
4.2.1. Identity Plurality.....	106
4.2.2. Acting Strategically.....	111
4.2.3. Emotions.....	116
4.2.4. English Language as a Gateway.....	123

4.2.5. Society and Context	126
4.2.6. Parting and Intersecting Identities	130
4.2.7. Performativity.....	133
5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION	139
5.1. Summary of the Key Findings	140
5.2. Interpretations of the Key Findings.....	141
5.3. Answers to the Research Questions	143
5.3.1. Research Question 1	144
5.3.2. Research Question 2.....	145
5.4. Discussion within the Pertinent Literature	146
5.4.1. Alignment with Existing Research.....	146
5.4.2. Divergence From Existing Research.....	151
5.5. Implications.....	155
5.6. Acknowledgement of the Limitations	156
5.7. Recommendations for Further Research	158
REFERENCES.....	164
APPENDICES	
A. APPROVAL OF THE METU HUMAN SUBJECTS ETHICS COMMITTEE.	211
B. SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW 1 QUESTIONS.....	212
C. SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW 2 QUESTIONS.....	213
D. SOLICITED JOURNAL 1 PROMPT	214
E. SOLICITED JOURNAL 2 PROMPT.....	215
F. SOLICITED JOURNAL 3 PROMPT	216
G. PARTICIPANT-GENERATED OBSERVATION REPORTS TEMPLATE	217
H. INFORMED CONSENT FORM	218
I. PROFESSIONAL CONSULTATION FORM / KONSÜLTASYON FORMU ..	220
J. THE LIST OF EXAMPLE INITIAL CODES	224
K. SAMPLE CODING IN MAXQDA	226
L. TURKISH SUMMARY / TÜRKÇE ÖZET	227
M. THESIS PERMISSON FORM / TEZ İZİN FORMU	242

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Data Collection Timeline	55
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

LGBTQI	Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transexual, Queer, and Intersex
ENDA	Employment Non-Discrimination Act
CISHET	Cis-Heterosexual
TEFL	Teaching English as a Foreign Language
ELT	English Language Teaching
TOEFL	Test of English as a Foreign Language
IELTS	International English Language Testing System
GRE	Graduate Record Examinations
PTE	Pearson Test of English
EPE	English Proficiency Exam
ESL	English as a Second Language
TEP	Teacher Education Program
ITEP	Initial Teacher Education Program
ST	Student Teacher
GSD	Gender and Sexual Diversity
LGB	Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual
LGT	Lesbian, Gay, and Transexual
CP	Civil Partnership
QDA	Qualitative Data Analysis
AERA	American Educational Research Association
CIMER	Presidential Communication Center
IDI	In-Depth Interview
RTA	Reflexive Thematic Analysis
IRB	Institutional Review Board
HSEC	Human Subjects Ethics Committee
BA	Bachelor of Arts
MA	Master of Arts

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

LGBTQI educators are often considered to contribute to the field of education as agents of inclusivity and representatives of diversity. Their presence in educational contexts is crucial even merely for the sake of perpetuation of equal rights of professionalism for all identities and individuals. However, heteroprofessionalism, a professional value that excludes homosexuality (Mizzi, 2013), does not make their presence in professional settings any easier for them, considering all the challenges it brings along, that pertain to their processes of identity negotiation and professional experience navigation. Today, a dearth of global scholarly attention to the presence of LGBTQI educators is incontrovertible (Antonelli & Sembiente, 2022) despite the compelling challenges they confront within the context of their professional workspaces (Jennings, 2005). However, the critical analysis of the peculiar predicaments, experiences, and contributions that LGBTQI educators engage in educational environments, many of which comprise socio-politically constructed cis-heteropatriarchal expectations (Rich, 2003) and institutionalized cis-heteronormative (Warner, 1991) mechanisms, is pivotal to comprehending the importance of diversity, fostering inclusivity, equity, and social justice (Cantos et al., 2023), and drawing wider implications for educational policies and practices. Accordingly, designed as a single intrinsic case study that explores the intersectionality of an LGBTQI language educator's identity negotiation, experience navigation, and the ideological notion of institutionalized heteroprofessionalism (Mizzi, 2013) in the Turkish context, this study investigates how her multiple identities (Bennett et al., 2015; Mayo, 2023) intersect within the context of her professional workplace environment. Conclusions drawn from this study are anticipated to present helpful implications for all stakeholders and institutional policymakers within the context of education, calling for efforts to mitigate normative regulations in educational

contexts and develop inclusive and supportive workplace environments for the ongoing development and wellbeing of LGBTQI educators. This chapter presents background information on the study, the niche and the research problem, the research objectives of this study, the guiding research questions, the significance of the study, and several key terms that are important to the conceptual understanding of this study.

1.1. Background to the Study

Including all stakeholders from students and alumni to educators, administrators, and policymakers, integration of LGBTQI identities within institutional contexts of education is an endeavor that is of great value (Antonelli & Sembiente, 2022; Dentato et al., 2016; Haddad, 2019). Educators navigate their professional responsibilities and roles along with diverse personal identities (Gray & Harris, 2014), which often result in identity duality and delicate tensions for them to navigate (Jackson, 2009; Johnson, 2006). Considering the complex nature of their identities and the heteroprofessional work environments, these tensions might get even more challenging for LGBTQI educators. Therefore, scholarly attention toward their overall presence within institutional and educational contexts should be enhanced to provide equity and social justice for these practitioners.

Especially in the Global North, today's educational environments are designed more mindful of inclusivity and support for diverse identities (Dawson et al., 2022; DeLuca, 2013; Waling & Roffee, 2018) compared to what has been practiced so far, acknowledging their essentiality for the good of all individuals included (Patton et al., 2023). However, when it comes to creating welcoming and nonnormative environments for LGBTQI identities and supporting them through their academic and professional journeys, institutional policies, practices, and efforts are still not adequate across the globe (Catalano et al., 2025; Cui, 2022; 2024; Day et al., 2019; Jaekel & Nicolazzo, 2020; Mizzi & Star, 2019; Pryor, 2020; Tompkins et al., 2019a; Unwin et al., 2024). Among all the relevant literature, the great majority of studies explored the experiences of LGBTQI students at various levels with regard to their identities, emotions, perspectives, needs, and how their academic and personal

experiences can be enhanced (Lewis & Ericksen, 2016; Payne & Smith, 2011; Swanson & Gettinger, 2016). Herewith, it is also important to note that the increasing attention LGBTQI identities, including students, have received in the global academic milieu in the last few decades has been particularly observed in the Western context (Kulpa, 2016; Mizzi & Star, 2019; Mizzi et al., 2021). However, studies centering LGBTQI educators' identities, emotions, tensions, thoughts, and experiences are not manifold (Antonelli & Sembiente, 2022; Coda, 2019), especially in Global South contexts, where issues of gender and sexuality are mostly overlooked. These educators frequently withstand unique challenges with respect to identity duality, tensions, negotiation, and disclosure (Brett, 2022; Haddad, 2019) while navigating heteroprofessional norms, microaggressions, and normatively regulated expectations within their workspaces (Gray, 2013; İpekçi, 2022). Thus, exploring their dynamic worlds is pivotal to fostering nonnormative, welcoming, and inclusive educational and institutional policies and practices as well as supporting their professional development and well-being (Grace, 2020; Smith et al., 2008).

In the Global South in particular, there is an intricate intersection of LGBTQI educators and professional workplace contexts in education. However, all around the globe, previous research delves into difficulties they face such as discrimination toward their identity enactment (Eckes, 2017; Graves, 2018), continuous concealment of their personal identities (Jackson, 2009), and the experiences of navigating workspaces that might not entirely allow for diverse identities (Ferfolja, 2007; García & Slesaransky-Poe, 2010). Nevertheless, research particularly scrutinizing how LGBTQI language educators negotiate their multiple identities and navigate their professional experiences within heteroprofessional workspaces is still lacking. Studies so far focused on the overall professional experiences of language teachers (Barkhuizen & Wette, 2008; Early & Shagoury, 2010; Jun, 2022; Williams et al., 2012; Yuan & Lee, 2013), the complexities of their identity-related processes (Mora et al., 2016; Tajeddin & Yazan, 2024; Uzum et al., 2022; Varghese et al., 2005), and language teacher cognition (Borg, 2003; Feryok, 2010; Golombek, 2015; Johnson, 2018). On the other hand, several studies investigated the institutionalized heterosexist, heteronormative, heteroprofessional, and microaggression experiences of LGBTQI identities in various professional contexts (Beagan et al., 2022; Davies &

Neustifter, 2021; Giddings & Pringle, 2011; Mizzi, 2024). However, considering the already complex nature of language educators' identity-related processes, experiences, and cognitions (Pennington & Richards, 2016; Yuan & Lee, 2013; Zheng, 2013), exploration of such of those identifying as LGBTQI maintains its necessity of more scholarly attention, delving particularly into their own perceptions of their positioning, experiences, and identity-related processes within their workspaces. Within the Turkish context, wherein the present study takes place, studies conducted to explore the intricacies of language teacher identity, let alone focusing particularly on LGBTQI language educators, observably lack in number.

Indubitably, heteroprofessionalism as a concept necessitates the investigation of how LGBTQI educators endeavor to achieve a balance between their personal identity enactment and professional roles and responsibilities. This investigation is especially necessary within workplace contexts monopolized by heteronormativity, heterosexism, and LGBTQI-phobia. Despite the increasing consideration that the issue of LGBTQI inclusivity has received in educational contexts (Day et al., 2019), efforts of understanding the processes of identity negotiation and experience navigation of LGBTQI educators within their heteroprofessional workspaces remains underexplored. Correspondingly, drawing on the concept of intersectionality, which contextually posits an intersection of multiple identities (e.g., sex, gender, sexual identity, cultural identity, professional role) having direct or indirect influences on their experiences within social structures (Crenshaw, 1989), and the concept of heteroprofessionalism, which is “a professional value that screens out homosexuality” (Mizzi, 2013, p.1), this thesis study examines how an LGBTQI language educator negotiates her multiple identities and navigates her professional experiences in a Turkish higher education workplace context amidst institutional and societal norms and expectations that she does not conform to.

1.2. The Niche and the Research Problem

As aforementioned, studies in the relevant literature focused on several concepts explored in this study as well. However, these foci have seemingly been piled up as isolated reservoirs of scholarly work, elaborately but singly investigating each

concept. Identities and experiences of language teachers as well as predominating institutional projections of ideologies such as heteronormativity (Warner, 1991) and LGBTQI-phobia have drawn increasing attention in the last few decades. It is notable that this attention should still be appreciated yet enhanced by further research. Approaches mindful of the concept of intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989) in studies investigating LGBTQI language educators and their presence in professional settings have been observed to be lacking in the existing literature. The great majority of the studies conducted with similar objectives have been observed to overlook the concepts of intersectionality and heteroprofessionalism (Mizzi, 2013). In spite of the expanding body of literature regarding identity-, ideology-, and experience-based discussions on LGBTQI educators, a significant gap remains in understanding the delicate intersectionality of these components. As previously discussed, earlier research carried out in various cultures and contexts has predominantly scrutinized each of these components in isolation, overlooking the intricate interplay they have in between. The research problem of this thesis study is brought forth by the paucity of research examining how these intersecting components are manifested in the professional lives of LGBTQI language educators within the Turkish context (İpekçi, 2022; Taşkın et al., 2022), more in particular – North Cyprus. Therefore, the primary research problem is: The intricate interplay between and the intersecting dynamics of LGBTQI language educators’ multiples identities, workplace experiences, and the ideological notion of institutionalized heteroprofessionalism within the Turkish educational context remains underexplored.

The increasing recognition of inclusivity, diversity, and social justice within educational settings (McCabe & Rubinson, 2008) and educational institutions as workplace environments (Mayo, 2023), especially in the Global North, is promising and encouraging. However, the exploration of LGBTQI language educators’ identities and experiences amidst heteroprofessionalism in various context around the globe still requires more observation in the interest of providing well-being and equity (Hong et al., 2023; Kahn & Gorski, 2016) to these practitioners. Considering the layers of complexity continuously added to LGBTQI language educators’ professional experiences by the interplay of their multiple identities (Kayi-Aydar, 2015; Racelis & Matsuda, 2014), i.e., personal identity, sexual identity, racial

identity, professional identity, and cultural identity, under-exploration and lack of social recognition would only perpetuate the status quo of institutionalized norms and regulations that are expected to be abided by (Kelly et al., 2020) irrespective of who they are, what they are, what they want, and what they deserve. Therefore, in order to tackle this problem and foster the development of more inclusive and supportive yet less normative and oppressive workspaces for these practitioners (Gray et al., 2016; Mizzi, 2022), it is essential that the intersectionality of the aforementioned components is acknowledged and understood. Accordingly, the present study aims to address this niche by delving into the multifaceted nature of an LGBTQI language educator's identities and workplace experiences, exploring how they intersect with heteroprofessional institutional ideologies, practices, policies, rules, and regulations within the Turkish educational context, where socio-political and socio-cultural climate tends to ignore them despite all the pertinent struggles they often experience.

1.3. The Purpose of the Study

This study explores the intersectionality of an LGBTQI language educator's identities, workplace experiences, and the manifestation of the concept of heteroprofessionalism within the context of the Turkish educational system. As suggested by Graneheim and Lundman (2004), there is not just one accurate answer in qualitative studies. Instead, there is the most plausible significance from a specific point of view. This study is motivated by the emergent necessity to understand and address LGBTQI language educators' professional experiences in the Turkish context, as well as to put forth implications to be drawn upon for fostering inclusivity and equity for these practitioners within institutional settings of education. In-depth scrutinization of the identities and professional experiences of an LGBTQI language educator officially practicing in the Turkish context amidst institutionalized heteroprofessionalism is aimed this study. In addition, the study aspires to add up to broader scholarly discussions surrounding diversity, equity, social justice, and inclusion. It is also aimed by this study to inform educational authorities and institutional policy makers, as well as advocating for reforms and changes in institutional practices that would support the empowerment of LGBTQI professional

identities in educational contexts (Wright & Smith, 2015). All in all, one of the two core purposes of the study is to aspire to make constructive contributions to the relevant literature, promoting inclusivity and equity for LGBTQI educators within the Turkish educational context and ultimately endeavoring toward more affirming and welcoming workplace environments for these practitioners.

The other purpose of this study is to provide implications for the psychological and professional well-being of LGBTQI educators in similar contexts. Although the study prioritizes the exploration of the intricacies of a single participant in a particular case (Stake, 2005), with no intention of generating findings to generalize to broader populations (Creswell, 2013; Merriam, 2009), scrutinizing the case and understanding the participant enabled valuable implications to consider. Those implications are expected to inform educational and institutional policies, practices, rules, and regulations to further promote inclusivity and encouraging more welcoming and inclusive workspaces as well as equal professional opportunities for all. Considering the socio-political and socio-cultural climate of the Turkish context for the last two decades, which implicitly favor heterop professionalism, the concept should be considered even more dangerous for LGBTQI identities in professional workspaces. Accordingly, exploring the particular challenges and unique strengths of an LGBTQI language educator practicing amidst heterop professionalism, this thesis study was also designed with the hopes of informing professional development (PD) initiatives, preservice teacher education programs, and in-service teacher training services as much as possible. Ultimately, the present study endeavors to empower all LGBTQI educators through validation, acknowledgement, appreciation, and celebration of their presence in workplace contexts. It is also aimed to add up to a broader understanding of the challenges they confront, thereby arguing in favor of their basic right of practicing within more equitable workspaces. Established upon the preceding purposes, the following research questions guided this study in the process of scrutinizing the uniqueness of this case (Merriam, 2009) in all its “ordinariness” (Yin, 2018, p. 52):

RQ1: From the perspective of an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context, how does heterop professionalism, if any, manifest itself within her workplace context?

RQ2: How does an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context negotiate her identities and navigate her professional experiences within her heteroprofessional workplace context?

1.4. Significance of the Study

This study is significant mainly because it offers the potential to further our comprehensive understanding of a contemporary phenomenon (Yin, 2009, p. 14) that is how an LGBTQI language educator's identities, professional experiences, and the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism intersect within the real-life context (Yin, 2009, p. 14) of a Turkish educational institution. This is made possible by exploring the single participant recruited through purposive sampling, thereby representative of the community addressed (Ishak & Bakar, 2014). Thus, although no generalization of findings is intended, this exploration intends to provide greater awareness of the particular challenges encountered by LGBTQI language educators in Turkish educational institutions by illuminating the difficulties, coping strategies, and advocacy initiatives of the participant. Furthermore, findings drawn from this study can assist authorities, Turkish educators, and policy makers in establishing more inclusive and affirmative policies and procedures (Dykes & Delpont, 2018), which will eventually serve in formation of more secure, encouraging, and welcoming professional atmospheres for all LGBTQI educators.

Furthermore, by expanding our comprehension of the compelling experiences and resilience of an LGBTQI language educator practicing within the heteroprofessional framework of a Turkish educational institution, this study offers perspectives that further research may draw from. In other words, in addition to providing implications to inform authorities, future research is expected to be encouraged by this study as well. Thereby, more detailed studies can be carried out concerning similar research problems as well as exploring comparable contexts. In addition to that, utilizing similar research designs, various subjects enacting and representing diverse identities can be examined. Considering that the LGBTQI community comprises a wide, colorful scope of identities (Blechinger, 2016; Bosse & Chiodo, 2016; Hulko & Hovanes, 2017), it is no doubt that at least "one" of each of those identities practices

as an educator somewhere around the world. On the basis of their personal, sexual, cultural, professional, racial, and gender identities and multiple additional identity markers, their experiences as educators may vary. Their emotions, beliefs, perspectives, and stances with regard to their professional experiences (Lineback et al., 2016) and normative practices (DePalma & Atkinson, 2010; Ferfolja, 2007; García & Slesaransky-Poe, 2010) they experience will differ accordingly. Therefore, each may be addressed and explored on their own unique terms as particular cases. In that way, the intricate issue of how they perceive their own presence within educational workplace settings (Lineback et al., 2016; Llewellyn & Reynolds, 2020) can also be examined. Also, drawing on the frameworks this study draws on in its design and conduct, further research can be expected to be encouraged to delve into various other aspects of all LGBTQI educators, gaining their perspectives and informing authorities to take action accordingly. Ultimately, in view of the plethora of societal and professional challenges that the LGBTQI community perpetually suffers from, alongside direct or indirect contextual discrimination and violation of their basic human rights and liberties (Richard, 2013), any further research aspiring after similar research objectives to this study would be appreciated. On to that, considering the probability that all LGBTQI educators are frequently compelled to abide by oppressively normative institutional norms and practices (Bracho & Hayes, 2020; Wells, 2017), as well as withstanding behaviors based off of microaggressions by all stakeholders (Beagan et al., 2020; Lee, 2019b; Neary, 2013; 2017), research directing focused attention to their unique experiences is of particular importance and should be promoted. Correspondingly, this research is considered significant due to its design and conduct, and the fact that it can indeed encourage further relevant research, which has been an urgent matter of necessity over an extended period of time now.

In addition to all these, issues of representation and visibility are of great importance for the whole LGBTQI community (Bell & Keer, 2021; Edward & Greenough, 2020; Ryan-Flood, 2022). Nevertheless, the community has not received the greatest attention either in educational or scholarly contexts in general (Katz-Wise & Hyde, 2012). Considering this lack of attention paid to their presence within various contexts in societies across the globe, all initiatives, steps, and actions taken to

simply represent them contribute to their overall visibility. Although no ideological stance is expected to be altered by this visibility, hearing LGBTQI individuals' narratives and appreciating their voices, societies' overall awareness and sensitivity can be enhanced, leading to mitigated microaggressions toward their presence in various contexts (Nadal et al., 2016; Nadal, 2018; Patterson et al., 2019; Resnick & Galupo, 2018). In this respect, the present study contributes to the visibility of the LGBTQI community, particularly in educational contexts, by serving as a critical reflection and representation of the broader systemic concerns they are coerced to perpetually consider in environments in which they are frequently felt unfit (McCalla, 2015). More in particular, sticking up for a more reasonable conduct of professionalism that would welcome diverse identities in educational workplace environments, this study attempts to challenge the prevailing ideological notion of institutionalized heteroprofessionalism (Mizzi, 2013). By examining its interplay with the participant's identities and professional experiences, this report not only pronounces detrimental institutional practices but also aspires after inspiring and encouraging further research and advocacy endeavors that would enhance the representation and visibility of all LGBTQI educators. Particularly with respect to educators' perspectives, studies carried out to investigate the intersection of educational and queer topics are still rather few in number as discussed earlier. By virtue of the continuity of such representation and visibility efforts, a brake can be put on the perpetuation of normative ideologies and practices that further complicates the professional experiences of LGBTQI educators, such as both the participant and the researcher of this study. Through a design that provided the participant with an opportunity to represent herself and validate her perspectives as well as by addressing systemically institutionalized inequalities and discrimination (Irwin, 2002) based off of heteronormativity, this study offers hope to make positive impact on the professional and institutional experiences of all LGBTQI language educators practicing within the Turkish educational system, where institutional heteroprofessionalism is frequently practiced at workspaces.

1.5. Conceptual Frameworks

Conceptual frameworks offer an overview of key concepts, terms, theories, and ideas, which helps understand the parameters of studies and guide the formulation of

research problems, objectives, and questions (Rocco & Plakhotnik, 2009). They provide clear points of reference for methodological decision-making, securing consistency in the process of planning designs, collecting and analyzing data, and reporting findings (Kivunja, 2018). Additionally, they can also facilitate positioning findings of studies within the relevant literature, allowing researchers to address and inform knowledge and research gaps and establish connections that advance areas of study. By this means, studies' integrity and credibility are enhanced, which expedites the process of communicating the investigation process and study findings to relevant academic communities, authorities, and all stakeholders. Correspondingly, the present study draws on two concepts, i.e., heterop professionalism by Mizzi (2013) and intersectionality by Crenshaw (1989). Understanding these concepts is pivotal to understand what is explored and reported in this study.

1.5.1. Heterop professionalism

Heterop professionalism, coined and defined by Mizzi (2013) as an exclusive professional value toward non-conforming LGBTQI identities within workspaces, serves as an essential concept in understanding the intersection of personal (sexual) and professional roles and identities of the participant in this study and how she is oppressed accordingly. Defined by (Mizzi, 2013, p.1), the concept refers to “a professional value that screens out homosexuality”. Put simply, heterop professionalism refers to implicitly or explicitly performed institutionalized normalization, projection, practices, rules, regulations, policies, expectations, and microaggressions (Adikaram & Liyanage, 2021; Papadaki et al., 2021; Resnick & Galupo, 2018; Soini, 2022) within professional workplace settings that treat heterosexual identities and behaviors as norms and assume, support, privilege, prioritize, and reinforce them, thereby imposing them as the default (Corlett et al., 2022; Giddings & Pringle, 2011; Lehtonen, 2016; McKenna-Buchanan, 2017; Öztürk, 2024; Watson et al., 2023; Woodruffe-Burton, 2016). Comprehending this framework is fundamentally important for conceptualizing how LGBTQI individuals navigate their professional roles, responsibilities, and identities in their institutional workplace environments that are often infested with heteronormative practices and impositions. According to Warner (1991), heteronormativity refers to practices and

politics that privilege heterosexuality and take it as the normative standard. Accordingly, performing heteronormative practices within workplace settings, from subtly phobic microaggressions to explicit executions and projections, can be asserted as a simple description of the concept of heteroprofessionalism.

The multifaceted nature of heteroprofessionalism is accentuated in Mizzi's work, wherein 2 international aid agencies are explored with regard to the workplace experiences of 8 gay male employees and the attitudes toward homosexuality, by outlining several dimensions of the concept. First and foremost, it imposes silencing, suppression, and marginalization of all non-heterosexual identities (DeSouza et al., 2017; McFadden & Crowley-Henry, 2017), which makes LGBTQI employees compelled to conceal their gender sexual identities to comply with prevalent institutional and professional cultures (Seiler-Ramadas et al., 2021). This oppressively projected camouflage frequently results in detriment of their psychological well-being as well as identity fragmentation, thereby affecting their overall performance and professional satisfaction (Bowring & Brewis, 2009; Holman et al., 2021; Madera, 2010; Newheiser et al., 2017). Secondly, numerous institutional and organizational policies and practices that either fail to safeguard LGBTQI employees or tacitly marginalize and exclude them (Baker & Lucas, 2017; Colgan et al., 2007; Özeren & Aydin., 2016) are involved in the concept of heteroprofessionalism. The existence or the absence of these policies is a reflection of broader social norms that acknowledge and value heterosexuality as the default, thereby perpetuating institutional injustices (Collins et al., 2021) in workplace environments.

In addition to rules, regulations, and policies, interactional dynamics and social intercourses within institutional workplace settings, wherein heterosexuality is frequently assumed, normalized, and celebrated through daily contact and socialization practices (Corlett et al., 2022), are also involved in the concept of heteroprofessionalism. Such intercourses reinforce an institutional workplace culture where heteronormative assumptions and impositions go unquestioned, hence perpetuating the status quo as well as rendering non-heterosexual employees oppressed, silenced, marginalized, and invisible (Bell et al., 2011; Felix et al., 2016;

Özeren et al., 2016; Willis, 2010). By drawing on the concept of heteroprofessionalism, researchers can have the opportunity to investigate the various ways in which heteronormative standards, assumptions, and values pervade professional workplace environments, having a considerable influence on not only the personal but also professional lives and identities of LGBTQI employees (Pezzella, 2018; Woodruffe-Burton, 2016). Through this framework, it is possible to critically examine the social interactional intercourses and institutional power dynamics that uphold and perpetuate heteronormativity (Beagan et al., 2022; Kelly et al., 2020). This examination would subsequently shed light on the compelling challenges LGBTQI identities encounter within their workplace settings as well as possible solutions and initiatives for fostering inclusive, welcoming, supportive, non-normative, and equitable workplace environments. Such environments would value diversity and social justice, thereby celebrate the presence of LGBTQI professionals. It is also important to note that heteroprofessionalism has never been drawn on to explore the experiences of an LGBTQI professional within an educational context of workspace. Correspondingly, in the context of this study, the concept is drawn on to examine how an LGBTQI language educator negotiates her identities and navigates her experiences within her heteronormative workplace setting. Exploration of the explicit and implicit mechanisms through which heteroprofessionalism is performed, its effects on the participant's experiences, and how she defies or complies with these normative practices are involved in this exploration.

1.5.2. Intersectionality

Drawing on Crenshaw (1989), the concept of intersectionality can be explained as the ways individuals are oppressed by power structures on their own terms, depending on how their multiple identities intersect. As a case in point, according to Crenshaw (1989), a black woman is not undervalued merely because she is a woman, or she is black. The reason she is frequently oppressed is because her racial identity and gender identity intersect, adding up to her overall oppression. Likewise, many other multiple identities of individuals may intersect, determining or influencing the ways they are targeted, marginalized, undervalued, or oppressed. Multiple identities of individuals comprise groups of communities they belong with, such as their

nationality, gender, sexuality, race, ethnicity, profession, and culture. In order to illustrate, Crenshaw (1989) draws an analogy of traffic flowing at an intersection. Our multiple identities are flowing in different directions, but they can intersect at any moment. Referring back to the black woman paradigm, she is expressly oppressed due to her gender identity in particular contexts. On the other hand, in some other particular contexts, she is expressly oppressed due to her racial identity. However, what the concept of intersectionality suggests is that she is oppressed on other terms when she is both a woman and black. The interplay of her two different identities is like how traffic flows in different directions may intersect and head to a new road together. In that road, the new traffic flow is not the same.

In the present study, the concept of intersectionality is drawn on due to the underlying suggestions that it offers at its core. This study explores a single participant and how she negotiates her multiple identities, intersection of which leads to a particular way of oppression in her workplace environment, navigates her experiences, and perceives institutionalized heteroprofessionalism. The participant of this study identifies as bigender and pansexual. Both her gender identity and sexual identity are nonconforming to societal norms and standards and institutional power structures. Her professional identity denotes being a language educator and practicing institutionally. With regard to her professional identity, it is worth mentioning that there are particular ways she is undervalued, silenced, or suppressed as a language educator. Her nonconforming, non-cis-heterosexual gender and sexual identities result in various other forms of societal discrimination, marginalization, and oppression. When these multiple identities of hers intersect, a particular way of oppression, i.e., heteroprofessionalism, should be addressed. Due to enacting nonconforming gender and sexual identities and practicing institutionally as a language educator, she is anticipated to be specifically influenced by the institutionalized rules, regulations, policies, or practices of the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism. Therefore, while examining how the participant is influenced by heteroprofessionalism in her workplace context and how she negotiates her multiple identities and navigates her experiences accordingly, it is imperative that the present study draws on the concept of intersectionality as well.

1.6. Definitions of the Key Terms

It is indispensable that the key concepts and terms at the core of the study are defined so that clarity, comprehensibility, readability, and consistency (Pettersson, 1993) can be ensured. By outlining these definitions, it is aimed to provide a thorough and clear understanding of the concepts covered and discussed in this study, which explores the intersectionality of an LGBTQI language educator's identities, experiences, and the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism within her workplace context.

LGBTQI: This acronym stands for lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer/questioning, intersex. Several umbrella acronyms are used to refer to the community. These comprise LGBT, LGBTQ, LGBTQ+, LGBTQI, LGBTQI+, LGBTQIA (asexual added), LGBTQIA+, GSM (gender and sexual minorities), and QUILTBAG (queer/questioning, undecided, intersex, lesbian, transgender, bisexual, asexual, gay). Throughout this study, LGBTQI will be used to refer to the community as chosen by the researcher. It is worthy pointing out that there is no particular reason behind the use of this specific acronym, other than it being the most frequently used one in the queer discourse.

Bigender: In the Dictionary of Words for Masculine Women compiled by Gary Bowen in 1995, bigender is defined as “having two genders, exhibiting cultural characteristics of male and female roles”. Simply put, the term denotes to individuals whose gender identity encompasses two distinct genders, either simultaneously or alternately. A bigender person may feel or exhibit characteristics of both genders at the same time or switch between them at different times. These genders can be male and female, but they can also include non-binary or other gender identities. The participant of this study reports bigender as her gender identity.

Pansexual: Freud first defined pansexuality in 1926 as “the pervasion of all conduct and experience with sexual emotions”. Today, the term “pansexual” denotes to individuals who are sexually, romantically, or emotionally attracted toward people of all genders, or regardless of their sexual or gender identities. The participant of this study reports pansexuality as her sexual identity.

Heteronormativity: Coined and defined by Warner (1991), heteronormativity refers to the “views, practices, and politics that privilege heterosexuality and, more or less articulately, take it as the normative standard within a group, community, or society”. On this basis, this study concerns the heteronormative practices that the participant is directly or indirectly confronted in her workplace context.

Heteroprofessionalism: The term was coined and defined by Mizzi (2013) as a professional value that screens out homosexuality. It refers to all the heteronormative rules, regulations, policies, practices, and microaggressions encountered by LGBTQI individuals within their workplace contexts. In this study, the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism is examined with regard to how it affects the participant as a result of the intersectionality of her personal (sexual and gender) and professional identities.

Microaggression: In an attempt to describe the brief, everyday insults and dismissals that he frequently witnessed non-black Americans imposing upon African Americans to convey animosity and bias, Harvard University affiliated psychiatrist Pierce (1970) coined the term microaggression. Today, this term refers to subtle, intentional or unintentional, comments, attitudes, and actions that communicates offense, prejudice, or discrimination against marginalized groups of individuals. Among the heteronormative practices reported to be experienced by the participant of this study within her workplace context are forms of microaggressions as well.

Identity: Identity is extensively discussed in the next chapter through various perspectives and approaches toward its meaning. However, simply put, according to Erikson, identity refers to who an individual is as a person and a contributor to society (Hoare, 2002). Additionally, the concept of multiple identities refers to the several roles that may be embodied by an individual, molded by factors such as culture, nationality, race, gender, sexuality, and profession. Also, Foucault (1980) discusses concept of social identity, putting forth that identities are not inherent or fixed. Rather, they are socially constructed through power dynamics as well as discursive practices. According to Foucault (1980), institutions generate and enforce particular identity categories for groups of individuals, forming how they perceive

and define themselves. This results in internalizing, normalizing, and regulating norms, leading to dynamic identities subject to change and resistance.

Intersectionality: As also aforementioned, drawing on Crenshaw (1989), the concept of intersectionality originally refers to the understanding that all individuals experience discrimination and oppression on their own terms, and that their multiple identities, i.e., gender, racial, sexual, national, professional, and cultural, can marginalize them in societies. Accordingly, this study examines how the participant, on account of her personal and professional identities, is affected by institutionalized heteronormative norms and practices through the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism as a form of oppression.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

The presence of LGBTQI individuals, teachers in particular, in educational settings around the globe has received increased scholarly attention over the past few years, shedding light on the unique challenges they confront due to the delicate intersection of their personal and professional identities (Guijarro-Ojeda et al., 2021). Lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, and intersex educators experience a challenging career path that is also highly influenced by societal norms, organizational and institutional policies, and intrapersonal identity dynamics (e.g., Brockenbrough, 2012; deLeon & Brunner, 2012; Duarte, 2020; Irwin, 2002; Neary et al., 2017; Roberts et al., 2007; Rottmann, 2006; Stones & Glazzard, 2020; Swanepoel, 2019; White et al., 2018; William Gust, 2007). Solely because of their identity, even some politics around the world portray LGBTQI educators as a menace to their countries' education systems. As a case in point, the majority of senators opposed the Employment Non-Discrimination Act (ENDA) in 1994-95 in the United States before the bill was legally passed in 2013, which liberated and empowered LGBTQI teachers in the US educational settings (Jackson, 2009). Back in 1994-95, the senators asserted that ENDA would pose a moral threat to their youth. An exclusionary legislative action in the US parliament is not the only systematic attack on LGBTQI educators across the world. From novice to highly experienced, outed or in-closet, virtually all LGBTQI educators are assumed to face a form of explicit or implicit hatred, discrimination, or microaggression within the context of their workplace environment (e.g., Brett, 2022; Coleman, 2023; Conrad, 2019; Dykes & Delpont, 2018; Ewing et al., 2003; Ferfolja & Hopkins, 2013; Hooker, 2018; Khayatt & Iskander, 2019; Lineback et al., 2016; McCarthy, 2003; Samuel & Jonathan, 2019; Takatori and Ofuji, 2007; Wright et al., 2019). This being the case, research on LGBTQI educators so far has focused mainly on three predominant themes: (1) the

dichotomy of professional and personal identities of LGBTQI educators (Añonuevo & Digo, 2023; Coda, 2019; Gates, 2011; Gray, 2013; Gray et al., 2016; Haddad, 2019; Jackson, 2009; Llewellyn, 2022; Orlov & Allen, 2014; Rudoe, 2010; Thomas-Durrell, 2019); (2) lived workplace experiences of LGBTQI educators (Brockenbrough, 2012; deLeon & Brunner, 2012; Duarte, 2020; Hooker, 2018a; Lee, 2019a; Libed et al., 2010; Mizzi et al., 2021; Simons et al., 2021; Swanepoel, 2019; White et al., 2018); and (3) ideological discussions on LGBTQI educators (Bartone, 2023; Clark, 2010; Davies & Neustifter, 2021; Gorski et al., 2013; Johnson, 2014; Kahn & Gorski, 2016; Llewellyn & Reynolds, 2020; Mitton et al., 2021; Resnick & Galupo, 2018; Scandurra et al., 2017). Neither these exemplified studies nor this chapter particularly focus on the intersection of queerness and being a language educator. The scope of the reviewed literature in this study should be considered at the intersection of queerness and being an educator in general.

The majority of the research conducted on LGBTQI educators has taken identity discussions as their focal point, particularly centering narratives and perspectives of LGBTQI educators on their non-conforming identities being the main reason for their oppression. Studies conducted to investigate the ideological discussions around and the lived experiences of LGBTQI educators, focusing on continued and perpetuated socio-cultural and socio-political ideologies that exacerbate their experiences of oppression, have fallen short within the global academic context. This, in turn, has led to superficially repetitive discussions on the presence of LGBTQI educators.

In their systematic review of research on LGBTQI educators' experiences, Antonelli and Sembiente (2022) elaborately scrutinized a certain insufficient number of studies due to the unfortunate lack of attention to the topic in academia. However, it is also conceivable that studies dedicated to examining identity discussions on LGBTQI educators have preponderated compared to ideology-based and experience-based studies of the same population considering the fact that the primary concern of LGBTQI educators is their identity management within the context of their workspaces (Llewellyn, 2022).

2.1. Identity-Based Discussions

A good number of studies have been conducted in different contexts to explore the identity-related discourse on LGBTQI educators. In her study, Jackson (2009) investigated how K-12 gay and lesbian teachers in the US context intertwined their personal and professional identities, reflecting upon their classroom practices. Jackson (2009) found that the participants put queer pedagogy in practice (although the majority of them did not identify themselves as queer) additively to their curriculum. As Palmer (1998) also stated, teachers teach who they are. It is practically impossible to completely separate one's personal identity from their professional one. Therefore, LGBTQI educators are also highly likely to find themselves in the midst of a dichotomy that would challenge their integrity as individuals by forcing them to carefully abide by particular features of different personas created to be taken on in different contexts of their lives. Orlov and Allen (2014) asserted that LGBTQI faculty often experience a dilemma of whether or not to be open about their sexual identities in their academic contexts due to the fear of probable consequences they might face because of the prepotency of heterosexism. Similarly, O'Brien and Fassinger (1993) state that the most detrimental issue facing LGBTQI educators is probably the fear of disclosure and maintaining a dual identity. Along with the fear of disclosure, LGBTQI educators also face the fear of being 'trapped in the closet' (Jackson, 2006; as cited in Thomas-Durrell, 2019). They experience a state of fear of losing control of their personal and professional identities, wherein multiple extrinsic mental health challenges (Lee, 2019a) regarding their identity dynamics would easily emerge. In her recent study, Llewellyn (2022) found that LGBTQI teachers discern the dichotomy of their identity and are able to separate their personal identity from their professional one. In addition to that, Llewellyn (2022) also found that a new teacher subjectivity emerges in the process. Previous research (Connell, 2014; Llewellyn & Reynolds, 2021; Neary, 2013) demonstrated a conflict between LGBTQI teachers' personal and professional identities (Llewellyn, 2022). However, in the study conducted in the UK context in 2022, the participant teachers expressed a new subjectivity to their profession, which acknowledged and celebrated being a part of the LGBTQI community.

There are delicate dynamics of striking a balance between their personal and professional identities due to sociopolitical norms and circumstances for LGBTQI educators. Therefore, ‘coming out’ within the context of their professional settings inevitably becomes an issue of making a decision between abiding by the socially predetermined portrayal of a teacher that perpetuates the ideas of whom the profession is for and choosing to preserve their personal integrity while successfully developing a professional one. Gray (2013) investigated the ‘coming out’ decisions of four LGB teachers within their professional contexts and if a negotiation between their personal and professional identities was required in the process. Three main preferences of strategy were found to be utilized, i.e., not to come out at all, coming out to colleagues, and coming out to colleagues and students (Gray, 2013). Similarly, Rockhill (1993) argues that LGBTQI individuals face the risk of losing their home, circle of friends and family, and their community whenever they attempt to interrupt the mechanisms of heteronormativity (Gray, 2013) or speak up about their identities freely, which applies to educational settings, classrooms in particular, as well (as cited in Gray, 2013). Gray (2013) also found that the participants that were open about their sexuality at work expressed greater professional satisfaction and a seamless interconnectedness between their personal and professional identities. In a similar vein, Gates (2011) shares his own experience exploring the benefits of ‘coming out’ in the classroom as a social work educator. Throughout the process of exploring the advantages of being open about his sexuality within the professional educational context as workplace, Gates (2011) utilized Palmer’s framework (1998). The framework prompts educators to contemplate (1) revisiting the subjects that choose us; (2) moving towards identity and integrity; and (3) finding the teacher within, which are worthy of further attention (as cited in Gates, 2011). Gates examined that ‘coming out’ in the classroom brings personal and professional rewards to the individual such as honesty, wholeness, openness, and integrity. Parallely, ‘coming out’ is described as being honest and open about one’s LGBTQI sexual identity (Davies, 1992; Morrow, 2006). However, teaching who you are or as you are as an LGBTQI educator can get you fired (Lineback et al., 2016; Palmer, 1998). Therefore, it would not be fair to put the blame of perpetuated heteronormative and heterosexist sociopolitical dynamics on the LGBTQI educators who prefer concealing their sexual identities within the context of their workplace

environments. For those educators, this is often at the cost of weakening the dynamics of their individual identity for the sake of keeping their job.

According to the identity-based motivation (IBM) offered by Oyserman and Destin (2010), individuals tend to claim their identities in “identity-congruent” ways. This means that their identities would feel contextually natural. Considering LGBTQI educators are required to negotiate boundaries of their personal and professional identities (Gray, 2013; Hardie, 2012), enacting their identity in a way that is “identity-congruent” becomes even more difficult for them to achieve. Consequently, this failure might lead to undesired behavior and mental health challenges. Allen (1995) offers experiential insights into being an openly lesbian teacher in the classroom and teaching family pedagogy by practicing feminist and queer pedagogical approaches, which are considered to encourage self-disclosure and assist the students of LGBTQI teachers in navigating multiple subjectivities (Allen & Farnsworth, 1993; Thompson, 1992; Walker, 1993). In other words, Allen (1995) asserts that she taught who she was and as she was (Palmer, 1998) as a marginalized teacher by practicing feminist and queer pedagogies, which are not very visible in curricula (Fredman et al., 2013). That way, Allen claimed to have rendered the school environment to a less challenging context (Jackson, 2007) both for herself and her LGBTQI students. Allen successfully and enthusiastically practiced her profession as a teacher. This lends credence to the notion that LGBTQI educators frequently put in more effort to showcase their qualifications and professional abilities (Concordia et al., 2009). They experience a great deal of worry as they work to prove themselves as capable educators. A variety of mental health issues are also brought on by this effort (Rubio & Green, 2009).

Some other variables should also be taken into consideration while discussing LGBTQI educators’ identity presence and integrity within the context of their professional settings. Investigating the intersectionality of the personal and professional identities of a gay and a lesbian university teacher, Bennett et al. (2015) incorporated the consideration of acculturation and its interference in the process of outing their sexual identities in their culturally homogenous and cross-cultural classrooms. In their cross-cultural classrooms, they had students with diverse cultural

backgrounds. Bennett et al. (2015) found that the gay teacher was out about his sexual identity to all his students and colleagues, with whom he articulated to be culturally similar and from the same background. He also experienced some pedagogical benefits of ‘coming out’ (Willman, 2009) in his classrooms. The lesbian teacher presented herself as being in a heterosexual relationship in her cross-cultural classrooms. She stated that this did not significantly affect her teaching abilities but was challenging for her to reconcile (Bennett et al., 2015). However, this approach contradicts the idea of teaching and learning about diverse populations in multicultural educational settings (Rottmann, 2006). Coda (2019) also shares his experience of being stuck in a dilemma of choosing to ‘come out’ or to ‘stay in the closet’ when one of his students asked him about his roommate who actually was his same-sex partner. For fear of retaliation, he decided to stay ‘in the closet’. This decision draws attention to a mental health issue LGBTQI educators experience. It stems from the uneasiness and insecurity caused by balancing two identities in personal and professional lives, which is also linked to sociopolitical discrimination and microaggressions (Markow & Fein, 2005). Feeling of insecurity in workspaces might lead to lack of professional confidence and competence, considering educators should feel safe and acknowledged in order to provide their students with the best education (Wright, 2010). Leithwood and McAddie (2007) also found that a feeling of safeness leads to increased self-efficacy in educators. Although there is no one accepted definition of teacher well-being (McCallum et al., 2017), feeling of insecurity that leads to decreased professional self-efficacy can be classified as a factor that would have a detrimental effect on the well-being of teachers. Guijarro-Ojeda et al. (2021) investigated the interplay between queerness and teacher well-being of seven university foreign language teacher trainers and found that the participants’ psychological capital enabled them to turn this negativity into queer activism in their personal and professional lives. Within higher education contexts, the discrimination and microaggression that LGBTQI individuals, including educators, have been studied and observed to not be too different. Rey and Gibson (1997) investigated the discriminatory behaviors performed by college students against LGBTQI individuals and found that a total of 95% acknowledged engaging in discriminatory conduct, and 32.7% acknowledged performing actions against gay men and lesbians that were assessed to be at least mildly harmful (as cited in Ewing

et al., 2003). At the higher education level or else, outed or in the closet, practically all LGBTQI individuals, including educators, have been observed to experience various forms of violence, hatred, discrimination, or microaggression (Brett, 2022; Ferfolja & Hopkins, 2013; Grace & Benson, 2000; Lineback et al., 2016; Samuel & Jonathan, 2019) solely due to their gender and sexual identities. This contributes to the perpetuation of the sociopolitical status quo of the heteronormative and heteropatriarchal notions and their detrimental repercussions on individuals and society by forcing them deeper in the closet once and again. Duarte (2020), Haddad (2019), Hardie (2012), Hooker (2018a, 2018b), Lugg and Koschoreck (2003), McKenna-Buchanan et al. (2015), Neary (2013), Nielsen and Alderson (2014), Takatori and Ofuji (2007) scrutinized inestimable lived experiences of LGBTQI educators regarding their quandary of choosing to ‘hide in the closet’ or to ‘come out’ within their professional workspaces. Whether choosing to stay ‘in the closet’ or to ‘come out’, or contemplating how to do either, the well-being and the key psychological traits of LGBTQI educators are destabilized (Guijarro-Ojeda et al., 2021) at work. This might bring forth various forms of mental health challenges, considering these educators endeavor to restabilize their well-being by trying to reorientate and maintain their individual integrity in clutches of forcibly dichotomized identity dynamics.

For novice teachers, first-year teachers in particular, the aforementioned phases are even more difficult to go through compared to their experienced colleagues. The shock that almost all first-year teachers experience in the real professional teaching settings is undeniable (Le Maistre & Pare, 2010; Riches & Benson, 2010) even though teacher education programs (TEPs) seek to provide their student teachers (STs) with solid foundational and theoretical knowledge of the profession (Benson et al., 2014). Cherubini (2009) also pointed out that teachers expressed a feeling of disillusionment with their TEPs, characterizing the transition from program to field as abrupt. For LGBTQI first-year teachers, this state of consternation is observed at a higher level compared to their cisgender heterosexual peers (Benson, 2008; Meyer, 2007). Stiegler (2008) examined how TEPs failed to satisfy the expectancy of addressing LGBTQI STs’ identity discussions as well. Similarly, Benson et al. (2014) investigated the transition process from program to field for LGBTQI STs

and the favorable impact of the workshops they designed for those STs in the TEP to ease the transition process for them. In her master's thesis at Brock University, Fleet (2016) also explored the feelings and opinions of LGBTQI STs in an Initial Teacher Education Program (ITEP) and found that the complexity of the queer teacher candidates' experience; the separation of personal and professional identity; silencing; and shame (Fleet, 2016) emerged as four main themes in her study, which attest the difficulties LGBTQI STs experience from TEPs to field (Benson et al., 2014). In a similar vein, Russell (2021) investigated the 'borderland' of Australian LGBTQI STs, and DeJean and Sapp (2010) noted that not enough had been discussed regarding LGBTQI STs' identities and experiences.

Varied approaches have been adopted by scholars to address the issue of LGBTQI educators. Meyer et al. (2015) conducted a comparative study on the perspectives of LGB and straight educators on the notion of gender and sexual diversity (GSD). Lee (2020) also approached the issue of the presence of LGBTQI educators within the context of professional educational settings and discussed why they would make exceptional school leaders. Moreover, Brady (2022) incorporated the issue of being an LGBTQI educator into a new context by providing experiential reflections upon how he navigated the intersectionality of belonging with the LGBTQI community as an international teacher, heteronormative notions and mechanisms, and racial bias. Laplante (2023) investigated how LGBTQI teachers navigated their personal and professional identities in her master's thesis at McGill University and found that LGBTQI teachers feel more promoted with regard to their identities in settings that provide them with resources for students, a supportive community, and professional development opportunities. Likewise, in his master's thesis at the University of Calgary, Anderson (2020) scrutinized the issue of enacting and performing an LGBTQI teacher identity in reprisal for conceptualization of the teaching profession that prescribe the visibility of queerness within contexts of professional educational settings as conflicting with the neutral subjectivity that teachers are expected to maintain. In Lawrence and Nagashima's (2019) duo-ethnographic study to explore the intersectionality of gender, sexuality, race, and native-speaker-ness in ELT teacher identity, Nagashima addresses her sexual orientation as a 'hidden identity' (Vandrick, 1997) within her professional context. This is rather scrutable considering

the great number of possible outcomes LGBTQI teachers might face depending on how open they are about their sexual identities with their students and colleagues (Haddad, 2019). In a similar vein, out of the five strategies McKenna-Buchanan et al. (2015) found that LGBTQI educators adopted to disclose or conceal their personal identities within their professional workspaces, ‘ambiguity’, ‘deflection’, and ‘avoidance’ became prominent. This aligns with the prevalence of the binary and heteronormative suppositions of gender and sexuality (Erickson-Schroth & Mitchell, 2009). The teacher participants that chose to disclose their identities by ‘selection’ or ‘reciprocity’ were observed to speak implicitly or explicitly against continuing heteronormativity, heteropatriarchy, or standardization and calibration of any particular form of heterosexuality (Epstein, 2017). In another recent testimonio-based duo-ethnographic study, Riquelme-Sanderson and Longoria (2023) explored their LGBTQI teacher identities and pedagogies as well. LGBTQI educators’ lectures have also been observed to be evaluated more negatively by their students when compared to their colleagues of unspecified sexual orientation (Ewing et al., 2003). This also attests the validity of their fear of being viewed unfavorably by students, colleagues, and administrators (Russ, Simonds, & Hunt, 2002). Henderson (2017) noted that the fear in LGBTQI teachers does not only include the dilemma of hiding or disclosing their sexual identities at their workplace, but it also concerns how they perceive the intersectionality of their own personal and professional identities. Similarly, Russell (2010) also explored how LGBTQI teachers dealt with an ethical dilemma. They faced a choice between maintaining the idea of children as innocent and LGBTQI as a societal threat or openly expressing their identities. By doing so, they could serve as role models for their students (Campbell, 2003; İpekçi, 2022). While LGBTQI teachers constantly find themselves between the devil and the deep blue sea regarding their multiple identities (McNair, 2017), their own perceptions of this delicate dichotomy (Russell, 2010), and the decisions they are socio-politically obliged to make, they are also deemed more likely to face sexual assault accusations by their students (Piper & Sikes, 2010). This compels them to tolerate frequent encounters with LGBTQI-phobic harassment and experience a feeling of anxiety when bringing up LGBTQI-related issues and topics to their students (Conrad, 2019), which contributes to the perpetuation of their silenced and damaged queer teacher identity (Coleman, 2023). Studying the identity management of six lesbian teachers

practicing in London secondary schools, Rudoie (2010) found that the intentional silencing of LGBTQI educators within their workspace contexts leads to an absence of ‘role models’ for queer youth to feel acknowledged and cherished. Approaching the issue of LGBTQI teacher identity from a different perspective, O’Loughlin (2019) retrospectively explores her own experience as a queer teacher and affirms the connection between racialization, sexual orientation, and coloniality in the heteronormative United States schooling system, wherein institutional heterosexuality (Epstein & Johnson, 1994) predominates. Ultimately, valuable insights into non-conforming LGBTQI identities of educators can be gained from the identity-based research that is presently available and primarily focused on the Global North. Contextual evaluation of studies demonstrate that the scope of the present scholarly discourse on the matter is currently constrained by this geographic imbalance. This limitation also indicates that voices with diverse narratives from the Global South continue to be underrepresented.

2.2. Ideology-Based Discussions

Research so far has examined the identities of LGBTQI educators in professional workspaces from various perspectives, mainly focusing on their identity disempowerment (Saxey, 2020) largely caused by heteropatriarchal systems and heteronormative stereotypes (Moore, 2021). However, there is still a dearth of scholarly interest in the ideological discussions on the presence of LGBTQI educators (Bartone, 2023) considering the number of studies carried out to scrutinize it. Studies conducted to investigate LGBTQI students’ identity management with regard to confronting heteronormativity and socially constructed heteropatriarchal mechanisms (Murphy, 2012; Patterson, 2013; Warner, 1991; as cited in Steck & Perry, 2016) in school settings have preponderated (Evans et al., 2017; Steck & Perry, 2017a; Ueno, 2023; Walker & Goings, 2018). However, studies conducted to investigate similar issues regarding LGBTQI educators (Bartone, 2023; Johnson, 2023) have not been available in sufficient amounts.

Llewellyn and Reynolds, (2021) explored dominant heteronormative discourses in school settings and the dichotomous positioning of LGB teachers with regard to

'hiding in the closet' or 'coming out'. They noted that the 'coming out' pressure on LGB teachers relate more to the ideological absence of their identities in school settings than the identities being 'different'. Under the guide of the notion of teacher exemplar (DeMitchell et al., 2009), numerous LGBTQI educators are deemed to have been dismissed from their jobs. Accordingly, this has gradually diffilicated the ways of combating LGBTQI-phobia and heterosexism (Kumashiro et al., 2004) in school settings. In her teaching note, Johnson (2014) scrutinized her experiential insights into how LGBTQI social work educators handled intentional or unintentional heterosexist impositions and microaggressions performed by their students. Such actions and practices compel LGBTQI educators to separate their personal and professional identities strictly (Ferfolja & Hopkins, 2013). Recently, Coda (2023) probed into how LGBTQI Spanish language teachers practiced their profession to challenge the privileging of heterosexuality through its normalization (Jackson, 2006) and noted that the teacher participants utilized the culture of the target language to problematize heteronormativity in their classroom settings. In their examination of the absence of problematic heterosexist and homophobic LGBTQI concerns in the U.S multicultural teacher education coursework, Gorski et al. (2013) found that LGBTQI issues are frequently ignored. That way, heteronormative patriarchal spaces are perpetuated for students to express their LGBTQI-phobia, which Johnson (2014) noted they perform most via their written assignments to which teachers cannot immediately react. In a similar vein, Evans (1999) discussed the reproduction and perpetuation of heteronormativity in schools as a result of homosexual repression (Pinar, 1994).

Reproduction and perpetuation of LGBTQI-phobic ideologies and compulsory heteropatriarchy (Rich, 2003), which facilitates spaces for microaggression against the LGBTQI community in their workspaces (Resnick & Galupo, 2018), is at least as much dangerous as explicitly expressed and performed LGBTQI-phobia itself. This is also applicable to the teaching profession, many of whose norms are heteronormative (Gray, 2013) in workspaces. Particularly novice LGBTQI teachers are often rather delicate and unprovided in terms of performing the profession they were trained for in such spaces. It is of great importance for teacher educators to provide their STs with safe (anti-phobic) learning environments (Cosier, 2016;

Dykes & Delport, 2018) when they are still in their programs. All novice teachers are already in their own 'sink-or-swim' situation (Varah et al., 1986). LGBTQI novice teachers have often been observed to 'sink' due to conventionally perpetuated heteropatriarchal ideologies predominating within workplace contexts, wherein practically all educators are assumed to be cis-heterosexual unless they disclose their LGBTQI identity (Bower-Phipps, 2020). Such presuppositions have been observed to be detrimental to the notion of 'queer thinking' (Nelson, 2020) and contribute to the loop of continual psychological violence (Grace & Wells, 2006) facing LGBTQI educators at their workspaces. Scandurra et al. (2017) studied 438 STs in terms of their stance on homophobia and transphobia relating it to sociodemographic features of the context and noted that cis-male heterosexuality and political conservatism were found to be positively correlated to homophobia and transphobia. This attests the discussions of Cosier (2016) and Dykes and Delport (2018) on the poorness of TEPs in terms of being inclusive and educational regarding concerns and presence of LGBTQI STs. Clark (2010) also investigated a U.S.-based TEP and noted the ST participants' concerns regarding possible future heterosexist and homophobic work environments (Bower-Phipps, 2020).

Repetitively discussed along with workspaces, the notion of heterosexism has sparked off another LGBTQI concern, heteroprofessionalism, i.e., heteronormative version of professionalism that is a pushback against anti-discrimination policies (Mizzi, 2013). Recently, Davies and Neustifter (2021) investigated the concept of heteroprofessionalism in academia. Heteroprofessionalism was noted to regulate sexual diversity at workspaces, which demonstrated the importance of this newly emerging ideological term for LGBTQI educators as well. In his dissertation at North-West University, Beer (2020) explored the workplace experiences of LGBTQI teachers in the South African context, focusing on heterosexism. He highlighted their lived experiences, underscoring the need to address heteroprofessionalism in all school settings. LGBTQI educators in heteronormative schools often experience a multifaceted sense of fear (DePalma & Atkinson, 2010; Hooker, 2018a). The identity and ideology of LGBTQI educators in schools have been the subject of numerous studies, yet they are still underrepresented in scholarly research. Navigating their sexual identities at work is challenging due to the many obstacles they face in their

career paths (Herek, 2004; MacGillivray, 2008). Unlike their cis-het colleagues, LGBTQI educators often face fear of openness regarding their sexual identities and family lives (Rumens & Kerfoot, 2009; Williams & Giuffre, 2011), which is a challenge seldom experienced by others (DePalma & Atkinson, 2010). As noted by Ferfolja and Stavrou (2015) as well, the issue of enacting sexual subjectivity at work, wherein they historically have experienced ‘silencing’ and ‘discrimination’, is ongoing for LGBTQI educators. In a similar vein, Swanepoel (2019) drew upon his own experiences as a gay male teacher within the South African context and highlighted that he took hold on the ideological presence of his gay identity at work by upholding his personal values of inclusivity although he was confronted with numerous challenges of bias and prejudice. According to the comparative results of the National Survey of Educators’ Perceptions of School Climate conducted in 2007 and 2011 in the U.S context, presented by Wright and Smith (2015), it was reported that a great number of critical factors pertaining to providing LGBTQI educators with support either remained unchanged or even worsened. In another study in the U.S context, Brockenbrough (2012) took into consideration the intersection of race and sexual identity by interrogating possible affordances of ‘hiding in the closet’ for black queer male teachers. It was concluded that ‘the closet’ served as a shelter for black queer male teachers to adopt various pedagogical agendas. With such agendas, they could perform as anti-phobic agents of change. Hiding was also reported to provide them with protection within the context of phobic environments (Brockenbrough, 2012).

Libed et al. (2010) scrutinized the chronicle erasure of LG teachers from the educational settings of the U.S by means of interpersonal and institutional discrimination at workspaces (Irwin, 1999, 2002). Such experiences are deemed to cause the LGBTQI educators’ well-being to diminish considering how important lived experiences are to people as conscious human beings (Creswell, 1998). The impact of school climate on teachers’ well-being was also explored by Petegem et al. (2005) in general manner regarding a demographically wider population; their findings highlighted the pivotal role that an accepting school climate plays in the process of fostering teachers’ well-being. They observed that educators’ general well-being and professional satisfaction are positively influenced when they believe that

their workspace has an encouraging and inclusive atmosphere. Even though they are globally few in number, there are also such educational institutions as described (2015) wherein heterosexuality is not to be celebrated and rewarded (Foucault, 1978) and non-heterosexual individuals, including educators, are also valued and cherished. As a case in point, within the Southeast England context, White et al. (2018) examined the experiences of LGB students and staff at a Further Education college and noted that none of the 15 LGB students or 9 staff had either experienced or witnessed overt LGBTQI-phobia. However, this is unfortunately rarely the case for LGBTQI educators across the world. More often, they have been observed to articulate experiences of harassment and undervaluation (Wardle, 2009) stemming from cisheterosexuality being regarded as natural, normal, and fixed and heterosexism being historically omnipresent in schooling cultures (Ferfolja & Stavrou, 2015).

2.3. Experience-Based Discussions

Mizzi et al. (2021) investigated the experiences of 23 Western LGBTQI teachers practicing in non-Western educational contexts (e.g., Southeast Asia, The Caribbean, Eastern Europe, Japan) and highlighted four themes regarding how they navigated their challenging experiences as LGBTQI international educators; (1) shifting identities; (2) seeking to belong; (3) strong work ethic as personal security; and (4) LGBTQ initiatives and student engagement. Targeting a mildly different population with a similar purpose, deLeon and Brunner (2012) explored the lived experiences of lesbian and gay educational leaders and generated a model named Cycles of Fear. The fear in the LG educational leader participants was observed to range from severe physiological and/or psychological impacts to powerful, positive outcomes. This exploration also attests that LGBTQI educators are compelled to put much effort in processing the workplace challenges they face and the emotions resulting from them in order to thrive in their profession. Otherwise, they get punished through marginalization, harassment, and discrimination (Foucault, 1978). Although the LGBTQI community is still considered a taboo to study in educational settings (Duke, 2007), decades ago, Irwin (2002) delved into the data of the workplace experiences of 120 LGT individuals working in education (teachers, academics,

educators) drawn from a larger project investigating 900 individuals of the same population. Irwin (2002) suggests that it is employers' responsibility to ensure that their employees are protected from any sort of discrimination, hatred, microaggression, or phobia so that the hetero-privilege (deLeon & Brunner, 2012) predominating in professional educational settings shall be subjugated. That way, with the assistance of a top-down approach, LGBTQI-phobia might get stigmatized (McCormack, 2014) instead of the LGBTQI identities themselves. Likewise, Simons et al. (2021) thoroughly interrogated 24 LGB educators (teachers, mentors, and coaches) and highlighted how the educator participants considered their professions highly related to the whole community in a way that confirms the notion of educators being role-models to the overall social community (Graves, 2009). Socio-politically, however, LGBTQI educators have a long history of institutionalized oppression within the context of educational settings around the globe.

Section 28 of the Local Government Act in England stated that 'A local authority (including educators) shall not (a) intentionally promote homosexuality (b) promote the teaching in any maintained school of the acceptability of homosexuality as a pretended family relationship'. This positioned non-cis-heterosexual-identifying teachers in a situation where they were perceived as patients and sufferers (Ellis, 2007). Lee (2019a) argues that the teachers practicing within the time span of Section 28's validity in England until 2003 are still 'deeply affected' by their experiences regarding the enactment of their personal identities at their professional workspaces (Stones & Glazzard, 2020). Just like those sampled in Lee's (2019b) study, numerous LGBTQI educators all over the world make compelling concessions on the integrity of their individual identities on the purpose of promoting an idealized teacher-self (Kitching, 2009) that is socio-politically set and institutionally projected. Nonetheless, LGBTQI teachers have never been observed to be fully acknowledged and celebrated let alone idealized in terms of simply being fit for their profession. Intentionally or unintentionally, school administrators have also been observed to contribute to the perpetuation of schools as institutionalized heteropatriarchal workspaces (Rottmann, 2006) by performing direct LGBTQI-phobic practices or colluding with such of those by not vigorously challenging them (Irwin, 2002). Roberts et al. (2007) explored the experiences of two transgender teachers with

regard to the intersectionality of their transitioning and workplace experiences with all other stakeholders. They noted that one of the teacher participants was subjected to inappropriate behavior by his principle, who desired to disemploy him as he did not fit her idealization (Kitching, 2009) of an appropriately ordinary teacher anymore. Approaching the issue of LGBTQI teacher experience rather interestingly, Neary et al. (2017) probed into the dynamics between 15 LGB teachers and the stakeholders while entering a civil partnership (CP). Neary (2017) highlighted that legal structures of an LGBTQI teacher's romantic relationship does not have an overt impact on how they are perceived and treated by the stakeholders, who opt for contributing to the persistent conservatism of schools and their function as identity gatekeepers in the professional lives of sexually diverse teachers (Ferfolja & Stavrou, 2015). Against this attempt of gradual erasure from professional educational settings, LGBTQI educators often remain silent with fear of dismissal just because of their sexual identification (Eckes & McCarthy, 2008). That way, their invisibility is perpetuated, and their experiences as literate and highly educated people remain hidden (Reinharz & Davidman, 1992).

School administrators are not the only cause of this silence and oppression. Students as another face of educational stakeholders contribute to the perpetuation of the ideological oppression of LGBTQI identities (Vefikuluçay Yılmaz et al., 2022). William Gust (2007) drew upon his experiential insights on his autoethnographic study that scrutinizes the reflections of a gay teacher. He highlighted the intersectional importance of gay male teachers' outness and cis-heterosexual male students' stance on it that emits hegemonic masculinity (Nixon & Givens, 2011) and heteropatriarchal normativity. On the other hand, Macgillivray (2008) argues that his students gradually became accepting and welcoming of his openly gay teacher identity, and the situation did not cause any of his cis-heterosexual students to question their own sexual identity (Rofes, 2000). In addition to that, Macgillivray's LGBTQI-identifying students were observed to express their state of comfort thanks to having an openly gay teacher, which goes against the socially constructed discourse of minors as innocent and unknowing (Walls et al., 2013) as well. However, the preponderance of the studies carried out to investigate the 'coming out' experiences of LGBTQI educators have addressed fear and risk (Takatori & Ofuji,

2007). Let alone ‘coming out’, it is deemed that even bringing up LGBTQI concerns or tackling LGBTQI-phobia within the context of their workspaces puts teachers at risk of microaggression and criticism from parents, colleagues, students, and administrators (Ferfolja & Stavrou, 2015). Ullman (2020) studied 44 gender and sexuality diverse (GSD) educators’ experiences of discrimination and accentuated the relationship between individual encounters of discrimination and a diminished perception of well-being. In his study carried out to explore the retrospective reflections of 6 LGBTQI teachers across the U.S on their past professional experiences, Jr. (2020) remarks the participant teachers’ hesitation to fully express their genuine identities in all of their classroom settings. He also underscores that many critical workplace concerns of LGBTQI educators remain unchanged despite the increased number of discussions put forth to draw implicative conclusions regarding their presence and well-being in the workplace. Given the many challenges they face, it is crucial for LGBTQI novice teachers and STs to see changes in professional education. This can be achieved through practical insights from research on these issues, focusing on STs, novice educators, and TEPs. There is fortunately an increasing number in studies regarding such issues. Dykes and Delport (2018), Maher and Toledo (2021) and Manimtim et al. (2022) present their identity-based, ideology-based, and experience-based discussions on LGBTQI pre-service teachers and TEPs. In addition, Cutler (2023) and Tompkins et al. (2019b) explored the experiences of novice LGBTQI teachers in a way that may facilitate the process for queer individuals who are considering entering the teaching profession (Jr., 2020).

Samuel and Jonathan (2019) and Lineback et al. (2016) drew on Meyer’s (2003) Minority Stress Model and examined LGBTQI educators’ workplace experiences. It is underscored that the lived experiences of LGBTQI educators may also be influenced by the viewpoints of school administrators, the overall school environment, and their religious affiliations. Similarly, Davis (2023), Epstein (2017), Macgillivray (2008), and Neary et al. (2017) also discussed the intersectionality of religious affiliations and queer identity in educational contexts. Either due to religious issues or institutionalized heteropatriarchal mechanisms, LGBTQI educators are observed to have been disregarded within the context of professional educational settings. Accordingly, very few students so far have been taught by queer educators (Lundin,

2016) compared to cisheterosexual educators. Those who find permanent job opportunities in teaching persist in facing difficulties and limitations. Thus, they choose to ‘stay in the closet’ (Ferfolja & Hopkins, 2013) and not promote LGBTQI concerns (Neary, 2013). Recently, Cui (2022) explored the strategies employed by closeted gay academics in handling LGBTQI-related matters in China. It was underscored that the university contexts in China are constructed rather heteronormatively. This construction was noted to constraint LGBTQI-related discussions and outed LGBTQI educator identities. The perpetuated hegemony of heteropatriarchal, cis-heteronormative, and hetero-professional ideologies in professional educational settings damages the queer identities of LGBTQI educators (Coleman, 2023). It forces them to navigate socio-politically dichotomous identity dynamics and compels them to stay silent ‘in the closet’ (Duarte, 2020) despite the imperative to come out to be role-models to the queer youth (Russell et al., 2014). Correspondingly, Brett (2022), Khayatt and Iskander (2019), and Takatori and Ofuji (2007) reflect on the few affordances and numerous challenges of coming out and being visible in the classroom as LGBTQI educators in different contexts.

Considering the hegemonic masculinity (Nixon & Givens, 2011) of particularly male students and how it attributes characteristics and features to a ‘real man’ (Carian et al., 2022) that a male LGBTQI-identifying educator is also compelled to abide by to avoid negative evaluation by their students (Ewing et al., 2003), it might become even more difficult for gay male educators to safely disclose their identity (Lu et al., 2018) compared to closeted lesbian educators. This is also related to the socio-politically constructed and prevalently accepted and practiced discourse of ‘feminine inferiority’ and ‘masculine superiority’ (Hoskin, 2020). These ideas suggest that women are not attributed any features to secure. However, if a man practices a little non-assertiveness or direct femininity, he is not deemed a ‘real man’ anymore and should be degraded and devalued because of how he depreciates ‘superior masculinity’ with his practices of effeminacy. However, this presupposition is questionably not the case for all female-appearing LGBTQI educators around the world. Bridgman (2012), Hardie (2012), and Nielsen and Alderson (2014) demonstrated the assumption that being ‘outed’ at the workplace is relatively easier for lesbian educators is apocryphal. By reviewing the previous contextual literature

in a similar vein, Ferfolja (2009) suggests that it is at least as challenging for lesbian educators (Ferfolja, 2003, 2005, 2007, 2008; Neary et al., 2017) as other LGBTQI-identifying educators to claim the integrity of their identities by enacting their personal identities within the context of their workspaces and merging their identity dichotomy into a united self (Stones & Glazzard, 2020). For LGBTQI educators, managing the duality of their intrapersonal identity dynamics, such as deciding whether to stay in the closet or come out at work, has not been observed to be an easy task (Conrad, 2019; McCarthy, 2003; Wright et al., 2019). This is due to socio-political power dynamics and societal norms surrounding gender and sexual diversity, which reinforce the marginalization of LGBTQI educators and curricula in professional educational institutions that adhere to cis-heteronormative standards (Conrad, 2019; Dykes & Delpont, 2018).

In opposition to the existing ‘victimizing’ (Stones & Glazzard, 2020) literature, on the other hand, Stones and Glazzard (2020) researched the upsides of practicing as LGBTQI educators. They examined 4 gay teachers practicing in the British context and underscored numerous positive accounts and narratives of being a gay practitioner in that particular context. However, studies highlighting the affordances of practicing as LGBTQI educators in school environments (Haddad, 2019; Hooker, 2018), wherein they are compelled to negotiate their sexual orientation (Dykes & Delpont, 2018; Hooker, 2018) and personal and professional selves (Meyer & Ouellette, 2009), could still be counted on the fingers of one hand. Particularly regarding transgender educators, the amount of research in the literature is too sparse. This might be due to the lack of attention transgender individuals have been historically observed to get in various contexts (Simon, 2003) as highly stigmatized individuals (Gagne & Tewksbury, 1998). Let alone the educational contexts, the level of oppression facing transgender individuals in general society is insufferable (Catalano & Griffin, 2016). For the first time ever in the literature, McCarthy (2003) investigated a transgender teacher, Kelly, used as a pseudonym due to the participant’s fear of reprisal, who was a 33-year-old, white, female-bodied English teacher that identified as transgender and was practicing in a high school in the U.S context. McCarthy (2003) noted invaluable experiential insights into how Kelly navigated her (pronoun opted for to address the participant in the study itself)

personal and professional identities and workplace experiences. Likewise, Jaekel and Nicolazzo (2020), as two trans and critical educators, recently investigated 10 trans and gender non-conforming educators in higher education. Three main themes; (1) pedagogical (dis)embodiments of gender, (2) resistance about and to trans, and (3) the labor of trans faculty, were underlined. This highlighted the need for further research on transgender and gender non-conforming educators. The complexity of expressing a trans identity in roles of authority (e.g., teachers, academics, administrators) and the limited understanding of their workplace experiences (McCarthy, 2003; Roberts et al., 2007) make it difficult to promote their visibility (National Gay & Lesbian Task Force, 1991) and improve their working conditions.

Practically all these challenges of LGBTQI educators mentioned in the literature so far also relate to the concept of structuralism, which refer to how societal norms are (re)produced and (re)enforced through the social construction of systems and structures (Giddens, 1984). Institutionally cis-heteronormative school systems (DePalma & Atkinson, 2010) and socio-politically constructed cis-heteropatriarchal educational structures promote the perpetuation of such challenges of LGBTQI educators. Cis-heteronormative curricula, as perfect agents in cis-heteronormative educational systems, have been observed to partake in the aforementioned processes of perpetuating LGBTQI educators' professional workplace challenges. Despite the concise investigation into the content and delivery of LGBTQI-informed curricula (Meyer et al., 2019), studies carried out to examine the discourse of queering curricula have also fallen into the literature (Finn et al., 2021; Morris, 1998; Steck & Perry, 2017b; Suárez et al., 2019). Alongside cis-heteronormative curricula embedded in virtually all schooling systems across the globe and socio-politically promoted to be practiced and abided by, a great number of other heteropatriarchal mechanisms and structures play pivotal roles as extrinsic factors in shaping the challenging workplace experiences (Mizzi et al., 2021) of LGBTQI educators.

2.4. The Turkish Context

As discussions delving into such factors have become repetitive in the literature lately, umpteen of the issues remain practically uncharted. Particularly in Eastern

contexts (e.g. Asian, Mediterranean, Arabic, African), let alone LGBTQI educators, LGBTQI issues and concerns have scarcely been problematized within scholarly domain. The preponderance of the studies carried out to investigate LGBTQI educators' identity management and experiences has predominantly been based in the context of the United States (Brockenbrough, 2012; Gates, 2011; Harbeck, 1992; Jennings, 1994; Libed et al., 2010) and the United Kingdom (DePalma & Atkinson, 2010; Gray, 2013; Nixon & Givens, 2002; Rudoe, 2010) so far. Additionally, the Irish, Canadian, and Australian academic milieus have also been calling attention to such matters lately (Boulay et al., 2020; Callaghan, 2015; Callaghan & van Leent, 2019; Gray et al., 2016; Horgan, 2020; Neary, 2013; Tompkins et al., 2019b; Wells, 2017). However, no more than a handful of studies (İpekçi, 2022; Taşkın et al., 2022) have been conducted in the Turkish educational context in order to explore the intersectionality of personal and professional identities, add to the ideological discussions, or shed light to contextual experiential insights of LGBTQI educators. Concerning LGBTQI issues in general, an escalating quantity of scholarly investigations within the Turkish context (Aslan et al., 2019; Ayhan Balik & Bilgin, 2019; Biçmen & Bekiroğulları, 2014; Engin, 2015; Keleş et al., 2018; Soner & Altay, 2020; Soyer et al., 2023) has been presented lately. Practically all these examinations have added to the discussion that LGBTQI-related matters within the Turkish contexts still remains a taboo (Ördem & Ulum, 2020). Additionally, Akgül and Güneş (2023), Göçmen and Yılmaz (2017), İncekara and Ulaş (2023), Özeren (2014), Özeren et al. (2016), Ulaş-Kılıç et al. (2019), and Yılmaz and Göçmen (2016) delved into the workplace dynamics of individuals identifying within the LGBTQI spectrum, scrutinizing their multifaceted identity management and professional experiences. Although none of them elaborated on the teaching profession, it was noted in all these examinations that identifying as an LGBTQI within the Turkish context and navigating your workplace dynamics while endeavoring to claim your identity integrity by enacting both your personal and professional identities is exceedingly challenging (Özeren et al., 2016). This might be due to several socio-politically constructed institutionalized ideologies from statutory cis-heteropatriarchy (Baars, 2019) to undercover hetero-professionalism (Mizzi, 2013). Concentrating particularly on the professional milieu of LGBTQI-identifying educators practicing in Turkey, wherein heteronormative school

mechanisms (Hooker, 2018a) predominate, Taşkın et al. (2022) investigated challenges facing 12 LGBTQI educators in their inestimable study. Participants ranged from teachers at schools to scholars at universities in terms of profession. They self-identified as “trans, lesbian, queer, gay stable, gay-dominated bisexual, bisexual, gay, homosexual man” in terms of sexual identity. Two of them were practicing in public educational institutions whereas the remainder were practicing in private educational institutions. Facilitated by a semi-structured interview, it was found in their study that while the majority of the participants believed their sexual orientation was recognized, several withheld it by virtue of concerns about negative consequences. Additionally, some articulated to have openly declared their identities by dint of institutional support. Participants reported a mix of positive experiences, such as supporting students, and negative ones, including exposure to homophobic language and job loss. It was also noted that the coping strategies of the participants varied from individual approaches to activism. In a similar vein, İpekçi (2022) amalgamated the lived experiences of queer teachers in İstanbul with ideology-based discussions regarding heteronormativity and neoliberal school policies. Investigating 5 queer teachers based and practicing in İstanbul, İpekçi (2022) probed into how neoliberal school policies and mechanisms impacted their professional experiences. The challenge of navigating societal expectations with the burden of setting heteronormative examples is underscored in the study. It is also noted that the queer teachers in the particular context operate within a repressive "Don't Ask, Don't Tell" system, facing arduousness regarding embracing their politicized sexual subjectivities. İpekçi (2022) also highlighted that, feeling compelled to be advocates of their personal identities within the context of their workplaces in order to uphold effective role modeling (Campbell, 2003), plethora of queer teachers eventually prefer changing careers on account of the perceived impossibility of enacting their sexual subjectivities within extant coercion. Although there are still numerous governments around the globe that criminalize the mere existence of LGBTQI community through various enforcements (Kavanagh et al., 2025), Turkish law does not legally criminalize LGBTQI identities (Göçmen & Yılmaz, 2017), and EĞİTİM SEN (Education and Science Workers' Union) included “sexual orientation and gender identity” in its 2014 covenant to protect the rights of all (Taşkın et al., 2022). Despite that, LGBTQI-related issues, including educators, are still largely excluded

from the Turkish educational context (Acar, 2023). Queerness is often portrayed as sinful, deviant, and disgusting (Basaran, 2003; Sakallı & Uğurlu, 2002). The volume of scholarly investigations related to the intersection of the Turkish educational context and LGBTQI-associated matters (Aker et al., 2023; Güney, 2021a, 2021b, 2023; Mert-Karadaş et al., 2023; Ördem & Ulum, 2020; Özbay & Candan, 2023; Sakallı & Uğurlu, 2002; Saraç & McCullick, 2015; Selvi & Kocaman, 2020) has also been relatively limited. One prevalent implication from practically all these examinations has been the highlight on the lack of LGBTQI representation (Selvi & Kocaman, 2020) and the challenges confronting the LGBTQI individuals within the Turkish educational context (Saraç & McCullick, 2015). It is also highly important to note that such challenges strongly pertain to the political representation of the LGBTQI community in the Turkish context. The very continued influence of conventional ideologies and values on policymaking in the Turkish context has been reinforcing and perpetuating the marginalization of non-conforming gender and sexual identities, which expressly underscores an imbalance between the country's secular foundations and internationally recognized human rights standards (Engin, 2015).

2.5. The Niche

The quantity of scholarly examinations investigating the presence of LGBTQI educators on the basis of identity, ideology, and experience discussions has globally been augmented particularly in the last decade (Antonelli & Sembiente, 2022). Many researchers across the globe have studied the intersectionality of LGBTQI educators' personal and professional identities, delved into delicate ideological discussions revolving around their presence, and explored their workplace experiences within various educational contexts. Practically in all studies incorporated, occupational challenges of LGBTQI educators have been underscored. However, too few studies have been carried out to scrutinize the convergent nature of all these parameters. In this respect, scholarly documented life stories of LGBTQI educators remain limited (Cantos et al., 2023), despite their importance in exposing realities historically silenced. These stories shed light on how LGBTQI educators enact and manage their identities within cis-heteronormative and cis-heteropatriarchal educational settings,

wherein such ideologies are often (re)produced (Ferfolja & Robinson, 2004; Gray, 2013).

It is still notable that a multifaceted exploration has characterized the global academic discourse on LGBTQI educators. Hereby, a complex matter that manifests across intertwined dimensions has been scholarly delineated. Either published, in publication process, or unpublished – including master’s theses and PhD dissertations, the extant body of the literature on the presence of LGBTQI educators has conspicuously emphasized the facets of identity management, enactment, and disclosure (Orlov & Allen, 2014). Such studies have provided insightful examinations into the intricate interplay between the personal and professional identities of LGBTQI educators. A considerable corpus of research has concurrently undertaken fervent ideological discussions with regard to how LGBTQI educators claim spaces and navigate their workplace experiences within educational contexts that are prototyped and idealized by socio-politically constructed tenets of ideologies. To the full extent of their power, such examinations have dissected aforementioned prevalent constructs such as cis-heteronormativity (Warner, 1991) and cis-hetero-professionalism (Davies & Neustifter, 2021). Over time, this focus has significantly deepened our understanding of the challenging and often restrictive environment that LGBTQI educators face in their professional lives.

Nevertheless, critically reflecting on the prevailing scholarly discourse, a salient gap emerges. This niche in the relevant literature demands consideration and intervention within the discourse of academia. It pertains to the lack of thorough scrutinization that would comprehensively consider the substantial confluence of all three of the previously mentioned multifaceted dimensions of enacting an LGBTQI educator persona. Although isolated discussions on the identity enactment, negotiation, and management, ideological challenges, and workplace experiences of LGBTQI educators have deftly been captured by the extant research on a global scale (Antonelli & Sembiente, 2022), a pronounced dearth of inquiries meticulously conflating these dimensions into a cohesive domain persists. Such paucity of research tackling the intricate union of identity management, ideological deliberation, and experiential workplace dynamics of LGBTQI educators signifies a

hiatus within the scholarly discourse. An incomplete understanding of and repetitive discussions on the challenges facing LGBTQI educators in various educational settings (Ullman, 2020) have been perpetuated by the minimal focus on the intersectionality of these elements, leading to a lack of implicative conclusions for authorities to act upon. This should encourage researchers to go beyond traditional boundaries and take on studies that fill the gap in knowledge using more inclusive and intersectional approaches.

Herewith, there is an overt scholarly call to action. Research on the presence of LGBTQI educators should endeavor to transcend the constraints of isolated examinations. Instead, studies should adopt an all-encompassing investigation of the intertwining nature of the identity-, ideology-, and experience-based discussions revolving around their debated presence within various levels of educational settings. This imperative to expand the field of study underscores the value of in-depth analyses that take into account how the aforementioned interrelated components interact. Research holds the potential to present a more holistic understanding of the presence of LGBTQI educators within educational contexts by drawing scholarly focus toward the intersectionality of the discussions on their personal and professional identity navigation, causative ideological constructs, and their professional experiences. Along with enhancing our theoretical frameworks, this comprehensive approach, which embarks on the interconnectedness of these dimensions, might make a contribution to the practical implications, considerations, and interventions within various educational institutions around the world. By means of a more comprehensive, implicative, and insightful understanding of the presence of LGBTQI educators, the scholarly community may thus be offered an opportunity to promote inclusivity and foster diversity in educational contexts, along with furthering extensive knowledge in this urgently critical domain.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines the methodology employed to conduct this thesis study. The present investigation endeavors to scrutinize the intricate intersection of LGBTQI language educator identity, professional experiences, and heteroprofessionalism from the perspective of an LGBTQI language educator within the context of a Turkish institutional educational setting, placed in North Cyprus. The participant was selected by means of purposive sampling techniques through meticulous consideration in order to collect relevant and rich data that would assist the researcher in delving into the intricacies of the phenomenon under scrutiny. At the time of the study, she was employed and practicing at the English Preparatory School of a higher education institution (a state university in particular) in the Turkish context as an English language instructor. This indicates that the research setting is reflective of the academic milieu prevailing within Turkish universities though no intentional generalization of findings is aimed. A qualitative single intrinsic case study approach was utilized to achieve this aim, enabling analyses of the professional trajectory of a single participant, as case studies explain, describe, illustrate, and enlighten (Yin, 2009) unique phenomena. By means of a combination of recurring semi-structured interviews, periodically performed solicited journaling, and participant-generated observation reports, rich and triangulated data were collected, offering thorough insights into the lived experiences and perspectives of the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism experienced by an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context. The data collection process continued from May 13, 2024, to November 10, 2024, taking approximately 6 months in total from the first to the last interview. These were the first and last actions of collecting data, positioning the journal entries and the participant-generated observation reports through the middle of the process. The rationale behind this particular process is

elaborately outlined in this chapter as well. The data collected were subjected to thematic analysis through the medium of MAXQDA, a software tool particularly utilized for qualitative data analysis. Throughout the entire research process, participant anonymity and confidentiality, informed consent, and the mitigation of potential discomfort or harm were taken cognizance of due to ethical considerations. By engaging in validity checks (advisory supervision, professional consultation, reflexivity, peer debriefing, data triangulation, and member checking), and transparency in interpreting and reporting data, efforts were exerted to ensure the reliability and rigor of the study, which emerge as paramount criticisms of case studies. Expanding on the preceding exposition and cognizant of the methodological framework expounded upon, the two research questions driving this study are as follows:

RQ1: From the perspective of an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context, how does heteroprofessionalism, if any, manifest itself within her workplace context?

RQ2: How does an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context negotiate her identities and navigate her professional experiences within their heteroprofessional workplace context?

The study aims to address the research questions through a carefully structured process that explores each aspect and phase of the investigation. In this chapter, definition and justification of the research design, sampling of the study, participant of the study, research setting, data instrumentation, and data collection and analysis procedures, researcher positionality, validity checks, and ethical considerations are thoroughly outlined for a conceptual understanding of the methodology employed in this study.

3.1. Definition and Justification of the Research Design

This study employs a single intrinsic case study approach to explore the nuanced dynamics surrounding LGBTQI language educator identity, professional experiences, and the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism. A case study,

which is a type of empirical research that delves deeply into a contemporary phenomenon and examines it within its real-life context (Yin, 2009), is often distinguished by its elaborate investigation of a particular case or unit of analysis. According to Creswell (2007), the primary purpose of a case study is to comprehend the case or cases themselves through interpreting data collected by means of different instruments. In particular, an intrinsic case study comprises a situation where researchers need to become intimate with a particular case (Stake, 1995). In the present study, the "case" refers to the lived workplace experiences, perspectives of an LGBTQI language educator navigating her workspace in the Turkish context.

To explore the research questions, an intrinsic case study approach was employed in this study. Understanding the case itself and particularizing it is the main aim of case studies (Stake, 1995). Thus, this approach is especially well-suited for encapsulating the multifaceted narratives of an LGBTQI language educator and illuminating the challenges she faces within her workplace context. In addition, this study was designed as a single case study that would ideally explore a single subject and attain deeper understanding of her narrative (Dyer & Wilkins, 1991). By concentrating on a single case, this research design facilitated the exploration of the intricate interplay between LGBTQI language educator identity, professional experiences, and heteroprofessional institutional dynamics in the Turkish context, providing insights into the participant's lived workplace experiences and the broader concerns of inclusivity and diversity in the field.

The objectives of the present study, which aspire to comprehend the multilateral nature of LGBTQI language educator identity negotiation and professional experience navigation, align with how a single intrinsic case study approach would function without aiming to build a theory (Stake, 2000). Although this approach does not aim for generalization to broader populations (Creswell, 2013), it allows for a detailed understanding of a specific phenomenon (Patton, 1990). The research design examines the complex dynamics surrounding institutionally constructed heteroprofessional norms, both formal and unenacted, along with professional interactions and societal attitudes toward the involvement of LGBTQI language educators in the Turkish context. In other words, insights and implications emerged

from this exploration are anticipated to contribute to a deeper understanding of how LGBTQI language educators negotiate their identity and steer their professional experiences while navigating heteroprofessionalism within their workspaces.

Often, case studies are classified into three main types in the scholarly context, i.e., intrinsic case studies, instrumental case studies, and collective case studies, which are “distinguished by the size of the bounded case, such as whether the case involves one individual, several individuals, a group, an entire program, or an activity” (Creswell, 2007, p. 74). An intrinsic case study approach was decided to be employed in the present study for a number of reasons. Regarding researcher positionality, the case explored in this study is of particular interest to the researcher (Creswell, 1998; Stake, 2000) rather than a general area to be investigated through an instrumental case study approach. In addition to that, generalization of the study findings or implications to broader populations is not the aim of this study. Rather, understanding the complexities of a particular case (Stake, 2005) without purposefully intending to produce generalizable findings (Merriam, 2009) is prioritized. Moreover, this study was designed to function inductively. Therefore, an exploratory research approach was considered to suit well to the entire process, and intrinsic case studies allow researchers to explore the complexities of the phenomenon they investigate (Marshall & Rossman, 2016; Thomas, 2011). Also, context is of great significance in this study. Intrinsic case studies provide the researcher with an opportunity to delve elaborately into the contextual understanding of the phenomenon explored, which goes beyond surface-level observations (Gerring, 2004). The present study takes place in a geographically and culturally complex context, wherein the research problem in question does not commonly draw scholarly attention. Hence, the number of research studies conducted to investigate it is rather infrequent. Accordingly, an intrinsic case study approach was considered to enable the researcher to present insights and implications that would address the contextual characteristics of the study. This, in turn, would contribute to a contextual understanding of the research problem as well.

In addition to the reasons rendering an intrinsic case study design superior to an extrinsic one for this study, there are also reasons as to why a single case study

approach would suit better than a multiple case study one. Considering a deeper understanding of the case is primarily aimed, a single case study approach was considered a better fit, since it provides the researcher with an opportunity to deeply delve into the explored subject (Dyer & Wilkins, 1991). Furthermore, a single case study offers more time to the researcher to become intimate with the subject of the study (Gerring, 2004), which facilitates the objective of the present study that is to comprehend the perspectives of the participant of showcasing the intersectionality's multifaceted nature. Also, a single case study approach is argued to be the better of the two when the researcher desires to study a single subject, e.g., a person, a group of people, an institution. As aforementioned, this study was also designed to explore the perspectives of a single participant, which naturally made a single case study approach a better fit for its design. Complexity and uniqueness of the case were influencing factors as well. As Merriam (2009) asserts, researchers can uncover important implications by delving into the specifics of a single case that might not be evident in more typical or common cases. Also, Stake (2005) argues that when the case is characterized by complexity and multiple interrelated factors, a single case study approach enables a thorough examination of these dynamics, offering insights that may not be attainable through broader comparative analyses, which would disregard the unique attributes and contexts of the case (Creswell, 2013).

Consequently, it was decided that the single intrinsic case study approach provides a robust design for exploring the intersectionality of an LGBTQI language educator's multiple identities, professional experiences, and the ideological notion of institutionalized heteroprofessionalism in the Turkish context. Through investigation of a single case by means of triangulated data, the present study aims to offer contextually grounded implications and insights that might inform both conceptual understanding and practical interventions geared toward promoting inclusivity and social justice for all LGBTQI educators, particularly those practicing in the Turkish context.

3.2. Sampling of the Study

As argued by Patton (2014), the foundation for ensuring the relevance, depth, and validity of study findings is the carefully crafted process of participant selection. The

present study required a process of careful consideration for selecting the participant to delve elaborately and reliably into the case under exploration. The criteria governing the participant selection process of this study were made aligned with its particular focus and research objectives. It was imperative that the targeted participant for this study self-identified as an LGBTQI individual openly and confidently, or 'in-closet', currently practicing as a language educator within the Turkish context.

Practicing upon Stake's (2005) guidance, purposive sampling, i.e., criterion-based sampling, frequently adopted in qualitative studies, emerged as the methodological basis for selecting the participant for this study. Defined by Teddlie and Yu (2007), purposive sampling is "selecting units (e.g., individuals, groups of individuals, institutions) based on specific purposes associated with answering a research study's questions" (p.77). By means of this strategic sampling approach, the participant was intentionally selected for the study. She possessed the necessary characteristics to provide valuable insights that address the research problem and align with the research objectives (Creswell, 2007; Stake, 2005), supporting the study's in-depth investigation. One of the supervisors of the study initially named the participant as a possible candidate for the study. After that, the participant was verbally invited to participate in the study by the researcher himself. Although generalizing findings from qualitative research employing purposive sampling might be implausible, this recruitment strategy supported the selection of a representative sample (Merriam, 2009) as much as possible, reflective of LGBTQI educators in the Turkish context. This approach facilitated the collection of relevant, rich, and informative data (Marshall & Rossman, 2016) to contribute to scholarly discussions on how these educators negotiate their identities, manage professional experiences, and navigate institutional heteroprofessionalism.

3.3. Participant of the Study

Melisa, a safeguard pseudonym attributed to the participant, is an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context in Northern Cyprus. In order to ensure her well-suitedness for addressing the research questions (Merriam, 2009), the researcher

intentionally recruited her, as her characteristics, which are to be mentioned in this report, are tailored for the particular focus of this investigation (Creswell, 2013). Considering the consensus in the field that educators practicing for less than, or five years are classified as novice professionals, the 26-year-old participant of this study is a novice language educator, institutionally practicing for four years.

In her bachelor's degree (BA), Melisa graduated from the program of Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL) at one of the most reputable universities of North Cyprus, specializing particularly in foreign language education. Alongside that, she had her minor degree in the program of General Psychology at the same institution. The medium of instruction in both of these programs is English. She completed both her major and minor in BA at the same time in 2020. In addition to her BA degrees in TEFL and General Psychology, she also had her master's degree (MA) in the program of English Language Teaching (ELT) in, again, one of the most reputable universities of Turkey in 2023. All these programs were completed in one of the most reputable universities in Turkey. Thus, she should be considered an intellectual, having attained distinguished academic qualifications.

Before her graduation from BA in 2020, Melisa had practiced as a part-time language educator at several institutions (summer language schools and language academies) for a few years along with general and private tutoring. As of 2020, she commenced her official professional journey as a language educator. Before her ongoing position as an English language instructor at her current institution in Northern Cyprus, she also practiced the same position and title at another higher education institution in Turkey. The former was a foundation university whereas the latter is a state university. At the time of the study, she practiced as a full-time English language instructor at her institution. She taught both English language grammar and language skills to considerably a large population of students. The university admits around 300 new undergraduate students each year. Therefore, her student profile can be considered as late adolescents/young adults as they are newly incoming university students learning at the English Preparatory School of the institution. The main objective of the preparatory school is to enhance students' English language competency and proficiency for a year-long period before they

commence their BA degrees in their own programs of specialization, whose medium of instruction would also be English. The participant has been practicing at the university's English Preparatory School as a full-time English language instructor for approximately a year now.

Sexual identities are conditional on several variations encircling personal, social, and biological dimensions. Thus, apart from her professional identity, it is important to note that understanding her LGBTQI identity was an intricate endeavor that required active dialogues between the researcher and Melisa with time, empathy, critical thinking, effort, and direct definitions by herself. Her biological sex is female. However, Melisa does not identify as solely female. Her self-gender-identification goes as bigender, and she embraces pansexuality as her sexual orientation. That is, Melisa is not a cisgender individual whose gender identity matches the sex assigned to her at birth. With her bigender and pansexual identifications, her identity transcends traditional binary classifications, challenging societal norms and conventions. Instead of strict gender classifications (denoting to their sex or not), a genderfluidity is experienced by bigender individuals. They are considered to fluctuate between feminine and masculine manifestations, unsettling the socially stiff dichotomy of gender. Furthermore, identifying as pansexual goes beyond the confines of normative or conventional sexual orientations (heterosexuality and homosexuality), welcoming attraction to all individuals irrespective of their biological sex or gender identity.

All in all, although she acknowledges her sex as female, Melisa cannot be rigidly classified as a woman or man. She embraces she/her/he/him as her pronouns. She prefers to be referred as she/her lately and presents her consent to be referred as she/her by the researcher at the time of the study and in the study report. In her own words, she elaborates on her gender identity and sexual orientation as follows:

I wanna be two genders at the same time, not the other gender, the two, male and female. I am both of these things. It's less about what's in my body, it's more about femininity and masculinity. So, someday, I would like to be referred as hi/him, I would like to be referred as a handsome guy. Some other days, I wanna be she/her, and would love to be referred as this beautiful woman. Honestly, this month, I feel a lot of she/her, so you can go with that.

Next month, it might change. My sexual orientation is pansexuality. I didn't know pansexuality existed in Turkish, or in Turkey, or in Turkish communities, because I have never heard about it before, but I found myself being attracted to all types of people. I just didn't know the name, and I thought I was an anomaly, an abomination in fact. Then, I learnt some English. I started googling, turned out I have a name, ohh, I'm normal actually, there are other people who are like me.

In a single intrinsic case study, understanding the participant utterly is pivotal for the overall reliability of the interpretation. Thorough participant analysis provides the researcher with a strong contextual understanding for interpreting the findings of the study. Gaining insights into individuals within their particular contexts facilitates a more detailed and nuanced understanding of the phenomena under scrutiny (Creswell, 2013). Although the researcher of the present study did not initially know the participant at a personal level, they started having multiple casual meetings and continuous texting as friends months before the study was commenced. That way, the researcher had the opportunity to get to know the participant at a deeper level before putting the researcher hat on.

This depth of comprehension was fundamental for the researcher to reach meaningful conclusions and secure that the discussions were both relevant to the participant and accurately reflective of her experiences. Detailed analyses of participants may help gathered data to be contextually grounded and comprehensive. This might as well enhance the reliability and validity of studies. Therefore, understanding participants altogether, particularly those of single-participant studies, can be considered to promote the formation of in-depth insights and help reduce researcher bias. Emphasized by Stake (1995), research with larger scopes may miss out broader principles that can be presented through the uniqueness of single case studies. By means of focused analyses on subjects in such studies, even without a particular aim of generalization, novel patterns and insights that might add to the wider body of knowledge can be uncovered. Ultimately, detailed participant analysis was indispensable in this single-participant case study. It enriched the researcher's contextual handling of this exploration, enhanced the overall reliability and validity of the study, and provided insights that might lead to implications extending beyond this individual case under scrutiny.

3.4. Research Setting

The present study takes place in a higher education institution within the Turkish context, in North Cyprus. Although, they share numerous values and practices at sociopolitical and sociocultural levels, Turkey and North Cyprus are two different countries. The “baby land” (North Cyprus, as referred to by Turkish people of Turkey), reflecting a considerably good number of values of the Turkish culture, is where Melisa had lived, studied, and worked for years before she started participating in this study. With the researcher of the study, they had multiple conversations around the cultural similarities and possible differences that might affect the interpretation of findings in this study and came to the conclusion that there was no salient difference to preconceive unless any pops up to consider. While evaluating this judgement, it is important to keep in mind that Melisa has experienced both places for years and expressly chooses to refer to the culture as a united “Turkish culture/context”. While Melisa points out no major differences, it is still notable that Northern Cyprus has its own unique socio-cultural and socio-political nuances as well. Influenced by a history of British colonialism, some aspects of daily life, professional life, socio-cultural practices, socio-economical status quo, and socio-political norms in Northern Cyprus may differ subtly from those of such in mainland Turkey. These differences, though often overlooked, can indeed impact individuals’ perspectives and behaviors in regardable ways. Thus, while the term Turkish culture/context is still broadly applicable to the setting of the present study, possible distinctions should always be kept in mind while interpreting its key findings.

Geographically and culturally, the Turkish context has unique attributes. It is situated at the crossroads of the Balkans, Caucasus, Middle East, and eastern Mediterranean. Put simply, it is where Asia and Europe intersect, complicating rigid descriptions of its culture as well. Turkish culture is complex and multifaceted in many ways due to the historical interaction it has had with several other cultures for centuries. In the context of this study, the prevalent Turkish culture of approaching the LGBTQI community should be cared for, without disregarding that the institution is located in North Cyprus. For decades now, it has been observed that the LGBTQI community

has never been fully welcomed in the Turkish context (Engin, 2015; Özeren & Aydin, 2016). The prevalent conservative culture of preserving traditional norms and practices has been observed to exclude and marginalize the LGBTQI community (Özbay et al., 2022; Özeren & Aydin, 2016). Visibility of the community has only enhanced in the last few decades, positioning it as “a new trend” that is insidiously pervasive among youth and endeavoring to “convert” their identities (Yabancı & Sağlam, 2023) into things that are inappropriate to the Turkish culture (Özbay, 2021). The challenges LGBTQI individuals face in the Turkish context are extensive and concerning, ranging from considerably subtle hate crimes in public to multiple instances of homicide. These difficulties are often exacerbated by discriminatory rhetoric from conservative political figures in various social and institutional contexts. Consequently, LGBTQI individuals frequently encounter hate, discrimination, marginalization, and other significant obstacles (Erdur, 2022; Kamenou, 2023; Yılmaz & Göçmen, 2016). Understanding such contextual challenges is essential for framing the focus of this study.

Melisa practices as an English language instructor at the preparatory school of a higher education institution (a prestigious state university). Although the university is well-known for its far liberal political stance, instances of violations of rights, such as the criminalization of queer pride parade and the police brutality against it, still occur on campus and are often considered a shame by the majority of its officially affiliated academic staff and students. The core objective of the program is announced as providing students with below proficiency English level with basic language competencies and skills so that major difficulties they may encounter pursuing their undergraduate programs at the university can be eliminated. The program as a whole comprises sections of speaking, writing, listening, and reading skills, as well as grammatical competency of the English language. To provide students with the terminology they would be exposed to in their own fields of study, tailored materials are offered. As a case in point, several audio-visual exercises and activities are designed for and provided to students. That way, their note-taking skills are improved for the particular type of the English language they will be coming across and utilizing from onset of their freshman year to the end of their undergraduate education. There are nine courses in the program offered to students to

cater to different parts and aspects of the English language. Regarding the instructors teaching in the program, an annual workshop festival is arranged. The aim is to provide scholars, educators, researchers, practitioners, and specialists with a platform to contemplate and discuss contemporary issues with regard to language teaching and learning. The event also supports the promotion of collaboration, exchange of ideas, and professional development among the program's instructors. Although this is not reflected on by Melisa in the data, it is important to keep in mind that community of practice is considered important for all instructors in the program. In addition to these, there are self-study centers and opportunities in the program provided to all students to support their academic development, as well as encouraging learner autonomy. Finally, there is an English proficiency exam (EPE) held at the commencement and conclusion of each academic year for a few reasons. The EPE of the program is held in several face-to-face sessions and its results are claimed to be in strict alignment with international exams such as TOEFL, IELTS, GRE, and PTE academic.

3.5. Data Collection, Instrumentation, and Analysis Procedures

3.5.1. Data Collection

One of the underlying goals of the present study is to delve into rich, context-specific insights that would shed light on the participant's perspectives of the studied phenomenon by exploring the particular intricacies of this single case. This inquiry, which is established on the basis of a single intrinsic case study method, emphasizes depth over breadth. Accordingly, extensive strategies to collect and analyze data (Yin, 2009) were employed.

With regard to the data collection methods and strategies, which often comprise observations, document analyses, and interviews in qualitative inquiries (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Punch, 2009), journaling, participant-generated observation reports, and interviewing were exercised in this study, calling for a significant investment of time and dedication both from the participant the researcher throughout the collection and analysis processes. Due to issues of practicality and convenience in terms of time and

location at the expense of both parties, as well as the nature of the research design that aspires after gaining insights into the participant’s perspectives of her own reality, no sort of researcher observation was included in the process of gathering data. However, data were triangulated by means of three consecutive (periodically set) journal entries, two semi-structured interviews, and multiple participant-generated observation reports, enhancing the process of achieving rich data. As Zimmerman and Wieder (1977) also argue, even without the researcher directly observing, the interconnected use of journals, interviews, and participant-generated observation reports led to an echo of participant observation. This approach allowed the study to interpret and discuss the participant's perspectives on the phenomenon under scrutiny. The questions of the interviews, prompts of the solicited journals, and defined target behaviors to be observed and reported by the participant in the participant-generated observation reports were all targeted toward scrutinizing the case being explored. Also, aside from the questions, guidance, and the prompts, by nature, journals are widely believed to capture ordinary thoughts and feelings of participants regarding phenomena, which may contribute to the process of gathering rich data in social studies. Additionally, journal entries collected from the participant for this study are fully textual materials that could have failed to capture the subtleties of verbal communication had the journals and interviews not been performed complementarily. **Table 1** demonstrates the timeline of collecting data for this study.

Table 1. Data Collection Timeline

Data Collection Tool	Time
Interview 1	2024, May 13
Journal Entry 1	2024, May 27
Journal Entry 2	2024, June 10
Journal Entry 3	2024, June 24
Observation Reports	2024, September-October
Interview 2	2024, November 10

Illustrated in the preceding table, the entire process of collecting data from the first to the last day took approximately 6 months in total. As asserted by Patton (2002) as

well, qualitative researchers often seek understanding and interpretation, which requires investments of time and effort, instead of prediction and explanation. The series of semi-structured interviews, participant-generated observation reports, and solicited journals were designed and performed to obtain a thorough understanding of the participant's perspectives regarding the studied phenomenon, thereby serve the nature and essential aims of the study along the right lines.

The sequential unfolding of the data collection process, commenced with the first interview, was strategically designed by the researcher and advisors with the purpose of fostering rapport with the participant along with further acquainting her with the studied phenomenon. This aligns with Creswell's (2013) claim that qualitative inquiries highlight the nuanced investigation of lived experiences through an interpretive naturalistic approach to subject matters at hand. Furthermore, the familiarization on the initial interaction (the first interview) was considered to foster interactional and communicative comfort, which concurrently enhanced retrospection and introspection by the participant (Jacelon & Imperio, 2005). In addition, necessary amount of time for the researcher to assess the participant's initial stance on working with journals and participant-generated observation reports was secured to prepare for how the raw data would look. This was an indispensable contemplation, considering the various potential takes of individuals on working with participant-generated data, particularly writing solicited journals with prompts, ranging from viewing them as an opportunity to reflect on themselves to positioning them as chores to be completed (Milligan et al., 2005).

Upon the first interview, a series of three periodic participant journal entries were solicited, each accompanied by different prompts designed separately and strategically by the researcher and advisors to steer the participant's reflections for relevant data. Following a biweekly schedule and encapsulating approximately a six-weeks span of time in total, an introspective room for the participant to vocalize her continuous feelings, thoughts, introspections, and retrospections was afforded by this journaling process, aligning with Creswell's (2007) accentuation of the iterative nature of qualitative research. Moreover, taking into account the importance of collecting reliable and valid data (Merriam, 2009) through journaling, this process

was also strategically designed by the researcher and advisors to facilitate the participant's retrospection process, considering biweekly journal entries would require less effort to recall due to their time-wise proximity to the occurrences, thereby minimize recalling errors as well. Also, one of the most essential benefits of a fixed-schedule journaling process, which is considered discipline, was gained in this study by designing a time-based process and thoroughly informing the participant of its entirety in advance. Upon journal entries, participant-generated observation reports were collected from the participant as an alternative format to illustrate and describe her own reality. The time for observation was allocated by the researcher as one full month. However, the participant wanted to take more than that to observe and did so. Before the observation process commenced, a session was held by the researcher with the participant, wherein he trained and guided her on how to navigate the process. In the session, the target behaviors to be observed by the participant, i.e. LGBTQI-phobia, heteronormativity, and heteroprophesionalism, were also communicated and negotiated. Accordingly, the participant was provided with a template to follow in the process of reporting her target behavior encounters. Those encounters were anticipated from all stakeholders related to her profession and institution, from her students to parents, administrators, and colleagues. By that means, the participant was provided with an opportunity to observe her workplace environment and report her observations in accordance with her perspectives. As the present study seeks to gain the participant's perspectives of the studied phenomenon, participant involvement and empowerment throughout the whole research process was of great importance. Also, what notably differentiates the solicited journals from the participant-generated observation reports was the objectives of each tool. While it was aimed to gain insight into the participant's thoughts, retrospections, reflections, and feelings with the journals, the participant-generated observation reports were targeted at the participant's perspectives of what was happening within her workplace context.

Along with solely addressing the research questions as its essential purpose, the last interview, taking place two weeks after the concluding participant-generated observation report entry, functioned as the culmination of the data collection process as well, providing an opportunity for the researcher to explore emerging themes in

greater detail and clarify any uncertainties and ambiguities. Case studies help locate the researcher in the world of the phenomenon, and there is a variety of materials and interpretive processes that make that world visible (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018). The iterative approach to gathering data for the present study, comprising semi-structured interviews, solicited participant journals, and participant-generated observation reports, echoes this assertion that case studies are multifaceted with many dimensions. Accordingly, this study, through utilization of the expounded methodological framework, seeks to shed light on the participants' perspectives of her identity negotiation, experience navigation, and the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism, aspiring after adding up to a greater understanding of the phenomenon under exploration.

3.5.2. Data Instrumentation

The term “triangulation” is derived from the idea that utilizing several points of observation may assist in locating a place in the sphere of navigation. In research, several methods can be employed to triangulate studies, a rather reliable one of which is considered data triangulation. Patton (1999) defines data triangulation in qualitative research as drawing data from multiple sources to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the studied phenomenon. In case studies, it is prevalent to use multiple data sources to facilitate elaborate examination. This approach helps validate findings and interpretations, enhance the study's overall quality, and provide a more detailed understanding of the phenomenon under exploration (Tracy, 2010).

Data triangulation was considered the only convenient method of triangulation for the present study due to several reasons including “restrictions of time and money” (Denzin, 1978, p. 306). Environmental and theoretical triangulations were nonapplicable due to the nature of the research design. Investigator triangulation, similarly, could not be employed on the ground of thesis study requirements. In a single intrinsic case study that was designed to be inductively conducted by a single researcher, none of the aforementioned methods of triangulation were applicable except for data triangulation. Thus, the data gathered on the purpose of gaining

insights into the participants' perspectives and address the research questions were gathered using three different data collection instruments: self-administered semi-structured interviews, solicited journals, and participant-generated observation reports.

3.5.2.1. Interviewing

An interview is a unique type of communication where interviewees and interviewers exchange information verbally or nonverbally on a particular topic. Particularly, a qualitative interview, according to Oakley (1998), is a form of framework where practices are both documented, attained and strengthened. In studies that investigate the experiences, feelings, perspectives, and interpretations of human participants, interviews are argued to make rather suitable instruments to collect data. Though considered to be implausible to have an entirely unstructured interview, three main types of interviews are frequently described in the qualitative context of the academic milieu, i.e., structured interviews, semi-structured interviews, and unstructured interviews. Compared to structured interviews, in which questions and answer options are predefined (Punch, 2009), semi-structured interviews, thanks to its flexibility in questioning, assist qualitative researchers better in gathering in-depth data due to the nature of their design. Hence, they are regarded as in-depth interviews (IDI) by qualitative researchers. IDI is one of the most operable and convenient sources of collecting in-depth data to investigate human subjects and their perspectives and interpretations of situations (Punch, 2009). IDI method is argued to provide qualitative researchers with a thorough understanding of their human subjects' thoughts, feelings, behaviors, experiences, and perspectives through open dialogue and rapport. That way, it may assist them in uncovering as much information as possible regarding the intricacies of the studied phenomenon. To address the research objectives and questions of this study, semi-structured interviews were conducted to collect rich and detailed data on the intersection of the participants' identity negotiation, experiences, and the concept of institutional heteroprofessionalism. This approach involved using a predefined set of open-ended questions while allowing flexibility to adjust the number and sequence of questions based on the flow of the conversation. Interview questions were collaboratively

written by the researcher, one of the professional consultants, and advisory supervisors. In total, two interviews were administered in the beginning and at the end of the data collection process. Both interviews took slightly more than an hour and half. They both were administered via Zoom due to the researcher and participant living in different places. All interview questions can be found in Appendices A and B.

Ultimately, this method enabled scrutinizing the complex phenomenon under investigation by fusing the flexibility of unstructured interviews with the organization of structured interviews. This allowed for the examination of various viewpoints while ensuring that key points were covered methodically. As qualitative researchers, particularly in case studies, do not depend on data collection instruments developed by other scholars in the field to investigate other phenomena (Creswell, 2013), both interviews were also self-administered by the researcher with the assistance of the advisors. Through self-administered semi-structured interviews, recorded in full on *Zoom* as the conversations naturally unfolded, the aim was to capture the participant's experiences, perspectives, thoughts, and feelings as comprehensively as possible. This approach helped ensure that interpretations were based on detailed, contextually grounded data.

3.5.2.2. Journaling

“Documents, both historical and contemporary, are a rich source of data for education and social research” (Punch, 2009, p. 158). In case studies, one method of collecting data from primary sources of written, printed, or recorded materials, which may include letters, models, operational schedules, personal diaries/journals, reports, and photographs of activities (Lincoln & Guba, 1985), is considered documentation. Among these instrumentations, journaling, developed in the disciplines of psychology and anthropology, stand out by offering proof of authentic actions and retrospective perspectives of humans. It should be noted that some researchers prefer naming them “diaries” as well, and both “diary” and “journal” refer to the same instrumentation. The present study will use the term “journal”.

Defined by Krishnan (2002), journals are personal accounts of events that are chronicled by individuals over time. In social studies, particularly in qualitative research, the rising curiosity and interest toward employing the journaling technique as a data collection technique has lately been overt. This is because exploratory research benefits from its nature of offering documentation of phenomena. Informants (participants) are required to record events more or less as they occur (Butcher & Eldridge, 1990) and keep the information provided continuous. Simply by documenting their experiences and how they reflect on them in terms of their thoughts, feelings and retrospections, participants provide researchers with their own perceptions of studied phenomena (Jacelon & Imperio, 2005). Moreover, journals are also argued to shed an intimate light on the lives of individuals, which might enhance some of the most essential characteristics of deep, soft, interactive, and detailed qualitative data. As the present study aims at capturing and presenting the perspectives of an LGBTQI language educator on the intersectionality of her identities, experiences, and heteroprofessionalism, the journaling technique was considered a good fit in its design. Keeping journals assisted the participant in recalling her experiences, reflecting on them, and rediscovering her own perception of the intersectionality under investigation. This process offered rich and accurate data to the researcher. By employing the journaling technique, subjective information exhibiting the participant's perspectives was gathered to understand and interpret her own social reality (Gray, 2013).

Gathering data by means of journaling is not a one-way method. Broadly, participant journals can be classified into two forms of documents, i.e., unsolicited journals and solicited journals. Unsolicited journals and solicited journals denote different techniques of data instrumentation in research. Unsolicited journals refer to documents that are written and submitted by participants voluntarily and without a request or prompt. These entries are freely provided by participants as already-written documents rather than being expressly requested by researchers for particular studies. In other words, researchers gather participants' personal diaries that were written without a scholarly purpose hence might only include information significant to informants. On the other hand, solicited journals entail a purposeful call from researchers to participants to submit written documents of their daily lives and lived

experiences for review. Simply put, they are written by participants to intentionally facilitate researchers' inquiry. Although solicited journals are criticized to cause a loss of naturalness of studied settings, they are still considered to ensure a focused gathering of relevant information as data. A wide variation of viewpoints, depth, and amount of information may be presented in unsolicited journals.

Solicited journals, on the other hand, provide researchers with more control over journal entries through prompts. This makes the instrumentation semi-structured. That way, journal entries are assumed to better align with study goals, which might enhance the overall validity and relevance of collected data. This study employed the solicited journaling technique with the aim of capturing the participant's contextualized perception of the investigated intersectionality with regard to her retrospective feelings, subjectivities, reflections of actions, and lived experiences. Journaling prompts were also collaboratively prepared by the researcher, one of the professional consultants, and advisory supervisors. Three journal entries in total were required, digitally kept once in two weeks. Without an attempt of individual analysis, the researcher read all the journal entries one by one as they were collected along the way. Although, according to the initial plan, any emerging questions were to be discussed with the participant during the last semi-structured interview, there were no unclear points in the journal entries that necessitated this kind of a process. In total in all three journal entries, one thousand two hundred fifty-six words were produced by the participant. Ultimately, by means of gathering solicited journal entries from the participant over an active employment period of time, i.e., approximately four weeks in total, insights into her versions of reality with minimum recall bias were aimed. See Appendices C, D, and E for all journal prompts.

3.5.2.3. Participant-Generated Observation Reports

In research, particularly qualitative studies, incorporating participant-generated data in study designs has lately received increasing attention. Both solicited and unsolicited journals are great examples of participant-generated data as they include no interference from researchers in the process of their generation. Moreover, visual data have been observed to be way more prevalent as participant-generated data

compared to textual data. Plethora of studies employed participant-generated visual data in their designs. However, in this study, textual participant-generated data were collected in the form of observation reports along with solicited journals. These reports were crucially important with regard to allowing the participant to document her own experiences and observations. That way, her presence was empowered, and her involvement was increased in the research process. It also helped obtaining data that is intensely embedded in the context of her workplace environment.

Observations done by participants may provide an opportunity to capture the intricacies and subtleties of social interactions within research settings that may be overlooked by external observers, including researchers. Creswell (2013) underscores how participant-generated data can improve the credibility and enhance the authenticity of qualitative research findings, considering that it allows researchers to gain direct insights into their participants' perspectives of the studied phenomena. In the present study, rather than the participant's emotions, thoughts, or reflections, which are targeted to be obtained with solicited journals, gaining insights into what happens around her and how she perceives things happening in her workplace environment is targeted by incorporating participant-generated observation reports. Also, this tool complies with the principles of participatory research, wherein participants are frequently involved and actively engaged in the process of data collection, promoting a sense of participant empowerment (Reason & Bradbury, 2008), as well as fostering a more collaborative approach to the study. Accordingly, the participant was empowered in this study by having an opportunity to observe her workplace environment and report them, alongside interviews and journal entries, through which she was often expected to express her thoughts, feelings, retrospections, and reflections. Much as they sound similar, solicited journals and observation reports are different in nature. While journals were aimed at getting insights into the participant's timeless thoughts and feelings, the main purpose of the observation reports in this study was to see what was happening at her workplace in terms of timely and specific instances through her lens, which helped interpret the overall key findings at the end. In the initial plan of data collection, observation reports were not present. However, with the aim of further triangulating the data and gathering information of particular instances within the context of the participant's

workplace environment, they were added into the plan right after the first interview took place.

The participant was asked to take her observation notes over a half-guided template, digitally or on paper depending on her preference and what the specific instance would require. The template is not considered designed fully guided, considering the participant was not asked to follow particular questions, she was rather asked to follow what the headings required her to do while taking her notes down, which provided her with more of an autonomy while doing so. The template, which can be found in Appendix F, was also collaboratively designed by the researcher, one of the professional consultants, and the advisory supervisors and was approved by the participant. A pre-observation process meeting was held with the participant to inform her of the overall process and what she was required to do during that process. In order to avoid unintentional manipulation through the guidance of the template, the researcher made sure to give careful attention to how he communicated what he wanted the participant to focus on as the target behaviors and that they negotiated on those behaviors before the actual observation process was commenced. In addition to all these, during the pre-observation process meeting, it was clearly communicated by the researcher to the participant that, if an instance of interest occurred, she was only required to take small observation notes that would provide the researcher with an objective lens to look at what she saw was happening within her workplace context. That way, the participant's perspectives were targeted at through the participant-generated observation reports, while her thoughts and feelings were eliminated, which emerged as the most salient difference between them and the solicited journals during the data collection process.

By guiding the participant how to navigate the report template as well as determining the target behaviors to be observed, the researcher also engaged in the process, yet rather indirectly and inactively regarding the generation of the reports. The target behaviors, namely LGBTQI-phobia, heteronormativity, and heteroprofessionalism, were determined by the researcher and negotiated with the participant in the pre-observation session. These target behaviors were not necessarily anticipated to be performed against the participant herself. All that she saw, heard, experienced, and

witnessed within her workplace environment were solicited by the researcher. These included all forms of social interactions taking place within the research setting, such as student-student, student-participant, student-colleague, participant-colleague, participant-admin, colleague-admin, and student-admin interactions including small-talks, utterances, actions, and conversations.

3.5.3. Data Analysis

Qualitative data analysis aims to uncover deeper meanings, patterns, and themes within non-numeric data. It is often employed to shed light into human experiences, behaviors, and perspectives within their own unique social realities. As highlighted by Saldaña (2013), qualitative data analysis is more than merely a mechanical or linear process, rather, it is indeed a reflective and iterative exercise. In this process, collected data is carefully familiarized with, revisited, questioned, and interpreted by the researchers in the light of his own positionality, experiences, perspectives, and the identities he shares with the participant. Hereby, the aim is to derive rich, thick, and meaningful findings. In order to do this, the researcher often needs to be in active engagement with the data, exploring both its overt and covert meanings.

Researchers' role in the process of qualitative data analysis is key. Qualitative research, particularly in case studies, aims to explore the intricacies of cases to provide holistic and contextual insights. Researchers should dive deep into the data as active interpreters whose subjectivity impacts the process rather than as detached or disinterested observers (Stake, 1995). This understanding also aligns well with Creswell's (2013) argument that qualitative data analysis comprises a process of "layered" interpretations. This process requires researchers to come up with initial codes to combine within broader themes, which are generated to present overall narratives that capture the essence of studied phenomena.

There are various approaches proposed to be employed to analyze qualitative data. Among those of many, Braun and Clarke's Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) (2006) has gained recognition for its methodical and flexible framework. This framework highlights researchers' reflexivity and subjectivity in identifying patterns

of meaning across gathered data (Braun & Clarke, 2013). RTA acknowledges and values the subjectivity of researchers and their roles in generating themes in a way that aligns with the interpretivist paradigm that the most qualitative research is based on. Braun and Clarke's six-phase data analysis framework was chosen for this study due to its emphasis on flexibility and reflexivity as well as researcher subjectivity. As aforementioned, researcher subjectivity was never intended to be left out of this study. Although the study aims at gaining insights on the participant's perspectives through rich and meaningful data, due to several shared identities between the researchers and the participant, researcher subjectivity was always acknowledged, optimized, and carefully considered throughout the whole investigation process.

Thereby, in addition to its flexibility, which novice researchers often need in their analysis procedures, its acknowledgement of researcher subjectivity and reflexivity rendered RTA the best framework to analyze data gathered for this study. The framework of RTA progresses through the following six stages: 1) familiarizing with the data, 2) generating codes, 3) combining codes into themes, 4) reviewing themes, 5) determining the significance of themes, 6) reporting findings. Through this process, systematic and deep engagement with the data was allowed for, ensuring that the emerging themes captured the participant's lived experiences as well as the researcher's critical interpretations of her perspectives.

With regard to coding, Saldaña's (2013) two-cycle coding approach was incorporated in the data analysis process of the present study, beginning with descriptive coding in the first cycle and progressing to pattern coding in the second. Descriptive coding was employed as it is suggested by Saldaña (2013) as appropriate for "beginning qualitative researchers learning how to code data, ethnographies, and studies with a wide variety of data forms (e.g., interview transcripts, field notes, journals, documents, diaries, correspondence, artifacts, video)" (p.87). By combining this coding cycle with Braun and Clarke's framework, the analysis aimed to achieve both breadth and depth, systematically exploring emerging themes from the semi-structured interview transcripts, solicited journal entries, and participant-generated observation reports.

It is also important to note that:

“Reliability is used in qualitative research in several ways, one of the most popular being the use of intercoder agreements when multiple coders analyze and then compare their code segments to establish the reliability of the data analysis process” (Creswell, 2013, p. 265).

Accordingly, intercoder agreement was employed in the process of data analysis of the present study. After agreeing upon descriptive coding, a codebook was developed by the researcher of the study and a fellow novice researcher (peer debriefer) by coding a journal entry of the participant collaboratively. Thereafter, the remaining journal entries were coded separately. Upon discussions on similarities and differences of individual coding of the remaining journal entries, a similar process was employed throughout the whole procedure. The data were coded and analyzed using the MAXQDA software, renowned for its strong qualitative data analysis qualities and intuitive interface.

3.5.3.1. Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA)

As aforementioned, RTA is a commonly acknowledged framework to qualitative data analysis, providing flexibility and highlighting researcher subjectivity. The framework acknowledges active construction of themes by researchers, not passive identifications, through their reflexive engagement with the data (Braun & Clarke, 2020). Reflexive practices, as emphasized by Terry et al. (2017), are pivotal to the RTA framework, demanding that researchers consider how their positionality, assumptions, and perspectives impact the analysis process and study findings. By means of the iterative and non-linear process of the RTA framework, the researcher was enabled to move back and forth between data, codes, and themes in the coding and analysis processes. This dynamic involvement reinforced the generation of meaningful patterns that captured the intricacies of all data collected for this study. Also, thanks to its theoretical flexibility, RTA is highly adaptable to interpretivist studies, such as the present study, that prioritize understanding participants' contextual meaning-making (Braun & Clarke, 2019), i.e., perspectives of their own realities. Accordingly, the RTA framework was considered particularly suited to the data analysis process of this study.

Stage 1: Familiarizing with the Data: The first stage of RTA requires researchers to immerse in the data to have a comprehensive understanding of its content and context (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This step involves repeated reading of the data while annotating, mostly broad patterns and initially occurring ideas. In this study, the semi-structured interview transcripts, solicited journal entries, and participant-generated observation reports were read time after time by the researcher and the fellow coder, and initial observations were documented accordingly. This process ensured a thorough understanding of the data by the coders, which served as the basis for subsequent coding.

Stage 2: Generating Codes: Systematically coding the data to develop meaningful features relevant to the research questions (Braun & Clarke, 2006) is central to the second stage. In the course of this stage, descriptive coding, as outlined by Saldaña (2013), was employed as the first cycle of coding to label data segments. Over 230 descriptive codes emerged, recording significant aspects of the participant's perspectives. All codes were managed and organized using MAXQDA, ensuring consistency throughout the dataset.

Stage 3: Combining Codes into Themes: During this phase, all initial codes were grouped into broader themes, seizing patterns of meaning within the dataset (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Pattern coding, as outlined by Saldaña (2013) as well, was employed to filter and classify the initial codes into higher-order categories. The 230+ codes emerging in the first cycle were synthesized into encircling themes.

Stage 4: Reviewing Themes: This stage requires researchers to refine and validate the preliminary themes, targeting coherence and alignment with and within the dataset (Braun & Clarke, 2006). During this stage, broader themes that emerged during Stage 3 were thoroughly re-evaluated against all data, and modifications were made as needed. A more unified thematic structure was aimed to be achieved by merging or eliminating themes that overlapped or lacked adequate support from the data. This stage also assisted the researcher in performing more reflexive practices with regard to his positionality, shared identities, and own perspectives. Carefully reconsidering

the emerging broader themes and reflecting on their generation process was found helpful by the researcher in terms of practicing reflexivity.

Stage 5: Determining the Significance of Themes: During this stage, all themes are put into final form by reevaluating their significance and relevance to the research problem and questions (Braun & Clarke, 2006). To make sure they reflected a unique and significant component of the participants' experiences, each theme was critically re-explored and examined. In addition to its significant presence in Stage 4, reflexivity was maintained by the researcher throughout this whole phase to mitigate researcher bias and ensure that the themes were reflective of both the participant's experiences and perspectives and the study's research objectives. Following Stage 4, this stage was the one wherein reflexive practices were performed most by the researcher for trustworthiness purposes.

Stage 6: Reporting Findings: As the last stage of the RTA framework, Stage 6 requires articulation of the finalized themes in an organized, structured, and coherent manner, reinforced by extracts from the dataset that aim illustration and validation of the findings (Braun & Clarke, 2006). It is important to note that this stage is not at all about merely listing the finalized themes, but it is more about establishing a meaningful narrative that links up with the study's objectives and research questions and provides more in-depth insights into the analyzed data (Braun & Clarke, 2019). Along with room to perform more reflexive practices, Stage 6 centers interpretation as the main activity.

In the present study, the finalized themes were aimed to be presented with as many elaborate descriptions as possible, each of which was accompanied by illustrative excerpts from the semi-structured interview transcript, solicited journal entries, and participant-generated observation reports. Illustrative excerpts, shared to support each theme, served to ground the themes in the participant's perspectives of the studied intersectionality. By that means, it was aimed to ensure that transparency and authenticity were present in the process of reporting findings. Study findings were presented in a methodical and rigorous manner thanks to the use of MAXQDA in arranging and obtaining pertinent data extracts as supportive illustrations. In addition

to these, the connections between themes were also explored and considered to offer a holistic understanding of the participant's lived experiences and perspectives. Reflexive practices were still preserved and sustained throughout this process as well. Hereby, it was aimed to ensure that the narrative stood by the participant's perspectives, as well as echoing the researcher's own interpretations of the findings. Stage 6 concluded by connecting the findings with the research questions and conceptual frameworks of the study, aiming that the finalized themes addressed the fundamental objectives of the study. Accordingly, each of the final themes was considered with reference to the guiding concepts of the study, illustrating how the participant's experiences and perspectives aligned with, went against, or extended existing insights from the relevant literature. Through this process, both the contextualization of the established literature and the accentuation of the possible contributions of the present study were aimed to be provided in order to enhance the understanding of the studied phenomenon. By situating the findings within the particular context of the participant as well as the broader scholarly discourse, the relevance and significance targeted with this study were aimed to be articulated.

3.6. Validity Checks

Lincoln and Guba (1985) argue that validity checks are crucial in qualitative research for enhancing the reliability and credibility of study findings. Similarly, according to Creswell and Poth (2016), to reduce the possibility of subjectivity and biases on the part of the researcher, validity checks are fundamental in qualitative research. Researchers can improve the overall quality of their study by enhancing the rigor and trustworthiness of their data interpretation and reporting processes through multiple methods of validation.

As aforementioned, validity and credibility of qualitative study findings can be reinforced by correlating them and demonstrating the robustness of the researcher's interpretations by triangulating data from multiple sources (Morse et al., 2002). In addition, through reflexivity, member checking, and peer debriefing (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Merriam, 2009; Morse et al., 2002), i.e., engaging in methodological transparency (Silverman, 2015), validity of a qualitative investigation can also be

strengthened. Advisory supervision and professional consultation are also considered helpful in that sense. Researchers can enhance the overall rigor and credibility of their investigation process by collaborating with experienced mentors and professional consultants, who can offer them essential methodological skills and strategies for research, quality assurance procedures, and critical feedback on the process (Maxwell, 2013). Reflexivity is observed to appear as another methodological strategy qualitative researchers opt to employ to support the validity of their investigation (Guba, 1981). Assisting researchers with the ability of avoiding their researcher subjectivity (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018), defined by Marshall and Rossman (2016) as the influence of researcher's background, personal biases, perspectives, and previous encounters on the research process, reflexive practices play a critical role in enhancing the validity of qualitative research (Charmaz, 2014).

3.6.1. Advisory Supervision

Novice researchers may fail to achieve ethical, academic, and investigative excellence definitively due to their lack of scholarly experience. Shamo and Dunigan (2000) argue that researchers must put particular emphasis on ethical considerations not only in their own research endeavors but also when advising their students on conducting research. As the researcher of this study is a master's student, which renders him a novice researcher, advisory supervision by professional senior scholars was imperative for the sake of the grounded continuity of the entire research process. Together with the supervisor of the study, the researcher was also willingly mentored by a formal co-advisor. That is, aligning with the departmental regulations and procedures of METU, the present study was collaboratively conducted by the researcher, the supervisor, and the co-advisor. Periodically arranged sessions were held to discuss the research process, as well as keeping a joint track of everything planned. In addition to that, formal and informal gatherings were performed by all three to elaborate on the methodological aspects of the research as well. Maintaining rigor and trustworthiness (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018), this collaborative endeavor facilitated the research process by conjunctly navigating ethical considerations, mitigating bias, and enhancing the reliability of the study (Morse et al., 2002).

3.6.2. Professional Consultation

In order to enhance the validity and rigor of research studies conducted by novice researchers, professional consultation, i.e., expert opinion, is essential to be included in the process of research design in particular. As aforementioned, the present study was already supervised by an advisor and a co-advisor. In addition to that, professional consultation was also employed to enhance the overall quality of the research process. Upon collaboratively finalizing the tentative design, research questions, data collection instruments, and procedures to be employed in the study were shared with two other scholars in the field, who are efficaciously familiar with the research topic and study objectives, on the purpose of receiving extra professional critical feedback on improving the process. Accordingly, research design, methodological procedures, and ethical considerations were revised by the researcher, advisor, and co-advisor of the study in alignment with the constructive feedback provided by the professionals that the process was consulted with.

3.6.3. Reflexivity

Padgett (2008) elucidates reflexivity as the ability to examine one's self. Throughout the research process, maintaining methodological rigor in qualitative studies is considered to require reflexivity by the researcher as well. By means of reflexivity, researchers get the opportunity to reduce the impact of their subjectivity, accept it, clarify it, or make use of it (Gentles et al., 2014). Reflexive practices, according to Olmos-Vega et al. (2022), are rooted in an attitude that values subjectivity and pushes researchers to examine their influence on the field.

As previously discussed under researcher positionality, the researcher made much effort to acknowledge the potential subjectivity arising from shared individual, cultural, and professional identities with the participant. These shared identities could have significantly influenced the construction of knowledge during the investigation process due to common underlying beliefs and values. In order to optimize the potential benefits of this unique researcher positionality, the researcher kept periodic voice memos that facilitated the process of remaining cognizant of his own potential

biases and influencing perspectives. Overall research process, data collection procedures, interview sessions with the participant, data analysis procedures, interpretation and reporting of the data, and the writing process were all reflected on in the voice recordings kept biweekly by the researcher. It is also important to note that researcher subjectivity was not tried to be erased entirely, which is considered detrimental to qualitative research. Instead, it was tried to be neutralized and monitored by the researcher through employing personal reflexive practices (Dowling, 2006; Gentles et al., 2014). Eventually, acknowledging the researcher subjectivity and endeavoring to monitor it through reflexivity, another step was taken by the researcher to advertently strengthen the validity of the present study.

3.6.4. Peer Debriefing

Defined by Lincoln and Guba (1985), peer debriefing is:

“The process of exposing oneself to a disinterested peer in a manner paralleling an analytic session and for the purpose of exploring aspects of the inquiry that might otherwise remain only implicit within the inquirer's mind” (p. 308).

Simply put, peer debriefing is a cooperative process through which peer researchers share and debate study findings, interpretations, and methodological strategies of a research design during extensive discussions. These discussions comprise topics pertaining to early data collecting and analysis, data transcripts, subsequent methodological procedures, and the final analysis and interpretation, starting with the initial stages of the investigation (Guba, 1981). Thereby, qualitative researchers are provided with the opportunity to reflect on their research endeavors and receive critical constructive feedback from their fellow researchers through peer debriefing practices. The peer debriefer of the present study was a fellow master's student who was chosen by the researcher, advisor, and co-advisor to debrief the inquiry. Throughout the entire research process, several stages of the inquiry were included and discussed in the debriefing sessions by the researcher and peer debriefer on the purpose of enhancing the credibility and validity of the whole investigation (Spillett, 2003). Also, the peer debriefer identifies herself as cisHet, both cisgender (coined by

Dana Defosse in 1994) and heterosexual, embracing the gender she was assigned at birth and being attracted to the people of the opposite sex. She possesses no identity affiliation with the LGBTQI community, which renders her naturally disinterested (Lincoln & Guba, 1985) as a peer debriefer for this study and explains why she was chosen as one (Spillett, 2003).

Four consecutive debriefing sessions were held throughout the research process. The first session was built on discussing the methodological procedures and research design of the inquiry, in which the peer debriefer objectively declared her comments on how the investigation process would be anticipated to proceed and what to do to progress smoothly. The second and third meetings were held as pre-data collection and post-data collection sessions to discuss the eligibility of the data collection instruments and go over the transcripts. In the final debriefing session, the researcher and peer debriefer reviewed the interpretation of the study's collected data to ensure methodological rigor, monitor researcher subjectivity, minimize bias, and enhance credibility (Spillett, 2003).

3.6.5. Data Triangulation

When a research issue is approached from two or more points, it is referred to as triangulation (Flick et al., 2004). As discussed in the scholarly milieu, four types of triangulations are commonly employed in qualitative research. Put bluntly, data triangulation employs multiple data sources in the research process. On the other hand, several researchers, interviewers, investigators, data analysts, or observers are capitalized on to perform investigator triangulation. For theoretical triangulation, multiple theories are adopted to analyze a phenomenon. Lastly, diverse environments are utilized in environmental triangulation to validate study findings. By examining the research questions from several sources of data, the researcher of this study employed the method of data triangulation to validate the credibility of the investigation. As Patton (2014) also emphasizes, combining multiple methods, particularly in social-based qualitative inquiries, provides a more thorough and accurate representation of reality, i.e., the phenomenon under scrutiny. Researchers can obtain a greater comprehension of the topic investigated by utilizing a variety of

views and sources. Furthermore, data triangulation is considered to enhance the rigor and validity of interpretations by enabling researchers to mitigate the biases present in any particular approach. All things considered, data triangulation has thereby been an essential technique of validity in the milieu of qualitative research across an extensive span, enabling a more thorough and nuanced understanding of intricate social phenomena. However, the researcher also acknowledged the criticisms of data triangulation in qualitative research, which highlight that it assumes comparability between data points that may not hold equal weight. Caution is therefore necessary when interpreting convergent findings, as they may reflect flaws in each dataset (Heale & Forbes, 2013). Hereby, data triangulation, selected after a comprehensive evaluation of its advantages and disadvantages among the four methods of triangulation, was employed to enhance the validity of this study. Informed by the relevant literature, this approach was particularly applied during data interpretation to minimize researcher bias as much as possible.

3.6.6. Member Checking

In order to improve transparency in the process of data interpretation, as well as promoting and maintaining the overall validity of the investigation (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Stake, 1995), member checking is suggested. Defined by Birt et al. (2016), member checking, i.e. participant or respondent validation, is a method of validity check wherein participants receive transcripts of interpreted findings back from researchers to verify accuracy and fit with their statements before they are reported so that they too are provided with a voice in the investigation process along with researchers. Lincoln and Guba (1986) define member checking as:

“The process of continuous, informal testing of information by solidifying reactions of respondents to the investigator’s reconstruction of what he or she has been told or otherwise found out and to the constructions offered by other respondents or sources, and a terminal, formal testing of the final care report with a representative sample of stakeholders” (p.77).

On this point, another definition of member checking is provided by Creswell (2005) that goes:

“Member checking is the process in which researcher asks one or more participants in the study to check the accuracy of the account. This check involves taking the findings back to the participants and asking them (in writing or in an interview) about the accuracy of the report. You ask participants about many aspects of the study such as whether the description is complete and realistic, if the themes are accurate to include, and if the interpretations are fair and representative.” (p. 252).

In accordance with all these definitions, member checking is considered a practical method to validate qualitative research studies up one level.

Even though member checking is often considered a method of validity check, it is also criticized to be limiting to the inquiry design and detrimental to participants (Goldblatt et al., 2011). It is argued that it should be included into the investigation process sparingly or not at all, considering studies conducted to explore the perspectives of underprivileged populations, such as the participant of the present study, may be harmed by the member checking process due to explicit confrontation of their own utterances. On the other hand, several investigators of qualitative research argue that member checks are notably salutary for the aforementioned populations of participants (Harper & Cole, 2015).

Considering both its merits and demerits through the research process, member checking was twice and carefully performed in this study. Mainly guided by Creswell (2005; 2007; 2013) and Stake (1995; 2000; 2005), upon conducting the interviews, the researcher shared the transcripts of the sessions with the participant to strengthen their credibility. Findings were also provided to the participant for inspection before they were reported. Additionally, final manuscript was read and approved by her. That way, transparency and the overall validity of the inquiry were reinforced.

3.7. Researcher Positionality

Case studies explore an environment with the aim of understanding it. Punch (2009) argues that a case study offers comprehensive understanding and depiction of actual human behavior in a social context inside a particular natural setting. Illustrated

similarly by Stake (1995), researchers approach the scene eager to set aside presumptions in order to gain a genuine understanding of how actors perform in everyday activities and environments. In qualitative studies, researcher positionality is rather essential in practically all aspects and phases of research. This is due to the fact that it affects the questions researchers pose, the methods they employ, and the interpretations they make (Bourke, 2014). As it is essential for researchers to discern their positionality to latch on to the procedures of collecting, analyzing, interpreting, and reporting data (Lincoln & Guba, 1985), much effort has been put in to attach importance to comprehending, acknowledging, and embracing researcher positionality throughout this entire research process.

Creswell (2013) mentions researcher positionality as the recognition and contemplation of researchers' own background, experiences, biases, and viewpoints, which invariably influence the investigation process and interpretation of findings. Regarding a research endeavor and its social context, positionality relates to both a person's worldview and the stance they take. Like the participant, the researcher of the present study self-identifies as queer as well. Therefore, it was of great importance for the researcher to be cognizant of his positionality in this research process in order to be able to mitigate biases stemming from belonging to the same underprivileged community as the participant regarding their identities. In addition to that, the researcher and the participant share the same cultural and professional identities (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). They both were born and raised, hence exposed to the same sociocultural values from their early childhood to their professional lives as language teachers, which inevitably influenced the research design of this investigation as well. As an aforementioned case in point, purposive sampling was employed in this study due to the researcher's particular interest in addressing this specific research problem as both the participant and the researcher belong with the LGBTQI community, and they share the same educational context as language teaching professionals. In other words, the participant and the researcher of this study share their individual, professional, and cultural identities (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). Carefully contemplating any possible blind spots stemming from shared identities of the participant and the researcher was paid special attention throughout various stages of the research process in order to successfully alleviate them and prevent

them from turning into influencing factors particularly in the processes of data interpretation and reporting.

As argued by Creswell and Poth (2018), researchers can successfully negotiate the intricacies, challenges, and ethical considerations that come with qualitative inquiry by embracing their positionality. Along with acknowledging researcher positionality, several more steps were taken by the researcher toward minimizing researcher bias and maximizing the rigor of the study. Those included reflexivity practices, advisory supervision, professional consultation, member checking, and peer debriefing. Furthermore, careful examination of methodological choices and ongoing transparency and reflexivity (Maxwell, 2013) on the positionality and perspective of the researcher are essential to minimize researcher bias in case studies (Silverman, 2015). In order to ensure that the research objectives were disinterestedly addressed, data were triangulated for this study (Creswell, 2013). In other words, as suggested by Yin (2009), data were collected through more than one instrument to address the research questions, which is a rather prevalent strategy in case study research.

In addition to all these, the researcher sharing the same individual, cultural, and professional identities (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011) with the participant of the study did not only trigger biases and presumptions regarding the whole research process. On the contrary, researchers and participants in qualitative research possessing shared identities offer contributions as well. Those who share the same identities can build mutual trust, reciprocity, and understanding, which may allow for more candid and open communication throughout the research process, facilitating greater insights and more nuanced interpretations of participants' reports. Together with leading to acknowledged biases, shared identities between the researcher and the participant of this study fostered greater self-awareness and reflexivity by the researcher, which subsequently resulted in a more enriched research process and authentic findings as well. Both by the researcher and the participant, this was considered a reason as to why they had a strong sense of mutual trust and intimacy through the execution of steps in the process of this study. Also, by navigating the research process with more sensitivity and cultural competency by virtue of shared identities, as was observed in this study, researchers who share the same identities as their participants get to attain

the opportunity to mitigate power differentials and promote participant empowerment.

In essence, a collaborative research partnership based off of mutual respect and understanding between the researcher and the participant along with a deeper level of trust and rapport were fostered by these shared identities. Researcher bias stemming from the same shared identities was mitigated to the best of the researcher's ability of remaining vigilant in acknowledging the significance of his positionality and maintaining a rigorous process. In addition, reflexive practices performed along the investigation process were also of great assistance in minimizing researcher bias resulting from the researcher's positionality. Although researcher positionality and shared identities were acknowledged and celebrated in this study, further efforts were still put in to eliminate their potential negative impacts as much as possible while benefiting from their possible positive contributions to the study. Such contributions were salient in how the researcher and participant established rapport and trust. Being from the same culture with the participant, having practically the same academic journey with her, and belonging with the same non-conforming community of gender and sexuality have offered valuable first-hand insights to the researcher in terms of understanding and interpreting her narratives at a deeper level. On that note, through acknowledgement and celebration of their presence, researcher positionality and shared identities between the researcher and participant have certainly served more to the richness of findings than potential harms to the study's design. Ultimately, it was ensured that the unique opportunities researcher positionality brought into this study were maximized through benefiting from it as a lens throughout the entire research process instead of being impeded by potential methodological challenges (Charmaz, 2014) brought along with it, which would subsequently pose threats to the reliability and the validity of the investigation (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

3.8. Ethical Considerations

Careful preparation and adherence to ethical principles are considered imperative in qualitative studies in order not to overlook the basic consideration that participants

may feel physically or mentally threatened by unethical behavior (Macrina, 2013). Beyond informal moral dynamics maintained between qualitative researchers and participants, ethics should also officially be implemented into the research process (Creswell, 2013; Creswell & Poth, 2016).

According to Mack et al. (2005), the overall wellbeing of human subjects in research must always come first, and the importance of research questions is always secondary. In other words, the research will be compromised if coerced to choose between jeopardizing a participant or the research, which underscores how important ethics is for qualitative researchers that are visiting private spaces of the world (Stake, 2005). On the substantiality of basic tenets of morality, AERA (American Educational Research Association) (2002) states:

“It is of paramount importance that educational researchers respect the rights, privacy, dignity, and sensitivities of their research populations and also the integrity of the institutions within which the research occurs. Educational researchers should be especially careful in working with children and other vulnerable populations” (p. 3).

Thus, in addition to its essential presence in all research with human subjects, research conducted to explore vulnerable and underprivileged populations should never concede ethics.

Ethical considerations were attached special importance to throughout the entire research process of this study. Although participant confidentiality is argued to be challenging to handle in qualitative research due to difficulties of hiding participant identity, anonymity was consistently secured for the participant along the course of this study. A pseudonym was attributed to the participant as a safeguard. In addition to participant anonymity, all information stated by the participant through the data collection process was kept confidential between the participant, researcher, and peer debriefer of the study. No other individual affiliated with this study, including the advisors and professional consultants, was provided with the data transcripts, which could include identifying information regarding the participant’s identity that was requested to be kept hidden. Defined as “researcher-participant contract” by Dane

(1990), a consent form informing the participant about the entire research process was provided to the participant before the research process commenced. The form included information regarding the research design, data collection tools and procedures, her right to withdraw from the study at any time without justification or consequence, and whom/how to contact regarding her potential concerns and questions. Although multimedia consent forms are lately argued to be acceptable or even superior, the provided informed consent form was a paper-based form that was electronically communicated to the participant. There were no unequal power positions between the researcher and the participant, nor was there any form of material or moral remuneration offered by the researcher to the participant. Hereby, participation in the present study was entirely voluntarily performed. Without including a third party, participation consent was given by the participant as she possesses the physical and mental capacity to consent herself. Also, no vulnerable subject was explored in this study. Melisa is an adult, who does not at all need a legal guardian. In order to have it ratified by a legally dependable agency that appropriate steps were taken by the researcher to protect the participant, ethics committee approval, often argued to be of great significance for studies conducted to explore human subjects, was obtained for this study from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of METU on 10/04/2024 upon previously providing the committee with all required Human Subjects Ethics Committee (HSEC) forms in full. Eventually, ethical considerations were carefully addressed in this study. These included the careful application of established ethical principles, adherence to relevant institutional guidelines and disciplinary regulations, and the implementation of robust measures to protect the participant's rights, welfare, anonymity, and autonomy. This helped ensure that the study's methodological procedures and subsequent analyses were legitimate and ethically sound (Tolich & Tumilty, 2021).

CHAPTER 4

FINDINGS

The present investigation aims to provide insights into a university-level LGBTQI language educator's perspectives of her identity negotiation, experience navigation, and the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism. Findings presented in this chapter are guided by the following research questions:

RQ1: From the perspective of an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context, how does heteroprofessionalism, if any, manifest itself within her workplace context?

RQ2: How does an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context negotiate her identities and navigate her professional experiences within her heteroprofessional workplace context?

The first research question investigates the manifestation of the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism in Melisa's workplace environment. More in particular, in what ways heteroprofessionalism is practiced and how she encounters the concept is inquired about. This question mainly draws on Mizzi's (2013) newly coined concept of heteroprofessionalism as its primary framework. On the other hand, the second research question examines the intersectionality of Melisa's identity plurality negotiation, professional experience navigation, and heteroprofessionalism. Acknowledging the idea of multiple identities' intersectionality, Crenshaw's (1989) concept of intersectionality was drawn on as the primary framework of this question. Nevertheless, it is important to note that the employment of the intersectionality concept does not directly aim at referring to race, gender, and identity in this study, as the original school of thought represents. Rather, it is acknowledged in this study that the intersectionality of multiple identities might as well be caused by any set of

identities. Also, intersectionality by Crenshaw (1989) as a framework should not be mistaken for the intersectionality of identity, experience, and heteroprofessionalism the present study seeks to investigate, since they refer to different understandings of intersectionality. Following Braun and Clarke's (2006) RTA framework in the process of data analysis, the findings are presented below in this chapter under each research question, accompanied by illustrative data extracts and the researcher's remarks on them. All excerpts have their own unique codes with abbreviations and numbers. While "Int" refers to "interview", "JE" means "journal entry", and "PGOR" denotes "participant-generated observation report". "E" refers to "excerpt" in all cases. Numbers are added to all excerpts to list them for reference. To illustrate, "Int1E1" would correspond to "Interview1 – Excerpt1".

4.1. Research Question 1

According to Melissa, heteroprofessionalism manifests itself in various forms within her workplace context. She reports her own perspectives and experiences of the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism in her workspace. First and foremost, she comes to realization of her positioning as an LGBTQI language educator due to prevalent heteroprofessional practices, experiences, and microaggressions. In addition to that, some of the themes from analyzed data revealing her perspectives on her heteroprofessional workspace emerge as perception of heteroprofessionalism, perceived dangers of heteroprofessionalism, professional experiences of heteronormativity, institutional exclusion and microaggressions, acknowledging the impact of heteroprofessionalism, allyship and aloofness at the workplace, and resisting heteroprofessionalism.

4.1.1. Realization of Her Positioning

Melisa always remains aware of her own "lasting effect" (*Int1E1*) as an LGBTQI language educator at her workplace. Compared to her cis-heterosexual colleagues, she must do that to merely survive. When at work, Melisa is always alert. This state of compulsory constant alertness even impacts the rapport and personal relationships she builds with her students and colleagues. She is very conscious of how she is

perceived by all the stakeholders around her workplace environment as a non-conforming individual to heteronormative ideologies, assumptions, and expectations. She has no time to rest. Melisa always needs to have her guard up.

Oh, by trying to survive. It's like survival 102, not 101 anymore because we're a little bit more advanced than that. I have to think about my own lasting effect and my own survival at any given point no matter the circumstance. Another instructor who lives a heteronormative life doesn't have to think about these things, but I have to think about every interaction I have, like, to think about whether I will let them add me on Instagram or even on LinkedIn. You should be able to let your students connect you on LinkedIn. But the stuff I have to share and the talks they will have. On dating apps, when I was single in here, I was on dating apps. But I was so scared I had to buy all the premiums because I didn't want them to see it. What can you do? You got to think about everything (Int1E1).

Melisa realizes that her non-conforming gender and sexual identities come first even at work. They have a huge determining impact on how she navigates even her personal life that could bite her back in her professional life.

It could be a challenge for a very heteronormative English teacher too, but even more so it becomes a challenge for someone like me (Int1E2).

She compares her experiences to her cis-heterosexual colleagues' experiences as well (Int1E2). Much as she acknowledges common challenges, Melisa expresses that "someone like her" (Int1E2) is uniquely affected by heteroprofessionalism.

I am the resident "social justice critical pedagogy" expert here. This often means I'm handed anything related to diversity and inclusion. As the queer teacher around here, though they don't care, they still tend to bring anything diversity/inclusion-related stuff to me. The only reason they do this is they know I'm queer, and they think just because of my personal identity, I must be the one that's supposed to be knowledgeable about these issues (Int2E1).

Melisa is well aware of her positioning as an LGBTQI language educator, or as she puts, "as the queer teacher around" (Int2E1), at her workspace. She realizes that she is labeled with her sexual identity at her workplace context.

Hetero norms are quite applicable at our professional workplace, and I often sound and look out of those norms (Int2E2).

She highlights the prevalence of “hetero norms” (Int2E2) at her workplace environment to make it clear that she is “different”, more in particular, non-conforming to those norms.

Since she (a student) thought I looked “queer” enough for that to be “fine”. It was a nightmare (Int2E3).

In addition to comparing her own experiences to cis-heterosexual colleagues’ experiences of the same workspace, Melisa also believes her positioning as an LGBTQI female-bodied instructor also affects her interactions with her students (Int2E3) at her heteroprofessional workplace context.

Then, there is this other stuff, like, your interactions with your co-workers. For example, I have a coworker here and her husband is our coordinator, and I feel like I am the only one she's comfortable with when it comes to being in the same room with the guy. She has this understanding, and I understand her thinking. Don't get me wrong but, like, I should still be considered as danger as much as the other ladies, but I'm not. I mean, I like it. I like to be the friend but yeah (Int1E3).

How her colleagues view her is also acknowledged by Melisa (Int1E3). Along with her students, another stakeholder is found to be involved in her realization of her positioning.

So if you're living in a very, I don't want to say shallow, but if you're living in a very sequestered life where you have only met the people exactly like you and nothing more, nothing less, nothing different, nothing alternate, then, that means, I, who is going to be your co-worker, working at the same level as you, we are not going to get along pretty well (JE2E1).

Her LGBTQI identity is determining Melisa’s current professional trajectory. Her sexual identity plays a determining role on her interactions with people at her workplace environment (JE2E1).

She is conscious of how she is perceived and viewed by the stakeholders at her workplace environment. Along with her professional identity, she is also “the one”. Melisa, at the end of the day, is “the queer teacher around” (Int2E1), and she realizes that.

4.1.2. Perception of Heteroprofessionalism

Melisa perceives heteroprofessionalism as a socially constructed notion. According to her perception of the concept, it is merely “a fake idea” (*Int1E4*). As a female-bodied professional language educator, Melisa acknowledges the societal status quo and thinks that heteroprofessionalism predetermines the expectations and assumptions of her presence in her social context. She believes that heteroprofessionalism helps perpetuate the idea of stereotypical female-bodied English language teachers in the Turkish context. Melisa is in disbelief of heteroprofessionalism.

Heteroprofessionalism is a fake idea of how we should be acting at work. Like, that's the norm, that's the default and everything else is “not norm”, abnormal, or nonconforming. This is not true, obviously, but this is how it is at the moment. For example, as a woman, as a young woman language educator, there are certain stereotypes around us. People think English teachers are very popular with “men”. For example, we have, there's this stereotype in Turkey, that they should be pregnant all the time. You have heard this before, right? For example, the makeup, the hair, the Instagram accounts, etc., and I do not conform into any of these things (Int1E4).

First of all, she thinks the concept predefines our expected actions at the workplace, and this is normalized. In addition, according to Melisa, heteroprofessionalism is fake (*Int1E4*). She believes in the social construction of the concept. Through its normalization, all other forms of identity enactments are marginalized. She is not in approval of this marginalization, nor does she think that the marginalized is abnormal. Also, she thinks that being a female-bodied English teacher comes with predetermined expectations within the Turkish context (*Int1E4*). Melisa does not align with the expectations and socially attributed heteronormative characteristics of a female-bodied English teacher in her cultural context. Though she is content with her non-conforming state to such expectations, they result in a form of alienation from her professional identity.

They (female-bodied English teachers in the Turkish context) don't talk about their personal lives. They only “entice” students. Lots of students have crush on them. Believe me when I tell you this is not the reality for my situation, which I'm quite happy with, but I fall out of line with that. So, I-, what I do

think is it's very false but lots of people believe this automatically because they don't question it. The moment they start questioning, they realize they themselves don't actually fit in these categories. Until they actually question it, they think this is the default (Int1E5).

Heteronormative societal attributions of characteristics and cultural definitions to her profession as a female-bodied language educator do not define Melisa (Int1E5). She is quite happy with her non-conforming state to those expectations. However, she is also alienated from her professional identity along the way. She thinks she falls out of line with those expectations. Melisa is not cis-heterosexual and does not have a husband. She is not concerned with her outlook, nor does she have popular, aesthetically appealing social media accounts on fashionable platforms. She does not follow the socially predefined ideas of a female-bodied English teacher in the Turkish culture, which makes her fall out of line (Int1E5) and alienate her from her own profession.

Yes, it's (heteroprofessionalism) definitely there. Everyone else knows this too but only realized it recently when they started working with me (Int2E4).

However, according to Melisa, she is not the only non-conforming one in the game. Heteroprofessionalism is not undeniable only for her in her workplace. Not necessarily relating to a non-conforming sexuality, others also realize their non-conforming aspects when they start questioning heteroprofessionalism. Working with her assists some of her colleagues in realizing how intensely heteroprofessionalism actually is manifested at their workplace environment (Int2E4). The only reason they think it is the default is that they do not question it, according to Melisa.

4.1.3. Perceived Dangers of Heteroprofessionalism

Melisa thinks heteroprofessionalism is dangerous in two different forms. First it is dangerous because of the impact it has on critical thinking skills and the quality of education. It makes people less of critical thinkers (Int2E5) and has a detrimental impact on the quality of language education they are provided with in the Turkish context. These two have an ongoing interplay.

Systematically, critical thinking is undermined by practicing heteroprofessionalism at workplaces. Heteroprofessionalism makes people less critical, less analytical, and less aware. They don't think things through. This affects both faculty and students' ability to think critically and adapt to situations. In turn, this affects the overall quality of education students are provided with. It's no wonder that Turkey has the lowest English proficiency rate in Europe (Int2E5).

She thinks this is systematic. People are made less critical and analytical through practice of heteroprofessionalism (Int2E5). They are made less aware of the things they are surrounded with. By people, Melisa refers to both students and faculty. She is not only concerned about students, but she is also concerned that faculty are made less critical and analytical as well. Heteroprofessionalism influences the way people think, according to Melisa. Due to its practice, people do not tend to think things through. As a result of this, the overall quality of education provided to students is also lowered (Int2E5). Melisa directly links this to her country's low English proficiency rate. From her point of view as a language educator, though indirectly, heteroprofessionalism is detrimental to her people's proficiency level of the English language, since both students learning it and the faculty teaching it are negatively affected by the concept's practice in educational institutions.

Another danger of heteroprofessionalism is directly about herself. According to Melisa, her LGBTQI identity makes her vulnerable to threats and dangers from stakeholders (JE1E1), which might negatively affect her professional career.

Most recently, I've been dealing with two students who were very close to me until they got a low grade and turned on me. They have complained about me to all my superiors, threatened to take their complaints to CIMER (Presidential Communication Center of Turkey), and they even wrote a whooping 8-page report on my so-called problematic behavior. They did all this, and I know for a fact they would have done worse if I had openly told them I was queer or even implied it. This is because these students know that they can hurt someone's career, livelihood and maybe even freedom if they can make an accusation about queer identity, anti-government regime propaganda or something that relates to this. I felt like they had this sick power over me. I combed through my social media accounts over and over again because I knew they would use whatever they can find there. I am not hiding myself actively, but I am incredibly careful with how I share my truth. To live and survive in these lands, and to have a decent career means to hide and effectively knock some of your most beautiful parts out. Experiences like

these wound me. They determine the next time I am being authentic in class (I won't be); the next time I help a queer student (I won't); the next time I take a stand against the system (I might not) (JE1E1).

In addition to the danger it holds toward both students' and faculty's critical and analytical thinking process and the overall quality of language education provided in the Turkish context, Melisa also think heteroprofessionalism is dangerous on a personal level. It creates a pressure on her agency and advocate identity. According to her experience with two of her students (JE1E1), she faces unfavorable aftermath due to simple professional incidents. She was threatened to be complained about to CIMER (Presidential Communication Center of Turkey), which could have cost her entire career, considering the legal power that this governmental organization holds. Melisa thinks those students who got low grades turned against her because of her LGBTQI identity (JE1E1). Since students are aware of the contextual power they have over an LGBTQI teachers professional career, Melisa associates their demeanor and the chain of actions they took to her LGBTQI identity. From her point of view, those students could have done even worse if they had known of her sexual identity explicitly. Therefore, she puts a distinction between how she enacts her multiple identities. She separates her personal identity from her professional identity. Though she does not actively hide her sexual identity at her workspace, she remains careful and on guard.

This is not just with students, in fact, most of the time, you can be just fine with students. But you need to be able to talk to your fellow language educators and be a good manipulator. For example, I know for a fact, if you want to make a friend out of a co-worker, you need to ask for their help with small stuff that they can easily do, manipulation 101, stuff like this (JE2E2).

Melisa is actually mostly on good terms with her students. She thinks it is not that difficult for her to be on good terms with her students (JE2E2). However, in order to eliminate the dangers of heteroprofessionalism coming from her colleagues, she manipulates them, and she thinks it is important to be a good manipulator as an LGBTQI language educator. Asking for help with the simple things she is usually sure that they are capable of doing is a form of manipulative strategy (JE2E2) she employs to avoid dangers of heteroprofessional practices that might come from her colleagues. Again, Melisa is on constant guard.

4.1.4. Professional Experience of Heteronormativity

I had seen lots of heteronormativity (Int1E6).

Melisa utters the above sentence (Int1E6) while talking about the heteronormative experiences she has had at her workplace environments. During the second interview on Zoom, she brought up how she would like to have her pronouns up on her official Zoom title (Int2E7). Some of her colleagues do this. They have no fear or do not go through second thoughts and careful consideration. As Melisa states, ironically, this started as a queer movement. In support of transsexual individuals and their right to their preferred pronouns, often different than their birth attribute pronouns, people around the world started putting their preferred (or attributed but acknowledged) pronouns next to their names on social media platforms such as Instagram, X, Snapchat, Skype, or more professional virtual platforms such as Zoom, LinkedIn, and Teams. Herewith, transsexual people were considered to feel better and unexcluded with regard to their preferences on their own pronouns.

I see you have your pronouns written here on your official Zoom work account. Believe me, I would love to do that. And you know what, even some colleagues of mine here do it. But if I were to put my pronouns, it would be something very different than what I appear to be, and I know very well that this would cost me heavily. This is a work account, and I cannot even put my pronouns on my profile (Int2E7).

Upon seeing the researcher's pronouns up on his Zoom account next to his name during an interview session, Melisa expressed her willingness to do the same (Int2E7). However, she is afraid to do so. As an LGBTQI, Melisa does not feel comfortable putting her pronouns next to her name on her official Zoom account for work. She is concerned about the possible consequences she might face at her workplace if she puts the pronouns that conflict with her outlook, considering she is not a cis-heterosexual-looking person. She is non-conforming to such heteronormative norms and worried that this non-conformity would cost her issues at her workplace.

Coworkers are a married straight couple. We were all discussing our Friday night plans. They said they were probably going to have a quiet night in. I

talked about wanting to go see the new Venom movie with my girlfriend. We exchanged pleasantries and went about our day. Saturday night mind-numbing Instagram scrolling showed me stories of these coworkers hanging out with another married couple coworkers; the wife of the couple is one of our coordinators. On Monday, I got the extra, unpaid invitation duties even though my friends- the straight couple- were available as well. When I complained about this to an unrelated coworker, she said being chummy with the coordinator pans out. I wasn't chummy with the coordinator because, for example, me and my girlfriend were not invited to the Friday night out. They said it was a "couples thing." (PGORIE1).

Her colleagues lied to Melisa about how they would spend their Friday night by telling her that they would stay in (PGORIE1). Melisa and her girlfriend were not even considered a couple by her colleagues. Melisa's colleagues implicitly expressed that by not inviting them to the event and calling it a "couples thing" (PGORIE1) afterward. Though they only implied it through their words and actions, this is an explicit experience of heteronormativity.

Husbands only come with wives, or doctor is a he and nurse is a she, or general language teacher stuff that we have to encounter and then break apart. Why do you think it was a she? Sometimes in class a boy says "I have a girlfriend, he name is..". This is an English issue, but as soon as he says this, his other guy friends start laughing. They start laughing because they are actually "a little bit" homophobic. They don't know what it is yet but like, on that harmful scale of homophobia, they're at the bottom, yes, okay, but they don't know it yet (Int1E7).

In addition to how she experiences it with her colleagues and administrators, Melisa also encounters heteronormativity through her professional discipline. As a language educator, she criticizes the material they use for perpetuating heteronormativity. In jobs units, Melisa relates portraying nurses as she/her and doctors as he/him to heteronormativity. In all materials, husbands having only wives and wives having only husbands is also criticized by Melisa. Also, she acknowledges that her students are homophobic too sometimes (Int1E7). Apparently, she is struggling with calling them out for being homophobic, as she thinks they are just "a little bit homophobic" (Int1E7). The example instance above (Int1E7) about her student calling her girlfriend a "he" and his friends laughing at it is directly related to the English language, which Melisa teaches. English language has binary gender pronouns attributed to female and male sexes. This is an instance Melisa encounters due to the

pronoun system the language she teaches has. It is unlikely that a math teacher encounters such an instance in the Turkish context. The heteronormativity Melisa experiences at work also appears to be related to her profession as a language educator, and she intervenes in such unintentional microaggressions from students. As their teacher, she breaks apart the topics when such instances occur. Melisa is proactive, and from her point of view, being a language educator is one of the reasons why she is being proactive. She employs the question-posing strategy to encourage her students to think critically on their own words and actions.

4.1.5. Institutional Exclusion and Microaggressions

Due to her LGBTQI identity, Melisa experiences instances of exclusion and microaggression at her workplace environment. Heteroprofessionalism derives from heteronormativity, and heteronormativity tends to exclude those that do not conform with its norms from social contexts. Melisa is excluded from some social interactions at her workspace as a result of heteronormativity, which she confronts with due to her LGBTQI identity. In addition to that, she also experiences instances of microaggression at work. Discrimination manifested through microaggressions are often considered subtle, indirect, or even unintentional. However, at the end of the day, it is certainly a very detrimental form of discrimination against minority groups. Microaggressions further marginalize underprivileged communities and help perpetuate their oppression. At workspaces, heteroprofessionalism might also be communicated through microaggressions. Accordingly, Melisa confronts exclusion and microaggressions at her workplace:

I have tried my best in navigating these relationships but honestly sometimes, more often than not, in fact, I get the feeling everyone is in on a joke that I'm not on, that I don't know anything about. Sometimes, I feel like there are subtle nuances that I will never be able to touch personally because I don't understand them, or if someone was to tell me about them explicitly, I would judge it, would not find a rationale behind it, or would just not comply with it (JE2E3)

Here, exclusion comes from within. At least, it is intrinsically supported. Considering she refers to her colleagues by the use of indefinite pronouns “everyone” (JE2E3)

and “someone” (JE2E3), Melisa feels like an outsider at work. She constantly feels as if she is missing out on social cues. Her state of having a “different” identity than most of her colleagues makes her feel excluded. She feels that “everyone” (JE2E3) is united. They all share things through social interactions. However, Melisa is not included. First, she feels incompetent about catching the “nuances” (JE2E3) of social interactions her colleagues have. Moreover, no one attempts to explain anything in effort of inclusion. However, even if they did, Melisa thinks she would not be able to understand. Further, she would judge them. At this point, the exclusion is intrinsically supported as well. In addition to her colleagues’ apathy and inaction with regard to including her, Melisa herself feels misfit around them. Let alone feeling misfit, she thinks she would be judgmental toward their sense and performance of interaction at the workplace.

She is explicitly excluded in the instance where she and her girlfriend were not invited to the “couples” Friday night out (PGORIE1). Her colleagues arrange a social event to spend time together out of work and do not let her know about it, since it was a “couples thing” (PGORIE1). Melisa’s exclusion in this instance does not have anything to do with how she feels or thinks about it. This is rather directly extrinsic and intentional. Her relationship with her girlfriend does not render them a couple in the eyes of her colleagues. Moreover, this is explicitly expressed. While this is an instance of a social exclusion, coming from colleagues relates it to her workplace. Considering that the couples arranging and participating in this event are in cis-heterosexual relationships, their motive behind excluding Melisa and her girlfriend from the event is their heteronormative mindsets. Melisa reacts to this act of social exclusion by not mentioning her girlfriend at her workplace environment. In fact, she started avoiding discussions about relationships altogether.

I started to stop including my girlfriend in my sentences. In fact, I started avoiding discussions about relationships altogether. Next time, I will directly reject any extra duty though (PGORIE2).

Although Melisa’s thoughts and feelings are not the point of origin of this social exclusion, she adds up to it by isolating herself by hanging back on discussions on

relationships and not including her girlfriend in such relevant dialogues with her colleagues (*PGORIE2*).

In addition to social exclusions, Melisa also confronts microaggressions from the stakeholders at her workspace.

*At the start of the semester, we had an opening ceremony attended by the rector and some other high-profile officials. While working at the event, I heard a colleague, looking toward me, say, "I hope some of us don't attract negative attention." I know he said this just because he knows how hetero norms are quite applicable at our professional workplace and I often sound and look out of those norms. He wanted to make me feel bad for nothing there. Ironically, I was the only one who had a one-on-one with the rector later, who didn't seem to know or care about my identity, strangely. However, these microaggressions accumulate and are exhausting (*Int2E8*).*

In this instance, she is publicly shamed at her workplace due to her LGBTQI identity. Though it is performed subtly and indirectly, it is still an attack toward her presence at the ceremony (*Int2E8*). Also, she is well aware of the fact that her colleague does this because they know she is a non-conforming looking and sounding educator working at an institution where cis-heterosexual norms, i.e., heteronormativity is frequently practiced (*Int2E8*). She also thinks that the colleague attacks her identity in this instance because they want to make her feel bad for no reason. At this point, the sole motive of microaggression in this instance is purely ill-intentioned. However, Melisa resists and reacts to this microaggressive attack from her colleague. She is being verbally responsive to her attacker, which implies she acknowledges that the attack is definitely targeted toward her though there was no direct sign of it other than the attacker looking toward her way. Melisa finds it “ironic” to be the only one to have a private meeting with the authority figure in this instance, and she also finds their indifference toward her LGBTQI identity “strange” (*Int2E8*).

Married colleagues were given extra breaks and leniency, but I was overburdened simply because I was single and queer. They had partners and they were considered in relationships as they were in heterosexual marriages. On the other hand, I was not even considered in a relationship with my girlfriend as a “female” in their eyes. When I complained, the

heteroprofessional principal did not even talk through this with me but made his wife do it for him in his own office. The woman told me that I was actually lucky I was not dealing with men, and I was also lucky that I couldn't get legally married, which she said sucked (Int2E9).

Here, she is assigned with extra duties and cannot benefit from the extra breaks her cis-heterosexually married colleagues are provided with. They are entitled to this flexibility thanks to their official marital status. On the other hand, let alone being legally permitted to marry her girlfriend, Melisa was not even considered in a relationship by her administrators at work (Int2E9). Consequently, she was assigned with extra duties as a single, time-wise flexible employee. In this instance, Melisa is reacting to the attack again. When she complains about the situation to her superiors at work, her “heteroprofessional principal” is not even willing to talk with her about it. Instead, he is having his wife do it for him. Not being willing to communicate with your teacher as someone with an administrative title is microaggressive itself. On top of that, the wife makes the situation worse by telling Melisa she is lucky that she does not deal with men (Int2E9). She implies her awareness of Melisa’s LGBTQI identity through sarcasm. This stands as another form of microaggression in this instance. At the end, the wife also hints at her awareness of Melisa’s LGBTQI identity and her non-cis-heterosexual relationship by articulating the legal barrier she has to marriage, which manifests as the last microaggressive attack in this instance.

Upon hearing that I would get a small stipend due to my mother's recent death and her social security, a male coworker jokingly said it was sexist that only girls would get this monthly stipend and not sons of the deceased. When I told him that only unmarried daughters are paid this money, he said that this made more sense as the husband would be able to take care of the wife, so she wouldn't need money. Two female coworkers were there too, and one agreed with him (PGOR2E1).

The third instance demonstrates a different form of microaggressive attack. While the first one (Int2E8) includes a public attack and the second one (Int2E9) is more private, Melisa is verbally attacked by a male colleague in a more conversational manner during a social interaction at work (PGOR2E1). Upon bringing up the stipend she receives due to her mother’s loss, the attacker starts with commenting on the issue by saying that it is sexist how only daughters of the deceased get this stipend but not the sons, which is the case in Turkey. Melisa responds by saying that

it is only those daughters who are not married that could get the stipend. After that, the male colleague goes on to make his hetero-sexist remark that it makes sense as the husbands would take care of their wives in such cases. One of the female coworkers in the context agrees with his comment. Furthermore, he makes the situation even more awkward by saying that it is great for Melisa and her girlfriend that they can keep the stipend coming in until their own death. In this statement (PGOR2E1), Melisa's legal barrier to marriage with an LGBTQI relationship is underscored again by someone else at her workplace environment. He makes his last attack subtly as he is leaving the scene. It is linguistically quite indirect too, which microaggressions often tend to be. However, once again, Melisa is being verbally responsive to the attack.

My best work friend and I were drinking our teas at the café during a break. We were joking about how I hadn't slept because I was up all night-not from fun activities, but due to writing and grading. One of my friends joked that her husband would not let a night of not sleeping go to waste, so I jokingly said my girlfriend wouldn't either. During this chatting, another friend was chit-chatting with a male instructor from an engineering department. I do not even know the guy's name. He interrupted our conversation to ask me, "Is it better to be a lesbian than be with men?" He meant to say, "have sex," I think, but thought better of it (PGOR4E1).

The last instance (PGOR4E1) shows a similar situation to the third one, except with more of a linguistically direct manner. While Melisa and her work friends are joking about their sex lives with their partners during their break, an irrelevant male colleague, whose name she does not even know, asks her if it is better "to be a lesbian than be with men" (PGOR4E1). The question comes out of the blue unexpectedly and interrupts Melisa and her work friends' friendly conversation. Melisa is aware that he means to refer to having sex. However, Melisa responds by saying that yes, it is better, as women do not tend to pose inappropriate questions to her. First, the male colleague assumes Melisa's sexual identity and attributes lesbianism to her by only knowing that she is in a non-conforming, non-cis-heterosexual relationship with a woman. On top of that, although being a total stranger, he does not pull back from making his remark about the sex life she has in her non-conforming relationship. Melisa thinks that male colleague is incorrigible, since she does not believe he is communicated the intended effect of the laughter

Melisa's response to him brought to the context. Ultimately, Melisa is being verbally responsive to another microaggressive attack.

Her experiences reveal various instances where she encounters subtly LGBTQI-phobic, direct/indirect, and intentional/unintentional non-physical attacks to her LGBTQI identity within her workplace environment. Since they might foster a hostile atmosphere that would threaten her sense of safety and professional validity, LGBTQI-phobic microaggressions toward her identity in the workplace may pose detrimental effects on her identities. Such subtle, often inadvertent kinds of discrimination might weaken her self-esteem and psychological well-being. This jaundiced climate also hinders her capacity to fully interact with her students and colleagues. Considering her discipline as a language educator depends on teaching and promoting communication and connection, this can negatively impact her professional performance and well-being. Also as seen in the previously shared instances, by conveying the message that her identity is undesirable or inferior, these microaggressions contribute to a culture of exclusion and deter her from speaking up courageously and comfortably at her workplace environment.

All these instances of institutional exclusion and microaggressions (*JE2E*; *PGOR1E2*; *Int2E8*; *Int2E9*; *PGOR2E1*; *PGOR4E1*) demonstrate how they can come in various forms. Melisa is microaggressively attacked by multiple people at her workplace environment from her colleagues to her administrative institutional superiors due to heteroprofessionalism. Some take place publicly (*Int2E8*), while some require private talk (*Int2E9*). Some occur in more conversational manners in social contexts at work (*PGOR2E1*; *PGOR4E1*), while some are practiced through one-on-one meetings (*Int2E9*). However, there are two common patterns in all these instances of institutional exclusion and microaggressive attacks. They are performed by male colleagues, and Melisa is being responsive. Except for the second one (*Int2E9*), wherein the male administrative institutional superior is getting his wife to have the actual conversation with her, Melisa is directly attacked by male colleagues' microaggressive attacks in all instances. The second instance demonstrates indirect microaggression by the male administrative institutional superior through avoidance of direct conversation with Melisa as her institutional authority as well. At this point,

all instances include male figures' microaggressive attacks. Moreover, in all these cases of institutional exclusion and microaggressions, Melisa is being verbally responsive. She responds back to her colleagues' exclusion attempts and microaggressive attacks through mostly sarcastic conversational manners. She shows that she is neither silent nor can be silenced by these attempts and attacks. She chooses to claim her ground by being explicitly responsive to almost all instances of institutional exclusion attempts and microaggressive attacks rooted in heteroprofessionalism at her workplace environment.

4.1.6. Acknowledging the Impact of Heteroprofessionalism

There are several instances where heteroprofessionalism has affected me greatly (Int2E10).

Melisa acknowledges heteroprofessionalism manifests itself intensely at her workplace environment. She is aware she works at a heteroprofessional institution. She also knows that she is affected by it (Int2E10). Her professional experiences, including her social interactions with her students, colleagues, and institutional superiors, shape her perception of working at a heteroprofessional institution as an LGBTQI language educator. She feels that heteroprofessionalism is certainly there, and she is under its constant influence.

Anything out of the perceived norm of a “female’ English teacher” becomes a topic of gossip and often leads to being called to the director’s office for the smallest things. It’s exhausting (Int2E11).

As aforementioned, according to Melisa, Turkish culture requires young, female English language teachers to embrace the feminine fancy. By feminine fancy, engaging with men, being concerned with hair, make-up, outfit, having popular and aesthetically appealing social media accounts, being married, having a husband, being pregnant, and having children is meant. Melisa thinks she is out of that box (Int1E5). She does not comply with all these characteristics attributed by the Turkish societal culture to young, female-bodied English language teachers. However, she is also aware that, at her workplace, her non-compliance with all these attributions is

frequently made topics of gossip. Melisa thinks people talk behind her back at work, and the reason is often her mismatch with the Turkish society's cultural understanding of a female-bodied English language teacher. This might be the ultimate impact of heteroprofessionalism on a language educator practicing within the Turkish context, and Melisa acknowledges this impact. As a result of this detrimental impact of heteroprofessionalism, Melisa is often called to her director's office for trivial incidents unlike her colleagues. In brief, heteronormativity defines a set of characteristics to be attributed to the female-bodied English language teachers within the Turkish societal culture. Melisa does not conform with them. For that reason, as a non-conforming female-bodied language educator, she is a topic of gossip at her workspace (*Int2E11*). Heteroprofessionalism makes it easier for her institutional superiors to escalate trivial incidents to the director's office. At the end of the day, Melisa falls victim to it.

While reporting the instance of a microaggressive attack coming from a colleague during an institutional ceremony (*Int2E8*), Melisa emphasizes her awareness of the motive of that attack. From her perspective, she was subjected to this microaggressive attack as her colleague knows that heteronormative practices are prevalent at their workspace, which renders it heteroprofessional. Frequently practiced heteroprofessional patterns and applications not only disempower Melisa at her workspace, but they also empower the heteronormative mindsets of her cis-heterosexual-conforming and normative colleagues. Heteroprofessionalism makes it easier for her non-LGBTQI normative colleagues to assert dominance over her LGBTQI identity at work. It gives them power to microaggressively attack her without any fear of condemnation, let alone institutional punishment. On top of these all, the situation is even worse, considering these people are her colleagues, i.e., teachers, that have their own unique students to educate.

In my first year of teaching, a female student kissed me in front of the class as a prank. It was humiliating and escalated quickly because my girlfriend at the time was observing me as part of a peer evaluation. Everyone, including my colleagues, blamed me for "giving the wrong signals" as a queer language educator, who confuses them. Turns out the girl thought she was gay and wanted to try it with me to make sure she was actually gay and kissed me,

since she thought I looked “queer” enough for that to be “fine”. It was a nightmare. (Int2E12).

In this unfavorable experience, Melisa is accused by her colleagues although she was the actual victim there (*Int2E12*). A female student is kissing her teacher in the classroom during a peer observation, with hopes of finding out about her own sexual identity. Unsurprisingly, the issue escalates, and colleagues find out about it. Again, unsurprisingly, at a heteroprofessional workplace, they put the blame on Melisa, although she was sexually assaulted. From Melisa’s perspective, the assaulter’s motive behind her actions is Melisa’s LGBTQI identity (*Int2E12*). She is comfortable enough to kiss her teacher in the middle of the classroom, since the teacher is an LGBTQ language educator. Language educators are often observed to build stronger rapport with their students within the Turkish culture. Adding this to Melisa’s LGBTQI identity, the assaulter feels comfortable enough to do what she is doing in this incident (*Int2E12*). Here, two points stand out. Melisa is assaulted by a bicurious student who wants to experiment with her own sexual identity, and Melisa is accused by her colleagues of confusing her student as a result of this incident. This accusation by her colleagues is a testament to heteroprofessionalism at her workplace. Melisa’s awareness of the accusation’s relevance to her LGBTQI identity shows her acknowledgement of the impact of that heteroprofessional manifestation.

Further, upon her complaint about extra duties after not being invited to the night out (*PGORIE1*), Melisa is told that you need to be on good terms with the coordinator to break free from extra duties. She is not “chummy” (*PGORIE1*) with her coordinator. She believes there is not really a point in being on extra good terms with people who do not see you and your girlfriend whom you are in a non-cis-heterosexual relationship with a couple. She is well aware of the fact that they are marginalized as a couple by her coordinator and colleagues due to their non-conforming, non-cis-heterosexual relationship. In heteronormative terms, a person cannot be in a romantic relationship with a same-sex individual. The binary norm of a couple is considered comprising a man and a woman in heteronormative ideologies. Herewith, the reflection of heteronormative ideologies is observed at Melisa’s workplace, which, ultimately, renders it heteroprofessional.

4.1.7. Allyship and Aloofness at the Workplace

Only one of my colleagues supported me through those times, who turned out to be gay as well, no heterosexual ally support at the workplace (Int2E13).

This is an intricate statement by Melisa in terms of what she perceives as ally support and how she defines it. After the unfavorable experience of a female student kissing her in the classroom (Int2E12), she gets the support of only one colleague, who turns out to be gay. She underlines the fact that she only gets the support of another LGBTQI individual at her workplace during hard times. She also thinks there is no actual allyship coming from her cis-heterosexual colleagues. Although the incident shows that she is indeed supported by a colleague at her workplace, cis-heterosexual colleagues' aloofness stands out for her (Int2E13). She prefers to put a line between getting the support of other LGBTQI colleagues and her cis-heterosexual colleagues. Other incidents show signs of support, though Melisa does not particularly classify them as such.

When he left, female coworkers said sorry about his remarks (PGOR2E2).

After her male colleague microaggressively remarks on the stipend she receives due to her mother's loss (PGOR2E2), female colleagues in the scene attempt to apologize on behalf of him. Melisa does not particularly classify this act as a way of support. The male colleague's remarks directly refer to her LGBTQI identity and the non-conforming, non-cis-heterosexual relationship she has with her girlfriend. After he leaves, the female colleagues are aware of this as well, and they apologize to Melisa on behalf of the microaggressive attacker. In an indirect way, they attempt to show their support to her non-conforming sexual identity and relationship.

Everyone laughed at that. I don't think the laughter reached his ears (PGOR4E2).

In addition to that, when she tells another male colleague that it is better to be with women than men as they do not ask her inappropriate questions in a humorous way (PGOR4E2), the other colleagues in the scene laugh at her response, which indicates that they side with her. The fact that Melisa is not particularly classifying these acts

as forms of allyship does not change the fact that she is indeed supported by some of her cis-heterosexual colleagues. However, what matters more is how Melisa views support and perceives allyship. With regard to her own definition of allyship and support, she might not feel supported in these instances. Allyship is as much impactful as it reaches to an individual. At this point, female colleagues' instant apology or their laughter to Melisa's responses in these incidents do not reach her.

My student visited my friend-colleague's class during the break. Apparently, they made a slightly homophobic joke about having sex with Ryan Reynolds (Deadpool & Wolverine had been on the news). My friend told me about it, (and I told my students) it is okay to find someone attractive regardless of their gender or sexual identity. The student talked about this in the other class again. Today, my friend told me how she found my handling of this very well done and discussed it with another level's coordinator who is her friend too (PGOR3E1).

After Melisa takes an opportunity to bring up issues of gender and sexuality to her students, she is explicitly appreciated by a colleague (PGOR3E1). Although this colleague is a friend, she still gets her appreciation for a gender and sexuality issue she handles well at the workplace. This is a very subtle form of support. However, it can still be classified as allyship as the friend is appreciating her explicitly and attempting to share the incident with a coordinator with good intentions.

This other level's coordinator is a 40-ish-year-old woman who is only trying to get a master's degree now because of the changes in laws. She told my friend that while she agreed with how well I handled things, she found it dangerous and borderline propaganda to discuss such issues in class as it might come to bite me back if the students complain about me (PGOR3E2).

However, following that (PGOR3E1), no support is received from the coordinator. After her colleague shares the incident with a coordinator (PGOR3E2), the coordinator, a woman in her 40s, agrees on how well Melisa handles the issue. However, she goes on to claim that it is dangerous and borderline propaganda to discuss gender and sexuality related issues in class. Her rationale behind this claim is that it might end up unfavorably for Melisa if students complain about her. The coordinator's word choice speaks volumes about how she perceives what happens. Her genuineness of the concern she has about Melisa's institutional safety in a case

of student complaint remains to be known. Ultimately, the coordinator is not happy that Melisa brings up gender and sexuality issues in her classes, which can be classified as aloofness toward her LGBTQI identity as well.

Because if you act like an outlier or out of the norm, you're not going to get much out of these usually fossilized colleagues. Not always, not all of them are fossilized, obviously, which makes the work life bearable, but most of the time, this is the case (JE2E4).

Melisa is well aware of her colleagues' demographic profile. She refers to her colleagues as "fossilized" (JE2E4) people. She also believes that acting like an "outliner" or "out of the norm" (JE2E4) would not be supported by those "fossilized" (JE2E4) people. Ultimately, Melisa finds herself unsupported by her colleagues, which might result in her facing challenges that affect both her personal and professional identities. The lack of solidarity from her colleagues might create a sense of alienation from her personal identity, considering she remains careful about not being an "outliner" (JE2E4). Although she is subtly and implicitly supported in a few instances, Melisa does not particularly refer to those as support. This pertains to her understanding of allyship, which matters in her case. Without the explicit support coming from her colleagues, she feels unsupported in instances of professional difficulty. Her LGBTQI identity hinders the collaborative atmosphere she needs to thrive as a language educator. This does not seem to erode her professional confidence though, which indicates that she sets a line between her personal and professional identities. Eventually, Melisa's presence at her workplace environment is not explicitly celebrated by her colleagues, let alone supported. She does not emphasize any particular instance of her LGBTQI identity being supported by her colleagues at work. Melisa's LGBTQI identity is either implicitly shown support or ignored completely by her colleagues.

Further, in the instance wherein she feels "overburdened" (Int2E9) with duties because she is "single and queer" (Int2E9) in her administrative institutional superiors' eyes, she is not receiving any support from her cis-heterosexual colleagues when she complains about it either (PGORIE1). Her non-conforming, non-cis-heterosexual relationship with her girlfriend is completely ignored as it does not

comply with the heteronormative ideologies of her administrative institutional superiors. As strong testaments to it, such incidents (*Int2E13*; *PGOR2E2*; *PGOR4E2*; *PGOR3E1*; *PGOR3E2*; *JE2E4*) enhance the heteroprofessionalism practiced at her workplace environment even further. Ultimately, Melisa is either subtly, implicitly supported by some of her colleagues, or completely ignored.

4.1.8. Resisting Heteroprofessionalism

Heteroprofessionalism manifests itself in various forms at Melisa's workspace, and she often resists to it. Through subtle satires, indirect verbal attacks, institutional practices, or more explicit instances of microaggression, Melisa faces heteroprofessionalism at work. It usually comes from her colleagues. However, it is practiced by her administrative institutional superiors as well. In almost all instances of her encounters with heteroprofessional practices at her workplace environment, Melisa shows a sign of resistance in the form of reaction.

In two aforementioned instances, relating to the "Friday night out" (*PGOR1E1*) and "being single and queer" (*Int2E9*), Melisa is assigned with extra duties at work. She associates both cases to her non-conforming, non-cis-heterosexual relationship with her girlfriend. As their relationship does not conform with the heteronormative understanding of a romantic relationship, they are not considered a couple at Melisa's workplace either. Therefore, when extra duties come up, they are not assigned to her colleagues that are in straight marriages, since they need flexibility for their families. In that case, all extra work is assigned to Melisa, "simply because she is single and queer" (*Int2E9*). In both instances, Melisa reacts to what happens. In the first one (*PGOR1E1*), instead of directly getting in touch with her administrative institutional superiors, she complains about the issue to an irrelevant colleague. She does not remain silent, which indicates she is not silenced. She still attempts to bring up the heteroprofessional practices performed at her workplace context through complaint. In the second one (*Int2E9*), the complaint is directed toward the administrative institutional superior. Melisa is being vocal about the unjust situation she finds herself in. This time, it is not discussed with a fellow

colleague, rather, she escalates it to people with higher institutional status. Either way, Melisa resists heteroprofessionalism.

I've only heard of attracting positive attention (Int2E14).

Melisa does not only complain. She also shows instantaneous reactions to heteroprofessional practices.

Hell yes! Women don't ask me about random inappropriate crap they come up with (PGOR4E3).

In these moments of microaggressive attacks by her colleagues (*Int2E14; PGOR4E3*), she instantly responds to them verbally. She utilizes humor and sarcasm in her responses to her attackers in both instances. She is being vocal and responsive, which indicates that she is not silenced by her colleagues either.

As he was leaving, he said, "For you guys, this is great. You can have this money until your own death." (PGOR2E3).

During only one of the microaggressive attacks by her colleagues, Melisa is unresponsive. When the male colleague, as he is leaving the scene, makes a remark about the stipend she receives due to her mother's loss (*PGOR2E3*), Melisa remains unresponsive. This might be because she does not have the time to respond back to his comment as he is already leaving the scene, or she gets emotional as the topic of discussion includes a loved one's loss. Either way, Melisa remains unresponsive in this instance. However, in all other encounters of heteroprofessionalism, Melisa resists by being vocal and verbally responsive, and claiming her own ground. As she states, she does not purposefully hide her LGBTQI identity at her workplace context, she only enacts it a bit too carefully and remains reserved about it. Within the Turkish context, Melisa could be acting this carefully due to the lack of legal support. She might be too attentive to how she reacts instead of resisting all the way, as she knows her non-conforming identities are not legally supported by the authorities either. Therefore, it is important to note that her resistance against constant heteroprofessionalism at work requires courage, determination, and stamina. Finding all within herself, Melisa resists heteroprofessionalism.

4.2. Research Question 2

While heteroprofessionalism manifests itself in various ways within Melisa's workplace context, she still has her ways to negotiate her multiple identities and navigate her professional experiences at work. Identity plurality, acting strategically, emotions, English language as a gateway, society and context, parting and intersecting identities, and performativity are the emerging themes to be presented in efforts of answering the second research question.

4.2.1. Identity Plurality

First of all, it is important to remember how Melisa identifies herself, describes her gender and sexual identity, and what terminology she uses while doing that. Melisa is not a conforming individual to what societal heteronormative ideologies gender and sexuality doctrines. She is not cis-heterosexual. Melisa belongs with the LGBTQI community and puts her gender and sexual identity in her own words.

I wanna be two genders at the same time, not the other gender, the two, male and female. My sexual orientation is pansexuality (Int1E8).

Melisa identifies as bigender. She does not feel completely like a man or a woman at all times. Sometimes, she feels like a woman, and other times she feels like a man (Int1E8). Her gender identity does not conform with the binary norms of heteronormative ideologies. She does not fit in people's boxes of being either a man or a woman. Her sexual identity is defined as pansexuality (Int1E8). Melisa finds herself attracted to all types of individuals regardless of their gender or sexual identifications.

My gender identity is something I call bigender (Int1E9).

Melisa is being conscious about how she expresses her gender identity. She doesn't have a given expectation of people to know the term "bigender" (Int1E9).

The moment they (colleagues) start questioning, they realize they themselves don't actually fit in these categories (In1E10).

According to her, their ignorance is rooted in their non-questioning state (*Int1E10*). It does not relate to all of them being categorized as fully conforming in all senses.

They've (colleagues) been swimming in this norm their whole lives (Int2E15).

She acknowledges and assumes people's lack of knowledge in non-conforming gender and sexual identifications. Her word choice (*Int2E15*) is a testament to this assumption as well.

My girlfriend has a hard time keeping up but she's learning (Int1E11).

Although her girlfriend identifies as an LGBTQI individual as well, Melisa is still understanding of everyone's learning process with regard to gender and sexuality.

Honestly, this month I feel a lot of she/her, so you can go with that. Next month it might change (Int1E12).

Melisa does not identify with any particular nonbinary pronouns. She requests to be referred as she/her in this study (*Int1E12*). That way, she acknowledges her own gender fluidity, which further validates her bigender identity, if needed. She is also not in approval of societal expectations of conforming gender and sexuality. This also relates to her profession as a language educator within the Turkish context.

But I fall out of line with that (Int1E13).

As a female-bodied language educator practicing in the Turkish context, Melisa does not conform with societal and cultural attributions to her identity, which might possibly create a tension of identity plurality. Melisa "falls out of line" (*Int1E13*) with what a female-bodied English teacher is expected to look, and sound like in the Turkish context, and she is well aware of this non-compliance.

General language teacher stuff that we have to encounter and then break apart. "Why do you think it was a she?" (Int1E14).

As an English language teacher, her LGBTQI identity is also in contact with her professional identity. English language has binary gender pronouns historically

established in its roots. While teaching the language today, teachers may or may not prefer to address the paucity of the language's gender pronoun system for the LGBTQI community. Melisa does this, and she assumes that doing it is a "general language teacher stuff" (*Int1E14*). She might be doing this now that she is a language teacher that belongs with the LGBTQI community and wants to address the issue. However, she assumes all language teachers (at least in general) do it (*Int1E14*).

*I try to have them watch other shows where being a good human being, decency 101, is taught. So, it has some queer characters in positive lights. For example, I have this animated show, She-Ra, which I love, and I always recommend it to my students, or Sense8, or other shows like this. The things I cannot say, I try to say them through media like this. For example, I have them look at what's trending on Twitter in the US, as part of understanding colloquial English, today's English, modern English. For example, I taught them about the "me too" movement. They didn't know what it was. Some student asked me "what is "me too"?" I was like, okay, here we go. Let's start with Kesha. I try to use that to teach them, this community's students, who are coming 50 years behind other countries, other communities in these conversations. I try to give this vibe that this is normal. These conversations are normal, it's weird that we don't have them. I think it's working. Because only two people watch those shows with me, we start a conversation, and the others think it's cooler than their conversation. What I'm trying to do is basically I'm trying to make them want to be in that conversation, which may be a wrong way to go about this, I don't know, but so far, I've seen it work (*Int1E15*).*

Melisa also acknowledges that she might be imposing her own ideology to her students. She acts strategically and integrates the target language culture in her teaching philosophy. In order to teach her students about gender and sexuality issues, as a language educator, she makes use of the culture of the target language she is teaching them. She brings up contemporary movements in English-speaking countries, mentions shows in English, and encourages her students to be in touch with the English-speaking side of social media platforms (*Int1E15*). At this point, not to feel excluded, her students try to engage in the target language culture to take part in the conversations in class. Although this is a very prevalent technique in language teaching, considering Melisa's rationale behind and ways of employing it, it might be classified as ideological imposition. However, even if so, Melisa acknowledges that what she does might not be the right way of doing what she wants to do. She is open to questioning her own teaching philosophy as an LGBTQI language educator

(*Int1E15*), which demonstrates her plural identities and her perception of their interplay.

*So, what I do, even before I knew queering, was breaking these things apart. I would ask them “why are you laughing?”, “how could this be funny?”, and then I would turn this into a whole discussion. I did the same thing, because of this, because I open the door with sexual identities, I was able to do this with, for example, imprisonment. Why do you think poor people can never get out of “the life”?, and they have never thought about this before. Only crime unit we teach, “robber”, “cops arrested them”, “handcuffs”, etc., but I asked them, like, “do you know how many people are falsely accused or falsely imprisoned?”. Talking about the sexual identities actually helps me open these other doors because the students love talking about themselves no matter what. So, if I just start asking about their significant others, and I use this, significant other, instead of a boyfriend or a girlfriend they start using it as well (*Int1E16*).*

Critical pedagogy is among Melisa’s teaching philosophies of education. Once again, she takes a linguistic point of the English language as her starting point of bringing up discussions about critical issues in society (*Int1E16*). One of her students uses “he” pronoun to refer to his girlfriend, and the class starts laughing (*Int1E16*). Here, it is also important to note that the laughter comes from male students. This aligns with the pattern of microaggressive attacks mainly coming from her male colleagues. Taking this semantic mistake made by a student, Melisa starts employing the question-posing technique to encourage her students to question their own stance on societal issues (*Int1E16*). She believes that coming up with gender and sexuality related discussions helps her encourage her students to inquire more about the real-world issues that surround them. At this point, her professional identity is in an interplay with her LGBTQI identity. Just like being responsive against microaggressive attacks from her colleagues, Melisa is also being responsive to unintended LGBTQI-phobia performed by her students. She is also being attentive to her word choice in the language she teaches. She uses neutral words to refer to her students’ possible romantic partners, considering she would not enjoy being misgendered herself. Instead of using the words “boyfriend” and “girlfriend”, Melisa uses “significant other” (*Int1E16*), and she observes her students doing the same thing. She employs the “queering” technique in her classes. Once again, Melisa’s ideological stance on gender and sexual identity issues is passed on to her students

due to the activist approach in her teaching. As she already studies critical pedagogy and queering ELT as a researcher, her pedagogic agency is strong.

Because if you're questioning one thing, you can question everything else (Int1E17).

Melisa likes the question-posing technique and employs it in her teaching. She believes that questioning one thing leads to questioning other things (Int1E17). She encourages her students to inquire about the real circling around them. As an LGBTQI language educator, question-posing is one of the instructional strategies Melisa employs as part of her queering critical pedagogical stance through queering.

It's (the phobic culture) terrible and I have to do something (Int1E18).

Melisa feels an urge to be proactive. She wants to enact an activist approach in her professional identity. She refers to her students' culture of LGBTQI-phobia as something "terrible" (Int1E18).

I (talked) about how it is okay to find someone attractive regardless of their gender or sexual identity (PGOR3E3).

She wants to do take action to prevent LGBTQI-phobia from taking place in her workplace context. She wants to teach her students better (PGOR3E3). While doing so, she also acknowledges that she might not be employing the best techniques. She still gives herself room for improvement (Int1E15). Ultimately, as a result of the interplay between her personal and professional identities, Melisa is being responsive and proactive in her own teaching as a language educator.

But I want to make it clear that I don't want to enforce any type of thinking. I don't need to do this actually. I just have them ask the questions and then they can go about their own ways (Int1E19).

From her own perspective though, Melisa does not impose her ideological stance on her students. In fact, she does not project "any type of thinking" (Int1E19). She creates a counterhegemonic space for her students to think further. Her description

here might be a part of a perfect definition of the question/problem posing technique in language teaching. Without forcing any particular ideological stance upon her students (*Int1E19*), Melisa encourages them to question.

Hereby, Melisa attempts to negotiate her identity plurality by merging her personal and professional identities at her heteroprofessional workplace context. She does not at all let go of her LGBTQ identity at work. In fact, more often than not, she embraces and acts upon it as language educator. Her professional identity, including her teaching approaches, methods, techniques, principals, and the instructional strategies she employs in her teaching, is highly influenced by her personal identity. Considering the fact that she practices as a language educator at a heteroprofessional institution, Melisa is being relatively fearless by embracing the interplay between her personal and professional identities at the micro-level when she's in class compared to the institutional circumstances she has at the meso-level.

4.2.2. Acting Strategically

*First, I make sure to be the best at what I do professionally. Regarding language teaching, for example, I always make sure my knowledge of vocabulary, grammar, and teaching methodologies has to be bulletproof. I work three times as hard to be taken half as seriously as other colleagues around here, since I know very well if they catch me making a mistake, they might escalate it to some whole other issue. Second, I make friends strategically, especially with some high-profile colleagues. My friendships at my workplace can never be genuine. I calculate all of them strategically. What if they turn against me and use my queerness to hurt my professional career? I wouldn't know. I always help others in meaningful ways, like approving theses or assisting my colleagues with some profession-related complex tasks. I feel like these efforts build goodwill and make me sort of indispensable at my workplace. I help them so they think I'm very humble and helpful. That way, I make sure they don't turn against me. Because again, I wouldn't know if they would try and turn against me one day and harm my career (*Int2E16*).*

Melisa cannot make the navigation of her heteroprofessional workplace context an easy task only by embracing the interplay between her personal and professional identities. Accordingly, she does more than that. She takes up three different types of strategical acts (*Int2E16*) in her relationships with her colleagues and navigation of

her heteroprofessional workspace. First, whatever she does at work, she tries to do it perfectly. She does not want to be questioned. Melisa already believes that she needs to outperform her colleagues to be taken “half as seriously” (*Int2E16*). Therefore, she makes sure everything she performs professionally is flawless. As a language teacher, she tries to reach a level of incontestability so that she never attracts doubts about her professional competence (*Int2E16*). Because if she makes any mistake related to her discipline, she believes that her colleagues would escalate the issue to something it is not. Second, she makes friends strategically (*Int2E16*). Her friendships at work are not genuine friendships. She particularly goes for her institutional superiors while choosing people to befriend at her workplace context. She is concerned that if she attempts to make genuine friends out of her colleagues, they might possibly turn against her and harm her professional career at some point. In addition to these (*Int2E16*), she is being strategically helpful to secure good terms with her colleagues. She helps her colleagues in meaningful ways with their professional tasks so that she makes sure they think the best of her. Once again, she does this out of concern of being turned against. Melisa wants to keep her colleagues on good terms with herself so that she can ensure they would not turn against her and harm her professional career by using her “queerness”.

What I feel in these experiences is that, if you have to navigate heteroprofessional dynamics at your workplace, while being a language educator who happens to be queer, you have to care about three things. First, you have to be undeniably, in your face, good at your job. You're a language educator, so you should know the language the best. You should be able to go up to anyone, talk to them, and they will immediately know that you are the best in that language. You need to have excellent communication skills, beyond excellent, beyond superb, extremely. You need to be a very good manipulator. You need to have good manipulation skills and the navigation of conversations. This is not just with students, in fact, most of the time, you can be just fine with students. But you need to be able to talk to your fellow language educators and be a good manipulator. For example, I know for a fact, if you want to make a friend out of a co-worker, you need to ask for their help with small stuff that they can easily do, manipulation 101, stuff like this. The third thing I think one needs to have in order to be able to expert navigation of these situations is that one needs to recognize what the norm is, what people's perceptions of the norm are, what out of that norm is, and what people's perceptions of out of that norm are. A group of people think being a queer person is an extreme disadvantage because they have never met one. They only see them in the media, for example. Another group of people have

queer friends that they work at the same place with. They don't believe this, or they feel acculturated to what people's reality is (JE2E5).

Together with her efforts of being unquestionably good at her job, Melisa also uses manipulation and acknowledgement of cultural and societal norms as some other strategies of navigating her heteroprofessional workplace environment. She makes sure that she excels at manipulation as defense mechanism (JE2E5). She uses being helpful and asking for help as manipulation techniques of befriending her colleagues. She believes that manipulative communication skills are especially important in her relationships with her colleagues rather than students. Melisa also believes in the power of acknowledging people's cultural and societal norms (JE2E5). She is aware that people's perceptions of LGBTQI individuals may differ. Some think of belonging with the LGBTQI community as a disadvantage, and some others do not think that way. From Melisa's perspective, the difference pertains to whether or not those people have ever met or worked with an LGBTQI individual (JE2E5). Either way around, she thinks she needs to remain conscious of other people's perceptions of the LGBTQI community, which she refers to as their norms.

I have to create a guidebook on how to act, speak, and even look the right way (Int2E17).

Melisa feels as if she could only act in certain ways to keep herself out of trouble at her workplace context. She needs to "speak and even look" (Int2E17) the right way so that she can feel safe at work.

I can't act too butch or too feminine. Anything out of the perceived norm of a "female" English teacher" becomes a topic of gossip and often leads to being called to the director's office for the smallest things (Int2E18).

Also, as a female-bodied LGBTQI language educator, she needs to act in compliance with her culture's attributions to her profession. She is aware that if she falls out of line with those heteronormative attributions (Int2E18), things can easily escalate. Therefore, she is being extra attentive to how she acts, speaks, or looks at her workplace context.

I stayed silent the whole time as I knew how the interaction would go. I could even guess what he was going to say (PGOR2E4).

In addition to all these strategies she employs in navigating her heteroprofessional workplace context, Melisa also chooses to remain silent sometimes. However, she does not feel silenced, rather, she takes silence as another strategy to keep her peace at work. The above excerpt (*PGOR2E4*) is from when a male colleague remarked on the stipend that she receives due to her deceased mother's insurance. Melisa remained silent during the whole interaction after the male colleague's last unfavorable remark to avoid conflict.

In a similar vein, after not being invited to a couples night out and being assigned with extra work afterward, Melisa starts leaving her girlfriend out of her sentences at her workspace to avoid possible further conflicts (*PGOR1E2*). As she believes that she is already not seen in an actual relationship with her girlfriend by her colleagues and administrative institutional superiors due to their heteronormative ideologies and stance on non-conforming relationships, the best thing to do is to avoid relationship related discussions altogether (*PGOR1E2*). Once again, she consciously chooses to remain silent while navigating her heteroprofessional workplace context.

I would ask them (students) "why are you laughing?", "how could this be funny?", and then I would turn this into a whole discussion (Int1E20).

Melisa also uses intervention as a strategy in her navigation of heteroprofessionalism at her workspace (*Int1E20*).

But other than that, I have them (students) ask questions. That's how I go about it (Int1E21).

When she encounters or is informed about LGBTQI-phobia coming from her students (*Int1E21*), she does not choose to remain silent.

So, every time they (students) try to do this (performing phobic attitudes), I keep trying to interfere somehow (Int1E22).

Rather, she actively chooses to intervene (*Int1E22*), which, again, pertains to how she has stronger agency at the micro-level when she's in class.

I used the opportunity to talk about behavior and how it is okay to find someone attractive regardless of their gender or sexual identity (PGOR3E4).

Melisa takes these instances as “opportunities” (PGOR3E4) to educate her students beyond the class content.

So, I teach them that it's not cool or it's not funny or it doesn't make them attractive to be homophobic or transphobic or someone who makes fun of people that are different than them. I try to teach them that it's much more attractive to be not. Because that's what they're interested in right now. These are 18-year-olds, 20-year-olds. So, that's what I try to do (Int1E23).

She intervenes by asking questions to her students or leading them to ask questions, lecturing them on gender and sexuality related issues, using their age group characteristics to adjust her teaching (Int1E23), and looking down on the local LGBTQI-phobic culture and encouraging them to engage in the target language culture.

I refuse to let my students watch any Turkish TV shows. I, in fact, make jokes about it. I try to humiliate those shows so that they won't think it's cool to talk about them in class and I try to have them watch other shows where being a good human being, decency 101, is taught. So, it has some queer characters in positive lights (Int1E24).

In various ways, she somehow intervenes in the homophobic encounters in her classes instead of remaining silent and letting them slide. Slight imposition of her personal beliefs and values, rooted in her non-conforming identities, is among those ways, as seen in the above excerpt (Int1E24).

I don't want to get fired over some nonsensical trivial thing that they cannot say and they're trying to cover it up. So, I got to be smart about it (Int1E25).

Another reason Melisa chooses to act strategically in navigating her professional experiences at her heteroprofessional workplace context is that she wants to avoid conflicts. She does not want her language educator career to be terminated (Int1E25) due to her LGBTQI identity.

I make friends (at work) strategically (Int2E19).

Accordingly, she acts strategically (*Int2E19*) to secure her position at the institution. At this point, she cares more about keeping her job.

I am not hiding myself actively, but I am incredibly careful with how I share my truth (JE1E2).

Her relationships with her colleagues, her rapport with her students, how she looks, how she sounds, how she acts in certain ways, and how she enacts her personal identity at work (*JE1E2*) are all performed strategically.

A larger issue is me constantly checking and rechecking myself, going over what I said to the students and how I acted etc. (JE3E1).

Melisa does not seek genuineness at her heteroprofessional workplace context. What she seeks is survival (*JE3E1*).

4.2.3. Emotions

After all, Melisa is a human being. While negotiating her identities and navigating her professional experiences at her heteroprofessional workspace, she goes through a palette of emotions. Acting strategically and being smart certainly helps her in this trajectory. However, feeling what she experiences is inevitable. Fear, exhaustion, and feeling of disapproval are some prominent emotions Melisa demonstrates. Before these emotions though, acceptance (*Int1E26*) and disbelief stand out.

This is how it is at the moment (Int1E26).

Melisa accepts what the status quo is. She does not try to think of it differently, neither does she attempt to create a delusion of it.

Until they actually question it, they think this is the default (Int1E27).

She is well aware of the real world that surrounds her. She acknowledges that people need to inquire about the status quo (*Int1E27*) to notice something wrong with it.

They're trying to go about this the same way everyone else does (Int1E28).

Melisa also does not believe that her colleagues care about their workplace being heteroprofessional.

She has this understanding, and I understand her thinking (Int1E29).

She also does not believe that her colleagues care about their workplace being heteroprofessional.

They (colleagues) know the workplace is heteroprofessional and they're just fine with this. Why would they care? (Int2E20).

She thinks they are just fine with this situation, and they do not actually need to care about it (Int2E20). She knows what the status quo is, and she accepts it (Int1E29). Ultimately, for Melisa, it is what it is.

I should still be considered as danger as much as the other ladies, but I'm not (Int1E30).

Even though she accepts the status quo, she is still in disbelief with doctrines and practices of heteronormativity. She does not take these heteronormative ideological practices as the truth (Int1E30), neither does she believe in their accuracy (Int1E31).

So, why is this the norm? One question we asked there was who was profiting from this false information (Int1E31).

She is in total feeling of disbelief with regard to societal norms or cultural doctrines pertaining to heteronormativity. However, when such norms are practices at her workspace in the form of heteroprofessionalism, she seeks constant reassurance about doing things the right way. Melisa is on constant guard (JE3E2).

Constantly checking and rechecking myself (JE3E2).

Heteroprofessionalism keeps Melisa on alert at all times at her workspace (JE3E2). Her LGBTQI identity is not purposefully hidden. However, she does not carelessly enact at her workplace context either due to heteroprofessionalism.

I need to make sure there are no unsafe strangers around when I make my jokes. Being a person with wit power, I should clear the room first. Make those kinds of jokes only when safe people are around (PGOR4E4).

From her point of view, she always needs to be careful about how she appears at work (Int2E22). The way she walks, the way she talks, the way she looks, and the way she acts (PGOR4E4) are always checked and kept under her control.

I combed through my social media accounts over and over again because I knew they would use whatever they can find there (JE1E3).

She even feels that she should be very careful with how she presents herself on her social media platforms (JE1E3).

Again, this is about feeling obliged to be extra careful with everything and anything at the workplace (Int2E21).

She feels as if she constantly needs to be on guard as she feels “obliged” (Int2E21) to it. According to her, the enactment of the intersection her multiple identities is overtly limited by the institution.

I always feel like I have to be extra careful with my actions and appearance (Int2E22).

Her personal and professional identities are always in an interplay in her navigation of heteroprofessionalism at her workspace, which makes the navigation of her professional experiences at work even more difficult due to heteroprofessional institutional practices.

Being called to the director’s office for the smallest things (is) exhausting (Int2E23).

Melisa tries to negotiate her multiple identities while navigating her professional experiences due to feelings of insecurity. She wants to be safe at work. However, she is often exhausted (Int2E23).

Just to spite them all, I might become even more of a critical pedagogue! (PGOR3E5).

She feels frustrated (*PGOR3E5*) and exhausted (*Int2E23*). Heteroprofessionalism obliges (*Int2E21*) her to do things certain ways at her workspace. She does not feel content with this situation at all.

*As a queer instructor, this whole concept makes it all even more difficult for me. Trying to abide by and get used to some very disturbing heteroprofessional norms and practices makes it even more difficult for me to focus on the quality of education I provide my students with. I feel like it's all a never-ending loop (*Int2E24*).*

She believes that “as a queer instructor” (*Int2E24*), heteroprofessionalism makes everything even more difficult for her. She does not think she navigates her professional experiences in the same ways as her cis-heterosexual colleagues. She feels as if even her professional competence is affected by heteroprofessionalism. Melisa doubts the quality of education she provides her students with and finds heteroprofessionalism as the reason behind this.

*It takes up a lot of my brain power, patience, and joy (*JE3E3*).*

She is constantly way too concerned (*JE3E3*) with heteroprofessionalism and cannot focus on her professional quality as a language educator.

*I have to ponder on my every move to make sure it does not come back to hurt me, be used to hurt me, my open identity (*JE1E4*).*

Fear keeps Melisa question everything she does at work. It's among the factors that keeps her on guard.

*But seventy nine percent of moments, I feel like I might not be a hundred percent safe here (*JE2E6*).*

“Seventy nine percent of moments” (*JE2E6*), Melisa is not safe around her heteroprofessional workspace. At least, that is how she feels (*JE1E4*). She has a fear of enacting her LGBTQI identity to its fullest at her workplace context.

Because I know for a fact that if a student reports me to someplace or complains about me regarding my sexual orientation (which I never say

anything explicit about to my current students), the school/the admin would not back me or support me in any way. While I do my best to be inclusive in class and out, I also am extremely aware of this scary fact (JE3E4).

She does not purposefully hide it; however, she does not explicitly talk about it either. She constantly keeps it on thin ice (JE3E4), which might come with numerous tensions.

I wouldn't know if they would try and turn against me one day and harm my career (Int2E25).

Melisa also has a fear of getting hurt. She does not fully trust her colleagues or students. She feels like they can harm her at different levels and aspects of her life (Int2E25), knowing that she is non-conforming. This also pertains to how she tries to build a healthy rapport with her students as well as keeping herself on good terms with her colleagues.

I keep trying to interfere somehow. Not overtly, I try my best not to do it overtly because then they're going to take one look at my short hair and they will decide I am this Dyke, which is true, but I don't want them to think about it or use it as a way to degrade me (Int1E32).

A constant feeling of paranoia with regard to losing her job (Int1E25), getting her career hurt (Int2E25), and being degraded at work by her students or colleagues (Int1E32) is always present. In addition to all these, Melisa also has a fear of institutional hierarchy and punishment due to heteroprofessionalism.

I know very well that this (putting pronouns up on her work Zoom account) would cost me heavily (Int2E26).

Institutional hierarchy and punishment (Int2E26) are some intense fears of Melisa. She certainly wants to keep her job (Int1E33), and she is aware that, with her LGBTQI identity, this is not an easy task to do within her heteroprofessional workplace context.

But the higher up they go, the more silent I become (Int1E33).

More often than not, one thing leads to another, things escalate (often to the director's office). Thus, she also keeps herself silent around her administrative superiors (*Int1E33*), rather than constantly reacting to hetero professionalism.

The school/the admin would not back me or support me in any way (JE3E5).

The state of acknowledgement of her institutions' official lack of support (*JE3E5*) in a possible conflict rising from her non-conforming identities is another factor that keeps Melisa concerned and silent.

If they're cool, I can say it. Okay, so, coordinator, maybe if it is a cool person, foreign languages director, perhaps, only if they knew me from before, but everyone else on higher levels, no, no, no, no, big no, I don't want to get fired over some nonsensical trivial thing that they cannot say and they're trying to cover it up (Int1E34).

Melisa does not want to find herself in a situation of termination due to some "nonsensical trivial thing" (*Int1E34*) that her institutional superiors "cannot say" (*Int1E34*) and try to "cover it up" (*Int1E34*). She refers to her LGBTQI identity here. This is how Melisa perceives her own gender and sexual identity at her workspace. In attempts of negotiating her personal and professional identities, she finds herself referring to her gender and sexual identity as "nonsensical trivial things" (*Int1E34*) that her institutional superiors cannot say and try to cover up. This is due to the fear of institutional hierarchy and punishment her hetero professional workspace spreads. She is exposed to this fear constantly simply because of her non-conforming gender and sexual identity.

I make friends (strategically) with some high-profile colleagues (Int2E27).

"The higher up" Melisa goes, "the more silent" she becomes (*Int1E33*). She does not want to find herself in conflicts with her institutional superiors due to her LGBTQI identity. She even tries to keep herself on good terms with them (*Int2E27*) as a befriending strategy at work. The fact that she is afraid does not change the fact that Melisa has a feeling of disapproval too though.

Yes, it's their culture and it's terrible (Int1E35).

Melisa has a feeling of disapproval for a few concepts. First of all, she does not approve of her students' and colleagues' culture (Int1E35) pertaining to LGBTQI related issues. As aforementioned (Int2E20), looking at the issue from their perspective, she sees no reason for them to be concerned about heteroprofessionalism, which she sees as the actual problem.

These conversations are normal (normalizing the LGBTQI community), it's weird that we don't have them (Int1E36).

From her perspective, they have an insufficient, inactive culture of inclusivity, which does not serve LGBTQI individuals at all. As a case in point, she wishes that she could discuss gender and sexuality related issues with more freedom and without fear (Int1E36) in her classes.

It is horrifying to think but, a couple of days ago, I found myself thinking, 'If I just had been a heteronormative person living an unremarkable heteronormative life, I would not lose my pride trying to deescalate things, instead I would speak my mind' (JE1E5).

She envisions being cis-heterosexual and living a hetero-normative life. Melisa clearly thinks this sort of a lifestyle is the better one for feeling good. As is, her life makes her swallow her pride at times (JE1E5), which makes her feel extremely bad. She thinks a hetero-normative lifestyle could give her the chance to have her head up.

A group of people think being a queer person is an extreme disadvantage because they have never met one. They only see them in the media, for example (JE2E7).

She is not in approval of ignorance and negligence either (JE2E7). Melisa finds the stakeholders around her heteroprofessional workspace ignorant and neglective.

However, what I realize with this new generation, and I'm going to sound like a boomer here, I'm sorry, I know we're not that much older than them but, oh

my God, they do not research anything. They just believe whatever they hear. Sometimes, I find myself spoon-feeding them information about identities and how people come to be. For example, one of my students, who has the best intentions by the way, just unbelievably ignorant, tells me gay people should be “psychopaths” because those are out of norm and gay people are out of norm as well (Int1E37).

Her students’ ignorance about gender and sexuality related issues does not make Melisa happy at all (Int1E37). However, she has a bit more of a temperate approach toward her students’ ignorance compared to how she completely disapproves of her colleagues’ ignorance. While still disapproving of their ignorance about gay people, Melisa chooses to give her students the benefit of the doubt (Int1E37). She believes they have good intentions, as young people, they just need to learn more to get over this ignorance. Her colleagues, as adults, do not stand a chance though. If they are being ignorant, Melisa is certainly calling them out. She has not much tolerance toward her colleagues’ ignorance. This might be why she also disapproves of institutional bullying.

I didn’t want to be asked about my sex life by a random person during a sleepless, mundane morning break (PGOR4E5).

The male colleague who asks her about being with women (PGOR4E1) is not tolerated by Melisa (PGOR4E5). She does not choose to give them the benefit of the doubt that she offers to her students (Int1E37) in instances of ignorance. Herewith, disapproving ignorance and negligence coming from both, Melisa is feeling more intolerant toward her colleagues and institutional superiors compared to how she feels toward her students. This might pertain to the possibility that she is prioritizing her professional educator identity in interactions with her students to focus on educating them properly.

4.2.4. English Language as a Gateway

As a language instructor, English language plays a critical role in Melisa’s negotiation of her personal and professional identities. From coming to terms with her own gender and sexual identity to taking up the teaching profession (Int1E38), English language has always been in an interplay with her multiple identities.

When I was a language learner, not a not a teacher yet, that's, the language, English language was the place I found my own terms of identity (Int1E38).

Rather than being directly related to navigating heteroprofessionalism at her workplace environment, English language emerges as a gateway for Melisa in her journey of realizing her own personal identity.

I learnt some English. I started googling, turned out I have a name, oh, I'm normal actually, there are other people who are like me. It's not a disease or anything like that (Int1E39).

English language was a gateway for Melisa to come to terms with her own identity. Before learning English and getting accustomed to the culture of the language, she feels like an abomination as a pansexual individual (Int1E39). Through her journey with English, Melisa realizes her normality. She finds a name for her non-conforming sexual identity and no longer feels like an abnormality. With the help of English, Melisa acknowledges that her difference from the majority does not necessarily render her an outsider. In fact, there are other people like Melisa, and she comes to this realization thanks to the English language. Later on, becoming a language educator, she is now a good communicator thanks to her profession, which makes her a good manipulator as well, which is a strategy she makes use of in her navigation of heteroprofessionalism at her workspace today. Thereby, rather indirectly, her discipline as a language educator is also in an interplay with how Melisa navigates her professional experiences at her workplace context.

If I didn't have the identity, I probably wouldn't have this level of proficiency at this moment (Int1E40).

By “the identity” (Int1E40), Melisa refers to her non-conforming LGBTQI identity. She thinks if she didn't have her LGBTQI identity, she would not be as proficient as she currently is in the English language, which would make a worse educator out of her. This is another way Melisa relates her personal identity to her professional identity. One of the underlying reasons behind her competence at her profession right now is her LGBTQI identity (Int1E40), considering it is her original motivation for learning the language and teaching it at some point. While navigating the

heteroprofessional climate of her workspace as a language educator, Melisa also realizes that some of her colleagues do not conform with heteronormative attributions either.

I see lots of people who don't conform as well (Int1E41).

Here, Melisa refers to her colleagues and other female-bodied English language educators that do not conform with the societal and cultural heteronormative characteristics they are attributed to within the Turkish context (*Int1E41*). In another discipline, Melisa would probably experience heteroprofessionalism in different ways. However, her non-conforming LGBTQI identity to the societal expectations attributed to her mere picture of a female-bodied language educator causes her to experience this ideological notion in a particular way. Normativity lays hold of Melisa at work. Her experiences as a female-bodied language educator practicing within the Turkish context makes heteroprofessionalism inevitable to encounter and navigate for Melisa.

My (master's) thesis is about a technique called queering. It has its basis on critical pedagogy, and it basically asks students to question whatever we provide or what is provided to them as the norm. So, why is this the norm? One question we asked there was who was profiting from this false information. So, obviously, it has the most fundamental side of it within socialism. The only reason I knew about this enough to write a thesis about it was because of all the experiences I had as a novice English teacher. Up until that point, I was teaching for two and a half years, and I had seen lots of heteronormativity (Int1E42).

Her LGBTQI identity influences Melisa's teaching philosophy as a language educator as well. She takes critical pedagogy as one her educational philosophies in her teaching (*Int1E42*). Queering is a teaching technique based on critical pedagogical philosophies. Question/problem posing is an instructional strategy that critical pedagogues frequently incorporate in their teaching. Melisa is a critical pedagogue. Her teaching has an activist approach. Through question-posing, she encourages her students to inquire about "what is provided to them as the norm" (*Int1E42*). In other words, considering she is doing this as part of her queering technique, she leads her students to ask questions about heteronormativity. Although

she has a fear of institutional hierarchy and punishment, which make her refrain from fully and openly enacting her LGBTQI identity at her heteroprofessional workplace environment including her own classes, she still attempts to find ways of incorporating the queering technique in her teaching. In fact, she even writes a thesis on it. From her perspective, “the only reason (she knows) about this enough to write a thesis about it” (*Int1E42*) is her experiences as a novice language educator. During the span of two and a half years she teaches before writing her thesis on critical pedagogy, Melisa experiences too many instances of heteronormativity in her professional journey as a language educator. Thereafter, she decides to write her thesis on a technique of language teaching in a particular educational philosophy. Both in her personal and professional identity negotiations, English language plays a significant role for Melisa.

4.2.5. Society and Context

Melisa was born, raised, and educated in Turkey, and she currently practices as an English language instructor at a state university located in North Cyprus. In Melisa’s identity negotiation, experience navigation, and perception of heteroprofessionalism, Turkish context and cultural and societal factors also emerges as factors to be considered. Melisa is aware of that as well.

One needs to recognize what the norm is, what people’s perceptions of the norm are, what out of that norm is, and what people’s perceptions of out of that norm are (JE2E8).

Melisa acknowledges the need for familiarity with societal and cultural norms (*JE2E8*) in her navigation of heteroprofessionalism. In fact, she believes that one should be familiar with what people in society perceive as the norm to be able to navigate it. Melisa claims that knowing the norm is not enough. One should also know what is not normalized (*Int1E43*) in society in order to be able to tackle heteroprofessionalism.

Heteroprofessionalism is a fake idea of how we should be acting. Like, that’s the norm, that’s the default and everything else is “not norm” or nonconforming (Int1E43).

Although she does not approve of the normalization of heteroprofessional practices, she still recognizes it. Melisa is aware that, within the context she practices as a language educator, heteroprofessionalism is the “default” (Int1E43) and any non-conforming presence is abnormal. She refers to heteroprofessionalism as a “fake idea of how we should be acting” (Int1E43). She perceives the concept as something that confines how people act in particular contexts. However, she is also aware that it is “fake” (Int1E43). She does not believe in the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism at all. From Melisa’s perspective, heteroprofessionalism is made up. It is a made-up concept to confine people to certain ways of looking, sounding, and acting within professional contexts, and it is now acknowledged as the “default” (Int1E43) by society.

I am the only one she's comfortable with when it comes to being in the same room with the guy (Int1E44).

Turkish culture is not the most LGBTQI-friendly culture. Accordingly, societal expectations and norms are mostly heteronormative. Melisa’s colleagues also have mostly heteronormative ideologies and values. Without being microaggressive or phobic, a coordinator being comfortable with Melisa being around her husband is also problematic as it pertains to her heteronormative culture. Although Melisa is attracted to all types of people irrespective of their gender identities, the coordinator does not regard her as a threat to her marriage (Int1E44) as she does not look like one according to her heteronormative culture. Melisa looks and sounds non-conforming to heteronormativity, which makes the coordinator think that she cannot be attracted to a “regular man” as she is not a “regular woman”, but a “Dyke” (Int1E32), herself. This is “their culture, and it’s terrible”. Much as this is a subtle indication of her coordinator’s values, more often than not, her colleagues assault her through microaggressive attacks or attempts of exclusion.

I heard a colleague, looking toward me, say, "I hope some of us don't attract negative attention.". I know he said this just because he knows how hetero norms are quite applicable at our professional workplace (Int2E28).

Heteroprofessionalism is the reflection of this at workspaces. For Melisa, tackling the normative ideologies prevailing over the Turkish context is also a factor to consider while negotiating her identities and navigating her professional experiences.

They made a slightly homophobic joke about having sex with Ryan Reynolds (PGOR3E6).

From the materials they use to teach English at her institution to her interactions and relationships with her colleagues, institutional superiors, and students, LGBTQI-phobia and heteronormativity are everywhere for Melisa as an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context. Sometimes, her students make explicitly homophobic jokes (PGOR3E6), some other times, they are being unintentionally homophobic (Int1E37).

There was a plethora of moments where I had to tone down my own personal identity just to fit in, just to be able to talk to people, just to be able to make my voice heard, because if you act like an outlier or out of the norm, you're not going to get much out of these usually fossilized colleagues (JE2E9).

Melisa is conscious that the heteronormativity and LGBTQI-phobia she confronts with is also the result of the culture and context within which she tries to negotiate her identities and navigate her professional experiences.

I have to think about my own lasting effect and my own survival at any given point no matter the circumstance (Int1E45).

Sometimes, she even finds herself contemplating having a conforming identity to her society so that she could speak her mind without losing her pride (JE1E5). Melisa tones herself down “just to fit in” (JE2E9). She wants to be heard. She is in survival mode (Int1E45). She is constantly thinking about her own safety at all times (JE1E6).

And more often than not, I try to say it because I want them to think about how they're acting (Int1E46).

While surviving, she also tries to encourage others to think about how they act (Int1E46). She is being proactive once again. One thing about Melisa is she is never completely silenced by the contextual oppressions, cultural practices and attributions, or societal normative ideologies. She always has a word to say, or an action to take. As long as she feels safe, she dares to defy.

To live and survive in these lands, and to have a decent career means to hide and effectively knock some of your most beautiful parts out (JE1E6).

However, “in order to survive in these lands” and “have a decent career” (JE1E6), Melisa also believes that sometimes she needs to remain silent. She needs to “hide some of (her) most beautiful parts” (JE1E6). She refers to her LGBTQI identity. Melisa keeps her personal identity under control around her heteroprofessional workplace environment.

Why does he think this? Because he has never had a gay friend, he was never exposed to gay media, he has no English, whatsoever, and the only thing he heard was, for example, our former prime minister (Int1E47).

Her perspectives on the sociopolitical factors within the Turkish context play an essential role in how Melisa negotiates her identities and navigates her experiences. Upon an explicitly homophobic remark her students make about gay people, Melisa thinks that he falls victim to his ignorance. She relates the student’s ignorance to him never having a gay friend and never being exposed to gay media (Int1E47). The only information he gathered about gay people comes from what he hears from a former Turkish primes minister. This comes as a testament to the indication that Melisa believes the Turkish context is socio-politically not the most LGBTQI-friendly context.

They had partners and they were considered in relationships as they were in heterosexual marriages (Int2E29).

In addition to that, she is also not considered in a relationship with her girlfriend by her administrative institutional superiors and colleagues due to the non-conforming nature of her romantic relationship to heteronormativity (PGOR1E1), which can be said to prevail over the Turkish context.

The woman told me that I was actually lucky I was not dealing with men, and I was also lucky that I couldn’t get legally married, which she said sucked (Int2E30).

Melisa is told that she is lucky for not dealing with men and not being legally able to get married (Int2E30). In fact, Melisa identifies as pansexual (Int1E8). She is also

attracted to men. If she ever loves a man and chooses to marry him one day, she can do this in the Turkish context. However, she cannot marry her girlfriend. This is why she is told that she cannot get married (*Int2E9*), and her relationship is not valid in others' eyes. All these are based upon the heteronormative culture in the Turkish context.

These students know that they can hurt someone's career, livelihood and maybe even freedom if they can make an accusation about queer identity, anti-government regime propaganda, or something that relates to this. (JE1E7).

Melisa also thinks her students have a “sick power” (*JE1E1*) over her. She believes that they know they can ruin someone's career or even take their freedom away if they make accusations about “queer identity” (*JE1E7*) or “anti-government regime propaganda” (*JE1E7*). She identifies with the LGBTQI community and thinks she sounds and looks out of Turkish heteronormative norms. Her political stance is obviously not in favor of the present Turkish government. Considering such circumstances, Melisa feels vulnerable before her students too. She does not completely feel safe with them either, as she is conscious of the power they over her identities and ideologies, granted by the Turkish societal culture.

I haven't said these things to myself since high school, so, it can be said that political Islam wears one down (JE1E8).

It is also important to note that Melisa believes political Islam, which she thinks prevails over the Turkish context, “wears (her) down” (*JE1E8*) as well. In various ways, Melisa's identity negotiation and experience navigation processes are influenced by the Turkish context and societal culture.

4.2.6. Parting and Intersecting Identities

While navigating her heteroprofessional workplace context as an LGBTQI language educator, Melisa's personal and professional identities intersect. Practically all types of oppression she endures at work as a language educator pertains to her LGBTQI

identity as well. While Melisa sometimes chooses to keep her personal and professional identities separated, some other times they intersect.

I try to have them watch other shows where being a good human being, decency 101, is taught. So, it has some queer characters in positive lights (Int1E48).

Melisa attempts to familiarize her students with her own ideological stance. By trying to discommend Turkish TV shows, she tries to encourage them to watch shows that include queer characters “in positive lights” (Int1E48). She refers to those shows as some that would teach her students the basics of “being a good human being” and “decency” (Int1E48). Due to her LGBTQI identity, Melisa tries to incorporate critical pedagogical techniques in her teaching as she does not want her students to remain ignorant regarding gender and sexuality related issues.

Even before I knew queering, was breaking these things (LGBTQI-phobic culture) apart (Int1E49).

The fact that Melisa implements queering throughout her entire professional career as a language educator, even before knowing about it as a teaching technique (Int1E49), is a testament to her LGBTQI identity being the reason for incorporating the queering technique.

My role as language educator and my queer identity interacts obviously. My professional experiences, especially at these heterosexual dynamics at my workplaces, previous and today, have heavily determined and influenced each other (JE2E9).

Melisa is conscious of the interplay her personal and professional identities have in between (JE2E9). She acknowledges the fact that her LGBTQI identity has an impact on her language educator identity. Melisa’s experiences pertaining to heteroprofessionalism helps her realize that her multiple identities indeed intersect (Int1E50), which brings about particular types of oppression. She is not oppressed only because she has a language educator identity, nor is she oppressed merely because she has an LGBTQI identity, or she is female-bodied. When all these different identities intersect with one another, they result in new forms of oppressions

due to heteroprofessionalism. Melisa knows that she is oppressed because she has a woman identity (considering she is female-bodied, which is enough for a heteronormative binary society to classify her as a woman), a language educator identity (since she has been institutionally practicing for a few years now), an LGBTQI identity (as she identifies as bigender/pansexual), and an anti-government activist identity (now that her ideologies do not overlap with mainstream sociopolitical ideologies of the Turkish society and government).

They intersect in a couple of ways. First, the language itself. When I was a language learner, not a not a teacher yet, that's, the language, English language was the place I found my own terms of identity (Int1E50).

Not all of these identities need to intersect for Melisa to face oppression. When even two of them intersect in a particular context, a new way of experiencing oppression emerges.

Another instructor who lives a heteronormative life doesn't have to think about these things, but I have to think about every interaction I have (Int1E51).

Melisa does not navigate her professional experiences in the same ways her cis-heterosexual colleagues do (Int1E51). She acknowledges the difference.

This whole concept was designed to support a queer movement, and yet I'm the one who cannot do it at my workplace as the queer employee, ironically. Let alone the official Zoom work account, they constantly check even our social media presence on some other different platforms too (Int2E31).

She does not want to appear as if she does anything out of the ordinary. She is in constant control of how she appears on her social media accounts (Int2E31), what she does with her work affiliated accounts on virtual platforms, and even how she uses dating applications. She pays for all the premium versions of dating applications (Int1E1) so that her students do not see her. Melisa does not feel safe even with students. She knows very well that everybody in her heteroprofessional workplace context, including her students (JE1E7), might harm her professional career at any point.

They determine the next time I am being authentic in class (I won't be); the next time I help a queer student (I won't); the next time I take a stand against the system (I might not) (JE1E9).

In order to avoid conflict at her heteroprofessional workspace arising from her intersecting multiple identities, Melisa attempts to separate them sometimes (JE1E9). Instead of fully openly enacting her LGBTQI identity, she tries to be careful with how she expresses it. She does not feel comfortable with contemplating the possible consequences of being fully open about her LGBTQI identity at her heteroprofessional workplace environment. Although they inevitably intersect in various ways, more often than not, Melisa avoids this intersection and keeps her multiple identities separated to have her back to the wall when she knows she is constantly surrounded by thorns of heteroprofessionalism as language educator practicing in the Turkish context.

4.2.7. Performativity

While navigating heteroprofessionalism as an LGBTQI-identified language educator, support from colleagues is of great importance. In order for this support to be actually efficient, it should not be performative. In simple terms, performativity refers to actions, behaviors, or statements that appear supportive or aligned with a cause but are actually superficial and lack genuine commitment. It is often a topic of discussion in evaluation of the genuineness of people's support toward marginalized groups and underprivileged communities. More often than not, the concept involves people adopting the appearance of advocacy or solidarity. This could be posting about LGBTQI rights on social media during Pride Month, incorporating inclusive language in business, or displaying symbols such as the rainbow flag but not taking any meaningful steps to actually support the LGBTQI community. This type of behavior typically targets social approval, avoiding criticisms of not being inclusive, or merely enhancing one's own social image. Contributions to real change or addressing systemic issues are not often among the aims of people adopting performative behaviors. It might definitely create an illusion of support to marginalized groups. However, it also overshadows genuine efforts of support and dilutes the focus on the real struggles and needs of underprivileged communities. As

an activist, LGBTQI-identified language educator practicing at a heteroprofessional institution within the Turkish context, where heteronormativity already prevails over as a strong societal culture of ideology, performative support from her colleagues is not even the last thing Melisa needs.

I know it's all performative. I know my colleagues don't truly believe in these (critical pedagogical) principles (Int2E32).

Melisa is conscious of the fact that her colleagues are often performative in their interactions with her. Just because they know, or assume she belongs with the LGBTQI community, they want her to engage in all the things pertaining to diversity and inclusion at work. This cannot be classified as real support, nor is it genuine (Int2E32). Her colleagues possibly attempt to benefit from her knowledge on those issues, or they try to build a relationship with her in the most wrong way possible. Performative actions are never welcomed by individuals belonging with marginalized groups in societies. By nature, those actions reduce their identities to only belonging with that underprivileged community. No marginalized individual would enjoy interactions merely based upon their socio-politically marginalized identity.

They (colleagues) bring anything diversity/inclusion-related stuff to me. The only reason they do this is they know I'm queer, and they think just because of my personal identity (Int2E33).

Melisa knows that her colleagues do not do this particularly because they care about her LGBTQI identity and want to establish genuine relationships through it. They think Melisa is supposed to be knowledgeable about issues related to diversity and inclusion. She also realizes that these actions have nothing to do with her professional identity (Int2E33), which renders them performative even more. Her colleagues do not want to discuss issues of diversity and inclusion with Melisa because they trust her professional competence as an educator. They do this because they know she is “queer” (Int2E33). By that means, while adopting an appearance of engaging in Melisa’s personal identity to interact with her, all they actually want to do is possibly benefit from her knowledge on issues they assume she would be knowledgeable about due to her personal identity.

I try to resist whenever I can. It is very limited unfortunately. It makes my life more difficult in different ways. As an example of a smaller issue, I have to be the resident queer expert on matters related to anything remotely non-traditional. It's a big responsibility to carry (JE3E6).

Performativity also makes it more difficult for Melisa to even try to resist heteroprofessionalism around her workspace. She “has to be the resident queer expert” (JE3E6) at work. From her perspective, any issue of discussion that is remotely non-traditional is taken to her. Melisa thinks these kind of performative actions burden her with “a big responsibility to carry” (JE3E6), which makes her professional experiences even more difficult to navigate. This is actually another form of manifestation of heteroprofessionalism. Her cis-heterosexual educator colleagues do not have to go through this experience, which makes work life worse and more difficult for Melisa. Merely due to her LGBTQI identity, Melisa is the one who is burdened with this responsibility of having to be knowledgeable about non-traditional issues and supporting colleagues when needed (JE3E6). On top of that, these kind of performative actions are not even a form of real support shown for Melisa’s personal identity at work, which makes them even more heteroprofessional. In addition to extra professional responsibility that Melisa is burdened with by her colleagues merely due to her personal identity, she is emotionally tired of these kind of performative actions as well (JE3E6). When support does not feel genuine, it might do more harm than good to people of marginalized communities. In Melisa’s case, she is also not happy to see that most of the support she receives from her colleagues are performative actions.

A couple of hours later, those same 4 coworkers were chatting and laughing about it (a microaggressive attack by a male colleague) (PGOR2E5).

After the male colleague remarks on the stipend Melisa, as the unmarried daughter, receives due to her mother’s loss and leaves the scene, some colleagues remain unresponsive, while some console her and apologize on behalf of him. After a while, Melisa sees the other unresponsive and commiserate colleagues at another site “chatting and laughing about it” (PGOR2E5). This is another form of a performative action. Those colleagues choose to remain silent or subtly console Melisa by apologizing about the male colleague’s remarks at the time of the incident. After

witnessing them chatting and laughing about it after a while, Melisa realizes that their consolations back then are not genuine at all. They adopt an appearance of showing affection and support, although they do not actually feel that way about Melisa. Such performative actions performed by them do not make them any better than the microaggressive male colleague in terms of worsening the heteroprofessional atmosphere of the workplace environment for Melisa. Perhaps, they might be even worse, considering how difficult they make it for Melisa to differentiate genuineness from fakeness at work.

I know female coworkers would be more sensitive, but it would mostly be performative since we are not close friends (PGOR2E6).

Melisa explicitly acknowledges her colleagues' performativity. In most instances, Melisa experiences heteroprofessionalism through male colleagues when it is not coming from students (though it also mostly comes from male students in her case). Therefore, Melisa perceives female colleagues as "more sensitive" (PGOR2E6). However, she is also well aware of the fact that there is not really a sense of genuineness in this sensitivity. Although female colleagues do not appear to be explicitly practicing heteroprofessionalism and harming Melisa through exclusion or microaggressions (which is only usually the case), they contribute to it through their performative actions. Performative actions are not any better than any other form of manifestation of heteroprofessionalism around Melisa's workplace environment. It might be argued by some people that acts of performativity are not as detrimental as other forms of heteroprofessional manifestations merely because they may at least indicate people's awareness or acknowledgment of underprivileged communities. However, these actions lack depth and might make heteroprofessionalism even worse to navigate sometimes. Many people perceive performative actions as a starting point or a way to maintain visibility for marginalized groups. However, they can actually be just as harmful as they frequently divert attention from meaningful and genuine support. Coming from colleagues, they might maintain a false sense of progress through fake efforts of advocacy while perpetuating the existing heteroprofessional practices at work. Melisa's female colleagues uphold the same power structures that are mostly enforced by the male colleagues and that they appear to be challenging.

Little do they know that their performative actions actually make the heteroprofessional workplace environment even more challenging for Melisa to navigate. Once again, Melisa falls victim to another concept.

This chapter explores and presents the findings of how the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism manifests itself in Melisa's workplace environment as an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context and how she negotiates her multiple identities while navigating her professional experiences, as the two research questions of the study aim to investigate. Ultimately, the findings demonstrate that the prevailing societal culture of heteronormative ideas within the Turkish context influence many aspects of her professional trajectory. These include societal expectations, assumptions, cultural attributions, social interactions, microaggressions, various forms of institutional exclusion, and performative actions performed by colleagues that limit how she expresses and enacts her multiple identities at work. Heteroprofessionalism creates a wide range of challenges for Melisa as she navigates her professional experiences and attempts to negotiate her personal and professional identities. Findings show that these challenges come in different forms for Melisa. While some take the form of subtle pressures to fit into normative ideologies and expectations, some others set forth more overt constraints on her self-expression. Although such difficulties make her professional career a challenging path to navigate, Melisa often demonstrates agency in how she responds to them. Being responsive to many forms of microaggressive attacks and attempts of institutional exclusion, Melisa employs strategies to maintain her personal authenticity while also meeting professional requirements. Along with that, she goes through an array of overwhelming emotions while attempting to manage how she separates her multiple identities, when she merges them through negotiation, and how she navigates her professional experiences. Her approach toward navigating heteroprofessionalism emphasizes the ongoing process of attempting to balance her identity plurality at a workplace context molded by societal and cultural heteronormative values and practices. These attempts of negotiation are not fixed at all. On the contrary, they require constant adaptation and resilience, which take Melisa much patience, courage, and mental stamina to manage and maintain. All in all, the findings reveal how cultural and societal heteronormative norms shape

Melisa's professional workspace experiences through heteroprofessionalism and build barriers for her as an individual belonging with an underprivileged community due to her marginalized personal identities. Therewithal, they also show in what ways she resists or complies with heteroprofessionalism while trying to negotiate her multiple identities and navigate her professional experiences.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Aiming at investigating the perspectives of an LGBTQI language educator practicing at the university level in the Turkish context on her own identity negotiation, professional experience navigation, and the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism, the present study is guided by the following research problem and questions.

The intricate interplay between and the intersecting dynamics of LGBTQI language educators' multiples identities, workplace experiences, and the ideological notion of institutionalized heteroprofessionalism within the Turkish educational context remains underexplored in the existing literature.

RQ1: From the perspective of an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context, how does heteroprofessionalism, if any, manifest itself within her workplace context?

RQ2: How does an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context negotiate her identities and navigate her professional experiences within her heteroprofessional workplace context?

While the first research question aims at investigating the forms of manifestation of heteroprofessionalism within the participant's workspace, the second question explores how she negotiates her identities and navigates her professional experiences within that context. In the light of the findings, this chapter puts forward the researcher's discussions and the conclusion pertaining to the research problem and questions of the study.

5.1. Summary of the Key Findings

The present study explored the experiences of an LGBTQI language educator, Melisa, practicing within a heteroprofessional state university located in the Turkish context, emphasizing her perspectives on the intersectionality of her identity negotiation, professional experience navigation, and the ideological notion of heteroprofessionalism at her workspace. Guided by two research questions, the study's findings reveal intricate dynamics that provide insights into both the challenges and resilience inherent in Melisa's professional trajectory as an LGBTQI language educator within the Turkish context. Heteroprofessionalism came forth as a rather predominant and multifaceted force practiced within Melisa's workplace environment, having a systematic influence on her professional experiences and social interactions at work. She is quite conscious of her positioning as "the queer teacher around", which emerges as a label that influences her interactions with all stakeholders from her colleagues to students. Before a language educator, Melisa is labeled as a queer individual, which makes her personal identity of gender and sexuality enforce impact on her professional identity of being a language educator. This hyperawareness of her own positioning compels Melisa into a state of being constantly alert and on guard, which comes off as extreme vigilance, impacting both her professional dynamics and personal relationships around her workplace context.

From Melisa's perspective, heteroprofessionalism is a social construct, collectively practiced as a "fake idea" by Turkish society. She identifies both professional risks and personal threats caused by the heteroprofessional practices in her workplace context. Binary expectations and societal attributions and assumptions on gender and sexuality, profoundly embedded in the Turkish context of institutional settings and cultural practices, further marginalize Melisa's LGBTQI identity at her workplace environment. At work, such ideals often manifest in the form of discriminatory remarks by her students, colleagues, and administrative institutional superiors. In spite of these complex challenges, Melisa claims her agency and actively resists heteroprofessionalism at her workplace context. Except for her strategic silence in particular contexts that Melisa infrequently prefers for her own professional safety,

she is usually outspoken and refractory. As much perseverance, patience, and mental stamina as it requires, she constantly remains defiant.

Melisa's LGBTQI identity is self-defined as bigender and pansexual, which embodies a fluid sense of self compared to binary assumptions and attributions of gender and socio-politically constructed heteronormative understanding and expectations of sexuality in the Turkish context. This plurality of her multiple identities informs her teaching philosophy and interactions, as she often merges her personal and professional identities. In order to be able to successfully navigate the intricacies of her heteroprofessional workplace context, Melisa puts into practice an array of strategic adaptations that juggle professional excellence, calculated social dynamics, and discretion of her personal identities. She prioritizes impeccable competence and execution in her discipline to dodge any form of inspection and malignant criticism that might actually arise out of mere biases against her LGBTQI identity. Furthermore, selective disclosure of her LGBTQI identity and contextual unresponsiveness become significant tools in the navigation of her heteroprofessional workspace. These acts of purposeful advocacy attempts emerge as a significant testament to the intersectionality of her multiple personal and professional identities. The negotiation of her identity plurality and the navigation of her professional experiences in her heteroprofessional workplace context are significantly influenced by the practice of the cultural and institutional norms of the Turkish context. Through these key findings, along with various forms of manifestation of heteroprofessionalism at her workplace context, its pervasive impact on the multiple identity negotiation and professional experience navigation processes that Melisa goes through as an LGBTQI language educator practicing within the Turkish context is underscored.

5.2. Interpretations of the Key Findings

In this section, the key findings of the study are interpreted by drawing on Mizzi's (2013) heteroprofessionalism and Crenshaw's (1989) intersectionality as the conceptual frameworks. These conceptual frameworks offer a greater understanding of the findings, pertaining them to broader structures of societal, cultural, socio-

political, and identity-related matters. Although Melisa does not identify herself as a homosexual, she belongs with the LGBTQI community, whose overall non-conformity to heteronormative ideologies of societies makes it a subject to heteroprofessionalism. Crenshaw defines intersectionality as a means of understanding how various forms of inequality can exacerbate oppression and create further barriers for marginalized identities. Through scrutiny of how heteroprofessionalism and intersectionality emerge as influencing factors on Melisa's experiences of oppression as an LGBTQI language educator practicing within the Turkish context, this section underscores the systemic challenges and her attempts of agency as an individual belonging with a marginalized and underprivileged community due to her non-conforming gender and sexual identities. The findings illustrate that heteroprofessionalism, as also articulated by Mizzi (2013), should not be considered merely an institutional force of structure, but as a set of ideologies and practices that normalize and perpetuate exclusion. Within Melisa's workplace context, heteroprofessionalism manifests in various ways, from overt microaggressions to subtle institutional exclusions. One of the most notable forms is Melisa's hyperawareness of her own positioning as an LGBTQI language educator. Acknowledging the role of "the queer teacher around", she is constantly alert and vigilant. Her personal identity is prioritized over her professional one, unlike her cis-heterosexual colleagues. This label brings overreliance on Melisa to handle diversity-related matters and imposes additional burdens and responsibilities. She is confronted with a barrier against her professional excellence, further proving how the intersectionality of her identities shapes her experience of oppression.

According to Melisa's reports, cis-heteronormativity emerges as a dominant socio-political ideology in the Turkish context. Non-conforming relationships are socially excluded and legally unacknowledged. These values are reflected within workplaces through heteroprofessionalism. Due to her LGBTQI identity and non-conforming relationship, Melisa experiences exclusion from workplace events and an unequal workload. These reflect how cis-heteronormative assumptions about relationships shape professional expectations and resource allocation. Heteroprofessionalism manifests through microaggressions and performative actions by colleagues. At a formal event, a colleague targets her LGBTQI identity to undermine her

professionalism. This reflects how heteroprofessionalism allows personal identity to be weaponized against professional legitimacy. While cis-heterosexual employees rarely encounter such instances of microaggressions, Melisa is frequently alienated from her professional identity through attacks that heteroprofessionalism eases the execution of. Although this alienation from her professional identity is indirectly performed, it directly helps undermine Melisa's professionalism. She also manages and limits her expressiveness while navigating her role as a language educator. Performative actions by female colleagues, such as apologizing for a microaggression while later joking about it, contribute further to the undermining of her identity. Meanwhile, student expressions of LGBTQI-phobia, though often attributed by Melisa to ignorance, mirror the broader cultural normalization of exclusion. In one case, a student's action becomes a flashpoint for scrutiny and blame toward Melisa, reinforcing how her personal identity becomes a disciplinary target in a heteroprofessional institution.

Despite these challenges, Melisa shows resilience. She uses critical pedagogy, queering techniques, and question-posing strategies to challenge norms and promote inclusion. Her gender identity, sexual identity, socio-political identity, and female-bodied identity intersect in ways that uniquely affect her. The intersection of these identities, rather than any single one, is the source of most institutional oppression she faces. She strategically manages how she presents herself and interacts with students and colleagues in order to protect her professional position while subtly advocating for equity. Ultimately, Melisa's identity negotiation and professional experience navigation are deeply shaped by heteroprofessionalism. She attempts to "survive" it smoothly, while also using her professional role to affirm her personal identities. Her story illustrates not only how heteroprofessionalism operates through institutional and interpersonal mechanisms but also how it can be resisted through personal agency, adaptability, and purposeful pedagogy.

5.3. Answers to the Research Questions

This section aims at answering the two research questions of the present study by drawing on the findings and their interpretations previously presented. In the light of

what has been discussed so far, the research questions are individually answered in this section to provide a concise understanding of the overall result.

5.3.1. Research Question 1

The findings demonstrate that heteroprofessionalism manifests in various ways within Melisa's workplace environment through structural, interpersonal, cultural, socio-political, and institutional mechanisms. Structurally, institutional policies align with cis-heteronormative ideologies in the Turkish context, reinforcing professional expectations that marginalize non-conforming identities. From Melisa's perspective, professional dynamics are framed by the assumption that cis-heterosexuality is the default. This is evident in how institutional practices fail to recognize her non-cis-heterosexual romantic relationship, excluding her and projecting an expectation that employees conform to traditional family structures. Interpersonally, heteroprofessionalism is expressed through microaggressions, performativity, exclusion, and the reductive label of "the queer teacher around." These acts alienate her professionally, create hypervisibility, and reduce her identity plurality. Social interactions frequently involve subtle undermining of her identities, such as dismissive remarks and laughter at gender-related mistakes, showing how heteronormative values shape everyday professional exchanges.

Cultural expectations for female-bodied English teachers, traditional views of gender and sexuality, and limited emphasis on inclusivity further marginalize Melisa. Socio-political forces including governmental attitudes, marriage laws, and majoritarian ideologies also influence how her workplace operates. These forces are institutionally reflected in practices that uphold traditional family models and devalue non-conforming relationships. Institutionally, her romantic relationship affects her workload through assumptions about her availability. Her complaints are dismissed by superiors, including a redirection to a superior's spouse who further marginalizes her through cis-heteronormative commentary. Together, these manifestations create a professional culture where exclusion is normalized and Melisa's professional identity is consistently subordinated to her personal identities, restricting her inclusion and empowerment.

5.3.2. Research Question 2

In order to authentically maintain the enactment of both her personal and professional identities while also mitigating potential professional risks, Melisa endeavors to negotiate her identity plurality and navigate her professional experiences through a calculated combination of strategic adaptation, resistance, and advocacy. One notable strategy she employs is selective disclosure. Through this strategy, Melisa can maintain a private and relatively controllable degree regarding how her LGBTQI identity is perceived by others around her workplace context, which perfectly aligns with the given demands of a heteroprofessionalism. Leveraging her professional identity as a way to perform advocacy and resistance efforts regarding her non-conforming personal identities is another significant aspect of Melisa's identity negotiation and professional experience navigation. She practices critical pedagogical approaches and instructional strategies through her teaching philosophy by incorporating queering and question-posing techniques to encourage her students in terms of questioning the instances of injustice in the world around them. Along with emerging as affirmation of her own non-conforming identities, these actions foster a more inclusive learning atmosphere for her students as well.

Melisa also negotiates her identities and navigates her experiences by strategically managing the interpersonal dynamics she has with her colleagues, students, and administrative institutional superiors. She cares about building allyship with her supportive colleagues as well as maintaining professional excellence as a language educator. Moreover, Melisa makes much use of humor and assertiveness in her interpersonal dynamics at work as means of responding to microaggressive attacks and acts of discrimination and exclusion coming from her colleagues. Within the Turkish context, wherein binary values of gender and cis-heteronormative assumptions of sexuality are profoundly entrenched and prevalently practiced, Melisa's strategic adaptations within her heteroprofessional workspace are reflective of a calculated balance between resistance and compliance. She carefully manages her processes of identity enactment as well as resisting heteroprofessional ideologies and values that are frequently practiced within the context of her workplace

environment. Even though she indubitably goes through a range of professional, personal, and institutional challenges, Melisa is not fully intimidated by heteroprofessionalism, neither is she silenced nor overawed by its discriminative, restrictive, and oppressive practices that prevail over the context of her workplace environment.

5.4. Discussion within the Pertinent Literature

In the light of the literature review chapter previously presented, this section aims to situate the findings of the present study within the broader relevant scholarly discourse. Even though the research questions of this study have not been greatly addressed within the Turkish scholarly discourse, as the literature review chapter demonstrates, studies conducted on similar issues are not that limited in number. Emphasizing aspects of alignment and divergence between existing research and the findings of this study, this sections provides particular references to key studies presented in the study's review of literature with the aim of bringing attention to both their contributions and the gaps addressed by this study.

5.4.1. Alignment with Existing Research

The most significant alignment of the findings of this study with other studies in the existing literature lies in the various struggles LGBTQI educators tackle while endeavoring to negotiate their personal and professional identities as well as navigating their professional experiences. As a case in point, Llewellyn (2022) highlighted the identity dichotomy faced by LGBTQI educators while attempting to navigate their professional workspace that strictly demands conformity to cis-heteronormative ideologies and values. Similar to Melisa, Llewellyn's participants were able to separate their non-conforming personal identities from their professional identities with extra effort, which came with further challenges of identity plurality negotiation. Although Melisa and Llewellyn's participants are somehow able to achieve this balance, more tension is experienced by all due to that. For instance, Melisa's professional experiences are rather approximate to Jackson's (2009) and Gray's (2013) explorations that LGBTQI educators frequently feel further pressure

to manage a duality of personas so that they can contextually separate their personal and professional identities and lives from each other. In a similar vein, while trying to enact a fully professional identity within the context of her workplace environment due to her forced dual personas, Melisa uses a strategy of selective disclosure, which demonstrates her fear of full disclosure of her LGBTQI identities at work. This fear of full disclosure, as also discussed by Orlov and Allen (2014) in their study of LGBTQI faculty at the university level and their navigation of disclosure, is observably evident in Melisa's calculated strategies of selective disclosure, highlighting how profoundly entrenched such concerns are in LGBTQI educators' identity negotiation in their heteroprofessional workspaces. These concerns are quite detrimental in terms of the overall well-being of LGBTQI educators (O'Brien & Fassinger, 1993).

However, in order not to feel 'trapped in the closet', which is another one of very prevalent fears of LGBTQI educators (Jackson, 2006, as cited in Thomas-Durrell, 2019) along with being unfavorably perceived by stakeholders (Russ, et al., 2002), Melisa also, even subtly and passively most of the times, attempts to enact her non-conforming personal identities within her workplace context. This is a form of resistance she frequently performs to claim her ground. Her integration of critical pedagogical techniques and instructional strategies in her teaching as a part of this objection parallels findings by Allen (1995), Gates (2011), Brockenbrough (2012), and Rodriguez and Pinar (2007), who examined how LGBTQI educators often make use of critical and radical pedagogies to resist the dominant cis-heteronormative norms and practices of their workspace contexts. The transformative potential of employing inclusive teaching practices is emphasized by these studies. Melisa's attitude of not avoiding discussions centering gender and sexuality issues in her classrooms are in alignment with these endeavors and efforts to foster inclusive educational spaces, even under the restraint of heteroprofessionalism. Through such classroom discussions with her students, she is also reflective of the duality of LGBTQI educators' roles as both professional practitioners and social advocates, which is a notably recurring theme in the relevant literature (Bennett et al., 2015; Mizzi et al., 2021). In a similar vein, Melisa's constant attempts of encouraging her students to engage in the target language's LGBTQI-affirming media align with the

findings of Ferfolja and Robinson (2004), who explored the significant role of popular media as a means of disturbing the prevalent cis-heteronormative values and practices in educational spaces.

Though her acts of resistance are rather similar to how Swanepoel (2019) performs resistance as a gay male teacher in terms of upholding their personal values, Melisa's most notable emotion emerging in the findings is still fear. Considering how, for fear of retaliation, she stops including her girlfriend in her conversations upon a very unfortunate incident with her colleagues, Melisa's professional experience navigation parallels with Coda's (2019) decision of not disclosing his LGBTQI identity due to fear when explicitly asked about by a student. Coda's documentation of his own experiences was more pertinent to his probable fear of being unfavorably perceived by his students, which is mostly the case when LGBTQI educators' experiences are compared with those who are sexually unspecified (Ewing et al., 2003) or simply cis-heterosexual (Rumens & Kerfoot, 2009; Williams & Giuffre, 2011). However, as the findings also reveal that Melisa is less distant to her students compared to her colleagues and institutional superiors, although they both experience selective disclosure due to fear, the source of their fear is different. While Coda's (2019) fear was directly related to his concern regarding how he was perceived by his students, Melisa's fear is more likely to be stemming from how she perceives the intersectionality of her own personal and professional identities, also noted by Henderson (2017) as another source of fear of LGBTQI educators. Along with that, her fear also reflects deliberate silence of LGBTQI educators with fear of dismissal merely due to their non-conforming gender and sexual identities (Eckes & McCarthy, 2008), considering she does not want to get fired over "trivial" issues due to heteroprofessionalism, which further exacerbates her identity negotiation by regulating sexual diversity at workspaces (Davies & Neustifter, 2021).

According to the findings, alignment with existing research also extends to the challenges of LGBTQI educators with regard to socio-cultural values, socio-political ideologies, and majoritarian practices as well. Considering Melisa practices as a university level language educator within the Turkish context, it is also important to point out that her professional experiences are reflective of broader systemic barriers

in that context, aligning with findings from İpekçi (2022) and Taşkın et al. (2022). It was emphasized in these studies that traditionally cis-heteronormative values of gender and sexuality within the Turkish context as well as a lack of institutional support further multiply the compelling challenges that LGBTQI educators face within their workspaces. Melisa's unpleasant professional experiences regarding being excluded by her colleagues from social events, such as the "couples" night out, and the extra workload she is forced by her institutional superiors to deal with due to cis-heteronormative assumptions about her being "single and queer", reflect the structural and interpersonal biases that were also identified by İpekçi (2022) and Taşkın et al. (2022).

Discussing Melisa's professional experiences as an LGBTQI employee without focusing particularly on her roles as an educator reveals more alignments with the existing research conducted in the Turkish context. As demonstrated by the findings, Melisa struggles a lot while endeavoring to negotiate her personal and professional identities as an LGBTQI employee. Her struggles regarding identity negotiation reflect the discussions of Akgül and Güneş (2023), Göçmen and Yılmaz (2017), İncekara and Ulaş (2023), Özeren (2014), Özeren et al. (2016), Ulaş-Kılıç et al. (2019), and Yılmaz and Göçmen (2016) on how difficult it is for LGBTQI professionals to strike a balance between their personal and professional identities, considering personal identity enactment at work is not an easy task for LGBTQI employees working in the Turkish context (Özeren et al., 2016). Socio-politically considering, Turkish LGBTQI identities are not officially criminalized by the Turkish laws (Göçmen & Yılmaz, 2017). However, as also observable in the interpretations of the findings within Melisa's narratives, LGBTQI-related issues are excluded from the Turkish educational context (Acar, 2023), wherein cis-heteronormativity operates through various mechanisms (Hooker, 2018a). Taking a socio-cultural point of view, Melisa's perception of her own gender and sexual identities as "abnormality" and "abomination" is reflective of how queerness in general is viewed and portrayed as sinful, deviant, and disgusting within the Turkish society (Basaran, 2003; Sakallı & Uğurlu, 2002). Such socio-political and socio-cultural parallels with the existing literature attest how majoritarian ideologies, values, norms, and practices coalesce in perpetuating cis-heteronormativity as default

in the Turkish context, leaving all other non-conforming identities belonging with the LGBTQI community is a social state of having to navigate environments that are rife with both implicit and explicitly acts of exclusion and marginalization.

Melisa's selective disclosure, strategic unresponsiveness, and passive advocacy efforts are reflective of her fear of reprisal and dismissal. According to Ferfolja and Stavrou (2015), tackling LGBTQI-related issues in the classroom may result in unfavorable reactions, microaggressions, and criticism from parents, colleagues, students, and institutional administrators. Such possibilities discussed by Ferfolja and Stavrou (2015) further validate Melisa's fearful silence at work, through which she compromises her non-conforming personal identities to avoid conflicts, microaggressions, and discrimination. Resnick and Galupo (2018) note that cis-heteronormativity and the normalization of LGBTQI-phobia, which are frequently practiced within Melisa's heteroprofessional workplace context, facilitate spaces for such forms of oppression for LGBTQI employees, as also observed in her experiences.

On the other hand, Melisa's responsiveness and proactive stance, along with her use of critical pedagogical strategies and the encouragement of LGBTQI-affirmative culture of the target language, also align with how LGBTQI Spanish language educators in Coda's (2019) study made use of the Spanish culture in their teaching to problematize cis-heteronormativity in their classrooms. Both strategies represent all these LGBTQI language educators', including Melisa, advocacy efforts stemming from their non-conforming personal identities to challenge oppressive structures through their professional identity. In addition to that, Melisa's proactive endeavors also align with Brockenbrough's (2012) findings, which underscored how LGBTQI educators leveraged their profession to perform as agents of change by transforming LGBTQI-phobic instances into teachable moments for their students to lead them to challenge their own biases and assumptions. In a similar vein, Allen (1995) also shared her own insights of integrating critical pedagogies in her teaching as an openly lesbian educator, which also helped her disclose her LGBTQI identity at work. Critical pedagogies and advocacy efforts through their integration into teaching were noted to encourage self-disclosure and assist the students of LGBTQI

educators in navigating multiple subjectivities regarding non-conformity (Allen, 1995). Although Melisa employs these pedagogical strategies to address LGBTQI-phobia as a broader societal issue, considering she neither actively hides her identity nor openly discloses it, her narratives and perspectives are still in alignment with Allen's (1995) experiences.

Ultimately, the findings of the present study reflect the existing literature on LGBTQI educators, employees, or individuals in general. This close alignment particularly pertains to the systemic challenges of negotiating identity plurality and navigating cis-heteronormative workplace contexts. Melisa's narratives and perspectives reaffirm the recurring concepts of marginalization and discrimination, whose instances were documented in prior research, while also highlighting her resistance, resilience, advocacy efforts, and agency as an LGBTQI language educator practicing within the Turkish context. The aforementioned alignments indicate a broadness of applicability regarding the frameworks that are prevalent in the relevant literature, which attests their pertinence across diverse socio-cultural settings. Along with that, they also further emphasize the significance of exploring the identity duality of LGBTQI educators regarding being both advocates and practitioners simultaneously, conducing a deeper understanding of their professional experiences.

5.4.2. Divergence From Existing Research

It is important to point out that the majority of the findings of this study directly align with relevant studies in the existing pertinent literature. However, there are still a few noteworthy divergences in some aspects of Melisa's experiences, which provide unique details that can contribute to the scholarly discourse. The Turkish educational context, which remains unfortunately but noticeably underexplored in global research on LGBTQI educators, is what these divergences are most perceptibly related to. Through comparison of Melisa's narratives and perspectives to what prior studies provided, this section presents observable discrepancies and provides insights into the impact of socio-cultural, socio-political, and institutional dynamics on the divergence of non-conforming individuals' experiences.

In prior research, a recurring theme pertains to how LGBTQI educators experience a strict identity dichotomy when it comes to the decision of disclosing or hiding their LGBTQI identity at work. Exploring the expressiveness of LGBTQI educators regarding their personal identities and family dynamics, Gray (2013) and Rockhill (1993) highlighted a very binary framework, where their participants had to choose between openness and concealment. This binary framework was discussed by both researchers to stem from a fear of oppression in various ways. However, this fear was not much related to the socio-political or socio-cultural contexts of those educators, rather, they were more of personal decisions, which they were contextually able to make. On the other hand, although she experiences fear in various ways, Melisa adapts a more strategically fluid approach in her disclosure navigation. She does not take on a single decision but contextually adapts the disclosure of her LGBTQI identity by strategically engaging with her students, colleagues, and institutional superiors. Her selective strategy is a result of both the values and practices of her institution and the restrictiveness of the Turkish context regarding the LGBTQI community. Rather than committing to a fully intrinsic decision on whether or not to disclose her LGBTQI identity within her workplace context, Melisa navigates a significant consideration of when to do it, how to do it, and which “fossilized” (JE2E4) colleagues to do it to, considering all the instilled cis-heteronormative values they uphold due to the cis-heteropatriarchal socio-cultural and socio-political contexts they are in, which are profoundly entrenched in the ideologies of most of Melisa’s colleagues.

Allen (1995) and Gates (2011) explored how openly LGBTQI educators leveraged their professional identity in their advocacy efforts regarding LGBTQI issues through critical pedagogical techniques and instructional strategies. However, those educators mostly had institutional and socio-cultural support to do that. Although Melisa performs advocacy by making use of her professional identity as well, conversely, she endeavors to do this within a more obstructive socio-cultural and institutional context, wherein explicit discussions on LGBTQI issues are still perceived as a taboo. Her experiences are significantly divergent from the strategies identified in these studies, considering her ability of subtly incorporating critical pedagogy into her teaching philosophy without drawing too much negative attention

from her institutional superiors. This underscores a notable niche in the pertinent literature: the integration of critical pedagogical techniques and strategies by LGBTQI educators within socio-culturally obstructive, often non-Western educational settings, wherein institutional support is also not emphatic. In a similar vein, Bennett et al. (2015) and Brockenbrough (2012) investigated how LGBTQI educators negotiated the intersectionality of their non-conforming personal and professional identities. However, this exploration took place within somewhat supportive or neutral contexts. On the other hand, Melisa's narratives and perspectives diverge in how her gender and sexual identities are negotiated with profoundly embedded cis-heteronormative values that are prevalent in the Turkish context. To illustrate, in contrast to the participants of Bennett et al. (2015), who were teaching in diverse and multicultural settings, Melisa experiences a binary set of strict socio-cultural challenges associated with how the Turkish society expects to see female-bodied individuals in professional roles, let alone considering her actual gender and sexual identities. This divergence in her experiences highlights the significance of context-specific investigations into how LGBTQI educators negotiate the non-conformity of their personal and professional identities while navigating their rather dissimilar professional experiences.

Similar to Melisa's narratives and perspectives, prior research mostly presented findings regarding institutional challenges LGBTQI educators often face at work, such as microaggressive attacks and systemic acts of social exclusion (e.g., Ferfolja & Hopkins, 2013; Mizzi et al., 2021). Nevertheless, there is still a discrepancy between how Melisa experiences those forms of oppression and how they were experienced by others. As a case in point, while Libed et al. (2010) and many other researchers in the pertinent literature, even subtly, indicated institutional support and defiance, Melisa's professional experiences demonstrate a divergence, considering her institution operates under an ethos of "don't ask, don't tell". This renders her experiences unique and different from those identified and discussed in most prior research in terms of a mixture of lacking active socio-cultural support and facing a perpetuated absence of institutional support, which further consolidates attempts of implicit silencing at work. Melisa's institution maintains a perpetuated invisibility of LGBTQI-related concerns, forcing her to find intrinsically supported resilience and

mental stamina within herself rather than through extrinsic support, which is in contrast to many participants in prior research, who identified and reported progressive support from their institutions.

In addition to all these, it is important to point out that prior research on student engagement and rapport mostly highlighted the experiences of openly LGBTQI educators in terms of building allyship and fostering open-mindedness. However, Melisa is not an openly LGBTQI language educator. She neither actively and deliberately hides her gender and sexual identities nor openly and proudly enacts them through her interactions with her students, which makes her experiences of student engagement unique. Also, along with her unique negotiation of her personal identities at work, her narratives and perspectives diverge from those identified and documented in prior research due to her workplace context as well, which severely restricts her attempts of directly confronting LGBTQI-phobia in her classrooms. Besides being an institutional issue, this limitation implicitly pertains to the prevailing socio-cultural values within the Turkish context as well. With LGBTQI educators revealing their identities and expressing them openly through their student engagement, gradual shifts in their students' perspectives regarding LGBTQI issues were documented in studies conducted within Western contexts (e.g., Allen, 1995; Bennett et al., 2015; Jackson, 2007; Laplante, 2023), wherein LGBTQI identities are relatively more socio-culturally supported. On the other hand, students within the Turkish context are discussed to contribute to the perpetuation of oppression for LGBTQI identities (Vefikuluçay Yılmaz et al., 2022). As a case in point, although she does not aim a deliberate harm, one of Melisa's students kisses her in the middle of her classroom to experiment with her own gender and sexuality. This instance is a subtle perpetuation of oppression for Melisa, considering both how her LGBTQI identity is prioritized by her students while her professional identity is pushed to the background at work and the high rate of sexual assault allegations LGBTQI educators face by their students (Piper & Sikes, 2010), which further complicates their identity negotiation processes. Therefore, rather than a change in attitude of others toward her non-conforming personal identities, her experiences reveal a persistency of struggles regarding the navigation of overt and covert forms of oppression within a socio-culturally obstructive context. Even though her approach

to this negotiation, which is mostly about striking a healthy balance between student engagement and conflict avoidance, is still valid, considering LGBTQI educators already feel anxious about bringing up LGBTQI issues to their students (Conrad, 2019), it provides an alternative understanding of the dynamics between LGBTQI educators and their students under socio-culturally and institutionally restrictive conditions. Ultimately, considering all these divergences, the present study highlights the significance of a contextualized understanding of LGBTQI educators' narratives, perspectives, and experiences, which may further enrich the scholarly discourse on their identity negotiation, advocacy efforts, and unique struggles within diverse socio-cultural contexts.

5.5. Implications

The most notable implications carried by the findings of the present study emerge for educational institutions and policymakers that aspire to foster more inclusive and equitable workspaces for LGBTQI educators. One key implication pertains to the pressing need for a change in the operation of institutional mechanisms, which are observed to perpetuate the structural and socio-cultural manifestations of heteroprofessionalism in this study. It is also evident in Melisa's experiences that institutional and governmental policies protecting LGBTQI educators from discrimination explicitly, offering spaces for reporting microaggressions and attempts of exclusion, and ensuring fair treatment in professional responsibilities and workload are crucial. Also, considering all various forms of oppression Melisa confronts due to heteroprofessionalism, training programs tailored for LGBTQI issues for authorities, staff, and institutional administrators through professional development practices can result in greater awareness for all stakeholders regarding the unique challenges that LGBTQI educators experience at work. This state of being elucidated can ease the processes of creating and fostering a culture that upholds the concepts of inclusivity, equalitarianism, and respect. In addition to these, informative practices offered to students at the university level regarding LGBTQI issues can cut into the overt and covert phobic actions and reactions LGBTQI educators face through their interactions with their students. Such changes, along with benefiting non-conforming educators like Melisa, can also provide overall organizational

diversity and equity and enhanced educational outcomes by supporting, valuing, and celebrating non-conforming identities.

On a practical level, the findings of the present study underscore how essential it can get for LGBTQI educators that are “in closet” within classroom contexts to integrate critical and inclusive pedagogical philosophies in their teaching as a means for advocacy and change. The way Melisa employs various strategies, even subtly and strategically, is a testament to how the professional language educator identity can be used to promote genuine wokeness among the youngster through such educational practices. Furthermore, educational institutions within the Turkish context can further enhance and maintain such initiatives through incorporation of gender and sexuality related topics into their curricula, teacher training programs, and professional development practices. Additionally, this study highlights an urgent need for a socio-culturally contextualized understanding of the experiences, narratives, and perspectives of LGBTQI educators, particularly in non-Western contexts like the Turkish context, considering how significantly impactful socio-political and socio-cultural values, ideologies, and practices are on how LGBTQI educators negotiate their identity plurality and navigate their professional experiences within the context of their heteroprofessional workplace environments. By exploring more region-specific issues and solutions, researchers and practitioners can expand on these findings and ensure that LGBTQI educators' perspectives are heard and represented diverse contexts.

5.6. Acknowledgement of the Limitations

The present study offers profound insights into very personal perspectives, narratives, and experiences of an LGBTQI educator practicing in the Turkish context. However, its design as a single intrinsic case study comes with particular limitations. While exploring Melisa, as the single participant of the study, enabled an in-depth and elaborate scrutiny of her identity negotiation and professional experience navigation, the research design also restricted the possible generalizability of the findings, which could allow for reaching broader populations with similar experiences. In addition to that, the unique socio-political and

institutional circumstances surrounding Melisa's case might not adequately capture the wide range of experiences, perspectives, and narratives of other LGBTQI educators practicing in the same, comparable, or totally dissimilar socio-cultural settings.

On the other hand, participant-generated observation reports, as one of the data collection tools of this study, presented another form of limitation. While this instrument offered rich and reflective insights into the participant's perspectives of her own experiences, they can also be intrinsically influenced by her subjective explication inherent in her non-conformity with regard to how she perceived what was happening around her workspace. At this point, triangulating the data with the help of multiple tools and drawing on Braun and Clarke's (2006) Reflexive Thematic Analysis framework in analyzing and interpreting them helped greatly in minimizing potential biases as much as possible. Nevertheless, along with the participant-generated observation reports, integrating an external form of observation that would incorporate third-party perspectives could have embellished what the overall data offered by presenting a more interpersonally triangulated understanding of Melisa's professional realities.

Additionally, drawing on Saldaña's (2013) two-cycle approach of data coding through employing techniques of descriptive and pattern coding followed by Braun and Clarke's (2006) RTA framework of data analysis was effective with regard to the identification of emerging themes. However, considering Melisa is a language teacher, other complementary methods, such as narrative analysis or discourse analysis, could also have helped delve deep into the intricate dynamics of language and power in professional contexts in other ways as well.

Along with being a particular strength for the research objectives this study, the cultural specificity of the Turkish context is accompanied by a limitation as well. Whereas the findings provide insights into an underexplored socio-cultural context, they are neither directly transferable to other socio-cultural contexts around the globe nor applicable in all institutional settings. Due to both the nature of the research design and the specificity of the research setting, the findings and their

interpretations are rather particular to Melisa's case. Conducting this study in the form of a comparative analysis between educators practicing in the Turkish context and those in other socio-cultural and socio-political contexts could have helped identify and compare more universal and contextual patterns in LGBTQI educators' experiences, perspectives, and narratives.

5.7. Recommendations for Further Research

The present study offers a number of pathways for further investigation that can enhance understanding of the narratives and perspectives of LGBTQI educators, particularly practicing within the Turkish context, as well as offering fresh perspectives to scrutinize the intersectionality of their identity plurality negotiation, professional experience navigation, and institutional hetero professionalism. One notable recommendation pertains to increasing the number of participants in further research. Due to the nature of the design of this research as a single intrinsic case study, all narratives belong to a single participant. Although there is no aim of generalization of the findings to broader populations of similar demographics, there might be several key findings that will be in alignment with the experiences of various LGBTQI educators as participants of future studies. However, it is still important to note that these findings stem from the experiences, perspectives, and narratives a single LGBTQI language educator practicing within a particular socio-cultural and socio-political context. Therefore, further research can conduct investigation of multiple LGBTQI educators through different research designs. Those participants might be practicing as educators across diverse settings, institutions, and educational levels within the Turkish context and beyond. Herewith, researchers can obtain deeper insights on the peculiar challenges LGBTQI educators go through as well as various strategies they employ to tackle those challenges and navigate their hetero professional workspaces. In addition to that, comparative research could also be of great help to further enrich understanding of the matter at hand. How some significant variables, such as practicing within rural or urban educational settings, or public or private institutions within the Turkish context, influence the experiences and perspectives of LGBTQI educators regarding hetero professionalism could be further explored. Along with that, comparative

studies conducted on LGBTQI educators from different socio-cultural and socio-political contexts around the world can also enhance understanding of how heteroprofessionalism functions within different contexts. In addition to these, demographic factors regarding hypothetical future participants of future research, such as different identities than Melisa's gender and sexual identity, race, socioeconomic status, socio-political stance, age, and professional experience, might require exploration as well. Hereby, researchers can understand how such aspects and dimensions of different identities influence the identity negotiation and professional experience navigation of LGBTQI educators with different demographics.

Designing longitudinal research is another recommendation for future studies. Although the present study takes place within 6 months due to the data collection process, findings do not aim to detect and document change in Melisa's perspectives or narratives. However, since the process of identity negotiation and the aspects of professional experience navigation are assumed to evolve over time, keeping a periodic track of hypothetical future participants' experiences and perspectives across different stages and levels of their career can also provide beneficial insights into how they negotiate their identities, navigate their professional experiences, and resist or submit to heteroprofessionalism. Finding from such studies would complement the findings of the present study by sizing the dynamicity of the aforementioned concepts and processes. Along with that, cross-cultural comparative research, exploring the experiences, perspectives, and narratives of LGBTQI educators practicing in other non-Western and Western contexts can contribute greatly to understanding their varied experiences across cultures. Research of this kind can provide valuable insights into global patterns and differences as well as region-specific variations and factors with regard to the influence of contextual circumstances and institutional and cultural norms on LGBTQI educators' perspectives of heteroprofessionalism along with their experiences and how they navigate them. Such studies can offer a more extensive understanding of how the perspectives, narratives, and experiences of LGBTQI educators are positioned within global discourses on equity and inclusion. Also, findings stemming from the hypothetical participants of such future studies would provide context-specific,

particularly valuable theoretical implications and practical applications that authorities and policymakers can address while endeavoring to create and foster equitable workspaces for LGBTQI educators, wherein while heterop professionalism is challenged, inclusivity is upheld and celebrated.

This study aims at exploring the perspectives of Melisa herself, as the single participant. Along with expanding the overall design of research, in similar single intrinsic case study designs, integrating third party perspectives can enrich findings with different purposes. For instance, collecting various types and forms of data from the hypothetical participants' colleagues, students, or institutional superiors can also provide a more extensive understanding of their professional experiences. Such external perspectives on the matter can give rise to another form of data triangulation and further explore how perceptions of others at work might be influencing LGBTQI educators' identity negotiation, professional experience navigation, and advocacy efforts within their heterop professional workplace contexts. In a similar vein, focusing particularly on the investigation of how their students perceive, interact with, and react to LGBTQI educators in ways that perpetuate heterop professionalism can be of great help in terms of a more focused understanding of an intricate issue regarding their professional experiences. Considering Melisa is more tolerant toward LGBTQI-phobia coming from her students compared to her colleagues and institutional superiors, yet her interactions with her students and the rapport she builds are also shaped accordingly, similar research centering the perspectives of students as the main focus could help provide answers to more particular research questions. Those answers could point at the complex interrelation between heterop professionalism and student interaction, considering students are one of the most influential factors over the professional experiences of all educators.

In addition to all these, it is also notable that institutional policies and practices entail deeper investigation as well. Melisa's institution is revealed to be rather heterop professional in the findings. While her institution, in the first place, does not have any particularly tailored policies that aim to protect its LGBTQI employees, it is still possible for those employees to experience heterop professionalism in various other ways within institutions that officially attempt to protect their rights and

provide them with equitable workspaces. Therefore, another form of comparative research can be conducted on the experiences of LGBTQI educators practicing at different institutions with and without explicit institutional anti-discrimination policies, focusing on the investigation of their possible impact on how those educators negotiate their identities and navigate their professional experiences within workspaces with unlike policies regarding issues of inclusivity and equity. Such studies can provide valuable insights into those educators narratives and perspectives as well as their engagement with different forms of institutional support systems. That way, applicable practices for fostering inclusivity for LGBTQI educators to protect them from heteroprophessionalism can be identified and documented. Additionally, considering its significance in the findings of the present study, examining the role of critical pedagogy as an advocacy effort in obstructive workplace contexts for LGBTQI educators is another recommendation for further research. Basing upon this study's findings as well, researchers can further explore how LGBTQI educators integrate critical pedagogical techniques in their teaching philosophies and practices as a way of enacting their non-conforming personal identities as well as preventing overt discussions on gender and sexuality related issues from remaining as an unchallenged taboo in many educational contexts. For that matter, in order to co-create and evaluate the efficiency of integrating such pedagogical techniques as a form of advocacy and fostering inclusivity, action research methodologies can be particularly drawn on in future research so that the findings would be practical, applicable, and rather reliable.

Genuine allyship and performative actions coming from colleagues is another promising area for further investigation. Considering Melisa's experiences of allyship and aloofness of her colleagues at work, along with how she perceives and narrates particular instances of those experiences, further research conducted on LGBTQI educators' evaluation of the genuineness of supportive colleagues as allies can provide meaningful insights into their perspectives on the socio-contextual circumstances surrounding them in their processes of identity negotiation and professional experience navigation. As aforementioned, much as they might look subtle and less harmful, the detrimental effects of performative actions in the form of allyship within their heteroprophessional workplace context on LGBTQI educators'

overall well-being is observable, as revealed in findings of the present study as well. Therefore, particular focus on how LGBTQI educators perceive and evaluate the supportive actions and reactions performed by their colleagues regarding the enactment of their non-conforming personal identities within their workspace context is called for to be examined in further research. In addition to that, as a language educator, Melisa's strategical use of the popular culture and media of the target language she teaches as a means of advocacy for equity, openly socio-critical discussions in her classrooms, and preferred representation of the LGBTQI community for her students emerge as a key finding in this study. Considering the significance of this particular finding for the identity negotiation and professional experience navigation of an LGBTQI language educator, further research can also examine what particular types of target languages' culture and popular media is taken advantage of by LGBTQI language educators in their efforts of advocacy for proper representation of their non-conforming personal identities, along with focusing on the questions of why and how so.

Future research can expand upon the findings of the present study by tackling these topics, which can offer more focused understandings of how LGBTQI educators navigate heteroprofessionalism and negotiate their identities in various educational, socio-political, and socio-cultural contexts. Such potential studies focusing on the aforementioned issues not only have the potential to contribute to the pertinent academic discourse, but they can also function as significant catalysts for meaningful and positive change. Their findings can present applicable and practical implications that inform authorities and policymakers, contributing to the creation of inclusive and equitable educational workplace settings, as well as fostering institutional practices that challenge heteroprofessionalism and prioritize official support for all LGBTQI educators. In today's world, considering that educational systems and institutional practices continually evolve, carefully sustained research on the navigation of heteroprofessionalism by LGBTQI educators will be critical in ensuring that they are always provided with the support, acknowledgement, protection, appreciation, and celebration they are worthy of just like their cis-heterosexual counterparts. Ultimately, such initiatives will present the potential to contribute to the creation and fostering of more equitable, supportive, and inclusive

global educational environments as workplaces for LGBTQI educators, where diversity is embraced, a sense of inclusion and equity is the norm, and all educators and students can prosper without fears of reprisal, prejudgment, punishment, exclusion, discrimination, or hatred, which should certainly not be mentioned in spaces where next generations are shaped.

REFERENCES

- Acar, M. (2023). Gender-Based Exclusion in Turkish Schools. *International Perspectives on Exclusionary Pressures in Education*, 313–325. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-14113-3_17
- Adikaram, A. S., & Liyanage, D. M. (2021). Undisclosed reality: harassment of gay male employees in Sri Lankan heteronormative workplaces. *Culture and Organization*, 27(6), 490–506. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14759551.2021.1919894>
- Aker, S., Mıdık, Z., & Böke, M. (2023). The Effect of Education on Homophobia and Attitudes Toward Gay Men and Lesbian Women among Medical Faculty Students: A Turkish Sample. *Teaching and Learning in Medicine*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10401334.2023.2215751>
- Akgül, T. D., & Güneş, V. (2023). Minority Stress of Workers as Internal Customers: A Case Study in Turkey. *Athens Journal of Business & Economics*, 9(1), 109–130. <https://doi.org/10.30958/ajbe.9-1-7>
- Allen, K. R., & Farnsworth, E. B. (1993). Reflexivity in Teaching about Families. *Family Relations*, 42(3), 351–356. <https://doi.org/10.2307/585566>
- Allen, K. R. (1995). Opening the Classroom Closet: Sexual Orientation and Self-Disclosure. *Family Relations*, 44(2), 136. <https://doi.org/10.2307/584799>
- American Educational Research Association. (2002). [Statement on ethics in research]. *American Educational Research Association*.
- Anderson, J. L. (2020). The Life and Politics of Passing: Gender, Professionalism and the Queer Teacher. Master's thesis, University of Calgary, Calgary, Canada. Retrieved from <https://prism.ucalgary.ca>

- Añonuevo, R., & Digo, G. (2023). Identities and Roles of Gay and Bisexual Teachers in Rural Philippines. *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(3), 1299–1312. <https://doi.org/10.55927/eajmr.v2i3.3507>
- Antonelli, M. A., & Sembiante, S. F. (2022). A systematic review of research on LGBTQ educators' experiences and LGBTQ curriculum in K-12 U.S. public schools. *Multicultural Education Review*, 14(2), 134–152. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2005615x.2022.2087031>
- Aslan, F., Şahin, N. E., & Emiroğlu, O. N. (2019). Turkish nurse educators' knowledge regarding LGBT health and their level of homophobia: A descriptive–cross sectional study. *Nurse Education Today*, 76, 216–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2019.02.014>
- Ayhan Balik, C. H., & Bilgin, H. (2019). Experiences of Minority Stress and Intimate Partner Violence Among Homosexual Women in Turkey. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 36(19–20), 8984–9007. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260519864371>
- Baars, G. (2019). Queer Cases Unmake Gendered Law, Or Fucking Law's Gendering Function. *Australian Feminist Law Journal*, 45(1), 15–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13200968.2019.1667777>
- Baker, S. J., & Lucas, K. (2017). Is it safe to bring myself to work? Understanding LGBTQ experiences of workplace dignity. *Canadian Journal of the Administrative Sciences/Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 34(2), 133–148. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cjas.1439>
- Barkhuizen, G., & Wette, R. (2008). Narrative frames for investigating the experiences of language teachers. *System*, 36(3), 372–387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2008.02.002>
- Bartone, M. D. (2023). “Who Wants to Be a Teacher in the Face of These Anti-queer Laws?” Burnout Perspective from a Gay Educator. *Drawn to the Flame*, 99–115. <https://doi.org/10.1108/s1479-368720230000045007>

- Beagan, B. L., Bizzeth, S. R., Pride, T. M., & Sibbald, K. R. (2022). LGBTQ+ identity concealment and disclosure within the (heteronormative) health professions: “Do I? Do I not? And what are the potential consequences?” *SSM. Qualitative Research in Health*, 2, 100114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmqr.2022.100114>
- Beagan, B. L., Mohamed, T., Brooks, K., Waterfield, B., & Weinberg, M. (2020). Microaggressions experienced by LGBTQ academics in Canada: “just not fitting in... it does take a toll.” *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 34(3), 197–212. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2020.1735556>
- Bell, K. M., & Keer, G. (2021). Representing Queer communities: news media stylebooks and LGBTQ visibility. In *Springer eBooks*, 1233–1252. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-32103-5_62
- Bell, M. P., Özbilgin, M. F., Beauregard, T. A., & Sürgevil, O. (2011). Voice, silence, and diversity in 21st century organizations: Strategies for inclusion of gay, lesbian, bisexual, and transgender employees. *Human Resource Management*, 50(1), 131–146. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.20401>
- Bennett, R., Hill, B., & Jones, A. (2015). In and out of the cross-cultural classroom closet: negotiating queer teacher identity and culturally diverse cohorts in an Australian university. *Higher Education Research & Development/Higher Education Research and Development*, 34(4), 709–721. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2015.1051008>
- Benson, F. (2008). Teacher educators’ practice of queer-care: A necessary expansion of Noddings’ model of care (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). McGill University, Montreal, QC.
- Benson, F. J., Smith, N. G., & Flanagan, T. (2014). Easing the Transition for Queer Student Teachers from Program to Field: Implications for Teacher Education. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 61(3), 382–398. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2013.842429>

- Biçmen, Z., & Bekiroğulları, Z. (2014). Social Problems of LGBT People in Turkey. *Procedia- Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 113, 224–233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.029>
- Birt, L., Scott, S., Cavers, D., Campbell, C., & Walter, F. (2016). Member Checking. *Qualitative Health Research*, 26(13), 1802–1811.
- Blechinger, D. R. (2016). Understanding the LGBT communities. In *Springer eBooks* (pp. 3–21). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-19752-4_1
- Borg, S. (2003). Teacher cognition in language teaching: A review of research on what language teachers think, know, believe, and do. *Language Teaching*, 36(2), 81–109. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0261444803001903>
- Bosse, J. D., & Chiodo, L. (2016). It is complicated: gender and sexual orientation identity in LGBTQ youth. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 25(23–24), 3665–3675. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.13419>
- Boulay, N., Yeung, B., Leung, C., & Burns, D. P. (2020). LGBTQ Role Models and Curricular Controversy in Canada: A Student Symposium. *Paideusis*, 22(1), 19–27. <https://doi.org/10.7202/1071462ar>
- Bourke, B. (2014). Positionality: Reflecting on the Research Process. *The Qualitative Report*.
- Bowen, G. (1995). *A dictionary of words for masculine women*. <https://news.lgbti.org/a-dictionary-of-words-for-masculine-women/>
- Bower-Phipps, L. (2020). Responding to heteronormativity: Lesbian, gay, bisexual and asexual preservice teachers' dreams and fears. *Current Issues in Education*, 21(1). Retrieved from <http://cie.asu.edu/ojs/index.php/cieatasu/article/view/1747>

- Bowring, M. A., & Brewis, J. (2009). Truth and consequences. *Equal Opportunities International*, 28(5), 361–377. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02610150910964231>
- Bracho, C. A., & Hayes, C. (2020). Gay voices without intersectionality is White supremacy: narratives of gay and lesbian teachers of color on teaching and learning. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 33(6), 583–592. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2020.1751897>
- Brady, B. (2022). “We Think You’ll Make a Great Fit”: Navigating the Precarity of Being a Gay International Teacher. *The New Educator*, 18(3), 225–239. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1547688x.2022.2085831>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2013) *Successful Qualitative Research: A Practical Guide for Beginners*. SAGE Publication, London.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2019). Reflecting on reflexive thematic analysis. *Qualitative Research in Sport Exercise and Health*, 11(4), 589–597. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2159676x.2019.1628806>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2020). One size fits all? What counts as quality practice in (reflexive) thematic analysis? *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 18(3), 328–352. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14780887.2020.1769238>
- Brett, A. (2022). Under the spotlight: exploring the challenges and opportunities of being a visible LGBT+ teacher. *Sex Education*, 24(1), 61–75. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681811.2022.2143344>
- Bridgman, B. L. (2012). Queer Girls in Class: Lesbian Teachers and Students Tell Their Classroom Stories. *Journal of LGBT Youth*, 9(1), 72–75. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19361653.2012.627504>

- Brockenbrough, E. (2012). Agency and abjection in the closet: the voices (and silences) of black queer male teachers. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 25(6), 741–765. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2011.590157>
- Butcher, R., & Eldridge, J. (1990). The Use of Diaries in Data Collection. *The Statistician*, 39(1), 25.
- Callaghan, T. D. (2015). Doctrinal Disciplining of Queer Educators in Canadian Catholic Schools. *Canadian Journal of Educational Administration and Policy*, 173, 9-27.
- Callaghan, T. D., & van Leent, L. (2019). Homophobia in Catholic schools: An exploration of teachers' rights and experiences in Canada and Australia. *Journal of Catholic Education*, 22(3). <https://doi.org/10.15365/joce.2203032019>
- Campbell, E. (2003). *The Ethical Teacher*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).
- Cantos, F. J., Moliner, L., & Sanahuja, A. (2023). Making sexual diversity visible through LGTBQ+ teachers' life stories: A descriptive study. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 132, 104214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2023.104214>
- Carian, E. K., DiBranco, A., & Ebin, C. (2022). *Male Supremacism in the United States*. Routledge.
- Catalano, D. C. J., Duran, A., Feldman, S., Gonzalez-Siegel, V., Jourian, T. J., Kannan, K., Oliveira, K., Pryor, J., & Woods, C. (2025). Hope Amid Relentless Challenges: Trans and Queer Center(ed) Diversity Workers Navigating the U.S. Sociopolitical Context. *Journal of College and Character*, 26(1), 38–48. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2194587x.2024.2439597>
- Catalano, D. C. J., & Griffin, P. (2016). Sexism, heterosexism, and trans* oppression: An integrated perspective. In *Teaching for diversity and social justice* (pp. 183-211). Routledge.

- Charmaz, K. (2014). *Constructing Grounded Theory*. Los Angeles: Sage.
- Cherubini, L. (2009). Exploring prospective teachers' critical thinking: Case-based pedagogy and the standards of professional practice. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 25(2), 228–234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2008.10.007>
- Clark, C. T. (2010). Preparing LGBTQ-allies and combating homophobia in a U.S. teacher education program. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 26(3), 704–713. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2009.10.006>
- Coda, J. (2019). Do straight teachers experience this? Performance as a medium to explore LGBTQ world language teacher identity. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education/QSE. International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 32(5), 465–476. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2019.1597206>
- Coda, J. (2023). Learning the rules and then disrupting them: LGBQ Spanish language teachers' resistance to heteronormativity. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 122, 103980. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2022.103980>
- Coleman, J. J. (2023). Narrative repair in teacher education: Restorying painful histories and “damaged” queer teacher identity. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 124, 104031. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2023.104031>
- Colgan, F., Creegan, C., McKearney, A., & Wright, T. (2007). Equality and diversity policies and practices at work: lesbian, gay and bisexual workers. *Equal Opportunities International*, 26(6), 590–609. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02610150710777060>
- Collins, J. C., Zhang, P., & Sisco, S. (2021). Everyone is Invited: Leveraging Bystander Intervention and Ally Development to Cultivate Social Justice in the Workplace. *Human Resource Development Review*, 20(4), 486–511. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15344843211040734>
- Concordia, K., Cortez, N., Panaligan, J.R. & Velasco, B. (2009). No gays allowed. *Philippine Daily Inquirer*.

- Connell, C. (2014). *School's out: Gay and lesbian teachers in the classroom*. University of California Press. <https://doi.org/10.1525/9780520959804>
- Conrad, J. (2019). Navigating identity as a controversial issue: One teacher's disclosure for critical empathic reasoning. *Theory & Research in Social Education*, 48(2), 211–243. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00933104.2019.1679687>
- Corlett, S., Di Marco, D., Munduate, L., & Arenas, A. (2022). Manifestations and Reinforcement of Heteronormativity in the Workplace: A Systematic scoping review. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 70(12), 2714–2740. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2022.2074334>
- Cosier, K. (2016). Teacher education, continuing education: Introduction. In A. Butler-Wall, K. Cosier, R. L. S. Harper, J. Sapp, J. Sokolower, M. Bollow Temple, (Eds.) *Rethinking sexism, gender, and sexuality* (pp. 368–371). Milwaukee, WI: Rethinking Schools.
- Crenshaw, K. (1989). Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory and Antiracist Politics, *University of Chicago Legal Forum*.
- Creswell, J. W. (1998). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- Creswell, J. W. (2005). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson.
- Creswell, J. W. (2007). *Qualitative Enquiry and Research Design: Choosing Among Five Approaches*, second edition. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 3rd Edition, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 4th Edition, SAGE Publications, Inc., London.
- Creswell, J.W. & Creswell, J.D. (2018). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. Sage, Los Angeles.
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2016). *Qualitative Inquiry & Research Design: Choosing among Five Approaches*. Los Angeles, CA: Sage Publications.
- Cui, L. (2022). ‘Teach as an outsider’: closeted gay academics’ strategies for addressing queer issues in China. *Sex Education*, 23(5), 570–584. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681811.2022.2103109>
- Cui, L. (2024). “I Don’t Expect the University to Support Queers”: Identity Management and Ambivalence toward Institutional Support for Queer University Students in China. *International Journal of Sociology*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207659.2024.2403863>
- Cutler, B. (2023). ‘Just wear their hate with pride’: A phenomenological autoethnography of a gay beginning teacher in a rural school. *Sex Education*, 23(4), 363–378. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681811.2022.2035344>
- Dane, F.C. (1990) *Research Methods*. Brooks/Cole Publishing Company, Pacific Grove.
- Davies, A. W. J., & Neustifter, R. (2021). Heteroprofessionalism in the Academy: The surveillance and regulation of queer faculty in Higher education. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 70(6), 1030–1054. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2021.2013036>
- Davies, P. (1992). ‘The role of disclosure in coming out among gay men’, in *Modern Homosexualities: Fragments of Gay and Lesbian Experience*, ed. K. Plummer, Routledge, London, pp. 75–83.

- Davis, A. (2023). [Views of Asexuality and Transgender Individuals: The Role of Religious Beliefs](#). [Master's Thesis, Georgia Southern University].
- Dawson, B. A., Kilgore, W., & Rawcliffe, R. M. (2022). Strategies for Creating Inclusive Learning Environments through a Social Justice Lens. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 12(0). <https://doi.org/10.5590/jerap.2022.12.0.02>
- Day, J. K., Ioverno, S., & Russell, S. T. (2019). Safe and supportive schools for LGBT youth: Addressing educational inequities through inclusive policies and practices. *Journal of School Psychology*, 74, 29–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2019.05.007>
- DeJean, W., & Sapp, J. (2010). SPECIAL ISSUE ON QUEER EDUCATORS AND QUEER STUDENT TEACHERS. *The Teacher Educator*, 45(4), 231–232. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08878730.2010.509682>
- deLeon, M. J., & Brunner, C. C. (2012). Cycles of Fear. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 49(1), 161–203. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161x12459482>
- DeLuca, C. (2013). Toward an interdisciplinary framework for educational inclusivity. *Canadian Journal of Education*, 36(1), 305–348. <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1002320.pdf>
- DeMitchell, T. A., Eckes, S., & Fossey, R. (2009). Sexual orientation and the public-school teacher. *BU Pub. Int. LJ*, 19, 65.
- Dentato, M. P., Craig, S. L., Lloyd, M. R., Kelly, B. L., Wright, C., & Austin, A. (2016). Homophobia within schools of social work: the critical need for affirming classroom settings and effective preparation for service with the LGBTQ community. *Social Work Education*, 35(6), 672–692. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02615479.2016.1150452>
- Denzin, N. K. (1978). Triangulation: A Case for Methodological Evaluation and Combination. *Sociological Methods*, 339-357.

- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2011). *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2018). *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research* (5th ed.). Los Angeles, CA: Sage.
- DePalma, R., & Atkinson, E. (2010). The nature of institutional heteronormativity in primary schools and practice-based responses. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 26(8), 1669–1676. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2010.06.018>
- DeSouza, E. R., Wesselmann, E. D., & Ispas, D. (2017). Workplace Discrimination against Sexual Minorities: Subtle and not-so-subtle. *Canadian Journal of the Administrative Sciences/Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 34(2), 121–132. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cjas.1438>
- Dowling, M. (2006). Approaches to reflexivity in qualitative research. *Nurse Researcher*, 13(3), 7–21.
- Duarte, B. J. (2020). Forced Back into the Closet: A (Queer) Principal’s Attempt to Maintain Queer Erasure. *Journal of Cases in Educational Leadership*, 23(4), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1555458920956310>
- Duke, T. S. (2007). Hidden, invisible, marginalized, ignored: A critical review of the professional and empirical literature (or lack thereof) on gay and lesbian teachers in the United States. *Journal of Gay & Lesbian Issues in Education*, 4(4), 19e38. https://doi.org/10.1300/J367v04n04_03
- Dyer, W.G. & Wilkins, A.L. (1991). Better Stories, Not Better Constructs, To Generate Better Theory: A Rejoinder to Eisenhardt. *Academy of Management Review*, 16, 613-619.
- Dykes, F. O., & Delport, J. L. (2018). Our voices count: the lived experiences of LGBTQ educators and its impact on teacher education preparation programs. *Teaching Education*, 29(2), 135–146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10476210.2017.1366976>

- Early, J. S., & Shagoury, R. (2009). Learning from the lived experiences of new language arts teachers working in diverse urban schools. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 26(4), 1049–1058. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2009.10.048>
- Eckes, S. E. (2017). The legal “Rights” of LGBT educators in public and private schools. *Texas Journal on Civil Liberties & Civil Rights*, 23(1), 29.
- Eckes, S. E., & McCarthy, M. M. (2008). GLBT Teachers: The Evolving Legal Protections. *American Educational Research Journal*, 45(3), 530–554. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831208314764>
- Edward, M., & Greenough, C. (2020). Queer literacy. *Springer eBooks*, 707–718. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-16759-2_57
- Eğitim Sen. (2014). Tüzük [Statute]. Eğitim ve Bilim Emekçileri Sendikası/Eğitim Sen [Education and Science Workers’ Union].
- Ellis, S. J. (2007). Community in the 21st Century: Issues Arising from a Study of British Lesbians and Gay Men. *Journal of Gay & Lesbian Psychotherapy*, 11(1–2), 111–126. https://doi.org/10.1300/j236v11n01_08
- Engin, C. (2015). LGBT in Turkey: Policies and Experiences. *Social Sciences*, 4(3), 838–858. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci4030838>
- Epstein, D. (2017). Teaching queer/queer teaching: an afterword. *Irish Educational Studies*, 36(1), 125–132. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2017.1289698>
- Epstein, D. & Johnson, R. (1994) Really straight and narrow: the heterosexual presumption and schools, in D. Epstein (Ed.) *Challenging Lesbian and Gay Inequalities in Education*. Buckingham: Open University Press.

- Erickson-Schroth, L., & Mitchell, J. (2009). Queering Queer Theory, or Why Bisexuality Matters. *Journal of Bisexuality*, 9(3–4), 297–315. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15299710903316596>
- Evans, K. (1999). “Are you married?”: Examining heteronormativity in schools. *Multicultural Perspectives*, 1(3), 7–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15210969909539908>
- Evans, R., Nagoshi, J. L., Nagoshi, C., Wheeler, J., & Henderson, J. (2017). Voices from the stories untold: Lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans, and queer college students’ experiences with campus climate. *Journal of Gay & Lesbian Social Services*, 29(4), 426–444. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10538720.2018.1378144>
- Ewing, V. L., Stukas, A. A., & Sheehan, E. P. (2003). Student Prejudice Against Gay Male and Lesbian Lecturers. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 143(5), 569–579. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224540309598464>
- Felix, B., Mello, A., & Von Borell, D. (2016). Voices unspoken? Understanding how gay employees co-construct a climate of voice/silence in organisations. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 29(5), 805–828. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2016.1255987>
- Ferfolja, T. (2003). Mechanisms of Silence: Sexuality Regulation in New South Wales High Schools. Perspectives from Lesbian Teachers. Unpublished PhD thesis, The University of New South Wales.
- Ferfolja, T. (2005). Institutional Silence: Experiences of Australian Lesbian Teachers Working in Catholic High Schools. *Journal of Gay and Lesbian Issues in Education*2(3): 51–66.
- Ferfolja, T. (2007). Schooling cultures: institutionalizing heteronormativity and heterosexism. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 11(2), 147–162. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603110500296596>
- Ferfolja, T. (2008). Discourses that Silence: Teachers and Anti-lesbian Harassment. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*29(1):107–19.

- Ferfolja, T. (2009). State of the Field Review: Stories So Far: An Overview of the Research on Lesbian Teachers. *Sexualities*, 12(3), 378–396. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1363460708099116>
- Ferfolja, T., & Hopkins, L. (2013). The complexities of workplace experience for lesbian and gay teachers. *Critical Studies in Education*, 54(3), 311–324. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17508487.2013.794743>
- Ferfolja, T., & Robinson, K. H. (2004). Why anti-homophobia education in teacher education? Perspectives from Australian teacher educators. *Teaching Education*, 15(1), 9e25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1047621042000179961>
- Ferfolja, T., & Stavrou, E. (2015). Workplace experiences of Australian lesbian and gay teachers: findings from a national survey. *Canadian Journal of Educational Administration and Policy*, (173), 113-138.
- Feryok, A. (2010). Language teacher cognitions: Complex dynamic systems? *System*, 38(2), 272–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2010.02.001>
- Finn, G. M., Ballard, W., Politis, M., & Brown, M. E. (2021). It's not alphabet soup – supporting the inclusion of inclusive queer curricula in medical education. *The British Student Doctor Journal*, 5(2), 27. <https://doi.org/10.18573/bsdj.276>
- Fleet, C. (2016). *Becoming a Queer Teacher: Perceptions of Queer Teacher Candidates in Initial Teacher Education Programs*. [Master's Thesis, Brock University].
- Flick, U., Von Kardoff, E., & Steinke, I. (2004). *A Companion to Qualitative Research*. SAGE.
- Foucault, M. (1978). *The History of Sexuality*.

- Foucault, M. (1980). *Power/Knowledge: Selected interviews and other writings 1972-1977*.
- Freud, S. (1926). Inhibitions, symptoms and anxiety. In J. Strachey, & A. Freud (Eds.), *The standard edition of the complete psychological works of Sigmund Freud* (pp. 77-175). London: The Hogarth Press.
- Fredman, A. J., Schultz, N. J., & Hoffman, M. F. (2013). You're Moving a Frickin' Big Ship. *Education and Urban Society*, 47(1), 56–85. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013124513496457>
- Gagné, P., & Tewksbury, R. (1998). Conformity pressures and gender resistance among transgendered individuals. *Social problems*, 45(1), 81-101.
- García, A. M., & Slesaransky-Poe, G. (2010). The Heteronormative Classroom: Questioning and Liberating Practices. *The Teacher Educator* 45(4), 244–256. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08878730.2010.508271>
- Gates, T. G. (2011). Coming Out in the Social Work Classroom: Reclaiming Wholeness and Finding the Teacher Within. *Social Work Education*, 30(1), 70–82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02615471003721202>
- Gentles, S. J., Jack, S. M., Nicholas, D. B., McKibbin, K. (2014). A critical approach to reflexivity in grounded theory. *Qual Rep.* 19(44):1–14.
- Gerring, J. (2004). What Is a Case Study and What Is It Good for? *The American Political Science Review*, 98(2), 341–354.
- Giddens, A. (1984). *The Constitution of Society*. Polity Press, Cambridge.
- Giddings, L. S., & Pringle, J. K. (2011). Heteronormativity at work: Stories from two lesbian academics. *Women's Studies Journal*, 25(2), 91–100.

- Göçmen, P., & Yılmaz, V. (2017). Exploring Perceived Discrimination Among LGBT Individuals in Turkey in Education, Employment, and Health Care: Results of an Online Survey. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 64(8), 1052–1068. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2016.1236598>
- Göçmen İ. & Yılmaz V. (2017). Exploring Perceived Discrimination Among LGBT Individuals in Turkey in Education, Employment, and Health Care: Results of an Online Survey, *Journal of Homosexuality*, 64:8, 1052-1068. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2016.1236598>
- Goldblatt, H., Karnieli-Miller, O., & Neumann, M. (2011). Sharing qualitative research findings with participants: Study experiences of methodological and ethical dilemmas. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 82(3), 389–395.
- Golombek, P. R. (2015). Redrawing the boundaries of language teacher cognition: language teacher educators' emotion, cognition, and activity. *The Modern Language Journal*, 99(3), 470–484. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12236>
- Gorski, P. C., Davis, S. N., & Reiter, A. (2013). An Examination of the (In)visibility of Sexual Orientation, Heterosexism, Homophobia, and Other LGBTQ Concerns in U.S. Multicultural Teacher Education Coursework. *Journal of LGBT Youth*, 10(3), 224–248. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19361653.2013.798986>
- Grace, A. P. (2020). Two good gay teachers: pioneering advocate-practitioners confronting homophobia in schooling in British Columbia, Canada. In *Routledge eBooks* (pp. 43–56). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429278853-5>
- Grace, A. P., & Benson, F. J. (2000). Using autobiographical queer life narratives of teachers to connect personal, political and pedagogical spaces. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 4(2), 89–109. <https://doi.org/10.1080/136031100284830>
- Grace, A. P., & Wells, K. (2006). The quest for a queer inclusive cultural ethics: Setting directions for teachers' preservice and continuing professional development. *New Directions for Adult and Continuing Education*, (112), 51e61, 2006 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ace.236>

- Graneheim, U. H., & Lundman, B. (2004). Qualitative content analysis in nursing research: concepts, procedures and measures to achieve trustworthiness. *Nurse education today*, 24(2), 105-112.
- Graves, K. (2009). *And They Were Wonderful Teachers*. University of Illinois Press.
- Graves, K. (2018). A matter of public concern: the First Amendment and equal employment for LGBT educators. *History of Education Quarterly*, 58(3), 453–460. <https://doi.org/10.1017/heq.2018.23>
- Gray, D. E. (2013). *Doing Research in the Real World*. SAGE.
- Gray, E. M. (2013). Coming out as a lesbian, gay or bisexual teacher: negotiating private and professional worlds. *Sex Education*, 13(6), 702–714. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681811.2013.807789>
- Gray, E. M., & Harris, A. (2014). Introduction: Marked Presence/Unremarkable Absence: Queer Teachers, ‘Identity’ and Performativity. In *Palgrave studies in gender and education* (pp. 1–10). https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137441928_1
- Gray, E. M., Harris, A., & Jones, T. (2016). Australian LGBTQ teachers, exclusionary spaces and points of interruption. *Sexualities*, 19(3), 286–303. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1363460715583602>
- Guba, E. G. (1981). Criteria for assessing the trustworthiness of naturalistic inquiries. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 29, 75-91.
- Guijarro-Ojeda, J. R., Ruiz-Cecilia, R., Cardoso-Pulido, M. J., & Medina-Sánchez, L. (2021). Examining the Interplay between Queerness and Teacher Wellbeing: A Qualitative Study Based on Foreign Language Teacher Trainers. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(22), 12208. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182212208>

- Güney, Z. (2021a). Discussing LGBTQ+ Issues with Muslim Students in the ESL Classroom: The Interface of Culture, Religion, and Sexuality. *Intersectional Perspectives on LGBTQ+ Issues in Modern Language Teaching and Learning*, 55–85. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-76779-2_3
- Güney, Z. (2021b). Pre-Service Teachers Discussing Queer-Inclusive Pedagogies in Turkish EFL Classrooms. *Advocacy for Social and Linguistic Justice in TESOL*, 166–181. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003202356-14>
- Güney, Z. (2023). In Pursuit of Queer Inquiry with Turkish EFL Preservice Teachers. *TESOL Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tesq.3262>
- Haddad, Z. (2019). Understanding Identity and Context in the development of Gay Teacher Identity: Perceptions and realities in Teacher Education and Teaching. *Education Sciences*, 9(2), 145. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci9020145>
- Harbeck, K. M. (1992). *Coming Out of the Classroom Closet*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Hardie, A. (2012). Lesbian teachers and students: issues and dilemmas of being ‘out’ in primary school. *Sex Education*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681811.2011.615595>
- Harper, M., & Cole, P. (2015). Member checking: Can benefits be gained similar to group therapy? *The Qualitative Report*. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2012.2139>
- Heale, R., & Forbes, D. (2013). Understanding triangulation in research. *Evidence Based Nursing*, 16(4), 98–98.
- Henderson, H. (2017). Silence, obligation and fear in the possible selves of UK LGBT-identified teachers. *Gender and Education*, 31(7), 849–865. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540253.2017.1354125>

- Herek, G. M. (2004). Beyond “Homophobia”: Thinking about sexual prejudice and stigma in the twenty-first century. *Sexuality Research and Social Policy*, 1(2), 6–24. <https://doi.org/10.1525/srsp.2004.1.2.6>
- Hoare, C. H. (2002). *Erikson on development in adulthood: New insights from the unpublished papers*. Oxford University Press.
- Holman, E. G., Ogolsky, B. G., & Oswald, R. F. (2021). Concealment of a sexual minority identity in the workplace: the role of workplace climate and identity centrality. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 69(9), 1467–1484. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2021.1917219>
- Hong, J., Francis, D. C., Haskins, C., Chong, K., Habib, K., Pinheiro, W. A., Noon, S., & Dickinson, J. (2023). Wellbeing under threat: Multiply marginalized and underrepresented teachers’ intersecting identities. *Teachers and Teaching*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2023.2263739>
- Hooker, S. D. (2018a). Lesbian and Gay Educators Functioning in Heteronormative Schools. *International Journal of Educational Reform*, 27(1), 63–85. <https://doi.org/10.1177/105678791802700104>
- Hooker, S. D. (2018b). Can gay and lesbian educators form authentic relationships in their school communities? *Education, Citizenship and Social Justice*, 14(1), 82–98. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1746197918760223>
- Horgan. (2020). Exploring Performances of LGBTQ Sexualities in Irish Primary Schools. *Student Teacher Educational Research E-Journal*, 3(2), 17–26. <https://www.ster.ie/>
- Hoskin, R. A. (2020). “Femininity? It’s the aesthetic of subordination”: Examining femmephobia, the gender binary, and experiences of oppression among sexual and gender minorities. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 49(7), 2319–2339. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-020-01641-x>

- Hulko, W., & Hovanes, J. (2017). Intersectionality in the lives of LGBTQ youth: identifying as LGBTQ and finding community in small cities and rural towns. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 65(4), 427–455. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2017.1320169>
- İncekara, H. S., & Ulaş, E. (2023). The Effects of Different Sexual Orientations of Individuals on Their Professional Lives. *Akademik Hassasiyetler*, 10(22), 610–638. <https://doi.org/10.58884/akademik-hassasiyetler.1276463>
- İpekçi, İ. C. (2022). The Lived Experiences of Queer* Teachers in İstanbul within the Scope of Institutionalized Heteronormativity and Neoliberal School Policies. *InterAlia*, 140–154. <https://doi.org/10.51897/interalia/cqvy6921>
- Irwin, J. (1999). *The pink ceiling is too low: workplace experiences of lesbians, gay men and transgender people*. Sydney.
- Irwin, J. (2002). Discrimination Against Gay Men, Lesbians, and Transgender People Working in Education. *Journal of Gay & Lesbian Social Services*, 14(2), 65–77.
- Ishak, N. M., & Bakar, A. Y. A. (2014). Developing sampling frame for case study: challenges and conditions. *World Journal of Education*, 4(3). <https://doi.org/10.5430/wje.v4n3p29>
- Jaekel, K. S., & Nicolazzo, Z. (2020). Institutional Commitments to Unknowing gender: trans* and Gender Non-Conforming Educators' experiences in Higher education. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 69(4), 632–654. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2020.1848146>
- Jacelon, C. S., & Imperio, K. (2005). Participant Diaries as a Source of Data in Research With Older Adults. *Qualitative Health Research*, 15(7), 991–997.
- Jackson, J. (2007). *Unmasking identities: An exploration of the lives of gay and lesbian teachers*. Lanham, MD: Lexington Books.

- Jackson, J. M. (2006). Removing the Masks: Considerations by Gay and Lesbian Teachers When Negotiating the Closet Door. *Journal of Poverty* 10 (2): 27–52. https://doi.org/10.1300/J134v10n02_03
- Jackson, J. M. (2009). “Teacher by day. Lesbian by night”: Queer(y)ing identities and teaching. *Sexuality Research & Social Policy/Sexuality Research and Social Policy*, 6(2), 52–70. <https://doi.org/10.1525/srsp.2009.6.2.52>
- Jaekel, K. S., & Nicolazzo, Z. (2020). Institutional Commitments to Unknowing Gender: Trans* and Gender Non-Conforming Educators’ Experiences in Higher Education. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 69(4), 632–654. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2020.1848146>
- Jennings, K. (1994). *One Teacher in 10: Gay and Lesbian Educators Tell their Stories*. Boston: Alyson Publishing.
- Jennings, K. (2005). *One teacher in 10: LGBT educators share their stories* (2nd ed.). London: Alyson Publications.
- Johnson, B. (2023). Exploring the impact of panoptic heteronormativity on UK primary teachers advocating for LGBTQ+ inclusive education. *Education, Citizenship and Social Justice*, 174619792311516. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17461979231151615>
- Johnson, K. E. (2018). Studying language teacher cognition: Understanding and enacting theoretically consistent instructional practices. *Language Teaching Research*, 22(3), 259–263. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168818772197>
- Johnson, L. M. (2014). Teaching Note—Heterosexism as Experienced by LGBT Social Work Educators. *Journal of Social Work Education*, 50(4), 748–751. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10437797.2014.947165>
- Johnson, T. S. (2006). Performing A/Sexual Teacher: The Cartesian Duality in Education. *The Review of Education/Pedagogy/Cultural Studies/Review of Education, Pedagogy, Cultural Studies*, 28(3–4), 253–266. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10714410600873175>

- Jones, T. (2018). A global human rights approach to pre-service teacher education on LGBTIs. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 47(3), 286–308. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359866x.2018.1555793>
- Jr., J. B. M. (2020). Queer teacher to queer teacher: reflections, questions, and hopes from current and aspiring educators. *Teaching Education*, 31(1), 32–44. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10476210.2019.1709813>
- Judd, C. M., Smith, E. R., & Kidder, L. H. (1991). *Research Methods in Social Relations*. Sixth Edition. Texas, *Harcourt Brace Javanovich*.
- Jun, J. (2022). Unheard Voices: Transformative workplace learning and support experiences of racialized migrant women English instructors in Ontario Higher education in Canada. *Journal of Underrepresented and Minority Progress*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.32674/jump.v6i1.4465>
- Kahn, M., & Gorski, P. C. (2016). The gendered and heterosexist evolution of the teacher exemplar in the United States: Equity implications for LGBTQ and gender nonconforming teachers. *International Journal of Multicultural Education*, 18(2), 15–38. <https://doi.org/10.18251/ijme.v18i2.1123>
- Kamenou, N. (2023). Queer in Cyprus? The LGBTIQ Movement, Normativity, and Resistance in a Changing (Trans)national Landscape. *Social Sciences*, 12(7), 419. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci12070419>
- Katz-Wise, S. L., & Hyde, J. S. (2012). Victimization Experiences of Lesbian, gay, and Bisexual Individuals: A Meta-Analysis. *The Journal of Sex Research*, 49(2–3), 142–167. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224499.2011.637247>
- Kavanagh, M. M., Srivatsan, V., Anam, F. R., Bok, L., Abinader, L. G., Sharma, A., Grant, C., Chen, Y. W., & Lynch, S. (2025). Global Legal environment for LGBTQ+ Sexuality and Public Health. *The Journal of Law Medicine & Ethics*, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jme.2025.60>

- Kayi-Aydar, H. (2015). Multiple identities, negotiations, and agency across time and space: A narrative inquiry of a foreign language teacher candidate. *Critical Inquiry in Language Studies*, 12(2), 137–160. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15427587.2015.1032076>
- Keleş, K., Kavas, M. V., & Yalın, N. Y. (2018). LGBT+ Individuals' Perceptions of Healthcare Services in Turkey: A Cross-sectional Qualitative Study. *Journal of Bioethical Inquiry*, 15(4), 497–509. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11673-018-9874-5>
- Kelly, M., Carathers, J., & Kade, T. (2020). Beyond tolerance: policies, practices, and ideologies of Queer-Friendly workplaces. *Sexuality Research & Social Policy/Sexuality Research and Social Policy*, 18(4), 1078–1093. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13178-020-00512-3>
- Khayatt, D., & Iskander, L. (2019). Reflecting on 'coming out' in the classroom. *Teaching Education*, 31(1), 6–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10476210.2019.1689943>
- Kitching, K. (2009). Teachers' negative experiences and expressions of emotion: being true to yourself or keeping you in your place? *Irish Educational Studies*, 28(2), 141–154. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323310902884201>
- Kivunja, C. (2018). Distinguishing between Theory, Theoretical Framework, and Conceptual Framework: A Systematic Review of Lessons from the Field. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 7(6), 44. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v7n6p44>
- Kline, N. S., Griner, S. B., Neelamegam, M., Webb, N. J., Morales, J. J., & Rhodes, S. D. (2022). Responding to “Don’t say gay” laws in the US: Research priorities and considerations for health equity. *Sexuality Research and Social Policy*, 19(4), 1397–1402. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13178-022-00773-0>
- Krishnan, L. A. (2002). Diaries: listening to “voices” from the multicultural classroom. *ELT Journal*, 56(3), 227–239. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/56.3.227>

- Kumashiro, K. K., Baber, S. A., Richardson, E., Ricker-Wilson, C., & Wong, P. L. (2004). Preparing teachers for anti-oppressive education: international movements. *Teaching Education*, 15(3), 257–275.
- Kulpa, R. (2016). Nations and sexualities – ‘West’ and ‘East.’ In *Routledge eBooks* (pp. 43–62). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315576107-4>
- Laplante, A. J. (2023). We Are Not Alone: Queer Teachers’ Navigating Personal and Professional Identity; A Qualitative Study. [Master’s Thesis, McGill University].
- Lawrence, L., & Nagashima, Y. (2019). The Intersectionality of Gender, Sexuality, Race, and Native-speakerness: Investigating ELT Teacher Identity through Duo-ethnography. *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*, 19(1), 42–55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15348458.2019.1672173>
- Lee, C. (2019a). Fifteen years on: the legacy of section 28 for LGBT+ teachers in English schools. *Sex Education*, 19(6), 675–690. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681811.2019.1585800>
- Lee, C. (2019b). How do Lesbian, Gay and Bisexual Teachers Experience UK Rural School Communities? *Social Sciences*, 8(9), 249. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci8090249>
- Lee, C. (2020). Why LGBT teachers may make exceptional school leaders. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsoc.2020.00050>
- Lehtonen, J. (2016). Experiences of Non-Heterosexual and trans youth on career choice and in the workplace. *Springer eBooks*, 289–306. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-29623-4_17
- Leithwood, & McAddie. (2007). Teacher Working Conditions That Matter. *Education Canada, Canadian Education Association*, 47(0013–1253).

- Le Maistre, C., & Paré, A. (2010). Whatever it takes: How beginning teachers learn to survive. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 26(3), 559–564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2009.06.016>
- Leung, E., Kassel-Gomez, G., Sullivan, S., Murahara, F., & Flanagan, T. (2022). Social support in schools and related outcomes for LGBTQ youth: a scoping review. *Discover Education*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44217-022-00016-9>
- Lewis, M. W., & Ericksen, K. S. (2016). Improving the climate for LGBTQ students at an Historically Black University. *Journal of LGBT Youth*, 13(3), 249–269. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19361653.2016.1185761>
- Libed, B. P., Arrington, C., Spain, J., & Rothblum, E. (2010). And They Were Wonderful Teachers: Florida’s Purge of Gay and Lesbian Teachers by Karen L. Graves. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 57(4), 588–590. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918361003609267>
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1986). But is it rigorous? Trustworthiness and authenticity in naturalistic evaluation. *New Directions for Program Evaluation*, 1986(30), 73–84.
- Lineback, S., Allender, M., Gaines, R., McCarthy, C. J., & Butler, A. (2016). “They think I am a pervert:” A qualitative analysis of lesbian and gay teachers’ experiences with stress at school. *Educational Studies :/Educational Studies*, 52(6), 592–613. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131946.2016.1231681>
- Llewellyn, A. (2022). Bursting the ‘childhood bubble’: reframing discourses of LGBTQ+ teachers and their students. *Sport, Education and Society*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2022.2106203>

- Llewellyn, A. (2023). "Because I live it.": LGB teacher identities, as professional, personal, and political. *Frontiers in Education*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1164413>
- Llewellyn, A., & Reynolds, K. (2020). Within and between heteronormativity and diversity: narratives of LGB teachers and coming and being out in schools. *Sex Education*, 21(1), 13–26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681811.2020.1749040>
- Loftin, C., Campanella, H., & Gilbert, S. (2011). Ethical issues in nursing education: the dual-role researcher. *Teaching and Learning in Nursing*, 6(3), 139–143.
- Lu, A., LeBlanc, A. J., & Frost, D. M. (2018). Masculinity and Minority Stress among Men in Same-sex Relationships. *Society and Mental Health*, 9(2), 259–275. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2156869318773425>
- Lugg, C. A., & Koschoreck, J. W. (2003). The Final Closet: Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgendered Educational Leaders. *Journal of School Leadership*, 13(1), 4–6. <https://doi.org/10.1177/105268460301300101>
- Lundin, M. (2016). Homo- and bisexual teachers' ways of relating to the heteronorm. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 75, 67–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2015.11.005>
- Macgillivray, I. K. (2008). Religion, Sexual Orientation, and School Policy: How the Christian Right Frames Its Arguments. *Educational Studies*, 43(1), 29–44. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131940701796210>
- Mack, N., Woodson, C., MacQueen, K., Guest, G. & Namey, E. (2005). Qualitative Research Methods: A Data Collector's Field Guide. *Family Health International (FHI)*, USA.
- Macrina, F. (2013). Scientific Integrity. *American Society for Microbiology Press*. Washington, DC.

- Madera, J. M. (2010). The cognitive effects of hiding one's homosexuality in the workplace. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 3(1), 86–89. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1754-9434.2009.01204.x>
- Maher, B., & Toledo, W. (2021). From Pre-Service to Professional Teaching: A Longitudinal Study of Two LGBTQ+-identifying First-Year Elementary Teachers' Experiences. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 69(12), 2126–2147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2021.1987747>
- Manimtim, J. S., San Juan, J. A., Padilla, E. D., Aterrado, J. S., & Blanquisco, H. R. (2022). Challenges of LGBTQ Pre-Service Teachers. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 2934-2939.
- Markow, D., & Fein, J. (2005). From teasing to torment: School climate in America, A survey of students and teachers. New York: GLSEN.
- Marshall, C. & Rossman, G. (2016). *Designing Qualitative Research*. 6th Edition, SAGE, Thousand Oaks.
- Maxwell, J.A. (2013). *Qualitative Research Design: An Interactive Approach*. Sage, Thousand Oaks.
- Mayo, J. B. (2023). Queer teacher to queer teacher: reflections, questions, and hopes from current and aspiring educators. *Routledge eBooks*, 32–44. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003379645-4>
- McBrien, J., Rutigliano, A., & Sticca, A. (2022). The Inclusion of LGBTQI+ students across education systems. *OECD Education Working Papers*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/91775206-en>
- McCabe, P. C., & Rubinson, F. (2008). Committing to Social Justice: The behavioral intention of school psychology and education trainees to advocate for lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender youth. *School Psychology Review*, 37(4), 469–486. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02796015.2008.12087861>

- McCalla, S. A. (2015). Policy characteristics for the Prevention of workplace bullying anteceded by Heterosexism: a Delphi study. *Journal of Psychological Issues in Organizational Culture*, 6(2), 39–62. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jpoc.21180>
- McCallum, F., Price, D., Graham, A., & Morrison, A. (2017). *Teacher wellbeing: A review of the literature*. Sydney, NSW AIS.
- McCarthy, L. (2003). Wearing my identity: a transgender teacher in the classroom. *Equity & Excellence in Education*, 36(2), 170–183. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10665680303510>
- McCormack, M. (2014). Is sexuality research ‘dirty work’? *Sexualities*, 17(5–6), 674–676. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1363460714531277>
- McFadden, C., & Crowley-Henry, M. (2017). ‘My People’: the potential of LGBT employee networks in reducing stigmatization and providing voice. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 29(5), 1056–1081. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2017.1335339>
- McKenna-Buchanan, T. (2017). It’s not all “One” story. *Departures in Critical Qualitative Research*, 6(1), 11–29. <https://doi.org/10.1525/dcqr.2017.6.1.11>
- McKenna-Buchanan, T., Munz, S., & Rudnick, J. (2015). To Be or Not To Be Out in the Classroom: Exploring Communication Privacy Management Strategies of Lesbian, Gay, and Queer College Teachers. *Communication Education*, 64(3), 280–300. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03634523.2015.1014385>
- McNair, R. P. (2017). Multiple Identities and Their Intersections with Queer Health and Wellbeing. *Journal of Intercultural Studies*, 38(4), 443–452. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07256868.2017.1341398>
- Merriam, S. B. (2009). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.

- Mert-Karadaş, M., Uslu-Şahan, F., & Yücel-Özçırpan, C. (2023). Predictors of health professional students' attitudes toward LGBTI individuals: A cross-sectional study from Turkey. *Archives of Psychiatric Nursing*, 44, 86–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apnu.2023.04.013>
- Meyer, E. J. (2007). " But I'm not Gay": What Straight Teachers Need to Know about Queer Theory.
- Meyer, E. J., Taylor, C. & Peter, T. (2015). Perspectives on gender and sexual diversity (GSD)-inclusive education: comparisons between gay/lesbian/bisexual and straight educators, *Sex Education*, 15:3, 221-234, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681811.2014.979341>
- Meyer, E. J., Quantz, M., Taylor, C., & Peter, T. (2019). Elementary Teachers' Experiences with LGBTQ-inclusive Education: Addressing Fears with Knowledge to Improve Confidence and Practices. *Theory Into Practice*, 58(1), 6–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405841.2018.1536922>
- Meyer, I. H. (2003). Minority stress and mental health in gay men. In L. D. Garnets, & D. C. Kimmel (Eds.), *Psychological perspectives on lesbian, gay, and bisexual experiences* (2nd ed., pp. 699–731). New York, NY: Columbia University Press.
- Meyer, I. H., & Ouellette, S. C. (2009). Unity and purpose at the intersections of racial/ethnic and sexual identities. *The story of sexual identity: Narrative perspectives on the gay and lesbian life course*, 79-106.
- Milligan, C., Bingley, A., & Gatrell, A. (2005). Digging deep: Using diary techniques to explore the place of health and well-being amongst older people. *Social Science & Medicine*, 61(9), 1882–1892.
- Mitton, J., Tompkins, J., & Kearns, L. L. (2021). Exploring the Impact of an Anti-Homophobia and Anti-Transphobia Program on a Teacher Education Program: LGBTQ Pre-Service Teachers Identify Benefits and Challenges. *Alberta Journal of Educational Research*, 67(1), 32–52. <https://doi.org/10.55016/ojs/ajer.v67i1.56915>

- Mizzi, R. C. (2013). “There aren’t any gays here”: Encountering Heteroprofessionalism in an international development workplace. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 60(11), 1602–1624. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2013.824341>
- Mizzi, R. C. (2022). Creating inclusive workplaces for LGBTQ international educators: Voices from the field. *The International Education Journal: Comparative Perspectives*, 2(2), 129-138. <http://iejcomparative.org>
- Mizzi, R. C. (2024). Understanding homoprofessionalism and the political context. *Routledge eBooks*, 42–56. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003128151-5>
- Mizzi, R. C., Schmidt, C., & Moura, G. (2021). Complexity amidst Diversity: Exploring the Lives of LGBTQ International Teachers. *Comparative and International Education*, 50(1). <https://doi.org/10.5206/cieeci.v50i1.11063>
- Mizzi, R. C., & Star, J. (2019). Queer Eye on Inclusion: Understanding lesbian and gay student and instructor experiences of continuing education. *The Journal of Continuing Higher Education*, 67(2–3), 72–82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07377363.2019.1660844>
- Moore, K. (2021). Sexual Orientation and Teacher Identity: Professionalism and LGBTQ Politics in Teacher Preparation and Practice. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 68(9), 1563–1565. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2021.1905387>
- Mora, A., Trejo, P., & Roux, R. (2016). The complexities of being and becoming language teachers: issues of identity and investment. *Language and Intercultural Communication*, 16(2), 182–198. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14708477.2015.1136318>
- Morris. (1998). Unresting the Curriculum: Queer Projects, Queer Imaginings. In *Queer Theory in Education* (1st ed., Vol. 10). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781410603760>

- Morrow, D. (2006). 'Coming out as gay, lesbian, bisexual, and transgender', in *Sexual Orientation & Gender Expression in Social Work Practice: Working with Gay, Lesbian, Bisexual, and Transgender People*, eds D. Morrow & L. Messinger, Columbia, New York.
- Morse, J.M., Barrett, M., Mayan, M., Olson, K. & Spiers, J. (2002). Verification strategies for establishing reliability and validity in qualitative research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 1, 1-19.
- Murphy, H. E. (2012). Improving the lives of students, gay and straight alike: Gay-straight alliances and the role of school psychologists. *Psychology in the Schools*, 49(9), 883–891. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.21643>
- Nadal, K. L. (2018). Measuring LGBTQ microaggressions: the Sexual Orientation Microaggressions Scale (SOMS) and the Gender Identity Microaggressions Scale (GIMS). *Journal of Homosexuality*, 66(10), 1404–1414. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2018.1542206>
- Nadal, K. L., Whitman, C. N., Davis, L. S., Erazo, T., & Davidoff, K. C. (2016). Microaggressions toward lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, and genderqueer people: A Review of the literature. *The Journal of Sex Research*, 53(4–5), 488–508. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224499.2016.1142495>
- National Gay And Lesbian Task Force, U. S. & National LGBTIQ Task Force, U. S. (1991). *National Gay and Lesbian Task Force / National LGBTQ Task Force*. United States.
- Neary, A. (2013). Lesbian and gay teachers' experiences of 'coming out' in Irish schools. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 34(4), 583–602. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01425692.2012.722281>
- Neary, A. (2017). Lesbian, gay and bisexual teachers' ambivalent relations with parents and students while entering into a civil partnership. *Irish Educational Studies*, 36(1), 57–72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2017.1289702>

- Neary, A., Gray, B., & O'Sullivan, M. (2017). Lesbian, Gay and Bisexual teachers' negotiations of civil partnership and schools: ambivalent attachments to religion and secularism. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*, 39(3), 434–447. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01596306.2016.1276432>
- Nelson, C. D. (2020). Queer Thinking about Language Learning: Current Research and Future Directions. *The Oxford Handbook of Language and Sexuality*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190212926.013.34>
- Newheiser, A., Barreto, M., & Tiemersma, J. (2017). People Like Me Don't Belong Here: Identity Concealment is Associated with Negative Workplace Experiences. *Journal of Social Issues*, 73(2), 341–358. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josi.12220>
- Nielsen, E. J., & Alderson, K. G. (2014). Lesbian and Queer Women Professors Disclosing in the Classroom. *The Counseling Psychologist*, 42(8), 1084–1107. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011000014554839>
- Nixon, & Givens. (2011). Queer in England: 1. In *Queer in Europe* (1st ed., p. 16). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315603209>
- Oakley, A. (1998). Gender, Methodology and People's Ways of Knowing: Some Problems with Feminism and the Paradigm Debate in Social Science. *Sociology*, 32(4), 707–731.
- O'Brien, K. M., & Fassinger, R. E. (1993). A causal model of the career orientation and career choice of adolescent women. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 40(4), 456–469. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0167.40.4.456>
- Olmos-Vega, F. M., Stalmeijer, R. E., Varpio, L., & Kahlke, R. (2022). A practical guide to reflexivity in qualitative research: AMEE Guide No. 149. *Medical Teacher*, 45(3), 241–251. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159x.2022.2057287>
- O'Loughlin, A. K. (2019). Gender-as-Lived: The Coloniality of Gender in Schools as a Queer Teacher Listens in to Complicated Moments of Resistance. *Indo-*

Pacific Journal of Phenomenology, 19(1), 41–49.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/20797222.2019.1643066>

Ördem, E., & Ulum, M. G. (2020). Gender Issues in English Language Teaching: Views from Turkey. *Acta Educationis Generalis*, 10(1), 25–39.
<https://doi.org/10.2478/atd-2020-0002>

Orlov, J. M., & Allen, K. R. (2014). Being Who I Am: Effective Teaching, Learning, Student Support, and Societal Change Through LGBTQ Faculty Freedom. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 61(7), 1025–1052.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2014.870850>

Oyserman, D., & Destin, M. (2010). Identity-based motivation: Implications for intervention. *The Counseling Psychologist*, 38(7), 1001–1043.

Özbay, C. (2021). Living like a hetero: Southern homonormativity in Istanbul. *Sexualities*, 25(8), 1058–1076. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13634607211014477>

Özbay, C., & Candan, A. B. (2023). Intersectionality and feminist/queer student activism in authoritarian Turkey. *International Feminist Journal of Politics*, 25(4), 664–686. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616742.2023.2204101>

Özbay, C., Erol, M., Bağcı, C., & Özkaplan, N. (2022). Secular but conservative? Youth, gender, and intimacy in Turkey. *Turkish Studies*, 24(1), 29–50.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14683849.2022.2085095>

Özeren, E. (2014). Sexual Orientation Discrimination in the Workplace: A Systematic Review of Literature. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 109, 1203–1215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.12.613>

Özeren, E., & Aydın, E. (2016). What does being LGBT mean in the workplace? A comparison of LGBT equality in Turkey and the UK. In *Edward Elgar Publishing eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781784719692.00012>

- Özeren, E., Uçar, Z., & Duygulu, E. (2016). Silence Speaks in the Workplace: Uncovering the Experiences of LGBT Employees in Turkey. *Sexual Orientation and Transgender Issues in Organizations*, 217–232. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-29623-4_13
- Öztürk, M. B. (2024). The propagation of workplace inequalities through sexual- and gender-identity normativities: understanding heteronormativity, homonormativity, cisnormativity, and transnormativity in organisations. *Edward Elgar Publishing eBooks*, 39–51. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800886605.00011>
- Padgett, D. (2008). *Qualitative Methods in Social Work Research*. SAGE.
- Palmer, P.J. (1998). The courage to teach: Exploring the inner landscape of a teacher's life. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Papadaki, V., Papadaki, E., & Giannou, D. (2021). Microaggression experiences in the workplace among Greek LGB social workers. *Journal of Gay & Lesbian Social Services*, 33(4), 512–532. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10538720.2021.1892560>
- Patterson, C. J. (2013). Schooling, Sexual Orientation, Law, and Policy: Making Schools Safe for All Students. *Theory Into Practice*, 52(3), 190–195. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405841.2013.804312>
- Patton, L. D., Tuitt, F., Haynes, C., & Stewart, S. (2023). Race, equity, and the learning environment. In *Routledge eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003446637>
- Patton, M. Q. (1990). *Qualitative Evaluation and Research Methods*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
- Patton, M. Q. (1999). Enhancing the Quality and Credibility of Qualitative Analysis. *Health Services Research* (34), 1189-1208.

- Patton, M. Q. (2002). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Patton, M. Q. (2014). *Qualitative Research and Evaluation Methods*. 4th Edition, Sage, Thousand Oaks.
- Payne, E. C., & Smith, M. (2011). The Reduction of Stigma in Schools: A new professional development model for empowering educators to support LGBTQ students. *Journal of LGBT Youth*, 8(2), 174–200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19361653.2011.563183>
- Pennington, M. C., & Richards, J. C. (2016). Teacher identity in language teaching: Integrating personal, contextual, and professional factors. *RELC Journal*, 47(1), 5–23. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0033688216631219>
- Petegem, K. V., Creemers, B. P. M., Rossel, Y. & Aelterman, A. (2005). Relationships between Teacher Characteristics, Interpersonal Teacher Behavior and Teacher Wellbeing. *Journal of Classroom Interaction*, 40(2), 33–43.
- Pettersson, R. (1993). Comprehensibility. *Presented at the International Symposium of the International Visual Literacy Association*.
- Pezzella, A. (2018). ‘Out’ and about at work. In *Routledge eBooks* (pp. 101–120). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315398785-7>
- Pierce, C. M. (1970). Offensive mechanisms. *The Black Seventies*, 265-282.
- Pinar, W. F. (1994). *Autobiography, Politics, and Sexuality*. Peter Lang Incorporated, International Academic Publishers.
- Piper, H., & Sikes, P. (2010). All Teachers Are Vulnerable but Especially Gay Teachers: Using Composite Fictions to Protect Research Participants in

Pupil—Teacher Sex-Related Research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 16(7), 566–574.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800410371923>

Pryor, J. T. (2020). Queer activist leadership: An exploration of queer leadership in higher education. *Journal of Diversity in Higher Education*, 14(3), 303–315.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/dhe0000160>

Punch, K. F. (2009). *Introduction to Research Methods in Education*. Sage, Thousand Oaks.

Racelis, J. V., & Matsuda, P. K. (2014). Exploring the multiple identities of L2 writing teachers. *Routledge eBooks*, 203–216.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315775135-15>

Reason, P., & Bradbury, H. (2008). *The SAGE Handbook of Action Research: Participative Inquiry and Practice*. SAGE Publications.

Reinharz, S., & Davidman, L. (1992). *Feminist methods in social research*. Oxford University Press.

Resnick, C. A., & Galupo, M. P. (2018). Assessing Experiences with LGBT Microaggressions in the workplace: Development and validation of the microaggression experiences at work scale. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 66(10), 1380–1403. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2018.1542207>

Rey, A. M., & Gibson, R. P. (1997). Beyond high school: Heterosexuals' self-reported anti-gay lesbian behaviors and attitudes. *Journal of Gay & Lesbian Social Services*, 7, 65-84.

Rich, A. C. (2003). Compulsory Heterosexuality and Lesbian Existence (1980). *Journal of Women's History*, 15(3), 11–48.
<https://doi.org/10.1353/jowh.2003.0079>

- Richard, A. C. (2013). LGBT: equally entitled to human rights and dignity. *DOAJ (DOAJ: Directory of Open Access Journals)*.
- Riches, C., & Benson, F. (2010). Nothing new under the sun: Mitigating the lament of betrayal in teacher education. In J. Maurer & W. Halloway (Eds.), *International research in teacher education: Current perspectives* (pp. 157–172). Armidale, NSW, Australia: UNE Conference Company.
- Riquelme-Sanderson, M., & Longoria, A. (2023). LGBTQ+ Language Teacher Educators' Identities and Pedagogies: Testimonio and Duo-ethnography. *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.21659/rupkatha.v15n1.07>
- Roberts, G., Allan, C., & Wells, K. (2007). Understanding Gender Identity in K-12 Schools. *Journal of Gay & Lesbian Issues in Education*, 4(4), 119–129. https://doi.org/10.1300/j367v04n04_08
- Rocco, T. S., & Plakhotnik, M. S. (2009). Literature reviews, conceptual frameworks, and theoretical frameworks: terms, functions, and distinctions. *Human Resource Development Review*, 8(1), 120–130. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484309332617>
- Rockhill, K. (1993). “Dis/connecting Literacy and Sexuality: Speaking the Unspeakable in the Classroom.” In *Critical Literacy: Politics, Praxis and the Postmodern*, edited by Colin Lankshear and Peter McLaren, 335–367. New York: Jung Press.
- Rodriguez, N. M., & Pinar, W. F. (2007). Queering Straight Teachers: Discourse and Identity in Education. *Complicated Conversation: A Book Series of Curriculum Studies*. Volume 22. Peter Lang New York. <https://www.eric.ed.gov/?id=ED498753>
- Rofes, E. (2000). Young Adult Reflections on having an Openly Gay Teacher during Early Adolescence. *Education and Urban Society*, 32(3), 399–412. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013124500323008>

- Rottmann, C. (2006). Queering educational leadership from the inside out. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 9(1), 1–20.
- Rubio, R. J., & Green, R. J. (2009). Filipino masculinity and psychological distress: A preliminary comparison between gay and heterosexual men. *Sexuality Research and Social Policy*, 6(3), 61–75. <https://doi.org/10.1525/srsp.2009.6.3.61>
- Rudoe, N. (2010). Lesbian teachers' identity, power and the public/private boundary. *Sex Education*, 10(1), 23–36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681810903491347>
- Rumens, N., & Kerfoot, D. (2009). Gay men at work: (Re)constructing the self as professional. *Human Relations*, 62(5), 763–786. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726709103457>
- Russell, K. (2020). 'I don't think my sexuality would come into teaching at all': exploring the borderland discourse of Australian LGBTQ+ pre-service teachers. *Gender and Education*, 33(5), 562–577. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540253.2020.1798360>
- Russell, S. T., Toomey, R. B., Ryan, C., & Diaz, R. M. (2014). Being out at school: The implications for school victimization and young adult adjustment. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 84(6), 635–643. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ort0000037>
- Russell, V. T. (2010). Queer teachers' ethical dilemmas regarding queer youth. *Teaching Education*, 21(2), 143–156. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10476211003735427>
- Russ, T. L., Simonds, C. J., & Hunt, S. K. (2002). Coming out in the classroom... An occupational hazard? The influence of sexual orientation on teacher credibility and perceived student learning. *Communication Education*, 51(3), 311–324. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03634520216516>
- Ryan-Flood, R. (2022). Queering Representation: Ethics and Visibility in research. *Routledge eBooks*, 100–112. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003302469-9>

- Sakallı, N., & Uğurlu, O. (2002). The effects of social contact with a lesbian person on the attitude change toward homosexuality in Turkey. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 44, 111–120.
- Saldaña, J. (2013). *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers* (2nd ed.). London: Sage.
- Samuel, S., & Jonathan, G. (2019). Using Minority Stress Theory as a Conceptual Lens to Frame the Experiences of Teachers Who Identify as LGBTQ+. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 18(7), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.18.7.1>
- Saraç, L., & McCullick, B. (2015). The life of a gay student in a university physical education and sports department: a case study in Turkey. *Sport, Education and Society*, 22(3), 338–354. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2015.1036232>
- Saxey, E. (2020). Sexuality and pedagogy in the accounts of lesbian, gay and bisexual teachers. *Pedagogy, Culture & Society*, 29(4), 593–610. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681366.2020.1774797>
- Scandurra, C., Picariello, S., Valerio, P., & Amodeo, A. L. (2017). Sexism, homophobia and transphobia in a sample of Italian pre-service teachers: the role of socio-demographic features. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 43(2), 245–261. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2017.1286794>
- Seiler-Ramadas, R., Markovic, L., Staras, C., Medina, L. L., Perak, J., Carmichael, C., Horvat, M., Bajkusa, M., Baros, S., Smith, L., McDermott, D. T., & Grabovac, I. (2021). “I Don’t Even Want to Come Out”: the Suppressed Voices of Our Future and Opening the Lid on Sexual and Gender Minority Youth Workplace Discrimination in Europe: a Qualitative Study. *Sexuality Research & Social Policy/Sexuality Research and Social Policy*, 19(4), 1452–1472. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13178-021-00644-0>
- Selvi, A. F., & Kocaman, C. (2020). (Mis-/Under-) Representations of Gender and Sexuality in Locally-Produced ELT Materials. *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*, 20(2), 118–133. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15348458.2020.1726757>

- Shamoo, A. E., & Dunigan, C. D. (2000). Ethics in research. *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine*. Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine, 224 4, 205-10.
- Silverman, D. (2013). *Doing Qualitative Research: A Practical Handbook*. Sage Publications.
- Silverman, D. (2015) *Interpreting Qualitative Data*. SAGE Publications, Thousand Oaks.
- Simon, S. (2003). The nation: Transgender chaperon ignites school dispute: Some insist on a rule on 'appropriate' attire after a dad dressed as a woman goes on trip. Los Angeles Times, Section A, p. 19.
- Simons, J. D., Hahn, S., Pope, M., & Russell, S. T. (2021). Experiences of educators who identify as lesbian, gay, and bisexual. *Journal of Gay & Lesbian Social Services*, 33(3), 300–319. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10538720.2021.1875947>
- Smith, N. J., Wright, T., Reilly, C., & Esposito, J. (2008). A National Study of LGBT Educators' Perceptions of Their Workplace Climate.
- Soini, A. (2022). A gay reflection on microaggressions, symbolic normativities, and pink hair. *Gender, Work and Organization*, 29(5), 1594–1611. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gwao.12851>
- Soner, G., & Altay, B. (2020). Determining attitudes of a group of nurses working in the northern region of Turkey towards LGBT individuals. *Progress in Health Sciences*, 10(1), 26–34. <https://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0014.1914>
- Soyer, M., Ziyanak, S., Henderson, L., Ethington, R., Walton, R., Soyer, G., Thomas, A., Wagner, I., & Wells, E. (2023). Empowering Students via Autoethnography Assignment: Fostering Inclusive Communities for Gender and Sexuality in Social Inequality Class. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 10(4), 43–57. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejecs/1607>

- Spillett, M. A. (2003). Peer debriefing: Who, what, when, why, how. *Academic Exchange*, 36-40.
- Stake, R. E. (1995). *The Art of Case Study Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Stake, R. E. (2000). Case Studies. In N. K. Denzin, & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of Qualitative Research* (pp. 435-453). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Stake, R.E. (2005). Qualitative Case Studies. In: Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S., Eds., *The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research*, 3rd Edition, Sage Publications, London, 443-466.
- Steck, A. K., & Perry, D. R. (2016). Fostering safe and inclusive spaces for LGBTQ students: Phenomenographic exploration of high school administrators' perceptions about GSAs. *Journal of LGBT Youth*, 13(4), 352–377. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19361653.2016.1185759>
- Steck, A. K., & Perry, D. (2017a). Challenging Heteronormativity: Creating a Safe and Inclusive Environment for LGBTQ Students. *Journal of School Violence*, 17(2), 227–243. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15388220.2017.1308255>
- Steck, A., & Perry, D. (2017b). Secondary school leader perceptions about the inclusion of queer materials in the school course curricula. *The Curriculum Journal*, 28(3), 327–348. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585176.2017.1292180>
- Stiegler, S. (2008). Queer youth as teachers: Dismantling silence of queer issues in a teacher preparation program committed to social justice. *Journal of LGBT Youth*, 5(4), 116-123.
- Stones, S., & Glazzard, J. (2020). Tales From the Chalkface: Using Narratives to Explore Agency, Resilience, and Identity of Gay Teachers. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsoc.2020.00052>

- Suárez, M. I., Meister, S. M., & Lindner, A. L. (2019). Envisioning queer curricula: A systematic review of LGBTIQ+ topics in teacher practitioner literature. *Journal of LGBT Youth*, 18(3), 239–255. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19361653.2019.1705223>
- Swanepoel, E. H. (2019). A Reflective Cybernetic Study on the Experiences of a Gay Male Teacher in the Free State Province. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 67(9), 1197–1212. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2019.1582222>
- Swanson, K., & Gettinger, M. (2016). Teachers' knowledge, attitudes, and supportive behaviors toward LGBT students: Relationship to Gay-Straight Alliances, antibullying policy, and teacher training. *Journal of LGBT Youth*, 13(4), 326–351. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19361653.2016.1185765>
- Tajeddin, Z., & Yazan, B. (2024). Language teacher identity tensions. In *Routledge eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003402411>
- Takatori, S., & Ofuji, K. (2007). My Coming Out Story as a Gay Teacher in Kyoto. *Journal of Gay & Lesbian Issues in Education*, 4(2), 99–105. https://doi.org/10.1300/j367v04n02_09
- Taşkın, P., Nayir, F., & Demirdiş, M. (2022). Is privacy enough to exist? LGBT+ teachers' experiences in Turkey. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 70(11), 2666–2687. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2022.2074332>
- Teddlie, C., & Yu, F. (2007). Mixed methods sampling: A typology with examples. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 1(1), 77-100.
- Terry, G., Hayfield, N., Clarke, V., & Braun, V. (2017). Thematic analysis. In *SAGE Publications Ltd eBooks* (pp. 17–36). <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781526405555.n2>
- Thomas-Durrell, L. (2019). Being your 'true self': the experiences of two gay music educators who teach in the Bible Belt. *Music Education Research*, 22(1), 29–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14613808.2019.1703921>

- Thomas, G. (2011). A Typology for the Case Study in Social Science Following a Review of Definition, Discourse, and Structure. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 17(6), 511-521.
- Thompson, L. (1992). Feminist methodology for family studies. *Journal of Marriage and the Family*, 54, 3-18.
- Tompkins, J., Kearns, L., & Kükner, J. M. (2019a). Queer Educators in Schools: The experiences of four beginning teachers. *Canadian Journal of Education / Revue Canadienne De L Éducation*, 42(2), 384–414. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1222235.pdf>
- Tompkins, J., Kearns, L.-L., & Mitton-Kükner, J. (2019b). Queer Educators in Schools: The Experiences of Four Beginning Teachers. *Canadian Journal of Education / Revue Canadienne de l'éducation*, 42(2), 384–414. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26823252>
- Tolich, M., & Tumilty, E. (2021). *Finding Your Ethical Research Self*. Routledge.
- Tracy, S. J. (2010). Qualitative Quality: Eight “Big-Tent” Criteria for Excellent Qualitative Research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 16(10), 837–851.
- Ueno, K. (2023). LGBTQ students’ experiences of heteronormativity in higher education institutions: focusing on Japan as the national context. *Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-023-01125-6>
- Ulaş-Kılıç, Z., Bayar, Z., & Koç, M. (2019). The Career Stories of LGB-Q in Turkey. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 68(10), 1699–1726. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00918369.2019.1705668>
- Ullman, J. (2020). Present, yet not welcomed: gender diverse teachers’ experiences of discrimination. *Teaching Education*, 31(1), 67–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10476210.2019.1708315>

- Unwin, S., Starcevich, R., Lembo, S., & Dobson, M. (2024). On becoming a queer educator: reflections on queer perspectives and approaches in initial teacher education. *Continuum*, 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10304312.2024.2335505>
- Uzum, B., Yazan, B., & Avineri, N. (2022). Becoming teachers of emergent bilinguals: Navigating ideological and identity tensions. *Language Teaching Research*, 136216882211276. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13621688221127646>
- Vandrick, S. (1997). The Role of Hidden Identities in the Postsecondary EMCKSL Classroom. *TESOL Quarterly*, 31(1), 153. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3587980>
- Varah, L. J., Theune, W. S., & Parker, L. (1986). Beginning Teachers: Sink or Swim? *Journal of Teacher Education*, 37(1), 30–34. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002248718603700107>
- Varghese, M., Morgan, B., Johnston, B., & Johnson, K. A. (2005). Theorizing Language Teacher Identity: Three Perspectives and Beyond. *Journal of Language, Identity, and Education*, 4(1), 21–44. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327701jlie0401_2
- Vefikuluçay Yılmaz, D., Değirmenci, F., Aksoy, A., Buldum, A., & Aksu, A. (2022). University Students' Attitudes Toward Homophobia and Related Factors. *Clinical and Experimental Health Sciences*, 12(3), 582–586. <https://doi.org/10.33808/clinexphealthsci.923740>
- Waling, A., & Roffee, J. A. (2018). Supporting LGBTIQ+ students in higher education in Australia: Diversity, inclusion and visibility. *Health Education Journal*, 77(6), 667–679. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0017896918762233>
- Walls, N. E., Wisneski, H. & Kane, S. B. (2013). School Climate, Individual Support, or Both? Gay Straight Alliances and the Mental Health of Sexual Minority Youth. *School Social Work Journal* 37(2):88–111.
- Walker, A. J. (1993). Teaching about race, gender, and class diversity in United States families. *Family Relations*, 42, 342-350.

- Walker, L. J., & Goings, R. B. (2018). Challenging Cultural Norms at HBCUs: How Perceptions Impact LGBTQ Students' Experiences. *Underserved Populations at Historically Black Colleges and Universities*, 147–160. <https://doi.org/10.1108/s1479-364420180000021010>
- Wardle, M. (2009). *Prejudice, Acceptance, Triumph: The Experiences of Gay and Lesbian Teachers in Secondary Education*. Twickenham: Athena Press.
- Warner, M. (1991). Introduction: Fear of a Queer Planet. *Social Text*, 29, 3–17.
- Watson, D., Benozzo, A., & Fida, R. (2023). Trans people in the workplace: Possibilities for subverting heteronormativity. *Work, Employment and Society*, 38(3), 744–765. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09500170231155059>
- Wells, K. (2017). Sexual minority teachers as activist-educators for social justice. *Journal of LGBT Youth*, 14(3), 266–295. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19361653.2017.1324344>
- White, A. J., Magrath, R., & Thomas, B. (2018). The experiences of lesbian, gay and bisexual students and staff at a Further Education college in South East England. *British Educational Research Journal*, 44(3), 480–495. <https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3443>
- William Gust, S. (2007). “Look Out for the Football Players and the Frat Boys”: Autoethnographic Reflections of a Gay Teacher in a Gay Curricular Experience. *Educational Studies*, 41(1), 43–60. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131940701308999>
- Williams, C., & Giuffre, P. (2011). From Organizational Sexuality to Queer Organizations: Research on Homosexuality and the Workplace. *Sociology Compass*, 5(7), 551–563. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9020.2011.00392.x>
- Williams, J., Ritter, J., & Bullock, S. M. (2012). Understanding the Complexity of Becoming a Teacher Educator: Experience, belonging, and practice within a professional learning community. *Studying Teacher Education*, 8(3), 245–260. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17425964.2012.719130>

- Willman, R. K. (2009). Coming out when you're not really in: Coming out as a teachable moment. *Feminism & Psychology*, *19*, 205-209.
- Willis, P. (2010). Laboring in Silence. *Youth & Society*, *43*(3), 957–981. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0044118x10377650>
- Woodruffe-Burton, H. (2016). Countering heteronormativity; lesbians and wellbeing in the workplace. *Springer eBooks*, 47–63. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-9897-6_4
- Wright, T. E. (2010). LGBT Educators' Perceptions of School Climate. *Phi Delta Kappan*, *91*(8), 49–53. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003172171009100810>
- Wright, T. E., & Smith, N. J. (2015). A Safer Place? LGBT Educators, School Climate, and Implications for Administrators. *The Educational Forum*, *79*(4), 394–407.
- Wright, T., Smith, N. J., & Whitney, E. (2019). LGBT Educators' Perceptions of Safety and Support and Implications for Equity-Oriented School Leaders. *Journal of Educational Leadership and Policy Studies*, *3*(2).
- Yabanci, B., & Saglam, E. (2023). Negotiated conformism: gender norms, everyday politics and pro-government actors in Turkey. *The International Spectator/International Spectator*, *58*(3), 20–39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03932729.2023.2220861>
- Yılmaz, V., & Göçmen, İ. (2016). Denied Citizens of Turkey: Experiences of Discrimination Among LGBT Individuals in Employment, Housing and Health Care. *Gender, Work & Organization*, *23*(5), 470–488. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gwao.12122>
- Yin, R. K. (2009). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case Study Research and Applications: Design and Methods* (6th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Yuan, R., & Lee, I. (2013). Understanding language teacher Educators' professional experiences: an exploratory study in Hong Kong. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 23(1), 143–149. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-013-0117-6>

Zheng, H. (2013). Teachers' beliefs and practices: a dynamic and complex relationship. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 41(3), 331–343. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359866x.2013.809051>

Zimmerman, D.H. & Wieder, D.L. (1977). The diary: diary-interview method. *Urban Life*, 5(4), 479-499.

APPENDICES

A. APPROVAL OF THE METU HUMAN SUBJECTS ETHICS COMMITTEE

UYGULAMALI ETİK ARAŞTIRMA MERKEZİ
APPLIED ETHICS RESEARCH CENTER

ORTA DOĞU TEKNİK ÜNİVERSİTESİ
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06 MAYIS 2024

Konu: Değerlendirme Sonucu

Gönderen: ODTÜ İnsan Araştırmaları Etik Kurulu (İAEK)

İlgi: İnsan Araştırmaları Etik Kurulu Başvurusu

Sayın Elvan Eda Işık

Danışmanlığınızı yürüttüğünüz Mehmet Şahin'in "*LGBTQİ Dil Eğitimi Kimlik Müzakeresi, Deneyim Seyri ve Kurumsal Heteroprosesyonellik Kesişimi: Bir Durum Çalışmasından İlgörüler*" başlıklı araştırmanız İnsan Araştırmaları Etik Kurulu tarafından uygun görülerek 0276-ODTÜİAEK-2024 protokol numarası ile onaylanmıştır

Bilgilerinize saygılarımla sunarım

Prof. Dr. Ş. Halil TURAN
Başkan

Prof. Dr. İ. Semih AKÇOMAK
Üye

Doç. Dr. Ali Emre Turgut
Üye

Doç. Dr. Şerife SEVİNÇ
Üye

Doç. Dr. Murat Perit ÇAKIR
Üye

Dr. Öğretim Üyesi Süreyya ÖZCAN KABASAKAL
Üye

Dr. Öğretim Üyesi Müge GÜNDÖZ
Üye

B. SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW 1 QUESTIONS

- 1.** How do you identify your LGBTQI identity? (sexual identity, pronouns, tendencies, etc.)
- 2.** How would you describe the intersectionality of your LGBTQI identity and language educator identity?
- 3.** How do you perceive the notion of heteroprofessionalism, could you define it?
- 4.** Can you provide specific instances of how your LGBTQI identity intersects with your role as a language educator?
- 5.** How do you position your LGBTQI language educator identity in the Turkish context?

C. SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW 2 QUESTIONS

- 1.** How do you think heteroprofessionalism manifests itself in your workplace?
- 2.** How do you navigate heteroprofessional dynamics in your workplace as an LGBTQI language educator?
- 3.** What is your perception of the impact of heteroprofessionalism on the intersection of your LGBTQI identity and professional experiences as a language educator?
- 4.** What challenges do you face in navigating your LGBTQI identity in your workplace, particularly concerning institutional norms and expectations of heteroprofessionalism?
- 5.** Can you exemplify the strategies you employ to navigate heteroprofessionalism in your workplace as an LGBTQI language educator?
- 6.** Would you like to share particularly challenging instances of experiences or anecdotes pertaining to navigating heteroprofessional dynamics in your workplace as an LGBTQI language educator?

D. SOLICITED JOURNAL 1 PROMPT

Please address instances where you have encountered heteroprophessionalism in your workplace as an LGBTQI language educator. How did these encounters impact your identity negotiation and professional experiences?

E. SOLICITED JOURNAL 2 PROMPT

Please consider the ways in which your role as a language educator and your LGBTQI identity interact. How do you think these interactions affect your professional experiences, particularly in navigating heteroprofessional dynamics in your workplace?

F. SOLICITED JOURNAL 3 PROMPT

Please reflect on the challenges of heteroprofessionalism you've faced in your workplace as an LGBTQI language educator. Do you reconcile your LGBTQI identity with institutional expectations and norms, or do you resist heteroprofessionalism in any way?

G. PARTICIPANT-GENERATED OBSERVATION REPORTS TEMPLATE

Target Behaviors for Participant-Generated Observation Report:

1. Heteronormative Behaviors
2. Heteroprofessional Behaviors
3. LGBTQI-phobic behaviors

Date	Context/Situation	Observed Behavior	Notes	Reaction/Impact (If applicable)

H. INFORMED CONSENT FORM

I am inviting you to participate in a research study as part of my METU ELT master's thesis project titled "Intersecting LGBTQI Language Educator Identity Negotiation, Experience Navigation, and Institutional Heteroprofessionalism: Insights from a Case Study". The aim of this study is to scrutinize the intersection of LGBTQI language educator identity, professional experiences, and the notion of heteroprofessionalism. If you agree to participate, you will be asked to take part in two interviews via Zoom, keep periodic journals for 1½ months, and engage in participant-generated reports for a month.

Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw from the study at any time without justification or consequence. Your identity and any information you provide will be kept strictly confidential, and your responses will be anonymized. If you have any questions or concerns about the study, you may contact the principal investigator, Mehmet Şahin, at _____ . If you have any concerns about your rights as a participant, you may contact the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of METU at _____. By signing below, you acknowledge that you have read and understood the information provided in this consent form, and you voluntarily agree to participate in the study under the terms outlined above.

Researcher:

Mehmet Şahin –

Supervisor: Elvan Eda Işık –

Co-Supervisor: Sebahat Yasemin Tezgiden Cakcak –

I have read and understood the explanation provided to me. I voluntarily agree to participate in this study.

Name & Surname:

Date:

Signature:

I. PROFESSIONAL CONSULTATION FORM / KONSÜLTASYON FORMU

Sayın Hocam,

Bu çalışma, Orta Doğu Teknik Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İngiliz Dili Eğitimi Programı kapsamında Assist. Prof. Dr. Eda Elvan Işık danışmanlığı ve Dr. Yasemin Tezgiden Cakcak eş danışmanlığında yüksek lisans öğrencisi Mehmet Şahin tarafından yürütülen yüksek lisans tezi araştırma çalışmasıdır. Araştırma sorularımıza yönelik veri toplama aracı olarak hazırlanan yarı yapılandırılmış mülakat soruları ve günce yönlendiricilerinin uygunluğuna ilişkin görüş ve önerilerinize ihtiyaç duymaktayız. Değerli eleştiri ve değerlendirmelerinizi bizimle paylaşmanızı rica ediyoruz. Katkılarınız için teşekkür ederiz.

Saygılarımızla.

Çalışmanın tanımı ve amacı:

Bu çalışma başlıca kendisini LGBTQI komünitesinin bir bireyi olarak tanımlayan dil öğretmenlerinin çalışma ortamlarını incelemektedir. Literatürdeki benzer çalışmaların kimlik, deneyim ve ideoloji temelli tartışmaları çoğu zaman birbirinden ayrı tutarak incelediği gözlemlenmiştir. Bu tez çalışması ise yukarıda belirtilen üç farklı tartışma alanının LGBTQI tanımlı bir dil eğitmeninin profesyonel çalışma alanındaki kesişimselliğine odaklanmaktadır. Çalışmanın esas amacı, LGBTQI tanımlı bir dil eğitmeninin heteroprofesyonel ideolojilerin tecellisi etkisindeki kimlik müzakeresi ve deneyim seyrini inceleyerek ilgili literatüre katkıda bulunmak ve LGBTQI tanımlı dil öğretmenleri için daha kapsayıcı ve adil çalışma ortamlarının tasarısı konusunda faydalı olacak çıkarımlar ve içgörüler sağlamaktır.

Veri Toplama Araçları:

Durum çalışmalarının gerektirdiği veri çeşitlemesini amaçlayarak, bu tez çalışmasının veri toplama süreci mülakat ve günce olmak üzere iki farklı veri toplama aracı içerecek şekilde tasarlanmıştır. Katılımcıdan toplanan veriler

MAXQDA yazılımı kullanılarak nitel veri analizi teknikleri yardımı ile analiz edilip yorumlanacaktır. Veri toplama süreci 1,5 aylık bir periyodu kapsayacaktır. İlk mülakat veri toplama sürecinin en başında yapılacaktır. Katılımcıdan iki haftada bir olmak üzere üç adet günce tutması talep edilecektir. Bu süreç katılımcının çalışma konusu ile aşına olmasına da katkı sağlayacaktır. Son aşama olarak katılımcı ile ikinci mülakat yapılacak ve veri toplama süreci son bulacaktır.

Çalışmanın Örnekleme:

Bu tez çalışması bir bütüncül durum çalışması olup tek bir katılımcı gerektirmektedir. Çalışmanın katılımcı örnekleme yetişkin, bir eğitim kurumunda tam zamanlı görev alan ve LGBTQI tanımlı olan bir dil eğitmeni şeklinde tanımlanmaktadır.

Çalışmanın Önemi:

Bu tez çalışması yukarıda bahsi geçen, LGBTQI tanımlı dil eğitmenleri popülasyonuna hitap eden kimlik, deneyim ve ideoloji temelli tartışmaları eğitim bilimleri ve pedagoji bağlamının doğu literatüründe birleştiren öncü bir çalışma niteliği taşıyacaktır. Bu çalışmanın araştırma yaklaşımı sebebi ile herhangi bir popülasyon hedefli genelleme amaçlamaması ile, çalışma sonunda ortaya çıkabileceği öngörülen çıkarımlar kapsayıcı bir eğitim politikası ve eğitmen refahı önceliklendirmeyi hedefleyen eğitim idare komisyonlarına yol gösterecek nitelik taşıyacaktır. Ek olarak, benzer çalışmalar Batı literatüründe yer aldığı kadar Doğu literatüründe akademik ilgi toplamamaktadır. Bu çalışmanın Doğu bağlamında gerçekleştirilecek olması sebebi ile kavramsal ve bağlamsal çıkarımlara katkı sağlayacağı düşünülmektedir.

Kontrol Grubu:

Bu tez çalışması bir durum çalışması olup benzer popülasyonlar için herhangi bir genelleme amaçlamamaktadır. Çalışma bütüncül durum deseni türü temellenerek tasarlanmış olup tek bir katılımcıyı inceleyecektir. Çalışma tasarısı ve araştırma yaklaşımı nedeniyle herhangi bir kontrol grubuna ihtiyaç duyulmayacaktır.

Araştırma Soruları:

From the perspective of an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context, how does heterop professionalism, if any, manifest itself within their workplace context?

How does an LGBTQI language educator practicing in the Turkish context negotiate their identity and navigate their professional experiences within their heterop professional workplace context?

Mülakat Soruları:

Bölüm 1

How do you identify your LGBTQI identity? (sexual identity, pronouns, tendencies, etc.)

How would you describe the intersectionality of your LGBTQI identity and language educator identity?

How do you perceive the notion of heterop professionalism, could you define it?

Can you provide specific instances of how your LGBTQI identity intersects with your role as a language educator?

How do you position your LGBTQI language educator identity in the Turkish context?

Bölüm 2

How do you think heterop professionalism manifests itself in your workplace?

How do you navigate heterop professional dynamics in your workplace as an LGBTQI language educator?

What is your perception of the impact of heterop professionalism on the intersection of your LGBTQI identity and professional experiences as a language educator?

What challenges do you face in navigating your LGBTQI identity in your workplace, particularly concerning institutional norms and expectations of heterop professionalism?

Can you exemplify the strategies you employ to navigate heteroprophessionalism in your workplace as an LGBTQI language educator?

Would you like to share particularly challenging instances of experiences or anecdotes pertaining to navigating heteroprophessional dynamics in your workplace as an LGBTQI language educator?

Günce Yönlendiricileri:

Please address instances where you have encountered heteroprophessionalism in your workplace as an LGBTQI language educator. How did these encounters impact your identity negotiation and professional experiences?

Please consider the ways in which your role as a language educator and your LGBTQI identity interact. How do you think these interactions affect your professional experiences, particularly in navigating heteroprophessional dynamics in your workplace?

Please reflect on the challenges of heteroprophessionalism you've faced in your workplace as an LGBTQI language educator. Do you reconcile your LGBTQI identity with institutional expectations and norms, or do you resist heteroprophessionalism in any way?

Görüş ve önerileriniz:

Mülakat Soruları Bölüm 1:

Mülakat Soruları Bölüm 2:

Günce Yönlendiricileri:

J. THE LIST OF EXAMPLE INITIAL CODES

- Sexual Identity
- Perceived expectation of female-bodied English speakers
- coming to terms
- Acknowledgement of sexual identity fluidity
- Pronoun preference
- Understanding of other peoples' lack of knowledge
- assuming lack of knowledge in the topic
- Professional Identity
- Acting strategically
- Conscious neutral word choice
- Acting strategically in navigation of heteroprofessionalism
- Intervention to homophobia
- Acting strategically to avoid conflict
- Acting strategically to be responsive
- Emotions
- Acceptance of the status quo
- Disbelief in societal norms
- Disapproval
- Disapproval of culture
- Disapproval of institutional bullying
- Disapproval of ignorance
- Disapproval of negligence
- Needing Reassurance
- Content with acknowledgement of her identity
- uncertainty of students' perceptions of her queerness
- Feeling alert
- Content with her non-conformity
- Feeling wounded and hurt
- Exhaustion of heteroprofessionalism
- Fear
- Perception and Experience of Heteroprofessionalism
- Realization of her positioning
- assumption of colleagues knowledge in the topic
- Professional experience of heteronormativity
- Institutional microaggression

- No ally support at the workplace
- Institutional exclusion
- Second degree problem (students)
- First degree problem (colleagues)
- Presumption of workplace dynamics
- linguistic openness about sexual identity at workplace
- Supportive colleagues
- Mutual silent agreement
- Impact of profession on hetero professionalism
- Resisting hetero professionalism
- Perceived dangers of hetero professionalism
- Acknowledging the impact hetero professionalism
- Impact of profession on perception of hetero professionalism
- Factors to consider navigating hetero professionalism
- impact of context on hetero professionalism
- English as a Gateway
- Acknowledging the importance of profession on formation
- Acknowledgement of other non-conforming ppl
- Impact of English on identity realization
- Impact of culture and language
- Societal impact on identity
- motivation to learn English
- Reasons up taking up the profession
- Society and Context
- Unintentional homophobia
- Intentional homophobia
- Impact of political context on phobia
- contemplating to fit in
- Disbelief in hetero professionalism
- Tackling the phobic Turkish context
- Societal expectation on gender and identity
- Social norms
- Intersectionality
- Imposing her ideological stance
- Distinction between prof and personal identities
- Separating professional and personal identities
- merging professional and personal identities
- Acknowledgement of multiple identity intersections
- Intersecting tensions of identity and profession
- Performativity
- Acknowledgement of performative dynamics
- Exhaustion of performative acts

K. SAMPLE CODING IN MAXQDA

The screenshot displays the MAXQDA software interface. At the top, there is a menu bar with options: Home, Import, Codes, Memos, Variables, Analysis, Mixed Methods, Visual Tools, Reports, MAXDictio, and TeamCloud. Below the menu is a toolbar with icons for New Project, Open Project, Reset Activations, Logbook, Teamwork, Merge Projects, Save Project As, Save Anonymized Project As, Project from Activated Documents, External Archive Files, and Data. The main interface is divided into several panels:

- Documents Panel (Left):** Shows a list of documents including Interview2 (69 paragraphs), JournalEntry1 (18), JournalEntry2 (22), JournalEntry3 (11), and PGOR (43).
- Codes Panel (Left):** Displays a hierarchical code list. The 'Acting strategically to be responsive' code is selected. Other codes include Sexual Identity, Professional Identity, Emotions, and Disapproval.
- Timeline Panel (Center):** A vertical timeline showing the application of codes to the text. Codes like '.Acting strategically to be responsive', '.Perceived expectation of female-bodied English teachers', and '.Realization of her position' are visible.
- Main Text Panel (Right):** Contains the text of the interview. It shows a paragraph from Melisa: "With a lot of finesse and manipulation. I have to create a guidebook on how to act, speak, and even look the right way. Again, this is about feeling obliged to be extra careful with everything and anything at the workplace. For example, as a queer language educator who 'appears' to be 'female and queer', I can't act too butch or too feminine. Anything out of the perceived norm of a 'female' English teacher becomes a topic of gossip and often leads to being called to the director's office for the smallest things. It's exhausting." Below this is a question from Mehmet: "Would you like to provide specific examples?" and another response from Melisa: "Yes, sure. For instance, I am the resident 'social justice critical pedagogy' expert here. This often means I'm handed anything related to diversity and inclusion, though I know it's all performative. I know my colleagues don't truly believe in these principles. They view it as a trend or a checkbox exercise. For example, one colleague used critical pedagogy classes for her data collection without truly engaging with the principles, creating an echo chamber of some actual harmful beliefs, on the contrary of the principles. Anyway, as the queer teacher around here, though they don't care, they still tend to bring anything diversity/inclusion-related stuff to me. The only"

At the bottom of the interface, there is a 'Retrieved Segments' panel.

L. TURKISH SUMMARY / TÜRKÇE ÖZET

LGBTQİ DİL EĞİTMENİ KİMLİK MÜZAKERESİ, DENEYİM SEYRİ VE KURUMSAL HETEROPROFESYONELLİK KESİŞİMİ: BİR DURUM ÇALIŞMASINDAN İÇGÖRÜLER

GİRİŞ

Eğitim alanında çalışmakta olan toplumun LGBTQİ camiasına mensup bireyleri, alanın mevcut işleyimindeki kapsayıcılık olgusunun uygulanışını destekleme, toplum düzeni için gerekli olan çeşitliliği sağlama ve adı geçen camianın olumlu görünürlüğünü temsil etme bakımından epey elzem bir yere sahiptir. Bahsedilen bu bireylerin eğitim alanının çeşitli kurumsal bağlamlarında ve farklı seviyelerinde varlık gösteriyor olması, yalnızca toplumdaki eşit ve adil mesleki hakların sürdürülebilmesi açısından dahi yüksek önem teşkil eden bir değer taşımaktadır.

Ne var ki, sıradışı cinsel kimlikler de dahil olmak üzere, bireylerin bazı toplumsal ve ekinse düzgüler ile bağdaşmama hallerini dışlamaya yönelik uygulanan bir mesleki değer olan “karşıcinsel meslekçilik” (Mizzi, 2013), bu bireylerin mesleki bağlamlardaki varlığını ve çalışma hayatlarını kolaylaştırmamakla beraber, kimlik müzakeresi ve mesleki deneyimlerini yönlendirme süreçlerinde fazladan birçok zorluk doğurmaktadır. Bu alanda günümüze dek yürütülmüş çalışmalar ile oluşmuş olan alakalı bilimsel alanyazın incelemeye alındığında, LGBTQİ eğitimcilerin eğitim alanındaki varlıklarına yönelik küresel ölçekteki bilimsel ilginin oldukça sınırlı olduğunu söylemek gerekir (Antonelli & Sembiente, 2022).

Oysaki bu bireylerin mesleklerini icra ettikleri kurumsal yapılarda karşılaştıkları çeşitli güçlükler, özellikle de toplumsal ve ekinseş düzgülerle şekillenmiş oldukça cinsiyetçi ve karşıcinsel beklentiler (Rich, 2003) ile kurumsallaşmış karşıcinsel düzgüsellik (Warner, 1991), çeşitliliğin ve görünürlüğün değerini kavramak,

kapsayıcılığı ve adaleti sağlamak ve eğitim esasları ve uygulamaları için anlamlı çıkarımlar elde edebilmek amacı ile önemle incelenmelidir (Cantos et al., 2023).

Bu bağlam çerçevesinde tasarlanmış olan mevcut çalışma, Türk coğrafyasında, spesifik olarak Kuzey Kıbrıs Türk Cumhuriyetinde, görev yapmakta olan LGBTQİ kimlikli bir dil eğitmeninin kimlik müzakeresi, mesleki deneyim seyri ve kurumsallaşmış karşıcinsel meslekçilik (Mizzi, 2013) düşüncesinin kesişimselliğini incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Mevcut tez çalışması, katılımcının kimlik çokluğunun (Bennett et al., 2015; Mayo, 2023) çalışma alanı bağlamında nasıl sergilendiğini çözümlenmeye almaktadır. Bu çalışmadan elde edilen bulguların, anlamlandırmaları ile beraber, başta Türkiye coğrafyasındakiler olmak üzere, benzer ekinel düzgüler paylaşan Küresel Güney bağlamının eğitim alanındaki tüm paydaşlara ve karar merciiilere kurumsal düzenlemeleri sorgulama ve LGBTQİ eğitmenler için destekleyici çalışma alanları oluşturma doğrultusunda faydalı olabilecek yol gösterici vasıtalar sunabileceği öngörülmektedir.

Bilimsel alanyazında rastlanılan günümüze dek yürütülmüş birçok araştırma, özellikle Küresel Güney bağlamlarında, kendini LGBTQİ camiası ile bağdaştırarak tanımlayan öğrencilerin kimlikleri, duyguları, bakış açıları ve ihtiyaçları üzerine yoğunlaşmışken (Lewis & Ericksen, 2016; Payne & Smith, 2011; Swanson & Gettinger, 2016), LGBTQİ kişisel tanımlı eğitmenlerin mesleki deneyimlerine ve kurumsal yaşantılarına ilişkin çalışmalar son derece sınırlıdır (Antonelli & Sembiente, 2022; Coda, 2019).

Oysaki bu eğitmenler, kimlik çoklukları, içsel gerilimler, cinsel kimlik açılım ve gizleme süreçleri (Brett, 2022; Haddad, 2019) ile birlikte, çalışma alanlarındaki karşıcinsel meslekçi düzgüler ve örtük saldırganlıklarla da sıklıkla yüzleşmektedir (Gray, 2013; İpekçi, 2022). Bu yüzden ki, bu eğitmenlerin çeşitli deneyimlerinin derinlemesine anlaşılması, kendilerine fayda sağlayabilecek kapsayıcılık ve eşitlikçilik doğrultusunda tasarlanmış olacak olan kurumsal uygulamaların zaman içerisinde gelişimi açısından oldukça önemlidir (Grace, 2020; Smith et al., 2008).

Küresel Güney bağlamında, özellikle Türk coğrafyasında, dil eğitmenleri de dahil olmak üzere tüm LGBTQİ eğitmenlerin çok katmanlı kişisel ve mesleki kimliklerinin

ve bu kimliklerin kurumsal çalışma ortamları ile çeşitli çatışmalarının incelenmesine yönelik yürütülmüş olan bilimsel çalışmalar neredeyse yok denecek kadar azdır. Karşıcinsel meslekçilik, bu eğitimcilerin kişisel kimlikleri ile mesleki sorumluluk ve görevlerini dengeleme çabalarını ve bu çabaların doğurduğu özgün zorluk ve mücadeleleri etraflıca kavrayabilmek bakımından merkezi bir kavramdır. Konuya daha genel bir açıdan yaklaşıldığında da, kurumsal çalışma yapılarının karşıcinselliği temel alan beklenti ve uygulamalı düzgüleri, LGBTQİ bireylerin yalnızca görünürlüklerini değil, mesleki doyumlarını ve iyi olma hallerini de büyük ölçüde olumsuz etkilemektedir (Collins et al., 2021; Özeren & Aydın, 2016).

Mevcut bu çalışmanın temel amacı, bir LGBTQİ dil eğitimcinin, Türk coğrafyasında, İngiliz Dili Öğretim Görevlisi olarak görev almakta olduğu yükseköğretim kurumundaki deneyimlerini ele alarak, birden çok kimliğinin kesişimselliği (Crenshaw, 1989) ile kurumsallaşmış karşıcinsel meslekçilik kavramını bağdaştırarak derinlemesine bir keşif yapmaktır. Katılımcı; çift cinsiyetli (bigender) cinsiyet kimliği ve cinsiyet ötesi (panseksüel) cinsel yönelim kimliği ile içinde bulunduğu toplumun ekinel düzgü yapılarının oldukça dışında kalmaktadır. Bahsi geçen bu kurumda öğretim görevlisi olarak görev yapan bu eğitimci, çalışma ortamında açık ya da örtük şekilde maruz bırakıldığı düzgüsel dayatmalar ve kurumsal uygulamalar karşısında direniş göstermek ile birlikte, belli sebepler dolayısıyla uyum sağlama çabaları da sergilemektedir.

Çalışmada iki araştırma sorusu bulunmakta olup, bu sorular katılımcının Türk coğrafyasındaki bu yükseköğretim kurumunda karşıcinsel meslekçilik düşüncesinin nasıl dışa vurduğunu ve çok katmanlı kimliklerini nasıl uzlaştırdığını anlamaya yöneliktir. Araştırma sorular aşağıdaki gibidir:

1. Türk coğrafyası bağlamında görev yapmakta olan bir LGBTQİ dil eğitimcinin bakış açısından, varsa, karşıcinsel meslekçilik düşüncüsü kurumsal çalışma ortamında ne şekilde dışa vurmaktadır?
2. Türk coğrafyası bağlamında görev yapan bir LGBTQİ dil eğitimcisi, tek yönlü meslekçi kurumsal ortamında kimliklerini nasıl uzlaştırmakta ve meslekî deneyimlerini nasıl yönlendirmektedir?

Bu bakımdan mevcut araştırma çalışmasının temel problemi, Türk coğrafyası bağlamında, bilimsel alanyazıdaki mevcut araştırma çalışmalarının, LGBTQİ dil eğitmenlerinin çoklu kimlikleri, mesleki deneyimleri ve kurumsal düşüncüler arasında kalan kesişim alanlarının yeterince irdelememiş olmasıdır (İpekçi, 2022; Taşkın et al., 2022).

Çalışmanın asli değeri, Türk coğrafyası bağlamında bulunan eğitim kurumlarında görev yapmakta olan, öncelikle LGBTQİ dil eğitmenleri olmak üzere, tüm LGBTQİ eğitmenlerin maruz bırakıldığı baskıları, bu baskılar ile başa çıkma yollarını ve tüm bunlar süresince devamlılıkla destek görme çabalarını görünür kılması imkanına sahip olmasında yatmaktadır. Katılımcının yaşamış deneyimlerinden elde edilen bulgular ve bu bulguların yorumlamaları, eğitim alanındaki kurumsal karar merciiilerin daha kapsayıcı, eşitlikçi ve destekleyici çalışma ortamları oluşturmaya teşvik konusunda çeşitli katkılar sunabilir (Dykes & Delpont, 2018). Buna ek olarak, mevcut çalışma, genel anlamda LGBTQİ camiasının eğitim bağlamında kurumsal çalışma alanlarındaki daimi temsiliyet ve görünürlük mücadelesine destek sağlayabilmesi bakımından da önemli bir katkı sunması imkanına sahiptir (Nadal et al., 2016; Ryan-Flood, 2022).

Bu araştırma çalışması, Mizzi'nin (2013) türettiği karşıcinsel meslekçilik ve Crenshaw'un (1989) ortaya koyduğu kesişimsellik kavramlarına dayalı olan kavramsal bir çerçevede tasarlanmış ve yürütülmüştür. Karşıcinsel meslekçilik, karşıcinselliği örtük bir biçimde de olsa düzgü varsayan, destekleyen ve kurumsal olarak dayatıp devamlı olarak gerektiren yapılarla açıklanırken, kesişimsellik kuramı bireylerin çoklu kimliklerinden (cinsiyet, cinsel yönelim, meslek, kültür) herhangi iki veya daha fazlasının bir araya gelmesi ile ortaya çıkan özgün baskı türlerini anlamayı destekler. Mevcut çalışma bağlamında kesişimsellik kuramı, katılımcının, karşıcinsel meslekçi çalışma ortamında, çoklu kimliklerinden bazıları bir arada sergilendiğinde karşı karşıya kaldığı birbirinden farklı yollarda dayatılan özgün baskıları derinlemesine anlayabilmek açısından büyük önem teşkil etmiştir.

Sonuç olarak mevcut bu tez çalışması, çift cinsiyetli/panseksüel bir LGBTQİ tanımlı İngiliz dili eğitmeninin, Türk coğrafyasındaki yükseköğretim kurumsal çalışma

ortamında yaşadığı karşıcinsel meslekçi deneyimlerin çok katmanlı yapısını kavramsal bir temele dayandırarak incelemektedir. Araştırma sonunda elde edilen bulgulardan doğan çıkarımlar, eğitim yönetmelik ve düzenlemeleri, meslek öncesi öğretmen eğitimi, meslek içi mesleki gelişim programları ve eğitim alanındaki kurumsal gereksinim ve uygulamaların olumlu yönde dönüşümü için yol gösterici nitelikte olma imkanı taşımaktadır.

YÖNTEM

Bu araştırma çalışması, Türk coğrafyasında bir yükseköğretim kurumu bağlamında İngiliz dili öğretim görevliliği yapan bir LGBTQİ dil eğitmeninin çoklu kimlik müzakere süreci, mesleki deneyim seyri ve kurumlarda yaygın olarak gözlemlenen karşıcinsel meslekçilik düşüngüsü arasındaki kesişimselliği incelemektedir. Buna bağlı olarak, nitel araştırma yaklaşımlarından içsel tekil vaka çalışması yöntemi uygulanmıştır. Yalnızca bir katılımcının özgün vakasını derinlemesine inceleyen bu yöntemle, araştırmanın merkezindeki hadisenin bağlamsal, özgün ve etraflıca anlaşılması (Yin, 2009) amaçlanmıştır.

Yine bu doğrultuda, katılımcının seçiminde amaçlı örnekleme yöntemi kullanılmış. Dolayısıyla, LGBTQİ tanımlı, Türk coğrafyası bağlamında görev yapmakta olan ve bu araştırmanın amaçlarına hizmet edebilecek nitelikte (Teddlie & Yu, 2007; Creswell, 2007) bir İngiliz dili eğitmeni özellikle belirlenmiştir. Katılımcı, Kuzey Kıbrıs Türk Cumhuriyeti bağlamında oldukça saygın bir devlet üniversitesinin İngilizce hazırlık programında İngiliz dili öğretim görevlisi olarak görev yapmakta olan, yükseköğrenim düzeyinde bilimsel ve alansal yeterliklere sahip bir öğretmendir. Araştırmanın hem yürütülme hem de yazılma süreçleri boyunca tüm ahlaki araştırma kuralları göz önünde bulundurulmuş, her türlü karar ve değişiklikte katılımcının onayı mutlaka alınmış ve veri gizliliği her koşul altında korunmuştur.

Mevcut çalışmanın veri toplama süreci toplamda yaklaşık olarak altı ay sürmüştür. Veri toplama vasıtaları olarak kullanılmış olan yarı yapılandırılmış mülakatlar, ön tanımlı günceler ve katılımcının kendisi tarafından çalışma alanı bağlamında oluşturulan gözlem tutanakları ile çok yönlü ve zengin içerikli bir veri toplama süreci

amaçlanmıştır. Katılımcı ile toplamda iki adet yarı yapılandırılmış mülakat gerçekleştirilmiştir. İlk mülakat 13 Mayıs 2024 tarihinde yapılırken, ikinci ve son mülakat 10 Kasım 2024 tarihinde tamamlanmıştır. Yine bu tarihler arasında ön tanımlı günce kayıtları ve gözlem tutanakları da toplanarak veri üçlemesi sağlanmıştır (Patton, 1999).

Bahsedilen bu veri toplama vasıtaları yoluyla, mevcut bu tez çalışması için yapılan bu araştırma, LGBTQİ tanımlı bir dil eğitmeninin karşıcinsel meslekçi çalışma ortamında maruz bırakıldığı karşıcinsel düzgüsel uygulamaların mesleki deneyimlerine ve çoklu kimliklerine nasıl yansıdığını kendi gözünden betimleyerek, özgün vakasını tüm yönleri ile derinlemesine anlamak ve mevcut düzenin olumlu yönde değiştirilmesi konusunda detaylı bulgular ile katkı sağlamaktır.

Yöntem bakımından, mevcut araştırmada içsel vaka çalışması uygulanması tercih edilmiştir. Bunun sebeplerinden biri araştırılan vakanın, konumsallık açısından araştırmacı için doğrudan bir anlam taşıyan, özgül ve bulgularının genellenmesi hiçbir şekilde amaçlanmayan bir durumu yansıtıyor olmasıdır (Stake, 2005; Merriam, 2009). Bu çalışma, betimleyici ve keşfedici bir yapıda tasarlanmış ve uygulanmış olup, araştırmanın veri toplama süreci yorumlayıcı bir anlayışla yürütülmüştür.

Araştırma bağlamı, katılımcının İngiliz dili öğretim görevlisi olarak görev yapmakta olduğu Kuzey Kıbrıs Türk Cumhuriyeti'ndeki yüksek öğretim kurumu olmakla birlikte, Türk ekinsel değer ve düzgülerinin büyük ölçüde yansıtılması sebebiyle "Türk coğrafyası bağlamı" şeklinde adlandırılmıştır. Bu toplumsal ve ekinsel yapı, LGBTQİ camiasına tanımlı bireyleri geleneksel düzgülere aykırı gören bir düşüncüler sistemiyle şekillenmesinden kaynaklı olarak, dışlama ve ayrımcılık gibi oldukça ciddi toplumsal sorunlara zemin hazırlamaktadır (Engin, 2015; Özeren & Aydın, 2016; Özbay, 2021; Erdur, 2022).

Bunlarla beraber, katılımcının cinsiyet ve cinsel yönelim tanımları da mevcut çalışmada önemli yer tutmaktadır. Biyolojik olarak kadın cinsiyeti ile tanımlanan katılımcı, kendini çift cinsiyetli olarak tanımlamakta ve tüm cinsiyet kimliklerine

karşı cinsel çekim duyduğunu belirtmektedir. Bu tanım, kendisi tarafından, cinsel yönelimini panseksüel şekilde belirlemektedir.

Çift cinsiyetlilik tanımı onun ne kadın ne de erkek olduğunu göstermektedir. Katılımcı zaman zaman kendisini her iki cinsiyetle de tanımlamaktadır; fakat bu ona ikililik dışı bir cinsiyet kimliği de atfetmemektedir. Ön tanımlı günce kayıtlarında ve mülakatlarında, katılımcının kendisini kimi zaman kadın, kimi zaman ise erkek olarak tanımladığını gözlemlenmiş ve bu kimliklerin gündelik yaşantısında nasıl karşılandığı ile alakalı detaylı deneyim aktarımlarına rastlanmıştır. Bu bağlamda mevcut çalışmadaki vaka, karşıcinsel düzgüsel yapılarla doğrudan çelişen bir cinsiyet kimliği ve cinsel yönelime sahip olan bu LGBTQİ tanımlı İngiliz dili eğitmeninin karşıcinsel meslekçi çalışma ortamı bağlamında var olma serüvenini ortaya koymaktadır.

Veri üçlemesi içerisinde bulunan veri toplama vasıtaları arasında öne çıkanı yarı yapılandırılmış mülakatlardır. İlk mülakat, katılımcıyla güçlü bir bağ kurmak ve onu araştırma sürecine hazırlamak amacıyla düzenlenmiş (Creswell, 2013), ardından iki haftalık aralıklarla, katılımcıdan üç farklı ön tanımlı günce tutanağı talep edilmiştir. Günce yazım süreci ile, bunun katılımcı için tamamlanması gereken bir iş olduğu hissinden mümkün olduğunca sıyırılarak (Milligan et al., 2005), onun duygu, düşünce, bakış açısı ve deneyimlerini özgürce dile getirmesini sağlamak amaçlanmıştır.

Bununla beraber, gözlem tutanakları katılımcının çalışma ortamı bağlamında deneyimlediği olaylara ve tüm bu vakaya dair betimleyici ve birinci elden bir bakış açısı imkanı daha sağlamıştır. Gözlem tutanakları, katılımcıya başlıca toplumsal ve ekinsel düzgüler ile uyumsuz cinsel kimliklere ve yönelimlere dönük ayrımcılığı, karşıcinsel düzgüsel kurumsal uygulamaları ve karşıcinsel meslekçilik düşüncesünü etkin şekilde gözlemlene ve kaydetme olanağı da sunmuştur. Böylece, yalnızca katılımcının öznel deneyimleri ve bakış açıları değil, aynı zamanda bağlamsal ortamda günlük yaşanan olaylar da betimlenebilmiştir. Bahsedile gözlem tutanaklarında katılımcı tarafından gözlemlenmesi ve aktarılması beklenen davranış örüntüleri, gözlem tutanakları bir veri toplama vasıtası olarak uygulanmaya

başlanılmadan evvel araştırmacı ve katılımcı tarafından birlikte belirlenmiş ve buna bağlı olarak bir tanımlayıcı yönlendirme şablonu hazırlanmıştır.

Anlatıldığı şekilde uygulanan, mevcut çalışmadaki bu veri üçlemesi yöntemi araştırmacının güvenilirliğini de artırmıştır (Tracy, 2010). Yarı yapılandırılmış mülakatlar, ön tanımlı günceler ve gözlem tutanaklarının birlikte veri toplama vasıtaları olarak kullanılması sayesinde yalnızca niceliksel olarak zengin değil, aynı zamanda niteliksel olarak da oldukça bütüncül bir veri kümesi oluşturulmuştur. Araştırma verilerinin mevcut çalışmanın araştırma soruları ile doğrudan olarak ilişkilendirilmiş olması, her veri türünün belirli bir boyutu betimlemeye yönelik kullanılmasına da olanak sağlamıştır.

Verilerin çözümlemesi, MAXQDA isimli nitel veri çözümleme yazılımı yardımı ile gerçekleştirilmiş ve bu süreçte altı aşamalı Yansıtılabilir Tematik Çözümleme (Braun & Clarke, 2006) yöntemi uygulanmıştır. Araştırmacı, ilk aşamada veriye etkin bir aşinalık kazandıktan sonra (Stake, 1995) betimleyici simgeler üretmiş, bu simgeleri örüntü simgelerine dönüştürerek izdemler geliştirmiştir (Saldaña, 2013). Bunun ardından geliştirilen izdemler incelemeye alınmış, her birinin uygunluğu araştırmacı tarafından yeniden değerlendirilmiş ve çalışmanın araştırma soruları ile direkt ilişkileri bağlamında yeniden düzenlenmişlerdir. Tüm bu geliştirilen izdemler, alakalı veri parçaları ile desteklenerek yeniden yapılandırılmışlardır. Bunlara ek olarak, çözümlenen izdemlerin araştırmacının kuramsal çerçevesi ve bilimsel alanyazın ile nasıl örtüştüğü de ayrıntılı biçimde tartışılmıştır.

Araştırmanın genel geçerlik ve güvenilirliğinin korunabilmesi adına tüm araştırma süreci boyunca çok yönlü denetim mekanizmaları benimsenmiştir. Danışman ve eş danışman denetimi, uzman görüşü, özdeşünümsellik, eşdüzey sorgulama, veri üçlemesi ve katılımcı kontrolü gibi yöntemlerin uygulamaları ile araştırmanın bütünlüğünün korunmasına özen gösterilmiştir (Creswell & Poth, 2016; Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Stake, 1995).

Araştırmacı, kendi öznel konumunun araştırma sürecine bilinçli biçimde yansıtılması ve katılımcı ile paylaşılan ortak çoklu kimlikler dolayısıyla doğabilecek öznelliğin

etkisini en aza indirgeme amaçları ile araştırma süresi boyunca düzenli olarak özdüşünümsel ses kayıtları tutmuştur. Katılımcının kurul tarafından belirtilen kırılgan nüfusta bulunmamasına rağmen, toplumsal olarak kırılgan bir konumda olması sebebiyle, ahlaki araştırma hassasiyetinin ortaya koyduğu tüm uygulamaların yüksek düzeyde korunması amaçlanmış, araştırma süreci boyunca kendisinin duygusal güvenliği de aynı doğrultuda gözetilmiştir.

Veriler üzerinden katılımcı onayı, görüşme tutanaklarının kendisiyle paylaşımı ve verilerin son halinin kendisi tarafından doğrulanması yolu ile sağlanmıştır. Katılımcıya, duygusal güvenliği ve iyi olma hali göz önünde bulundurularak (Birt et al., 2016), araştırmanın kendisi ve özellikle veri paylaşımı süreçleri boyunca her aşamada söz hakkı tanınmış, böylelikle çalışmanın yalnızca araştırmacı bakış açısı ile değil, aynı zamanda büyük oranda katılımcının da kendisine özgün ifade biçimiyle yürütülmesi sağlanmıştır.

Araştırmacının katılımcı ile benzer veya aynı bireysel, kültürel ve mesleki kimliklere sahip olması durumu araştırma süreci açısından hem olumlu hem de olumsuz etkiler doğurabileceğinden, bu durum araştırmacının kendisi tarafından süreç boyunca dikkatle yönetilmiştir. Bu benzerlik, araştırmacı ve katılımcı arasında kurulan güven bağını ve araştırmacının yorumlama yetisini olumlu yönde etkilerken, önyargı riskini de artırdığından kaynaklı araştırmacı çeşitli tarafından özdüşünümsel denetim süreçleri ile mümkün olduğunca kontrol altında tutulmuştur (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Araştırma ahlakı ilkeleri gereğince, katılımcının adı değiştirilmiş, takma isim kullanılmış (Melisa) ve araştırma süreci boyunca tüm kişisel bilgileri olabildiğince gizli tutulmuştur. Katılımcının her türlü güvenliği, araştırmanın olası tüm başarılarından daha öncelikli kabul edilmiştir (Mack et al., 2005). Ahlaki araştırma ilkelerinin yalnızca dolaylı olarak değil, mümkün olduğu kadar doğrudan olarak da araştırma sürecinin tamamına yerleştirilmesi sağlanmıştır (Creswell, 2013). Sonuç olarak, detaylandırılan bu araştırma yöntemi izlenerek, LGBTQİ tanımlı bir İngiliz dili eğitmeninin çalışma ortamı bağlamında yaşadığı deneyimlerin bütüncül biçimde ve derinlemesine kavranmasına ve sunulmasına olanak sağlanmasıyla beraber, sosyal

adalet ve kurumsal kapsayıcılığa katkısı olabilecek bağlamsal içgörü ve çıkarımların üretimi hedeflenmiştir.

TEMEL BULGULAR

Bulgular, Mizzi'nin (2013) karşıcinsel meslekçilik kavramını esas alarak, Melisa'nın çalışma ortamında karşılaştığı örtük saldırganlıklar, dışlanmalar, önyargılar ve toplumsal beklentiler çerçevesinde, çoklu kimlik müzakeresi ve deneyim seyrini ortaya koymaktadır. Melisa, toplumun karşıcinsel düzgüsel yapı ile uyumlu olmayan kimliklere sahip bir birey olarak çalışma ortamı bağlamında sürekli tetikte kalmak zorunda hissetmektedir.

Cis-karşıcinsel meslektaşları ile kıyaslandığında, temel sosyal etkileşimlerde dahi davranışlarında çok daha dikkatli olup, öğrencileriyle ya da yöneticileriyle olan birebir ilişkilerinde cinsiyet ve cinsel yönelim kimliklerinin görünürlüğünden doğabilecek olumsuzlukları önlemeye çalışmaktadır. Bu sürekli tetikte olma halinin kişisel hayatını da direkt olarak etkilediği ve kendi deyimiyle "hayatta kalma 102" tutumunu sergilediği gözlemlenmektedir (Int1E1, Int1E2, Int2E1).

Melisa'nın çalışma ortamındaki varoluşu "toplumsal adalet ve eleştirel öğretim" gibi kavramlar ile direkt olarak etiketlenmektedir. Bundan dolayı, çeşitlilik ve kapsayıcılık gibi konularda kendisine yorucu bir yük olarak fazladan sorumluluk yüklenmektedir (Int2E1). Toplumun ve kurumunun karşıcinsel düzgüsel yapıları ve uygulamaları nedeniyle öğrencileriyle ve çalışma arkadaşlarıyla kurduğu ilişkiler de sıklıkla sorgulanmaktadır. Özellikle cinsiyetçi düzgüselere ve kalıplara uymayan dış görünümü ve davranışları sebebiyle sıklıkla örtük tutumlu dışlanmalar deneyimlemektedir (Int2E2, Int2E3). Türk coğrafyası bağlamında kadın bedeni taşıyan İngiliz dili öğretmenlerine atfedilen beklentiler, örneğin süslü olmak, evli olmak, çocuk sahibi olmak gibi, Melisa'nın kendi kimliklerini ve mesleki aidiyetini sorgulamasına sebebiyet vermektedir (Int1E4, Int1E5).

Melisa, karşıcinsel meslekçilik düşüncesini ve bağıntılı kurumsal uygulamalarını birçok düzeyde tehlikeli bulmaktadır. Bu düşünce, Melisa'ya göre, insanların

eleştirel düşünme becerilerini köreltmekte ve aynı zamanda dil öğrenme yeterliklerini de olumsuz yönde etkilemektedir. Melisa bu durumu, Türk coğrafyası bağlamındaki bireylerin Avrupa'daki en düşük İngiliz dili yeterlik düzeylerinden birine sahip olması ile de ilişkilendirmektedir (Int2E5).

Öte yandan, kendisinin toplumsal düzgülerle uyumsuz cinsiyet ve cinsel yönelim kimliklerinin doğrudan hedef alındığı tehditleri de yaşamış. Örneğin bazı öğrencilerinin beklenenden düşük not aldıklarında Melisa'yı kolaylıkla üst makamlara şikayet etme tehditlerini deneyimlemiştir (JE1E1). Melisa bu durumu öğrencilerinin, toplumsal düzgülerle uyumsuz kimlikleri dolayısıyla, kendisi üzerinde sahip olduğu talihsiz bir güç ile bağdaştırmaktadır. Bu durum, onun çalışma ortamı bağlamında ve özellikle sınıfta, özgün, olduğu gibi davranabilmesine, olağan LGBTQİ öğrencilerini dilediğince desteklemesine ve mevcut sistem karşısı bir duruş sergilemesine engel olmuştur.

Melisa'nın kişisel tercihleri de içinde bulunduğu toplumun karşı cinsel düzgüsel yapısı ile sıklıkla çelişmektedir. Çevrim içi toplantılarda görünmek üzere bazı uygulamalardaki hesap kullanıcı isminde şahıs zamiri kullanımı gibi küçük tercihler dahi onun için büyük kurumsal sorunlar doğurabilme olasılığına sahiptir (Int2E7). Karşıcinsel düzgüsel kalıplar sebebiyle "olumsuz dikkat" (Int2E8) çekme riski taşımakla suçlanmaktadır. Dolayısıyla, çalışma ortamı bağlamındaki dilsel ve görsel sunumlarına oldukça özen göstermektedir. Aynı zamanda, sorunlu olarak nitelediği toplumsal cinsiyet temsillerinin bulunduğu öğretim gereçlerindeki önyargılı tutumları fark etmekle kalmayıp, onlara müdahale etmekte ve kendi öğrencilerinde bir farkındalık oluşturmaya çalışmaktadır (Int1E7).

Yalnızca dışlanma değil, Melisa aynı zamanda doğrudan ya da dolaylı olarak örtük saldırganlıklara da maruz bırakılmaktadır. Bunlar kimi vakit doğrudan sözel olarak ifade edilirken (PGOR4E1), zaman zaman ima yoluyla, sık sık da iş arkadaşları ile arasında yapılan görev paylaşımı sürecinde dışlama biçiminde gözlemlenmektedir (Int2E9). Bazı zamanlarda, yalnızca LGBTQİ kimlikleri nedeniyle ekstra iş yükü ile karşı karşıya kaldığı yetmezmiş gibi, aynı zamanda evli olan karşıcinsel çalışma arkadaşlarının faydalandığı esneklikler kendisine sunulmamaktadır. Özellikle

yöneticilerinin ve çalışma arkadaşlarının bahsedilen tarzda tutumları, Melisa'nın kurum içi ilişkilerinde çeşitli yollarla yalnızlaştırıldığını ortaya koymaktadır. Tüm bu örtük saldırganlık hadiseleri (JE2E; PGOR1E2; Int2E8; Int2E9; PGOR2E1; PGOR4E1) çoğunlukla erkek meslektaşları meydana gelmektedir. Melisa çoğu zaman sessiz kalmaktansa bu hadiseler akışında çeşitli tepkiler vermektedir.

Karşıcinsel meslekçiliğin kendisi için tehlikeli etkilerini kabul eden Melisa'nın mesleki kimliği içinde bulunduğu toplumun "kadın İngiliz dili eğitmeni" kalıbına atfettikleri ile uyumsuzluğu sebebiyle dedikodu konusu olmakta ve oldukça basit hadiseler dolayısıyla dahi kendisi sıklıkla yöneticilerinin odasına çağrılmaktadır (Int2E11). Öğrencilerinden birinin gözlem esnasında sınıf içerisinde kendisini öpmesi gibi ciddi bir meselede bile, yöneticileri ve iş arkadaşları tarafından "yanlış işaret vermekle" suçlanan taraf Melisa olmaktadır (Int2E12). Melisa bu hadise üzerinden, çalışma ortamının kurumsal karşıcinsel meslekçiliği benimseyen doğasını sorgulamakta ve kurumunun bu tarz durumlarda LGBTQİ eğitmenleri korumaktansa suçlayıcı tutum ve uygulamalar sergilediğini gözlemlemektedir.

Tüm bunlara rağmen, kurumundaki birkaç çalışma arkadaşı Melisa'ya destek de göstermektedir. Ancak söz konusu destekler çoğunlukla dolaylı ve üstü örtülü biçimde gösterilmektedir. Özellikle cis-karşıcinsel çalışma arkadaşlarının açık bir dayanışma veya destek göstermemesi, Melisa'nın çalışma ortamı bağlamında kendini daha yalnız hissetmesine yol açmaktadır (Int2E13, PGOR2E2). Küçük istisnalar dışında, Melisa'nın LGBTQİ kimliği çalıştığı kurumda ya göz ardı edilmekte ya da sadece benzer kimliklere sahip bireylerce destek görmektedir.

Sonuç olarak, Melisa mesleki kimliği ile kişisel kimliklerinin kesişimselliğinde bir denge durumu yakalamaya çalışırken çalışma ortamı bağlamında karşılaştığı karşıcinsel meslekçi düzgülere ve kurumsal uygulamalara karşı da bir direnç sergilemektedir. Her ne kadar karşıcinsel meslekçilik uygulamaları çok katmanlı bir biçimde kendisinin kimliğine çeşitli tehditler oluştursa da Melisa sınıf içerisinde kendi mesleki uygulamalarında toplumsal adaleti gözetmeye devam etmekle beraber, öğrencilerini etkin ve eleştirel bir şekilde düşünmeye ve sorgulamaya teşvik etmektedir. Bu durum, Melisa'nın dar (mikro) düzeyde (sınıf içinde) daha güçlü bir

özne olarak konumlanırken göstermektedir. Buna karşın geniş (mezo) düzeyde karşı karşıya bırakıldığı tehditlerle, daha tetikte konumlanarak, çalışma arkadaşları ve yöneticileriyle taktiksel bazı arkadaşlık ilişkileri geliştirerek, kusursuz bir meslek icrası sergileyerek ve gerektiğinde sessiz kalmayı tercih ederek başa çıkmaktadır. Böylelikle Melisa'nın öyküsü, Türk coğrafyası bağlamında görev yapmakta olan LGBTQİ camiasına tanımlı bir İngiliz dili eğitmeninin karşı karşıya kaldığı yapısal ve kurumsal zorlukların, kişisel mücadele, taktiksel adımlar, bilinçli tepki, karşı koyma ve direncin de dahil olduğu çeşitli birçok yol izlenerek nasıl aşılmaya çalışıldığını da resmeder niteliktedir.

TARTIŞMA VE SONUÇ

Melisa, LGBTQİ kimliklerini bilinçli bir şekilde saklıyor olmasa da çalışma ortamı bağlamında seçici açıklık taktiğini izlemekte, bu durum da onun sürekli tetikte olma haline sebep olmaktadır (bkz. Orlov & Allen, 2014; O'Brien & Fassinger, 1993). Bu taktiğini Melisa'nın öğrencileriyle ve çalışma arkadaşlarıyla olan ilişkilerini de derinden etkilemektedir. Öğrencilerine karşı daha açık davranıyor olsa da üstleriyle ilişkilerinde oldukça dikkatli davranmaktadır. Melisa'nın bu hali Coda'nın (2019) çalışmasında betimlenen kimliksel bazı kaygılar ile benzerlik göstermektedir.

Bununla beraber, Llewellyn (2022), Jackson (2009), Gray'in (2013) çalışmalarında ortaya konan LGBTQİ tanımlı eğitmenlerin kimlik çokluğu ile başa çıkma süreçleri de Melisa'nın deneyimleri ile örtüşmektedir. Fakat Melisa'nın karşıcinsel meslekçiliğe karşı olan etkin direnişi, eleştirel öğretim taktikleri ve yöntemleri kullanması ve öğrencilerine toplumsal adalet ile alakalı düşündürücü içerikler sunmasıyla görünürlüğünü artırmaktadır (Allen, 1995; Gates, 2011; Brockenbrough, 2012). Melisa'nın başlıca amacı, LGBTQİ komünitesi ile alakalı toplumsal düzgüsel önyargıları ortaya koymak ve öğrencilerini bu konuda eleştirel düşünmeye sevk etmektir. Bu durum, Melisa'nın yalnızca bir dil eğitmeni değil aynı zamanda bir toplumsal adalet savunucusu olması halini de desteklemektedir (Bennett et al., 2015; Mizzi et al., 2021).

Sınıflarına LGBTQİ-olumlayıcı öğretim gereçleri dahil ederek İngiliz dilinin kültürünü de mümkün olduğunca dahil ediyor olması, Ferfolja ve Robinson'un

(2004) temel bulgularını da yansıtmaktadır. Ne var ki tüm bu çabalarına rağmen, Melisa'nın en baskın olarak deneyimlediği duygunun korku olduğu da gözlemlenmektedir. Söz konusu bu korku hissi, öğrencilerinden daha çok kurum içi yetkili makamlardan ve yaşadığı toplumun keskin düzgülerinden kaynaklanmaktadır (Eckes & McCarthy, 2008; Henderson, 2017). Dolayısıyla, Melisa'nın suskunluğu taktiksel bir direniş yolu olarak da okunabilir (Ferfolja & Stavrou, 2015).

Melisa'nın deneyimleri, Türk coğrafyası bağlamında yürütülen İpekçi (2022) ve Taşkın et al. (2022) gibi çalışmalarda ortaya konan kurumsal bazı dışlayıcılık halleri ve karşıcinsel düzgüsel varsayımlar ile de oldukça benzeşmektedir. Bu durumun başlıca örnekleri LGBTQİ eğitimcilerin sosyal etkinliklerden dışlanması, Türk coğrafyasında yasal anlamda evliliğe olanak sağlamayan ilişkilerin görünmez kılması ve bu ilişkilerdeki bireylerin bekar varsayımlar olarak çalışma ortamlarında fazladan iş yükü ile karşı karşıya bırakılması gibi bazı kurumsal uygulamalardır. Buna ek olarak, Melisa'nın bazı deneyimleri yalnızca dil eğitimcileri değil, genel anlamda LGBTQİ tanımlı birçok meslek grubu çalışanının çoklu kimliklerini işleri ile bütünleştirme çabalarını da yansıtmaktadır (bkz. Özeren, 2014; Göçmen & Yılmaz, 2017). Melisa'nın, Türk coğrafyasının toplumsal düzgüleri ile uyumsuz olan kendi LGBTQİ kimliklerinin içinde yaşadığı toplum tarafından sapkın veya günah şeklinde yorumlandığı ile alakalı etkin farkındalığı da, toplumsal ve ekinel düzgülerin ötekileştirilmiş bazı kişiler ve gruplar üzerindeki oldukça derin olan etkisini de net bir şekilde ortaya koymaktadır (Basaran, 2003; Sakallı & Uğurlu, 2002).

Tüm bahsedilenler doğrultusunda düşünüldüğünde, Melisa'nın birçok deneyimi alakalı bilimsel alanyazın ile önemli ölçüde örtüşmektedir. Fakat bazı dikkate değer farklılıklar da mevcuttur. Buna örnek olarak, Gray (2013) ve Rockhill (1993) LGBTQİ eğitimcilerin açık olmak veya tamamen saklanmak arasında bir seçim yapmaları gerektiğini öne sürerken, Melisa'nın bu ikilemi reddetmesi ve daha çok duruma bağlı taktik geliştirmeyi gözetten bir seyir tercih etmesi gösterilebilir. Melisa, tam açıklık-gizlilik ikilemindense, bağlama özgü açıklık halini benimsemektedir.

Ek olarak, Allen (1995) ve Gates (2011) gibi çalışmalarda incelenen açık LGBTQİ eğitimcilerin toplumsal adalet savunuculukları, çoğunlukla destek verici kurumsal

çalışma ortamları ve toplumsal bağlamlarda gözlenmektedir. Ancak Melisa, dikkate değer bir destek göremediği ve LGBTQİ konularının engellendiği bir çalışma ortamında benzer çabaları göstermektedir. Benzer şekilde, Küresel Kuzey bağlamları merkezli araştırmalarda LGBTQİ eğitimcilerin çalışma ortamlarındaki kimlik açılımları ile alakalı öğrencilerinden olumlu dönüşler gözlemlenirken (Laplante, 2023), Melisa'nın bazı öğrencileri zaman zaman farkında olmadan olsa da baskıcı veya tehlikeli tavırlar sergilemektedir. Buna örnek olarak, öğrencilerinden birinin Melisa'yı "deney amaçlı" sınıf ortamında öpmesi olayı gösterilebilir. Bu tür hadiseler Melisa'yı yalnızca mesleki itibarının zedelenmesi açısından değil, onun kimlik müzakeresi açısından da zorlamaktadır (Piper & Sikes, 2010). Bu hadise aynı zamanda, Melisa'nın çalışma ortamı bağlamında LGBTQİ kimliğinin mesleki kimliğinin önüne geçirilmesi durumunu, dolayısıyla bir eğitimci olarak iş yerinde yaşadığı korku halinin ne kadar yerli olduğunu onamaktadır (Conrad, 2019).

Günün sonunda, Melisa'nın deneyimleri, mevcut bilimsel alanyazınla önemli ölçüde örtüşmekle birlikte, Küresel Güney'e, özellikle Türk bağlamına özgü birçok farklılık da göstermektedir. Araştırmanın bulgularındaki bu özgünlük durumu, LGBTQİ eğitimcilerin sadece Küresel Güney bağlamlarında ya da Batılı veya destekleyici ortamlarda değil, etkin bir şekilde baskılayıcı, dışlayıcı ve sessizleştirici çalışma ortamlarında da deneyimlerinin ve direnişlerinin etraflıca incelenip anlaşılabilmesi doğrultusunda bazı imkanlar sunmaktadır. Sonuç olarak Melisa'nın öyküsünün, Türk coğrafyası bağlamındaki LGBTQİ tanımlı bireylerin hem eğitimci hem de savunucu sıfatlarını aynı anda taşıma çabası halinde karşı karşıya kaldıkları çok yönlü ve çeşitli zorlukları açığa çıkarmak ve mevcut bilimsel alanyazına bağlamsal derinlik kazandırmak konularında olumlu bir etken olabileceği düşünülmektedir.

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